

**STRESS INDUCING FACTORS AND EMPLOYEES'
STRATEGIES TO REDUCE IT: A STUDY WITH SPECIAL
REFERENCE TO CABIN CREWS OF SELECTED INDIAN
INTERNATIONAL AIRPORTS**

**Thesis Submitted to the
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY**

**In Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for Award of the
Degree of**

**Doctor of Philosophy
in
Management & Commerce**

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September 2022

DECLARATION

I, **Mrs. Pavithra Kumari**, hereby declare that the thesis entitled “*Stress Inducing Factors and Employees’ Strategies to Reduce it: A Study with Special Reference to Cabin Crews of Selected Indian International Airports*” submitted to the Institute of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Management & Commerce is a record of the original research work done by me under the supervision and guidance of **Dr. P. S. Aithal** and the research work has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, fellowship or any other similar title.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “*Stress Inducing Factors and Employees’ Strategies to Reduce it: A Study with Special Reference to Cabin Crews of Selected Indian International Airports*” submitted to Srinivas University for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Management & Commerce is based on the original work done by **Mrs. Pavithra Kumari** in the Institute of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, under my guidance and supervision. The thesis has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, fellowship or any other similar title.

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APPROVAL OF THESIS WORK

This is to certify that the Thesis *“Stress Inducing Factors and Employees’ Strategies to Reduce it: A Study with Special Reference to Cabin Crews of Selected Indian International Airports”* submitted by **Mrs. Pavithra Kumari**, bearing **Reg. No: SUPHDMGMT2017/03** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of **DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY in Management & Commerce** as prescribed by Srinivas University, Mangalore is approved and after the examination it is entitled for the award of Degree.

Examiners:

Place: Mangalore

Date: ___ / ___ / _____

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

“What you get by achieving your goals is not as important as what you become by achieving your goals” – Henry David Thoreau

It has been a wonderful experience for me to work as a Ph.D. scholar at the Institute of Management and Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore. Writing a Ph.D. thesis is not an individual work; it includes the efforts of several persons. I am very grateful to several people who have been instrumental in guiding this thesis to completion.

Firstly, I would like to place on record my heartfelt gratitude to my guide and supervisor Dr. P. S. Aithal, Vice-Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mangalore. Words prove insufficient for his scholarly insights, inspired discussions, progressive vision, loving encouragement, meticulous care and friendly concern. Without his motivation and support, it would not have been possible to complete this research work. It has been a great pleasure and a privilege to work under his supervision. His keen interest in giving timely instructions and advice kept my spirit sustained and made the work progress towards successful completion.

I express my gratefulness to Honourable Chancellor of Srinivas University, Mangalore, for facilitating me to pursue my research work.

I express my gratitude to Honourable Pro-Chancellor of Srinivas University, Mangalore for his constant encouragement during my research work.

It is my pleasure to acknowledge my gratitude to Sri Anil Kumar, Registrar, and Dr. Shailashree V.T. of Srinivas University, Mangalore, for their continuous support during my Ph.D. programme.

It is my pleasure to acknowledge my gratitude to Dr. Shrinivasa Mayya D., Registrar Evaluation, Srinivas University, Mangalore for his invaluable assistance at various stages of the work.

It is my privilege to record my sincere thanks to my pre-colloquium Doctoral Committee members for their valuable comments and keen observations, which enabled me to shape my thesis in the right perspective.

I want to acknowledge with thanks Mrs. Kavyashri, Dr. Vaikunta Pai, Dr. Nethravathi, and Dr. Niyaz Panakaje for their timely help, shared knowledge, and kind co-operation during the period of my research.

Apart from my efforts, the success of any project depends largely on the encouragement and guidance of my family members and I express my hearty thanks to my family.

All praise is due to the Almighty. I would not be able to complete the work without the support of God, who shoulders me whenever I am downhearted and provides me with enough strength to complete the thesis successfully.

Pavithra Kumari

SYNOPSIS

“It’s not stress that kills us; it is our reaction to it.”

- Hans Selye

India's aviation industry is one of the world's fastest-growing aviation markets; it has the world's third largest domestic civil aviation industry, trailing only the United States and China in terms of size. Because of low flight fares, increased demand for domestic air travel and a continuous high level of tourism, the aviation job market has become a popular entry point for aspirants. The person or group of people in charge of the safety and security of an aircraft, passengers, and each other are referred to as flight attendants, air hostesses, cabin crew, flight stewardesses, or inflight crew. One flight attendant serves 15 to 20 passengers on average per flight, and the demands of the job, which include dealing with pushy or aggressive passengers, long shifts in a small space with little humidity, and exposure to certain levels of contaminants along with emergency services such as aborted takeoffs, emergency landings, smoke in the cabin, depressurization, dangerous items and spills in the cabin, emergency evacuations, hijackings, water landings, and survival abilities for the sea, jungle, and desert all these frequently result in high levels of job stress. Moreover, the crew experiences isolation and solitude as a result of their inability to maintain consistent social ties both at home and at work due to job demands, such as working with new co-workers on every flight, which can be a great benefit but may also limit opportunities to form a dependable group of colleagues for mutual support and may result in stress. Stress is the factor experienced by the pressure and fatigue of work, which can have a serious impact on both personal and professional life. All these aspects may result to serious issue among the Cabin Crews. While interacting with few of the cabin crews in Mangalore International Airport they pointed out that even though the cabin crew job seems to be a fascinating job, in reality there is lot of stress experienced by them. Hence, the researcher decided to take up ‘Stress Inducing Factors and Employees’ Strategies to Reduce it: A Study with Special Reference to Cabin Crews of Selected Indian International Airports’. The study is done among the cabin crews working in international airports in Karnataka. With this regard understanding the root cause of the stress, various stressors related to work pressure tends to be crucial. Hence, the primary goal of this research was to identify the elements that cause stress in cabin crew members and assessed its impact on

their work engagement. Moreover, the study also analysed the effectiveness of coping strategy in an enhanced work engagement of cabin crews. Lastly the study also ascertained the mediating role of stress coping resource between working stress and work engagement.

Review of related works depicted that various stressors that largely induces stress among cabin personnel are not identified and studied, also very few studies on Indian cabin crews have been undertaken which demonstrates scarcity of research on the stress coping techniques used by cabin crews. hence, major goal in this study was to discover the stressors that create stress among cabin crews. After the extensive review of literature, it was categorized under the head Stressors (Irregular working hours, Work hassles, Aircraft cabin environment and Social Isolation), Workplace stress, Stress coping strategies, Work Engagement and Emotional Labor.

Apart from that, the study demonstrated various concepts pertaining to the research with the theoretical background which includes irregular working hours, work hassles, aircraft cabin environment, social isolation, work engagement, stress coping resources and emotional labour. Based on which the conceptual model was framed with supportive evidences and hypothesis relationships were established. The study intended to apply the proposed model for a selected population that is cabin crews working in international airports.

The population of the study consisted of Cabin crews of airlines operating in Mangalore and Bangalore International airports. The calculated sample size for the study is 201, which includes from Bangalore Airline Companies 115 and from Mangalore Airline Companies 86. The sample has been selected based on snowball sampling technique. For gathering the required information, a survey method based on questionnaires was chosen. It was subsequently examined using the Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS) and IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Several descriptive statistics and inferential analysis techniques, including One-way ANOVA and Independent Sample t-test, were used to experimentally examine the data. The data was also examined using correlation, multiple regression, and structural equation modelling (SEM).

The present research also gave an overview of aviation industry from the Indian context to local context. After the key elaboration on Indian aviation industry, the study gave an overview on Bangalore International Airport and Mangalore International Airport as the study was conducted in these regions. Furthermore, profile of few selected domestic airline companies has been demonstrated along with the employee benefits provided by these companies. At the end, quantitative ABCD analysis have been undertaken to analyze the Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages of aviation industry.

Among the collected sample, majority of them found to be within the age category of 21-29 years and majority of the cabin crews are female and unmarried. Most of them work for 7 days or more consecutively. Stating the agreement level, all the constructs such as irregular working hour, work hassles, aircraft cabin environment, social isolation, workplace stress, work engagement, stress coping resources showed above average mean value that is 2.5. The study showed most of the cabin crews put on a “show” or “performance” when interacting with passengers and they cannot show their personal problems and sometimes have to give false smile.

The result exhibited significant difference in the agreement level of irregular working hours, Work Hassles, Aircraft Cabin Environments and Social Isolation among majority of the demographic factors of the selected cabin crews. Moreover, workplace stress is significantly different among various demographic factors except age and Current function. Whereas work engagement found to be significantly different among Gender, Experience, Maximum number of consecutive days of work and Average days off per month.

The thesis was divided into 7 chapters highlighting introduction, literature review, conceptual framework, research design, overview of aviation sector, data analysis and interpretation and quantitative ABCD analysis and summary of findings, suggestions and conclusion. Which is further discussed below;

Chapter 1: Introduction

It starts with an overview of aviation, then moves onto the definition of different types of stress, sources, its effects and finally to the conception of employee stress management. A multidimensional element of stress management is discussed, as well as the numerous models presented for employee stress management.

Chapter 2: Review of Literature

This chapter quotes earlier research on the subject of stress management in the aviation industry, which is pertinent to the study. After a thorough review of the available literature, a research gap is found.

Chapter 3: Conceptual Framework

This chapter describes various pertinent concepts with the theoretical background. The concepts have been described in detail. Based on the literature review, theoretical background and conceptual framework, the conceptual model has been developed in this chapter.

Chapter 4: Research Design

This chapter emphasises on the research design, analysis, conceptual framework, sample design (including sample size and sampling method), and questionnaire design for the current study, as well as the questionnaire's validity and reliability. It also goes into the data collection procedures and techniques that were used to interpret the results. Finally, the challenges encountered throughout the survey have been examined, as well as chapters from the thesis and the overall benefits of this study have been discussed.

Chapter 5: Aviation Sector Overview

This chapter presents an overview of India's aviation industry, with a focus on Karnataka and Mangalore. The importance of the aviation sector to the country's economic growth is discussed. Other aviation-related service industries are also examined in terms of progress and contribution to the country's economic development. In addition, the aspects of Human Resource in this sector are examined.

Chapter 6: Data Analysis and Interpretation and Quantitative ABCD Analysis

It is concerned with the use of statistical methods to the collected primary data. It is centered on the aviation industry as well as the answers of cabin crew members. It covers a variety of statistical approaches, as well as their outcomes and interpretations.

It undertakes quantitative analysis of various Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages (ABCD) of stress coping mechanism. It includes identification of numerous determinant issues and their key attributes which is further analysed through factor and elementary analysis. In the end of the chapter all the factors affecting determinant issues is calculated quantitatively and presented the results graphically.

Chapter 7: Summary of the Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion

The important findings in the aviation industry with respect to cabin crew are discussed in this chapter. It includes the discriminant scores, extracted components, and a regression model for projection.

The study proved a proposed conceptual model by finding the direct effect of stressor agents on workplace stress which showed negative impact on work engagement among the cabin crews. Moreover the study results also depicted the moderating effect of Age, gender, marital status, Current function and Experience of the cabin crews in relationship between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress. As far as the relationship between Workplace Stress and work Engagement is concerned Age, gender and marital status of the cabin crews showed a moderating effect but Current function and Experience showed no moderation effect.

As stress showed negative effect on work engagement, finding a solution for this issue was a major intention of this study which showed Stress Coping Resources as a significant solution; as the result demonstrated mediating role of stress coping resources between workplace stress and work engagement. The study gave a clear picture that higher stress coping strategy reduces the negative impact on work engagement created by workplace stress, whereas low strategy worsens the negative impact on work engagement. This outcome can be a major catalyst for a future research as well as an optimal solution for a stress related distress in aviation sector with special reference to cabin crews to increase the productivity and contributes to further development.

Based on the findings, suggestions were given in the study, which was further divided into two parts – suggestion for cabin crews and suggestion for management. At last, this study further opened a research direction for a future researchers interested in addressing the issues in this domain.

CONTENTS

Chapter No.	Title	Page No.
	<i>DECLARATION</i>	<i>i</i>
	<i>CERTIFICATE</i>	<i>ii</i>
	<i>APPROVAL OF THESIS WORK</i>	<i>iii</i>
	<i>ACKNOWLEDGEMENT</i>	<i>iv - v</i>
	<i>SYNOPSIS</i>	<i>vi - xi</i>
	<i>LIST OF TABLES</i>	<i>xiii - xvi</i>
	<i>LIST OF CHARTS AND FIGURES</i>	<i>xvii</i>
	<i>ABBREVIATIONS</i>	<i>xviii</i>
	<i>NOTATION</i>	<i>xix</i>
<i>CHAPTER I</i>	<i>INTRODUCTION</i>	<i>1 - 13</i>
<i>CHAPTER II</i>	<i>REVIEW OF LITERATURE</i>	<i>14 - 81</i>
<i>CHAPTER III</i>	<i>CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK</i>	<i>82 - 114</i>
<i>CHAPTER IV</i>	<i>RESEARCH DESIGN</i>	<i>115 - 130</i>
<i>CHAPTER V</i>	<i>AVIATION SECTOR OVERVIEW</i>	<i>131 - 153</i>
<i>CHAPTER VI</i>	<i>DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION AND QUANTITATIVE ABCD ANALYSIS</i>	<i>154 - 236</i>
<i>CHAPTER VII</i>	<i>SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION</i>	<i>237 - 254</i>
	<i>BIBLIOGRAPHY</i>	<i>i - xxxvi</i>
	<i>ANNEXURE 1 – Questionnaire 1</i>	<i>1 – 9</i>
	<i>ANNEXURE 2 – Questionnaire 2</i>	<i>10 - 13</i>
	<i>ANNEXURE 3 – Plagiarism Report</i>	<i>14</i>
	<i>ANNEXURE 4 – List of Publication</i>	<i>15</i>

LIST OF TABLES

Table No.	Title	Page No.
4.1	Reliability and Validity Results	120
4.2	Sample Size Distribution between Bangalore and Mangalore Airplane Company	122
4.3	Questionnaire Distribution among Cabin Crews Position wise	123
4.4	Sample Distribution among Cabin Crews Position wise	123
4.5	Variables / Factors Used in the Study	124
4.6	Results of Multi-collinearity Test	127
6.1	Age Profile of the Respondents	154
6.2	Gender Wise Distribution of the Respondents	155
6.3	Marital Status of the of the Respondents	155
6.4	Position wise distribution of the of the Respondents	155
6.5	Experience wise distribution of the of the Respondents	156
6.6	Changes in Lifestyle of the of the Respondents	156
6.7	Maximum Number of Consecutive Days of Work	157
6.8	Maximum Number of Consecutive Nights of Work	157
6.9	Average Days off Per Month	157
6.10	Emotional Labour Factors (A)	162
6.11	Emotional Labour Factors (B)	163
6.12	Emotional Labour Factors (C)	163
6.13	Emotional Labour Factors (D)	163
6.14	Emotional Labour Factors (E)	164
6.15	Emotional Labour Factors (F)	164
6.16	Emotional Situational and Problems	164
6.17	Provides Appropriate/Measures to Relieve Work Stress	165
6.18	Organization/Industry ever invested effort in development and implementation of new stress management strategies	165
6.19	History of Coping Well with Highly Stressful Situations	166
6.20	Exaggerating importance of bad situations	166
6.21	Decision-making power in the family	166

6.22	Decision-making power in working environment	167
6.23	Likelihood of seeing others as threatening, uncooperative, or exploitative	167
6.24	Extent of belief in the purposeful life	167
6.25	Level of Contact with Spiritual Community	168
6.26	Descriptive Statistics on Irregular Working Hours	168
6.27	Descriptive Statistics on Work Hassles	169
6.28	Descriptive Statistics on Aircraft Cabin Environments	170
6.29	Descriptive Statistics on Social Isolation	171
6.30	Descriptive Statistics on Workplace Stress	172
6.31	Descriptive Statistics on Work Engagement	173
6.32	Descriptive Statistics on Stress Coping Resources	174
6.33	Descriptive Statistics on Stressor Agent Factors, Workplace Stress, Stress Coping Resources and Work Engagement Variable	175
6.34	Correlation Results between Stressor Agent Factors, Workplace Stress and Work Engagement	175
6.35	One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test results between personal factors and Irregular working hours of cabin crews	177
6.36	One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test results between personal factors and Work Hassles of cabin crews	180
6.37	One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test results between personal factors and the Aircraft Cabin Environments of cabin crews	183
6.38	One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test results between personal factors and the Social Isolation of cabin crews	187
6.39	One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test results between personal factors and Workplace Stress.	190
6.40	One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test results between personal factors and Work Engagement.	193
6.41	Model Summary: Direct Effect of Stress Agents on Workplace Stress	196

6.42	ANOVA Results: Direct Effect of Stress Agents on Workplace Stress	197
6.43	Coefficients Results: Direct Effect of Stress Agents on Workplace Stress	197
6.44	Model Summary: Workplace Stress and Work Engagement	198
6.45	ANOVA Results: Workplace Stress and Work Engagement	198
6.46	Coefficients Results: Workplace Stress and Work Engagement	198
6.47	Estimate and Significant Value of Stress coping behaviour in relationship between Workplace Stress and Work Engagement	199
6.48	Standardized Estimation (SE) with Direct Effect, Indirect Effect and Total Effect	200
6.49	Results of Goodness of Fit Indices	200
6.50	Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients Results showing Age as a moderator between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress	201
6.51	Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients Results showing gender as a moderator between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress	202
6.52	Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients Results showing marital status as a moderator between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress	203
6.53	Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients Results showing Current Function as a moderator between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress	204
6.54	Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients Results showing experience as a moderator between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress	205
6.55	Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients Results showing age as a moderator between Workplace Stress and work Engagement	207
6.56	Model Summary: Mediating role of Gender in relationship between Workplace Stress and Work Engagement	208
6.57	Model Summary: Mediating role of Marital Status in relationship between Workplace Stress and Employees Engagement	209

6.58	Model Summary: Mediating role of Current Function of the Cabin Crews in relationship between Workplace Stress and Employees Engagement	210
6.59	Model Summary: Mediating role of Experience of the Cabin Crews in relationship between Workplace Stress and Employees Engagement	211
6.60	Estimate Workplace Stress and Work Engagement between low and high stress coping resources	212
6.61	Regression Weights: Estimate Value	213
6.62	Model Summary: Role of Stress Coping Resources in relationship between Workplace Stress and Work Engagement	214
6.63	Stress coping mechanism determinants and key characteristics	222
6.64	Factor Analysis of Stress Coping Mechanism using ABCD Framework	223
6.65	Advantageous factors affecting the determinant issues of stress coping mechanism and its critical constituent elements	226
6.66	Benefit factors affecting the determinant issues of stress coping mechanism and its critical constituent elements	227
6.67	Constraint factors affecting the determinant issues of stress coping mechanism and its critical constituent elements	229
6.68	Disadvantageous factors affecting the determinant issues of stress coping mechanism and its critical constituent elements	230
6.69	Total mean score of Advantageous factors influencing stress coping mechanisms and their CCEs	232
6.70	Total mean score of benefit factors influencing stress coping mechanisms and their CCEs	233
6.71	Total mean score of constraint factors influencing stress coping mechanisms and their CCEs	234
6.72	Total mean score of disadvantageous factors influencing stress coping mechanisms and their CCEs	235
7.1	One-way ANOVA and Independent Sample t-test Results	247
7.2	Simple Linear and Multiple Regression Analysis Results	248
7.3	Structural Equation Modelling Results	249
7.4	Quantitative ABCD Analysis of Stress Coping Mechanism	250

LIST OF CHARTS AND FIGURES

Figure No.	Title	Page No.
3.1	Cognitive activation theory of stress	86
3.2	Karasek Job Strain Model	92
3.3	Transactional Model of Stress	94
3.4	Various Consequences of Stress in Aviation Industry According to Professor Giovanni Costa	100
3.5	Wellbeing Wheel (FSF, 2020)	107
3.6	Proposed Conceptual Model	111
4.1	Histogram showing Normality of Workplace stress	125
4.2	Histogram showing Normality of Work Engagement	125
4.3	Test of Linearity between Stressor Agent and the Workplace Stress	126
4.4	Test of Linearity between the Workplace Stress and Work Engagement	126
4.5	Test of Linearity between Coping Behavior and Work Engagement	127
5.1	The Journey of BLR Airport	136
5.2	Complaints received during the fiscal year 2020-21 by SpiceJet	142
5.3	Number of employees in Indigo	143
5.4	Complaints received during FY 2021 by Indigo	144
5.5	Gender pay gap-Air Asia	145
6.1	Mediating effect of Stress coping behaviour in relationship between Workplace Stress and work engagement	199
6.2	Path Analysis Stressor Agent its impact on workplace Stress leading to Work Engagement	214
6.3	Factors affecting stress coping mechanism as per ABCD Analysis Framework	221
6.4	Graphical Representation of ABCD	236

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AGFI	: Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index
AMOS	: Analysis of Moment Structures
CFA	: Confirmatory Factor Analysis
CFI	: Comparative Fit Index
CSTV	: Chi-Square Test Value
df	: Degree of Freedom
EFA	: Exploratory Factor Analysis
FAO	: Food and Agriculture Organization
FETV	: Fisher's Exact Test Value
GFI	: Goodness-of-Fit Index
RMSEA	: Root-Mean-Square Error of Approximation
SEM	: Structural Equation Modeling
SPSS	: Statistical Package for Social Sciences
VIF	: Variance Inflation Factor
ABCD	: Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages
IWH	: Irregular Working Hour
ST	: Stress At Workplace
WH	: Work Hassles
ACE	: Air-Craft Cabin Environment
SI	: Social Isolation
WE	: Work Engagement
HS	: Highly Significant
S	: Significant
AAI	: Airports Authority of India
DAPB	: Disruptive Airline Passenger Behaviour
FAs	: FAs

NOTATIONS

p-value	: Significance Level
R²	: Coefficient of Determination
B	: Beta Coefficient
t	: t- Statistics
F	: F- Statistics
Z	: Z Test Value
Sig.	: Significant
χ^2	: Chi-Square Test
F	: F- Statistics
H	: Hypothesis
H₀	: Null Hypothesis
H₁	: Alternative Hypothesis
0.01	: 1 % Level of Significance
0.05	: 5 % Level of Significance
N	: Number of Observations
%	: Percentage
MRR	: Multiple Response Rate
Min.	: Minimum
Max.	: Maximum
S.D.	: Standard Deviation
Post Hoc	: Statistics
R	: Correlation
S.E.	: Standard Error
C.R.	: Critical Ratio
S. Estimate	: Standardized Estimate
U. Estimate	: Unstandardized Estimate

CHAPTER-I

INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

India's aviation industry is one of the world's fastest-growing sectors, with an annual growth rate of more than 20%. The Airports Authority of India (AAI) operates 126 airports and civil enclaves in India, out of a 449 airports and airstrips throughout the country. A total of roughly 100 airports/aerodromes handle commercial passenger flights on a daily basis. Moreover, Airfields owned by private companies (or joint ventures) serve the cities of Bengaluru, Delhi, Hyderabad, Kochi, Kolkata, Mumbai, Navi Mumbai, Ahmedabad, Goa, Lucknow, and Mangalore. In 2018, more than 341 million passengers travelled through India's airports. India has the world's third largest domestic civil aviation industry, trailing only the United States and China in terms of size. Because of low flight fares, increased demand for domestic air travel and a continuous high level of tourism, the aviation job market has become a popular entry point for aspirants. Consequently, as a result of increasing demand, the Indian government intends to increase the number of airports to 250 by year 2030 [1]. As aviation is the common model for modern tourism, the efficiency of the airline business depends on the effectiveness of customer services. Aviation customer services perform a variety of roles, including checking in passengers, helping VIP lounge patrons, assisting those in need of ticket information at the counters, running the flight control centre, and controlling luggage and loads, among others[2][3]. The person or group of people in charge of the safety and security of an aircraft, passengers, and each other are referred to as flight attendants, air hostesses, cabin crew, flight stewardesses, or inflight crew. A flight's cabin crew is made up of all the flight attendants [4]. One flight attendant serves 15 to 20 passengers on average per flight, and the demands of the job, which include dealing with pushy or aggressive passengers, long shifts in a small space with little humidity, and exposure to certain levels of contaminants, frequently result in high levels of job stress [5]. In addition to performing customer service tasks like distributing food and beverages, a flight attendant's primary responsibility is to protect the safety of the passengers [5].

Karnataka has five operational airports and among them Kempe Gowda airport in Bangalore and Mangalore airport are two international airports. These airports serve as gateways for tourists arriving in the state. Cabin personnel are crucial in these international flights [6]. They must be aware of any risks to the passengers' safety or health and know how to handle disruptive behaviour [7-9]. The breadth of services and

interactions provided by ground service agents ranges from helping passengers check in at the airport to competing with them for boarding [10]. Also included in their job description were emergency services such as aborted takeoffs, emergency landings, smoke in the cabin, depressurization, dangerous items and spills in the cabin, emergency evacuations, hijackings, water landings, and survival abilities for the sea, jungle, and desert. However, as stated previously, everything comes as a part of package, so with these types of job profile, a number of work-related difficulties like job stress, mental health concerns, and risk factors also come along [4]. The crew experiences isolation and solitude as a result of their inability to maintain consistent social ties both at home and at work due to job demands, such as working with new coworkers on every flight, which can be a great benefit but may also limit opportunities to form a dependable group of colleagues for mutual support [4]. Stress is added on because of lack of social connections and the changing crew composition [4]. High staff turnover, subpar job performance, and risky work practices are all effects of the crews' rising levels of stress [11]. According to a quantitative study of 28,000 employees in 214 different firms in the United States, stress at work can lead to poor performance at work, serious health problems, and staff burnout [3][12]. In spite of numerous studies on stress there is still need of identifying various stressors impacting the work engagement of the cabin crews, which also encourages the researchers to find the suitable measure to reduce the negative consequences of stressors on work engagement.

Stress in Aviation Sector:

The aviation industry is a well-known example of contemporary tourism. The efficiency of the aviation sector is highly dependent on the quality of customer service provided. Aviation customer service is responsible for a wide range of tasks. Airports and airfields serve as the primary locations for employees who engage in aviation customer service. According to various studies, there is a link between rising stress and the work of customer care representatives in the aviation industry. The increase in the crews stress levels has resulted in a large increase in staff turnover, poor job performance, and the adoption of potentially hazardous work behaviours [13-16]. It should be noted that the amount of evidence available to explain why there is such a high level of pressure among airplane customer service workers is insufficient; therefore, additional research should be carried out.

Stressors and Sources of Stress in Cabin Crews:

Stressors are any circumstances, situations, or occurrences that lead you to get anxious or stressed. Stress is encountered by almost all the population whether they are students, a professional, or a member of the family. However, because everyone perceives the world differently, no two people will react to stressors in the same way. There are some who will take this incredibly seriously, while others will reject it as unimportant. A high level of professional knowledge is required in the aviation industry, which is one of the most well-known industries in the world. Considering the amount of stress that comes with working in this profession, it would be an understatement. In theory, everything that requires a response might be considered stressful because it interferes with the ability of the individual to relax. To be clearer on the definition, stress will be described as a physical, mental, or emotional state that is triggered by external or internal stimuli of any kind. It is possible to significantly improve a crewmember's performance by developing a better awareness of the factors that cause stress and how to adapt when faced with stressful conditions. Knowing that various flight crewmembers may react differently to the same stressor is also crucial, as it can assist a flight crewmember in maintaining control of a situation that can quickly spiral out of control if one of the crewmembers has a poor reaction to the same stressor.

It is observed in numerous flight mishaps, including the recent air disaster at Mangalore Airport that stress is the main cause of any mishap in the aviation field. Stress reduction is the most effective treatment, and it is not hard to achieve. When stresses are dealt with by personnel who have received appropriate training, the stress level can be reduced. In this research study, after the data has been analyzed and the study has been able to comprehend the respondents' stress levels as well as the stressors, the researcher will attempt to investigate in depth a variety of relevant cognitive fitness issues that have an impact on the cabin Crews' performance at their place of employment. A variety of stressors related to job and personal traits will be assessed in order to establish the underlying cause of the anxiety. The pressures associated with the aviation industry team will be significantly minimized if they receive appropriate training.

Stress:

The bodily response of an individual to a threat or request is known as stress. This can be advantageous in short gusts, such as when you need to get out of a dangerous situation or hit a target. When stress lasts for a long time, though, it can be harmful to a person's health. Stress can also reduce a person's ability to work. Mental disease has both direct and indirect effects on a person. People are coping with stress, to put it that way. Experts agree that the first step in managing is to identify the stresses and the symptoms that develop following the exposure to these stressors. Creating or maintaining a healthy lifestyle that includes adequate rest, exercise, smart diets, avoiding drinks, and abstaining from tobacco products, among other things, can help you cope with stress.

Strategy:

Strategy, according to the Cambridge dictionary, is "A long-term decision to achieve something or achieve a goal, as well as the ability to carry out and about those plans". Coping as an interaction process between an individual and his environment, defined as the individual's endeavour to meet the demands of the environment in order to make them more bearable and minimize stress and conflict [15]. This indicates that a person's personality qualities and how they handle situations are important elements in determining whether or not they are happy following a stressful or inconsistent conversation. Furthermore, one of the factors that people consider during cognitive evaluation is the amount of time they have to complete the task.

Cabin Crews:

Cabin staffs' primary responsibility is to carry out the orders provided by pilots or co-pilots outside the cockpit. They are also responsible for the safety and comfort of passengers on a flight, and they keep passengers informed as needed. Also, they are responsible for safety of people on the flight, in addition to keeping people informed as required. Male and female flight attendants, often known as air hosts and air hostesses, make up the cabin crew. Cabin crew is chosen in accordance with specific rules established by aviation organizations, as well as the rules established by the Directorate General of Civil Aviation. They're in charge of the space between the cockpit entrance and the back kitchen. Outside the airplane and within the cockpit, the cabin crew is not in charge.

Emotional Labour:

Emotional labor is the process of controlling one's feelings and external behaviours to meet the demands of a work. Staff members are likely to maintain emotional control when interacting with clients, coworkers, and managers. This includes evaluation and judgment in regard to the expression of emotion, whether such sentiments are actual or imagined, as well as its opposite: the repression of those sensations are felt but not expressed. This is done in an effort to elicit a specific feeling from the consumer or client in order to make the company or organization succeed. Further description on emotional labour has been described in this chapter.

Work Engagement:

Work engagement is the term used to describe the happy, content, and productive mental state that employees display and is characterized by ardour, engrossment, and vigour. People who are committed to their occupations typically have a strong sense of enthusiasm, drive, and commitment towards their work. No matter what they do, such employees are said to be tremendously invested in their work. The three main characteristics of work are commitment, vigour, and absorption. When at work, those who are mentally present get deeply ingrained in their positions. The people who work there are the most crucial part of any firm. The company's competitive advantage and success depends on its workforce.

High employee turnover, subpar job performance, and risky work practices are all effects of the crews' rising levels of stress [11]. Flight attendants' spontaneous outbursts of rage or exasperation in response to rude passenger treatment were deemed to be unacceptable business conduct [18]. Lack of emotional control brought on by passengers' unruly behaviour does not translate into excellent business behavior [18]. Employees stress has a negative impact on their health, the effectiveness and safety of aviation, and company productivity [19]. The performance and work engagement of airline ground employees have been significantly influenced by workplace stress [20]. The aviation industry must undertake coping strategy to provide hassle free environment for a well-balanced life of a cabin crews [21]. This study intends to identify various stressors affecting workplace stress to cope up with these stressors for a better working engagement among cabin crews.

1.2 STATEMENT OF RESEARCH PROBLEM

Airports in Karnataka act as gateways for tourists descending on the state. At present, Karnataka has five functional airports at Hubli, Mysore, Belgaum, Mangalore and Bangalore. The Bangalore airport is extremely well connected with the rest of the country. International flights also operate in Bangalore airport. After Bangalore, Mangalore airport has become the second airport in Karnataka to operate flights to international destinations. In these international flights, cabin crews play an important role. While interacting with few of the cabin crews in Mangalore International Airport, they pointed out that even though the cabin crew job seems to be a fascinating job, in reality there is a lot of stress experienced by them. Crew members of an aircraft are on board to ensure passenger safety and comfort. Even if no food or drink is provided, the presence of a minimum cabin crew is required for safety reasons. Cabin crew members must give exceptional customer service while remaining cheery, approachable, and enthusiastic at all times, as well as maintaining a professional look, because they represent the airline's public image. Cabin Crews are a distinct occupational category in many aspects, including their irregular work schedules, peculiar set of job requirements, and distinctive way of life, to name a few. Due to long work schedule, Jet lag, Social Isolation, Work Engagement, Aircraft Cabin Environment etc., cabin crews feel stressed and sometimes causes to burnout. Stress is the factor experienced by the pressure and fatigue of work, which can have a serious impact on both personal and professional life. All these aspects may result to serious issue among the Cabin Crews. In this regard, understanding the root cause of stress, various stressors related to work pressure tends to be crucial. Hence, the primary goal of this research is to identify the elements that cause stress in cabin crew members, as well as the coping techniques that they use to manage their stress.

1.3 IDEAL SOLUTION AND PRESENT STATUS

In the present situation people prefer air travel to reach their destination within a short period of time. These passengers are taken care by the cabin crews in an airplane. They have to look after the comfort of passengers as well as their safety. But, being a cabin crew is not an easy job. It is obvious that cabin crews are well trained to be strong enough to face any situation during a flight. But, after all cabin crews are also human beings. They have emotions, feelings, commitments and also family bondage. Stress is most common among cabin crews. Therefore, the ideal solution is to reduce the stress

to zero in any working condition. But in practice, it is not possible. So, the stress level could be managed when the stressor could be handled by the cabin crews with adequate training given to them.

1.4 NEW RELATED ISSUE

The researcher will try to examine in depth, the other related mental health issues that have an impact on the work of the Cabin Crews. After the data analysis, the researcher will be able to understand the stress rank of the respondents and the stressors. To understand the root cause of the stress, various stressors related to work pressure and personal variables will be measured. By providing appropriate training for cabin crews, an attempt is made to reduce the stressors.

1.5 RESEARCH GAP

Number of studies has been carried out to identify the various problems of airline cabin crews. There are various scholarly articles which shed light on various factors which cause stress among cabin crews. In this review study, the researcher has reviewed numerous research papers/scholarly articles related to airline cabin crew stress. The authors of these papers have pointed out the various problems of cabin crews such as Work Stress & Burnout, Job Satisfaction, Fatigue, Social Loafing, Work Life balance, Physical problems due to stress, Emotional Labor, Work Hassels, Job Demands, Cross-cultural Competence, Job Performance etc. Some authors have also suggested few solutions for Fatigue, Physical Problems, Work Family Interface etc.

But still while going through all these research papers, the researcher has identified the following gap in the studies and this can be used for further research.

1.5.1 The stressors that largely induce stress among cabin personnel are not identified in the studies. The researcher's major goal in this study will be to discover the stressors that create stress among cabin crews.

1.5.2 The researcher has noticed that very few studies on Indian cabin crews have been conducted by Indian authors. This will provide the researcher with the opportunity to conduct a study on Indian cabin crews.

1.5.3 There are no studies on cabin crews who work in International Airports in Karnataka. The researcher has attempted to study the stressors and stress of cabin crews of international airports in Karnataka.

1.5.4 There is also a scarcity of research on the stress coping techniques used by cabin crews. The researcher will concentrate on this topic, studying the coping strategies used by cabin crews to minimize stress and developing a stress coping model that will assist cabin crews in using it when necessary.

1.6 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Due to Long work schedule, Jet lag, Social Isolation, Work Engagement, Aircraft Cabin Environment etc., cabin crews feel stressed and sometimes lead to burnout. Stress is the factor experienced by the pressure and fatigue of work, which can have a serious impact on both personal and professional life. These discussion drives us to formulate the below research questions.

RQ1: What are the various stressor agents contributing to workplace stress among cabin crews?

RQ2: Does work stress have an impact on work engagement?

RQ3: Does workplace stress have influence on the adoption of stress coping resources?

RQ4: Does stress coping resources of cabin crews enhances work engagement?

RQ5: What is the role of stress coping resource between working stress and work engagement among cabin crews?

1.7 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main goal of this study is to understand the stress inducing factors in cabin crews and the various strategies being applied by them to overcome stress. And after studying this, the researcher proposes a new model which cabin crews can apply during the stressful situations. The objectives of the study are:

1. To identify the stressors that contributes to workplace stress among airline cabin crews.
2. To assess the impact of cabin crew workplace stress on their work engagement.
3. To understand the various stress coping mechanism adopted by cabin crews.

4. To ascertain the mediating role of stress coping resource between working stress and work engagement.
5. To recommend the coping behaviours and coping strategies to reduce stress in the aviation industry.

1.8 POSTULATES

Analyzing the impact of various stressor agents on workplace stress effecting work engagement of cabin crews' attempted to assess their relationship between each other. As per Ballard *et al.*, (2006) [33] the stressors such as Isolation during professional travel, a lack of time or energy to fulfill obligations as a mother, partner, and community member, and dealing with unpleasant events causes workplace stress. These emotional and physiological stresses have a significant influence in flight operational performance [32]. Moreover, the studies suggest that crew members with greater experience may be more susceptible to weariness, which is most closely attributable to their age [78]. As a result man tends to put efforts to embrace stress coping strategies at work, reduce the prevalence of particular job stressors, and improve social assistance which is important to boosting the well-being and satisfaction of flight attendants [34]. These studies grabbed the researcher's attention towards various assumptions. Based on previous studies, observations and assumptions 11 postulates have been framed which is stated as follows;

Postulate P₀₁: Cabin crews are into more stress due to their personal factors.

Postulate P₀₂: Personal factors is the main reason for workplace stress among cabin crews.

Postulate P₀₃: Personal factors of the cabin crews highly impact their work engagement.

Postulate P₀₄: Various stressor agents are the reason for workplace stress among cabin crews.

Postulate P₀₅: The work place stress diminishes work engagement among cabin crews.

Postulate P₀₆: Stress coping resources mitigates the negative impact of workplace stress on work engagement.

Postulate P₀₇: Personal factors of the cabin crews has some extent of influence in determining the impact of stressor agents on workplace stress.

Postulate P₀₈: In determining the impact of workplace stress on work engagement, personal factors of the cabin crews has some extent of influence.

Postulate P₀₉: The cabin crews practicing high stress coping resources will reduce will improve the work engagement by reducing the negative consequences of workplace stress.

Postulate P₁₀: Stress coping resources of the cabin crews will show some extent of influence in determining the impact of workplace stress on work engagement.

Postulate P₁₁: Stress at workplace caused due to various stressor agents will reduce the work engagement of the cabin crews.

1.9 HYPOTHESES

The link between the variables is described with a hypothesis. The following hypotheses were framed in light of the aforementioned goals:

H1: The stressor agents of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their personal factors.

H2: The personal factors of cabin crews have significant influence on workplace stress.

H3: Work engagement is significantly different among various personal factors of cabin crews.

H4: Stressor agents have direct effect on workplace stress.

H5: Workplace stress of cabin crews has an impact on work engagement.

H6: Stress coping resources act as a mediator between workplace stress and work engagement.

H7: Personal factors of the employees tends to moderate the relationship between stressor agents and workplace stress.

H8: Personal factors of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between workplace stress and work engagement.

H9: The negative impact of workplace stress on work engagement is low in case of the cabin crews opted for high stress coping resources.

H10: Stress coping resources of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between workplace stress and work engagement.

H11: Stressor agent directly affects the workplace stress which in turn impacts work engagement.

1.10 RELEVANCE OF THE STUDY

Cabin Crew is a highly stressful job especially, when it comes to international flights they must fly between the countries, there are night shifts, they must adjust to the different time zones, disruptive sleep patterns, long flight hours etc. This undoubtedly causes stress among them, even though they might have been trained to adjust to these situations. The body and mind may not cooperate every time. While interacting with few of the cabin crews in Mangalore International Airport they pointed out that even though the cabin crew job seems to be a fascinating job, in reality there is lot of stress experienced by them. Hence, the researcher decided to take up the study on “Stress Inducing Factors and Employees’ Strategies to Reduce it: A Study with Special Reference to Cabin Crews of Selected Indian International Airports”.

1.11 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The scope of the study is explained in three parts

1. Aviation Sector: Cabin Crews of the Airlines (Cabin Service Director, Inflight Manager, Senior Cabin Crews, Junior Cabin Crews, Trainers etc.).
2. Demographic Location Considered: Karnataka has five functional airports at Hubli, Mysore, Belgaum, Mangalore and Bangalore. Mangalore and Bangalore being the first two largest airports in Karnataka have been considered as geographical scope of the study.
3. Airplane Companies Included: Airplane Companies that are available at Mangalore and Bangalore International Airport.

1.12 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. The respondents of the study were selected through personal networks using snowball sampling.
2. Coping behaviour of cabin crews has been addressed in this study, hence it cannot be generally implemented to the whole aviation personnel.
3. Due to security constraints, there were restrictions/protocols to enter airports and meet the cabin crews to distribute the questionnaires. Due to these security protocols the data collection process got delayed.

1.13 LAYOUT OF THE REPORT

This thesis is structured to provide a review of essential information on the theories and models of employee (cabin crew) stress management proposed by famous practitioners and academicians in the aviation industry. The research design, conceptual framework, research objectives, and hypotheses are also presented and examined in detail. The information gathered is examined to give evidence in support of the research goals and hypotheses. The research findings are then used to provide implications that are significant for the assessment of employee stress management in the aviation sector, using factor analysis and discriminant research models. The research is divided into chapters, with the following framework.

Chapter 1: Introduction

It starts with an overview of aviation, then moves onto the definition of different types of stress, sources, its effects and finally to the conception of employee stress management. A multidimensional element of stress management is discussed, as well as the numerous models presented for employee stress management.

Chapter 2: Review of Literature

This chapter quotes earlier research on the subject of stress management in the aviation industry, which is pertinent to the study. After a thorough review of the available literature, a research gap is found.

Chapter 3: Conceptual Framework

This chapter describes various pertinent concepts with the theoretical background. The concepts have been described in detail. Based on the literature review, theoretical background and conceptual framework, the conceptual model has been developed in this chapter.

Chapter 4: Research Design

This chapter emphasizes on the research design, analysis, conceptual framework, sample design (including sample size and sampling method), and questionnaire design for the current study, as well as the questionnaire's validity and reliability. It also goes into the data collection procedures and techniques that were used to interpret the results. Finally, the challenges encountered throughout the survey have been examined, as well as chapters from the thesis and the overall benefits of this study have been discussed.

Chapter 5: Aviation Sector Overview

This chapter presents an overview of India's aviation industry, with a focus on Karnataka and Mangalore. The importance of the aviation sector to the country's economic growth is discussed. Other aviation-related service industries are also examined in terms of progress and contribution to the country's economic development. In addition, the aspects of Human Resource in this sector are examined.

Chapter 6: Data Analysis and Interpretation and Quantitative ABCD Analysis

It is concerned with the use of statistical methods to the collected primary data. It is centered on the aviation industry as well as the answers of cabin crew members. It covers a variety of statistical approaches, as well as their outcomes and interpretations.

As a second part of this chapter quantitative analysis of various Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages (ABCD) of stress coping mechanism has been analyzed. It includes identification of numerous determinant issues and their key attributes which is further analyzed through factor and elementary analysis. In the end of the chapter all the factors affecting determinant issues is calculated quantitatively and presented the results graphically.

Chapter 7: Summary of the Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion

The important findings in the aviation industry with respect to cabin crew are discussed in this chapter. It includes the discriminant scores, extracted components, and a regression model for projection.

CHAPTER-II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Man's desire for innovation prompted him to develop a new means of transportation. This innovation i.e., air transportation turned out to be the most preferred mode of transport. The modern aviation industry is critical to every country's economic success. According to IATA, India has the world's fastest expanding domestic aviation market. It is common knowledge that the aviation industry not only benefits communities and economies all over the world, but also serves as a crucial stimulus for economic growth, social development, and tourism. In an aviation industry the role of cabin crews becomes vital. They are an important part of the airline industry. Cabin safety is a major aspect in an airplane. It also comprises passenger safety and services. In cabin safety the Cabin Crews play an important role and also, they deliver on-board services. As there are lot of work, the level of stress increases, and this work stress affects the physical and mental health of cabin crews. Normally whenever a person is stressed, he/she tries to tolerate it. They use few coping mechanisms to overcome stress. This literature review work is carried out to understand the stressors which causes stress among the cabin crews and the coping techniques they use to overcome work related stress in day today life. The document also provides relevant information about the subject and, by documenting it, can assist future scholars.

2.2 EXPLANATION OF KEYWORDS

2.2.1 Stress:

The bodily response of an individual to a threat or request is known as stress. This can be advantageous in short gusts, such as when you need to get out of a dangerous situation or hit a target. When stress lasts for a long time, though, it can be harmful to a person's health. Stress can also reduce a person's ability to work. Mental disease has both direct and indirect effects on a person. People are coping with stress, to put it that way. Experts agree that the first step in managing is to identify the stresses and the symptoms that develop following exposure to these stressors. Creating or maintaining a healthy lifestyle that includes adequate rest, exercise, smart diets, avoiding drinks, and abstaining from tobacco products, among other things, can help you cope with stress.

2.2.2 Stressor:

Any environment, condition, or event that raises your blood pressure is referred to as a stressor. Each person, whether a student, a professional, or a family member, will almost certainly encounter situations or settings that cause stress. However, due to variances in perception, no two people will react to stressors in the same way. Some people will take this extremely seriously, while others will take it more lightly. The aviation sector is one of the most well-liked industries that necessitate painting abilities. When working in such a field, it's easy to see how severe workplace stress can be. The most common pressures influencing worker organisational engagement are organisational components. In the aviation sector, there are various variables that put the majority of employees under stress. Venture demands, management style, organisational shape, interpersonal relations, technology uncertainty, and so on are examples of such elements.

2.2.3 Stress Coping Strategies:

Strategy, according to the Cambridge dictionary, is “a long-term decision to achieve something or achieve a goal, as well as the ability to carry out and about those plans”[17] described coping as an interaction process between an individual and his environment, defined as the individual's endeavor to meet the demands of the environment in order to make them more bearable and minimise stress and conflict. This indicates that a person's personality qualities and how they handle situations are important elements in determining whether or not they are happy following a stressful or inconsistent conversation. Furthermore, one of the factors that people consider during cognitive evaluation is the amount of time they have to complete the task.

2.2.4 Cabin Crews:

Cabin crews' primary responsibility is to carry out the orders provided by pilots or co-pilots outside the cockpit. They are also responsible for the safety and comfort of passengers on a flight, and they keep passengers informed as needed. Also, they are responsible for safety of people on the flight; in addition to they keep people informed as required. Male and female flight attendants, often known as air hosts and air hostesses, make up the cabin crew. Cabin crew is chosen in accordance with specific rules established by aviation organisations, as well as the rules established by the Directorate General of Civil Aviation. They're in charge of the space between the cockpit entrance and the back kitchen. Outside the aeroplane and within the cockpit, the cabin crew is not in charge.

2.2.5 Work Engagement:

Work engagement refers to the positive, productive, and contented mental state that is exhibited by employees and is marked by zeal, engrossment, and vitality. Employees who are committed to their jobs are frequently passionate, motivated, and deeply invested in their jobs. Such workers are described as being very invested in their work, regardless of what they perform. Work is characterised by three primary traits: dedication, vigour, and absorption. Employees that are mentally present at work develop a strong sense of integration with their jobs. Any organization's personnel are its most important component. Employees provide the company a competitive edge and are essential to its success. Employees who are engaged are a fantastic asset to their company. High levels of work engagement encourage talent retention, boost customer loyalty, and increase the value to stakeholders for domestic and international businesses.

2.2.6 Emotional Labour:

Emotional labour is the process of controlling one's feelings and external behaviours to meet the demands of a work. Staff members are likely to maintain emotional control when interacting with clients, co-workers, and managers. This includes evaluation and judgement in regard to the expression of emotion, whether such sentiments are actual or imagined, as well as its opposite: the repression of those sensations that are felt but not expressed. This is done in an effort to elicit a specific feeling from the consumer or client in order for the company or organisation to succeed. Further description on emotional labour has been described in this chapter.

2.3 REVIEW OF RELATED WORK

Based on the keywords mentioned above, literatures have been categorized into various sects which consists of articles related to workplace stress, stressors, work engagement, stress coping resources, cabin crews and emotional labors. Furthermore, relationship between these variables has been established in the second part of this chapter.

2.3.1 Workplace Stress:

1. Kim, H., Yu, M., & Hyun, S. S. (2022) [22] This research looks at how to improve the work attitude and mental health of "Problem Employees" in the air travel business. Five distinct handling approaches for problem employees were developed based on a study of prior studies: (1) ability-based duty assignment, (2) confidence beliefs,

(3) managerial coaching, (4) human understanding, and (5) mentor system. The study of these five handling approaches has an impact on the employee's work attitude, mental wellbeing and on the performance of their job. Empirical data was obtained from 200 airline crew members to test these hypotheses. According to the study, only three of the five varied management strategies of problem employee i.e. (1) ability-based duty assignment, (2) confidence beliefs, and (3) mentor system approaches had a positive impact on attitudes of workers job, mental wellbeing, and on execution of their duties. On the other side, managerial coaching had a negative impact on outcome factors. The study also revealed that existing industry handling practises had both good and negative effects on problem personnel. As a result of the conclusions of this study, airline businesses must manage problematic employees. Observers should especially need to verify the change in employee attitudes, especially when performing management training. The ramifications of the findings, as well as its limits and future research directions, are highlighted in this study.

2. Dursun, Erdal (2021) [23] People prefer air travel to other modes of transportation because it is faster, cleaner, and more convenient. The fundamental goal of airline firms is to give higher-performing offerings to their consumers and to achieve a long-term strategic advantage. On the one hand, economic progress has raised demand for air travel, while on the other hand, the extension of people's comfort zones has increased demand for air travel. Working employees struggle under this strain since aviation is a difficult industry that requires a tough working environment with both cost and safety issues. Workers experience sadness and burnout as a result of working in such a stressful environment. The time and effort to please people of different ethnicities, personalities, religions, dialects, and other demographic variables by providing good service, passengers waiting for service, insulting passenger taunts, the high probability of emergencies on aeroplanes, very safe evacuation of people in such situations Issues that put flight crews anxious are examples of crucial tasks. Individual and organisational factors contribute to stress, which is experienced differently by everyone. Meanwhile, burnout is viewed as a protracted process that develops as a result of individual and organisational stress factors, progresses slowly, and results in a decrease in employee performance and commitment to the business. Employees in the aviation business, who play an essential part in the industry, get physically and psychologically exhausted owing to the demanding nature of their jobs and the

challenges of working in the service sector. Employees are stressed and burned out as a result of these challenges, which include strong competition, high performance and productivity expectations, time pressure, and an excessive workload. As a result, employee engagement to their firms deteriorates with time. Employee burnout levels may reduce as a result of minimising work stress, and organisational commitment may rise.

3. Ozel, Engin, and Umit Hacioglu (2021) [24] In the present era, flight safety which is emerging as a flight safety hazard in the aviation sector, fatigue necessitates a thorough understanding and critical approach to proactive aviation management procedures. To avoid flight accidents, flight crew stress and weariness must be carefully monitored. Furthermore, stress and exhaustion have an undesirable impact on work satisfaction. The purpose of this study is to investigate the important fatigue risk factors that affect airline pilots' and crews' performance and safety in the aviation business. The association between burnout and job satisfaction sub-dimensions is also examined in this article. To understand this in a better way and with an objective to study this, a factor analysis was carried out by targeting a sample size of 254 international flight crews utilizing the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Survey and the Maslach Burnout questionnaire. The findings point out that (i) Stress and exhaustion affect cockpit and cabin crew teams work execution, (ii) Mental gloom, tension, and personal issues of the cabin crews are the main sources of enthusiastic weariness, (iii) Long flight hours and managing troublesome traveler's increase flight crew exhaustion, and (iv) Individual accomplishment concerns and depersonalization increases fatigue of flight crews.

4. Ihlebæk, C., & Rustad, M. H. (2022) [25] Cabin crew members work in a high-risk environment and acquire health issues such as insomnia, headaches, low back pain, and problems related to the digestive system and exhaustion. Cabin crew individuals who work in a high-risk climate often the victims of health problems which include sleep deprivation, migraines, low back pain, gastrointestinal issues, and fatigue. Musculoskeletal pain (MSP) was a common health issue among female cabin crew in previous investigations. According to the study when compared to male cabin crews normally female cabin personnel had higher degrees of pain in their necks, shoulders, and ankles and feet. Although the number of male cabin crew members has risen in

recent years, few research have looked into gender differences in psychological job stress and musculoskeletal discomfort in this profession. This study was conducted to investigate possible gender differences in psychological distress at work and in musculoskeletal pain (MSP) at one or more locations in cabin crews. In this cross-sectional study, 107 male and 329 female flight attendants from the three major Norwegian airlines answered a questionnaire on work-related psychological demands, control, social support and MSP. The analysis was performed using binary logistic regression models. There were no distinctions in gender differences in PSYJS, yet female cabin crews revealed more significant levels of social help from their companions ($p=0.001$) and nearest supervisors ($p=0.006$). MSP across different locales was accounted for by 70% of respondents. Beside a higher pervasiveness of foot pain among female flight attendants ($p=0.020$), there were no distinctions in sexual orientation in the commonness of single-site or multi-site MSP. Generally single and multi-site MSPs were related with altogether higher risks in both a high burden (33%) and detached (17%) work situation. Finally, notwithstanding the fact that there were little gender differences, both male and female cabin crew individuals detailed a high occurrence of MSP and high PSYJS. Specific consideration ought to be paid to this group to advance a sound psychosocial workplace, with an attention on supporting male cabin crews.

5. Elwezza, M. M., Elbadry, M., & Talaat, N. (2020) [26] Aviation law throughout the world mandates the use of professional cabin crew onboard aeroplanes for passenger safety and convenience. Their primary responsibility is to assure passenger safety as well as comfort. The nature of the cabin crew profession, with its set hours and locations, necessitates a great deal of flexibility on the part of cabin crew. These modifications may have an immediate influence on their current way of life. To cope with the shock of their new occupation, they should establish plans to help them adjust to their new lifestyle. This study looks into cabin crew work stress and how it affects airline costs. This was accomplished through a survey, which was designed as the research's major tool and constructed after a thorough examination of prior theoretical and practical studies on job stress that took into account the opinions of experts in the field. The field research is carried out with cabin crew from three distinct companies, each representing a different airline type (Scheduled, Low cost, Charter). A total of 157 surveys were sent out to the various types of airlines. After removing the invalid forms,

a total of 106 surveys were examined. The requisite percentages and frequency tables were calculated in order to meet one of the most important descriptive statistical procedures in identifying and describing the study variables as well as their frequency rates within the drawn sample. Workplace stress raises airline expenses by raising sick leave rates reported by cabin crew, which has a detrimental impact on flight operations, according to the findings of the study. Furthermore, training is proven to be a significant expenditure in airlines, as it is necessary for cabin staff to handle work stress.

6. Kedar, S. G., & Ujjain, S. (2020) [4] This paper reports on a stress study conducted among female cabin crew members working for an international airline. The female cabin crew members are from India and other parts of the world, and they work for an international airline that is part of a multinational corporation based in the United Kingdom (UK). A total of 100 women were included in the study's sample size. The respondents' ages range from 25 to 50 years old, and they come from a variety of races. In this case, a technique called "purposive sampling" was applied. The 'Stress, Strain, and Coping Styles among Airhostesses' measure was developed to investigate the factors that influence female cabin crew stress. Stress has been discovered to have an equal impact on all cabin crew members, regardless of how regular the feelings are. It's also assumed that everyone feels stretched in the same way, regardless of how regular the experience is. This paper provides a good overview of occupational stress and can be used by working professionals to assess their own stress levels.

7. Suthatorn, P. (2019) [27] The authors of this study wanted to see how cross-cultural competence (CC) helps airline cabin workers reduce workplace stress when dealing with guests from other cultures, as well as how cultural distance between airline cabin crews and foreign passengers influences the interaction. The study used cultural distance as a moderator of the link between cross-cultural ability and airline cabin crew job stress. The information was gathered through a poll of 208 international airline cabin employees in Thailand. The partial least squares regression analysis revealed that airline cabin personnel with high cross-cultural competency had decreased workplace stress while serving foreign guests. Furthermore, the findings from the moderating effect revealed that when cabin staff with better cross-cultural competence engaged with foreign passengers whose culture was significantly different from their own, stress levels tended to be lower. The findings of the study had practical implications for

the aviation sector. To reduce their stress, airline cabin personnel required to learn cross-cultural competency. Even while airline cabin attendants frequently contact with foreign passengers, this does not imply that they have a high level of cross-cultural competency to effectively handle intercultural situations.

8. Salwa Al Majali & Zuhrieh Shana (2019) [28] This was the first study to look at the psychological stress levels and sources of work-related stress among flight crews. The study also looked at how crew members deal with stress and examined the data based on several factors. The study included 226 crew members, including (73 pilots, 66 men, and 7 women) with an average age of 45 and a mean work experience of 20 years, and (153 flight attendants, 53 men, and 100 women) with an average age of 26 and a mean practical experience of (4) years working for Royal Jordanian Airlines. To improve this study, two scales were used: causes of work stress and skills for dealing with psychological stress. Face value, structural value, difference value, and the Cronbach's-alpha coefficient test were used to produce these scales, which are regarded to be reliable for the purposes of this study. According to the data, crew members' perception of stress at work is average (74.33 percent), job creates high pressure (11.50 percent), and they do not feel stressed in relation to work (14.15 percent). Surprisingly, men are more likely than women to feel stressed at work, and less experienced crew members reported higher stress levels. The most widely used approaches for dealing with psychological stress, according to the study, are cognitive skills, and interpersonal skills. Nevertheless, utilisation of these skills was below average, with avoidance skills being the least used.

9. Omolayo, Idowu Grace (2018) [29] The intention is to look at the impact of business-related weight on the exhibition of flight experts. (Take, for instance, the Nigeria Airspace Administration Agency (NAMA)). The review was led with the help of representatives of Murtala Muhammed International Airport (MMIA), Lagos, on the grounds that the air terminal has exceptional attributes of solid traffic, making the air terminal's staff experience the ill effects of business-related pressure. As per the discoveries, (i) Working environment stress essentially affects the family lives of both male and female laborers, (ii) Stress is advantageous to work development and usefulness, (iii) It impressively affects business related pressure (Job Struggle) and occupation execution. As per the review, business related pressure (home-interface

strain and position struggle) considerably affects work execution as well as work execution. According to the findings, the corporation should foster a positive organisational atmosphere for all employees rather than relying on power/autocracy and money to manage administrative behaviour and provide possibilities for achievement and development for those who work for the device.

10. Mumtaz, Syed Hammad (2017) [30] In today's world, mental health is a very essential problem. Every member of the aviation business is subjected to some form of stress that can put them both psychologically and physically to the test. The focus of this thesis is on cabin crew, who are typically overlooked in studies. The primary purpose of this thesis is to determine the levels of stress experienced by Emirates Airlines cabin crew. The data was collected using a triangulation research method. A stress survey was performed to provide quantitative results, which contained specific stress components to assess the participants' degree of stress. Interviews with cabin personnel were also undertaken as part of a qualitative approach. The study's findings revealed that Emirates Airlines cabin crew members are under a lot of stress, with rostering procedures being one of the most stressful areas. Following this study's examination of stress levels and mental health impacts, Emirates Airlines should seriously consider improving mental health awareness among their personnel, particularly cabin crew. It's difficult to specify exactly what a mental health issue is, but after performing this research, it appears that there are a number of significant aspects that can have a significant impact on cabin crews' lifestyle.

11. Omholt, M. L., T. H. Tveito, and C. Ihlebæk (2017) [31] In the recent years, the European non-military personnel aviation business has modified definitely. Notwithstanding this, little is known with respect with the impacts of business-related pressure and emotional wellbeing objections on Norwegian pilots. The objective of this study is to investigate the associations between business related pressure, self-adequacy in Norwegian business aircrew, as well as the incongruities among cockpit and crew team. Aircrew individuals from Norway's three significant carriers were sent a web poll. The connection between business related pressure, self-viability, and subjective health complaints was inspected utilizing direct relapse examination. 21% of those asked answered. Exhaustion, rest issues, bulging, low back agony, migraines, and neck uneasiness were the most widely recognized emotional wellbeing side effects among

the 843 review members. Lodge team revealed undeniably more subjective health complaints counts, prevalence, and mean qualities than cockpit group. In total, 20% of those surveyed revealed being under a ton of stress. Business related pressure was emphatically related to all SHC factors in all gatherings. The connection among stress and mental sicknesses in pilots and lodge group, was somewhat alleviated by self-adequacy. The model made sense of 23 and 32 percent of the difference in cockpit and crew group mental troubles separately. The investigation discovered that business aircrew in Norway detailed countless subjective health complaints, and that elevated degrees of business-related pressure were connected to countless subjective health complaints. More examination on physical, authoritative and psycho-social troubles is expected to give a solid working environment to cockpit and crew staff.

12. Alam, Muhammad Aftab (2016) [16] Mechanical headways in the aviation business work on yield while additionally expanding pressure. The objective of this study is for the author to make sense of the connection between technological pressure and team usefulness in the flight business, as well as the collaboration impact of job over-burden and value responsiveness in this relationship. The review saw three kinds of techno-stress: techno-complexity, techno-uncertainty, and techno-overload, and observed that as the group turned out to be more job over-burden and value touchy, their negative connection with team efficiency developed further. Members in the review were picked aimlessly from the flight business. The review found that in the aeronautics business, techno-stress and team usefulness are conversely related, and that this relationship fortifies when groups are overburdened with numerous obligations, as well as when they are exposed to biased treatment and become value touchy. The fundamental utility of bringing down group efficiency as an element of job over-burden and value awareness is clear in that it might help with making informed decisions about how to oversee flying usefulness. Since new innovations in versatility, mechanization, and independent direction give the essential useful potential, new techno-stress repositories are required.

13. Maymand, M. M., Shakhshian, F., & Hosseiny, F. S. (2012) [32] There are various aspects involved in having a safe and reliable flight, with the human factor being the most crucial. A man is constantly confronted with a variety of situations that bring him stress. Using a quantitative and qualitative approach, this paper examines the impact of

emotional, physiological, and environmental stress on airline flight performance. In terms of the specialised research questionnaire, the statistical population of the study includes all of Kish-Air Airlines' pilots, co-pilots, flight engineers, teaching pilots, and flight attendants, a total of roughly 400 people. In order to calculate the research sample size, a sample of 30 people is randomly selected from the statistical population. This questionnaire was created using the Likert 5 scale multiple-choice format. Structural Equation Modeling/Path Analysis was utilised to analyse data collected from the questionnaire, and the software used to analyse the data was LISREL 8.5 and SPSS 18. The Cronbach's Alpha technique was used to determine the study's dependability. We may assess the importance of each element using statistical and contextual analysis. The findings suggest that emotional and physiological stress have a significant influence in flight operational performance; however, the impact of environmental stress on flight operational performance is not shown in this case study.

14. Ballard, T. J., et al. (2006) [33] Despite the fact that working as a flight attendant can be difficult, stressful, and disruptive, little study has been conducted on the psychological health implications of this career. The impression that flight attendants' mental health is a problem was addressed in qualitative research of a sample of flight attendants in Italy. Isolation during professional travel, a lack of time or energy to fulfil obligations as a mother, partner, and community member, and dealing with unpleasant events are all workplace pressures. The researchers investigated the relationships between work-related risk factors and self-perceived health that was less than "good" and psychological distress among Italian female flight attendants. The authors conducted a cross-sectional survey on physical and mental health among 1955 past and present flight attendants using a postal questionnaire. A GHQ-12 score of six or above indicated that more current flight attendants than previous flight attendants had fair to poor self-perceptions of health and psychological pain. Current flight attendants who indicated fair to poor health were more likely to express job dissatisfaction and recent passenger sexual harassment. Low job satisfaction and frequent dispute with a partner over childcare were found to be associated with psychological distress. Current flight attendants reported greater levels of fair to poor subjective health, as well as psychological distress, which was linked to job characteristics and family difficulties. Perceived poor health has been connected to mortality, high job strain, and early retirement in the literature, whereas psychological discomfort has been linked to work

absenteeism. The effect of sexual harassment on flight attendants' perceived health may be relevant to other professional women who interface with the public. The health consequences of family/work conflicts, low job satisfaction, and sexual harassment among working women in various occupations should be studied further using qualitative and quantitative methods.

15. MacDonald, Leslie A., et al. (2003) [34] The researchers wanted to know if flight attendants (FAs) experienced chronic job stress and if there were any correlations between these stressors, psychological discomfort, and job discontent. 73 female flight attendants from two major airlines answered a detailed questionnaire. Standard questionnaires and scale measurements were used to assess job stresses, psychological discomfort, and job discontent. The association between job stress and these outcomes was investigated using multiple regression analysis. With the exception of tiredness, distress and work unhappiness were moderate to low. Job stressors were found to have a substantial impact on these outcomes after controlling for individual variables. Despite moderate-to-low levels of discomfort and dissatisfaction, tailored actions to alleviate specific job pressures and boost social support may be significant steps toward improving FAs' well-being and satisfaction. After controlling for individual factors, the findings of this study indicate that chronic job stressors such as high mental and/or psychological job demands, imbalance between job demands and outside obligations, low supervisor support, and motional load have a significant impact on psychological distress, perceived stress, and job dissatisfaction among flight attendants. Despite mild to moderate levels of discomfort and dissatisfaction, targeted actions to minimise controllable occupational stressors have the potential to significantly improve flight attendants' well-being and happiness. These data can also be used to assist determine the content and design of future studies on the stress of flight attendant jobs. These studies should record the expected fluctuating levels of psychological discomfort and occupational stress so that appropriate amounts of employee assistance can be determined.

16. Homan, Willem J. (2002) [35] Stress has always been a component of human biology and is necessary for survival. It's actually our body's natural "fight or flight" response, which allows us to react quickly to a threat. Our bodies go into high gear and mobilize for action when we perceive a threat. Stress, in reality, provides the spark that

the body requires to improve performance. One of the most distinguishing characteristics of stress is that it is self-inflicted, and the individual's response to the stressor is what matters. This research examines the present stress management literature and methods in a selective manner. The author offers tactics that commercial pilots might use to deal with stressful occurrences in the often-difficult flight environment, and lays the groundwork for future empirical study in the domain of human stress control in aviation settings. Sport psychology and management training programmes are used to examine stress management skills. The terms stress and distress are defined first, and then the physical, physiological, and emotional responses to stress are discussed. Following that, the biology of stress is examined. After considering traditional strategies of stress avoidance, the concept of stress hardiness is identified. Stress resistance training is positioned within the context of the overall stress experience through the use of a holistic management technique customized to the aviation environment. Finally, the Air Line Pilots Association's Critical Incident Response Program, which assists commercial pilots who have experienced emotional work-related traumas, is described.

17. Marks, Melanie, William Yule, and Padmal de Silva (1995) [36] Six cabin crew members who survived an airline disaster that killed 47 people were evaluated for posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and other mental health issues. Each was interviewed eight months after the crash and given questionnaires to complete that measured intrusive thoughts, avoidance, depression, anxiety, and terror. Ten months later, the questionnaires were re-administered. All cabin crews had PTSD, experienced a wide range of symptoms, and developed a fear of flying 8 months after the incident, according to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-III-Revised (DSM-III-R). 18 months after the collision, depression scores were normal, but all other measures remained unchanged, indicating a high level of traumatic stress. The three most senior members of staff with the most responsibilities on board, who had also experienced the most serious physical injuries, expressed the highest levels of distress.

18. Porter, P. (1988) [37] Work Schedule Stress among female South African Airways cabin attendants (CAs) was researched, as well as its link to health factors among CAs. Work Schedule Stress, in particular, was hypothesized to be a significant stressor for CAs and to be inversely associated to health indicators. Potency, Trait Anxiety, Trait Anger, and Social Support were also postulated as moderators of the link between Work

Schedule Stress and health factors. A total of 108 local and 43 international crew members were surveyed. Interviews and self-report inventories were used to collect data in two periods. The interview data were used in a qualitative study, but they were also content-analysed on a variety of dimensions and combined with the quantitative data from the questionnaire. The qualitative analysis, which was based on the grounded theory technique, was the research's backbone. To investigate moderator effects, the quantitative data were subjected to correlational analysis, which was augmented by subgroup analysis. Working Hours Stress has been shown to be a key stressor for CAs, with negative health consequences. The findings did not support the idea of moderating effects. Conclusions were formed, and recommendations for ways to improve wellbeing were provided to the SAA and CAs, as well as proposals for further research.

19. Bassett, Jack R., and Robert Spillane (1987) [38] In this study, 28 cabin crew members were divided into two teams and assigned to fly from Sydney to Los Angeles and back, with pauses in Los Angeles lasting 58 and 82 hours, respectively. Every urine sample was collected over a nine-day period, beginning two days before the trip. The volume and time the sample was passed were used to determine urinary cortisol secretion rates. The mood of the subjects was assessed on a scale of 0 to 9 at the same time the urine sample was taken. A control group was included in the study for comparison, and they were matched for age, sex ratio, and degree of manual labour revolved in their work but not revolved with the flights. Based on urine cortisol excretion rates, crews in Sydney before the trip and in Los Angeles were more stressed than the control group. Urine cortisol excretion rates were significantly greater in Sydney before the flight, Los Angeles, and on the return flight, but not on the way out. The increased excretion rates prior to travel were related to anxiousness, but the heightened levels in Los Angeles and on the return trip were connected to a circadian rhythm disruption. A component analysis of mood ratings revealed three significant variables indicating vitality, distress, and relaxation. According to the analysis of variance, the mood ratings showed significant changes during the course of the tour of duty for 13 of the 14 moods.

2.3.2 Stressors:

After elaborating various articles on stressors, it is further categorised into work hassles, irregular working hours, social isolation and aircraft cabin. The articles have been categorised based on these sub-headings.

20. Castro, M., Carvalhais, J. and Teles, J. (2015) [39] According to this study, in addition to their workload and particular environmental factors, flight attendants may experience irregular work schedules that interfere with their circadian rhythms and negatively affect their sleep, energy, health, social and family lives, and performance- which is essential to the safety and security of flight operations. This study concentrated on the irregular work schedules of the cabin crew as a cause of fatigue symptoms in a Portuguese airline under wet lease. It determined the tasks that the cabin staff must complete, whether they adhered to schedules and adequate rest breaks are fatigue-causing agents, and whether the cabin crew members exhibit signs of exhaustion. Despite the sample's good qualities, the research in this study showed that the aircraft cabin crew experienced weariness and the associated health issues. Women and older workers are particularly impacted. This study made recommendations for managing the danger of weariness, including work organisation, programmes for education and awareness raising, and particular preventative actions.

21. Rajaveraja, Sanni (2019) [40] The goal of this thesis is to have a better knowledge of the two occupational health concerns that flight attendants face: stress and tiredness. Cabin crew employment can be stressful because of the continually shifting work hours, mismatched day rhythms, and rapidly changing events that require the crew to respond swiftly. These circumstances make the job difficult, and the crew's competence is crucial to the passengers' safety and security. The focus of this research is on how flight attendants in their early careers deal with stress and exhaustion, and what strategies they use to retain a sense of balance in their lives. The goal is to help new cabin staff workers adjust to their new job more quickly. In autumn 2019, the study was conducted as a qualitative research project, with five cabin crew members at the start of their careers being interviewed. For data gathering, semi-structured thematic interviews were used. The data was then analysed using transcriptions of the recorded interviews. No statistical conclusions can be drawn from the data due to the small number of interviewees. The findings suggest that new flight attendants have adjusted well to their new careers, despite the lifestyle adjustments that have come with them. There had been very little stress and little exhaustion among the flight attendants. However, the findings led to sleeping problems, as well as a greater need for rest. On layovers, figuring out the best sleeping schedule for oneself and allowing adequate time for rest on free days could be advantageous. Nonetheless, the cabin crew members demonstrated that they

were learning about stress and exhaustion, and that they were employing a variety of risk-mitigation measures. This is a promising sign of a good training, but the data also indicated that the training programme was stressful. As a result, this conclusion might be investigated further. Trainees' performance may be harmed by excessive stress levels.

22. Chen, Ching-Fu, and Shu-Chuan Chen (2014) [41] Cabin crews are vital to an aircraft's cabin safety wellbeing execution, and they can possibly increase air travel security and reduce travellers' concerns. This study plans to analyse the causal connections between "work requests," "work assets," and cabin crew wellbeing rehearses in light of the restricted writing dedicated to cabin crews related research. Utilizing underlying condition displaying, information from a study of 339 airline cabin crews working for Taiwanese foreign airlines were examined. A variety of fit indices validated the overall model fit, and all of the model's routes were statistically significant. When the job demands resource model is used, the results demonstrate a negative association between "job demands" and "cabin crew safety behaviours," but "job resources" are positively associated with "upward safety communication," "in-role," and "extra-role" safety behaviours. The findings are discussed in terms of their relevance to practitioners and future study.

23. Ezzat, Hesham M., et al. (2015) [42] Neck pain is regarded as a major health issue in today's society. Several prior research have discovered that particular vocations are linked to this condition or increase the likelihood of having it in the future. Although mechanical elements are to blame for the pain, it can develop into a significant problem and produce other unusual symptoms like vertigo, headaches, and migraines. The goal of this study was to find out how common neck pain is among Saudi Airlines' cabin staff. During authors travels to King Fahad Airport, a cross-sectional study was conducted using questionnaires and measurements of many metrics on the available Saudi Airlines cabin personnel. Neck Discomfort Questionnaires were supplied to Saudi Airlines cabin workers, and all study participants completed assessment sheets to determine the prevalence and distribution of neck pain. All of the subjects underwent a physical therapy assessment of neck motions in various directions as well as particular tests to identify any problems. The prevalence of neck pain among cabin staff was determined using these data. The collected data was statistically evaluated using SPSS

software, which calculated the questionnaire's mean, median, and score. According to the study's scoring system, 31 (30.09 percent) of 105 Saudi Airlines cabin crew members suffered neck pain. As per the aftereffects of strategic relapse examination, the review showed a connection between this occupation and neck agony, and that this occupation is the main huge component that influences the positive pressure test. The commonness of neck torment among Saudi Airlines crew team individuals was underscored. The information show that neck inconvenience is normal among concentrate on members, with most of cases following a constant long-winded example. More exploration is expected to get familiar with the drawn-out course of neck torment, as well as its bigger ramifications and effects.

24. Henning, Sanchen (2015) [43] This article looks at the health of a few employees of a South African airline's cabin crew. The aircraft business exposes cabin crew to a variety of potential environmental stressors. The goal of the study was to look at the well-being of cabin crew members as well as the stressors they face in the workplace. Cabin crew play an important role as primary safety officers on board an aeroplane. Cabin crew must be in top physical and mental shape in order to give world-class hospitality to passengers. The study's framework was based on a systems theoretical perspective. This method resulted in a detailed description of the person-environment interactions. The type of inquiry chosen was qualitative research, and purposeful sampling fit the study's premise. A total of 12 semi-structured face-to-face interviews with cabin crew members were conducted at their offices. The content analysis was divided into three stages, each of which became increasingly sophisticated and abstract as it progressed. The researcher created 18 coding categories during the first-order study. The second-order analysis is the following step, which identifies eight pattern categories that describe the relationships between the coding categories. Finally, the third-order analysis provides a conceptual analysis, demonstrating how the various coding and pattern categories were merged and how they connect to systemic epistemology's generic notions. The study's findings revealed that the pressures faced by cabin crew are all related to the interruption of personal significant regularities or patterns. It appears that as humans, we have a need for some predictability and regularity in our lives, a sense of "lawfulness." Circadian cycles, interpersonal interactions, and cultural traditions are all altered as a result of aircraft cabin crew's itinerant lifestyle. Recommendations for intervention techniques were provided based

on the findings. Cabin crews were given psycho-educational training and limited flying durations to reduce the long-term consequences on their physical and mental well-being.

25. Signal, T. Leigh, et al. (2013) [44] Determine the amount and quality of sleep that the flight crew can get while flying, as well as the elements that influence their sleep. Flight groups from Everett, Washington, and Asia had their sleep polysomnographically checked for one night in a layover hotel and a 7-hour in-flight rest opportunity on flights averaging 15.7 hours. A layover hotel and in-flight crew rest facilities are available on the Boeing 777-200ER aircraft. The flight crew consists of 21 personnel (11 Captains, mean age 48 yrs. and 10 First Officers, mean age 35 yrs.). Actigraphy and polysomnography were employed to capture sleep during the tour of duty in a layover hotel and along the road. The factors influencing in-flight sleep were determined using a mixed model analysis of covariance. The layover hotel provided better sleep (70 percent vs. 88 percent), as well as greater nonrapid eye movement Stage 1/Stage 2 and awakenings per hour (7.7 vs. 4.6). During the flight, there was very little slow wave sleep (median 0.5 percent). When sleep opportunities presented themselves during the first half of the flight, less time was spent attempting to sleep and less sleep was obtained. Age appears to be the most consistent predictor of in-flight sleep time and quality, according to multivariate research. This study found that even while sleeping for extended periods of time, in-flight sleep is of worse quality than sleep on the ground. With longer flight times, the importance of in-flight sleep, in terms of quality and recovery for flight safety is expanding. Given that an age limit for flight crew members is being explored, the impact of age on sleep quantity and quality must be evaluated.

26. Houston, Stephen, Karen Dawson, and Sean Butler (2012) [45] In this study, the respondents discussed their experience with voluntary fatigue reporting among pilots and cabin personnel. This was a prospective study conducted inside one airline to investigate the crude incidence rate and principal reason for Fatigue Report Form submission among cabin workers and pilots. All crew duties were scrutinized at the 'roster construction' stage to ensure compliance with fatigue control procedures. The airline's medical officer reviewed files to determine the most common cause of weariness, which was then categorised into one of five categories. The frequency and proportion of reports within each category were determined. The crude incidence rate of tiredness report submission for pilots and cabin crew was 103 and 68 cases per 1000

people per year, respectively. The rostered duty pattern was recognised as the most important element in 27% of responses. 24 percent of the reports were due to roster interruptions, 17% to problems with layover accommodations or transportation, 23% to a domestic issue, and 9% to no obvious cause or were considered invalid. A sub analysis of the 'domestic' category discovered that commuting to or from work was the key cause in half of the cases. The number and pattern of reports received each month can be used to identify previously identified tiredness risks and suggest areas for improvement. Through fatigue reports, individual crewmembers can provide vital information on 'whole-of-life' tiredness hazards both inside and outside the workplace.

27. Chung, Chi-Ti, and Ue-Lin Chung (2009) [46] Quality of life is a hot topic in the medical field right now. Several studies have linked shift work to poor health and a lower quality of life. However, data on the quality of life of female flight attendants is limited. The goal of this study was to look into the quality of life and related aspects among female flight attendants who work on international routes, including demographics, work status, exhaustion, sleep quality, and family function. A cross-sectional research design was adopted in this study. The Aviation Medical Center gave a sample of 207 people on purpose. The questionnaire includes the Multidimensional Assessment of Fatigue, the Chinese version of the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index, the Family Apgar Index, and the Taiwanese version of the WHOQOL-BREF. The participants' average holistic quality of life score was 54.49 (SD=6.48), which is considered high intermediate. The psychological domain had the lowest mean score, while the physical health domain had the highest mean score. Religion, drug usage, work status, job stress, job passion, weariness, sleep quality, and family function all explained 34.2 percent of the variance in holistic quality of life, according to the findings of a hierarchical multiple regression analysis using the entry procedure. After controlling for demographics, the study discovered that three variables, weariness, sleep quality, and family function, accounted for 21.3 percent of the variation in overall quality of life. Healthcare practitioners should include exhaustion, sleep quality, and family function when planning future health promotion and disease prevention programmes for female flight attendants.

28. Nesthus, Thomas E., et al. (2007) [47] The Transportation and Treasury and Independent Agencies Bill of Appropriations includes a directive to the Federal Aviation Administration to perform a study on flight attendant fatigue (House Rpt. 108-671). The CAMI Fatigue Countermeasures Group at NASA's Ames Research Center

was tasked with conducting the research (FCG). This paper covers a review of the literature on fatigue as it may be experienced by flight attendants, an examination of actually utilised (real vs. scheduled) flight attendant duty schedules, and a comparison of these schedules to the current CFRs in order to achieve the study's objectives. The report also examines data from the Aviation Safety Reporting System (ASRS) and the National Transportation Safety Board on fatigue-related incidents and accidents (NTSB). One section of the article discusses how three separate performance and tiredness models were used to investigate how flight attendant duty schedules lead to escalating levels of weariness and expected changes in performance. The report concludes with six recommendations for future research, including: (1) Field Operations Survey. To ascertain the frequency with which persons experience fatigue, the circumstances under which it occurs, and the consequences that ensue; (2) Extensive study of incident reports (3) Fatigue Effects Field Research to better understand the facts of the issue to research the physiological and cognitive consequences of tiredness, drowsiness, circadian factors, and rest regimes on flight attendants. (4) Fatigue Assessment Model Validation (5) Review of International Carrier Policies and Practices: This is a critical stage in assessing whether and how models can be utilised in conjunction with field operations. (6) Training; to learn how other countries deal with these problems and what outcomes they achieve; and to learn how other countries deal with these problems and what outcomes they accomplish. FAs would benefit from learning more about fatigue, its origins and consequences, its association with circadian disruption, and how and when to deploy countermeasures (e.g., scheduled naps, physical activity, social interaction, caffeine).

2.3.2.1 Work Hassles:

29. Tatiana PhD, Filipieva (2009) [48] The aviation industry has spent a lot of money and time over the years trying to figure out how to limit the number of plane crashes, but they still happen, and airlines must learn to identify the unique requirements of those who survive or witness an accident, especially crew members. After any plane tragedy, the media focuses on the pilots, who are ultimately accountable for flight safety, but the cabin crew members receive far less attention. The FA's names are never mentioned in the media. Meanwhile, the FA maintains communication with passengers on board an aeroplane and is responsible for their safety and even life. Flight attendants who are directly or indirectly involved in airline crashes, hijackings, turbulence

occurrences, and other situations are at risk of suffering severe emotional stress. A critical event is an element of aviation's extreme vocations. Despite the efforts of the aviation industry to assist in the aftermath of a plane crash, post-traumatic stress disorder remains one of the most misunderstood and overlooked disorders that can affect a person. The writers of the paper, which is based on the findings of Russian and American aviation psychologists, attempt to address the following questions: How does post-traumatic stress effect cabin crew performance and the lives of flight attendants? How may early warning physical, emotional, and behavioural indicators be identified? What can be done to mitigate the detrimental impact of disaster-induced emotional injury on flight attendants' work and lives? How can we provide more effective psychological care to help people recover from emotional trauma?

30. Shao, Pei-Chi, Jin-Ju Yen, and Kung-Don Ye (2008) [49] The extent to which the flight crew can contribute to flight safety is determined by their ability to perform their tasks properly. Before they can carry out their next mission, the flight crew needs to get enough rest. If they sense mental and physical exhaustion as a result of their employment, not only will they be unable to deliver proper cabin services, but their awareness of anomalous events and response capacity will be harmed, posing potentially lethal hazards to flight safety. The purpose of this study is to assess cabin crew fatigue levels before and after flights on specific domestic carriers, as well as to look at cabin crews' subjective impressions of fatigue. The differences are then analysed to see how fatigue perception levels change before and after flights. The subject of the investigation was a specific domestic airline. In this study, the University Rene Descartes Exhaustion Scale and the Airbus Industry Fatigue Scale were utilised to assess cabin crew fatigue levels. Furthermore, this study investigates the elements that influence the arousal level of the cabin crew. In this study, the dependent variables are "arousal level before duty," "arousal level after duty," and "arousal level difference between before and after duty," whereas the independent variables are other conceivable factors. After that, a cross-analysis is performed to better understand the factors that influence cabin crew weariness.

31. Rhoden, Steven, Rita Ralston, and Elizabeth M. Ineson (2008) [50] The goal of this research is to raise awareness about concerns about cabin crew training in order to control disruptive airline passenger behaviour (DAPB). In-depth semi-structured

interviews with flight and cabin personnel, as well as trainers, were performed. The primary data was structured using template analysis. The majority of training courses were found to be too short, lacking in reality, and unable to cater for varied learning styles. Although longer and more frequent training courses better prepared cabin crew to deal with DAPB, there is no substitute for on-the-job experience, which enhances practical knowledge and skill application, and hence confidence. The importance of training to defuse and de-escalate DAPB has been highlighted in order to increase travel safety and security and alleviate tourism concerns.

32. Pollock, Neal W (2005) [51] Because atmospheric pressure decreases as altitude rises, hypoxia, or oxygen shortage, becomes a hazard for aircraft. The effects of low-grade hypoxia are frequently mild, and both flight crews and passengers may miss them. When high-profile incidents occur, the most severe consequences are generally recognised. After Payne Stewart, a professional golfer, and five other people were killed on October 25, 1999, when a Learjet flew for four hours on unmonitored autopilot before running out of fuel and crashing in South Dakota, the international community was shaken. After the aircrew acknowledged clearance to an altitude of 11900 meter's, radio contact was lost (39000 ft). The crew was rendered unconscious as a result of insufficient supplemental oxygen delivery following a loss of cabin pressurization, according to the accident report. The physics and physiology of hypoxia are discussed in this paper, as well as cabin pressurization and the health impacts of normal cabin pressure and unscheduled depressurization.

33. Ballard, T. J., et al (2004) [18] Identifying probable sources of psychological stress at work in order to develop relevant questionnaire items for a cross-sectional health research of 3000 Italian female flight attendants, as well as eliciting opinions on how to improve survey participation. Three focus groups of 6-7 participants each were used in this qualitative study, as were six in-depth individual interviews with 26 present and past female flight attendants. The discussion included topics such as the positive and negative aspects of the job, relationships with coworkers, bosses, and passengers, perception of occupational risk for serious diseases, work-family compatibility, and experiences with work-related stress and its impact on health. Emerging themes connected to risk factors for mental health problems were discovered using a transcript-based analysis of focus groups and interviews. The participants ranked mental health as their top concern. Several work-related risk factors, such as sadness and anxiety,

have been recognised as potentially being associated to negative outcomes. Isolation and loneliness were among them, as were anxieties of being insufficient wives and moms as a result of job obligations, passenger interactions, and employers' lack of protection from professional hazards and abusive passengers. The data was used to create a mental health module for the health survey questionnaire, which included questions about a history of severe depression or anxiety, suicidal ideation or attempt, substance abuse, workplace sexual harassment, social support, leisure activities, relationship with a partner, and role as a mother. The construction of relevant questionnaire items for a cross-sectional epidemiological research of female flight attendants was made possible by the use of qualitative methodologies to identify work-related sources of psychosocial stress. More qualitative research may be needed to contextualize the findings of the cross-sectional study and to evaluate measures or methods for preventing work-related health risks highlighted by the survey.

34. Brown, Norman M., and Charles R. Moren (2003) [52] For efficient guidance in business flight activities, good and successful communication between flight deck and cabin crew members is necessary. This type of clear and effective communication is required not only between these two elements, but also between flight crew members and other outside performers such as air traffic controllers and aircraft dispatchers. Several events and numerous deadly accidents have occurred as a result of the breakdown of the information transfer mechanism. To increase communication throughout flight functions, the research proposes that the study should go beyond self-report measurements.

35. Tsaur, S., Hsu, F. and Kung, L. (2020) [21] Examining the difficulties faced by cabin personnel was the aim of this study. The study's four themes of hassles-job, peer interaction, passenger service, and personal were retrieved by content analysis. Workplace difficulties are caused by the mismatch between work expectations and actual operations, by the aviation facility's insufficient service capabilities, by erratic work schedules, and by emergencies. Inconveniences with peer contact include unequal work assignments among cabin staff, poor work cohesion among cabin crew, and poor work cohesion between cockpit crew and cabin crew. Theft incidents on night flights, sexual harassment of the cabin crew, verbal and physical abuse of the cabin crew, and individuals hiding infectious diseases are all examples of passenger service issues. Work-family issues and physical health issues are examples of personal annoyances.

2.3.2.2 Aircraft Cabin Environment:

36. Wen, Candice CY, et al. (2021) [53] Shift work is common among aviation pilots and cabin crew, and it can cause circadian disturbance, sleep deprivation, and health problems. Pilot exhaustion and sleepiness certainly stand out enough to be noticed in aviation research, yet less is had some significant awareness of cabin crews. The objective of this study was to figure out what elements are related with exhaustion, sluggishness, shift work jumble, and depression in cabin crew. To concentrate on these components an unknown internet-based survey was shipped off all dynamic cabin crew members all through the world. It evaluated tiredness and fatigue as well as sleep deprivation, sadness, and shift work jumble. The researchers gathered data on people's routines and work schedules. A total of 930 valid responses were examined. 63.5 percent of the participants reported abnormal levels of weariness, while 46.9% reported excessive daytime sleepiness. 68.0 percent of the participants were at risk for SWD, 57.7% for insomnia, and 40.0 percent for depression. A sleeping disorder and shift work jumble were autonomously connected with caffeine, liquor, and sleep drugs, while sluggishness was anticipated by flight routes (international, domestic, both) and number of duty days out of every week. There was a significant incidence of exhaustion and drowsiness among cabin staff, as well as an increased risk of shift work jumble, sleeping disorder, and depression. Many cabin crew members engaged in sleep hygiene-harming behaviours, emphasising areas for future interventional investigations.

37. Suthatorn, Pornprom, and Peerayuth Charoensukmongkol (2018) [54] Cabin crews are the particular frontline employees that have direct get in touch with consumers within the airline industry. These people work in an industry where these people are frequently faced by numerous difficulties. Along with their obligations for ensuring the particular flight's safety, flight cabin crews face a substantial amount of tension when they should serve guests through other cultures. According to the findings, cross-cultural interaction can easily generate anxiety, especially for persons who work in the service industry. By and large, accidental miscommunication and improper ways of behaving by airline cabin crew individuals can cause misery among worldwide clients, prompting work nervousness among aircraft cabin crew representatives. The reason for this study was to check whether there was a connection between the degree of social insight showed by cabin crew individuals and the degree

of nervousness they felt while serving unfamiliar visitors. Intercultural correspondence capacity and administration mindfulness were proposed as two abilities that directed the connection between social knowledge and diminished cabin crew uneasiness. 372 Thai airline cabin crews who used to work for a significant global carrier in Thailand partook in the study. Intercultural correspondence capacity and administration mindfulness directed the connection between social insight and diminished cabin crew nervousness, as per the aftereffects of a halfway least squares relapse study.

38. Eriksen, Carina (2016) [55] Despite the value placed on cabin crew mental health, a deeper understanding of the complex processes involved in the management of physical and psychosocial work-related stress is certainly required before embarking on the path of respecting cabin crew mental health. This chapter looks at how cabin crew members cope with their unusual lifestyle, which is exacerbated by organisational systems that are often beyond their control. The clear interconnection of an assortment of stressors, which, when taken all in all, seem to represent an essentially more remarkable danger to mental weakness than the separated results of a solitary occasion, is specifically noteworthy. When faced with contradictory life choices, cabin crew decision-making skills become important, especially under the stress of physical weariness and jet lag. These realities may reflect a shift in thinking in the realm of airline crew mental health. Traditionally, the focus has been on the negative cognitive effects of frequent jet lag and shift work that isn't consistent. Although this reflects the significance put on crew performance, particularly in terms of passenger safety on board the aircraft, the impact of emotional illness on performance standards may be just as harmful as any direct cognitive impairment.

39. Sveinsdottir, Herdis, Hólmfríður Gunnarsdóttir, and Hildur Friðriksdóttir (2007) [56] The goal of this study was to characterize and compare the self-reported occupational health of female nurses, cabin crew, and teachers in relation to their working environments. The three occupations' similarities, such as the fact that they are all largely female and service-oriented, make them intriguing to compare in terms of health and working conditions. Female Icelandic cabin crew, nurses, and elementary school teachers were among those who took part. Data was collected using a questionnaire that included socio-demographic questions, work environment questions (addressing work tempo, job security, monotonous work, assistance, physically difficult labour, and physical

environmental elements), and a symptom list. The symptom list was factored into five symptom scales: Musculoskeletal, Stress and Exhaustion, Common Cold, Gastrointestinal, and Sound Perception. 1571 questionnaires were distributed in total. The response percentage varied by occupation, ranging from 65.7 to 69 percent. The data was acquired in 2002. The gastrointestinal, hearing, and common cold symptoms reported by nurses and instructors were worse than those reported by cabin crew. Teachers and flight attendants reported more stress and fatigue symptoms than nurses. When compared to teachers and nurses, cabin crew reported less job security and more physically difficult and boring employment. Nurses were more likely than teachers or cabin crew to seek assistance from co-workers or patients, as well as to care for an older family member. According to regression analysis, stress from environmental factors resulted in higher ratings on all symptom scales within each employment. Nurses are more worried and fatigued than teachers and flight attendants. Nurses are more likely than the other occupations to help one another with their work, to have job security, to report physically challenging work, and to care for elderly relatives. Because it demonstrates responsibility and connection, this should be promoted as one of the good parts of nurses' professions.

40. Lindgren, T., and D. Norback (2005) [57] Personal risk factors, occupation, and labour on intercontinental flights with environmental tobacco smoke exposure were evaluated in connection to health symptoms and cabin air quality perceptions among commercial cabin crew. In February and March 1997, a structured questionnaire was issued to all Stockholm airline crew on duty in a Scandinavian airline, as well as office staff from the same carrier. At the time, smoking was only permitted on transcontinental flights. The plane crew participated at a rate of 81 percent, while the office group participated at a rate of 77 percent. Multiple logistic regression analysis was performed in the statistical investigation, which took into account age, gender, atopy, current smoking habits, and occupation. The most common complaints among airline staff were fatigue (21%), nasal symptoms (15%), eye pain (11%), dry or flushed face skin (12%), and dry/itchy skin on hands (12 %). The most common source of CAQ was dry air (53 %). Airline crews reported more nose, throat, and skin irritation than office personnel. Crew members with a history of atopy had more nasal, throat, and dermal face and hand symptoms than the rest of the crew.

41. Bourgeois-Bougrine, Samira, et al. (2003) [58] Pilots may self-report fatigue-related incidents in the cockpit to confidential systems. The purpose of this study was to better understand what fatigue means for pilots on short and long-haul flights (SHF and LHF, respectively). Four separate airlines distributed questionnaires to pilots. The reported causes of fatigue, its indicators and symptoms in the reporting pilot and elsewhere, as well as the measures used to mitigate its impact, were all reviewed. 739 (21.5%) of the 3,436 distributed surveys were returned. Fatigue was mostly attributable to night trips (59%) and LHF jet lag (45%). Longer duty periods (multi-segment flights over 4 to 5 days) (53%) and frequent early wake-ups contributed to SHF fatigue (41%). Self-reported fatigue symptoms included decreased alertness and attentiveness, as well as a lack of concentration in 60% of LHF pilots and 49% of SHF pilots. Other crew members had slower response times and made minor blunders (calculation, interpretation). When pilots were tired, all flying tasks appeared to be more difficult than usual. Rest and sleep management were the most important strategies used to deal with fatigue in both LHF and SHF. According to the data, duty time is a significant predictor of fatigue, but it cannot be considered in isolation from the other contributing factors. Pilots in both LHF and SHF reported acute weariness due to sleep deprivation, owing mostly to work schedules: night flights, jet lag, and successive early wake-ups. During accident and incident investigations, these cause aspects might be easily analysed.

42. Nagda, Niren L., and Michael D. Koontz (2003) [59] A number of studies have looked into the impact of the aeroplane cabin environment and other elements on the health and comfort of flight attendants (FAs), but there is no comprehensive review of the research. This report examines studies published after 1980 that looked at the effects of FA on short-term health and comfort. The PUBMED database of the National Institutes of Health was used to find relevant material. Twenty-one studies were found and divided into two categories: in-flight surveys and general flight experiences surveys. The majority of research relied on questionnaires to gather information about passengers' views of the cabin atmosphere, comfort, and health-related symptoms, but some also incorporated objective measurements. A random sample or control groups were used in only a few studies. In general, the effects of confounding variables have not been studied. The majority of the studies had certain flaws, such as a low response rate, significant response bias, a dependence solely on questionnaires, and restricted

analysis. The research show that numerous concerns and symptoms reported by FAs tend to be linked to their job activities and the cabin environment when taken together. The symptoms of "dryness" caused by low humidity and "fatigue" caused by variables such as disruption of the circadian rhythm are the most noteworthy. Longer flight lengths increase virtually all symptoms. Studies indicating "poor aeroplane cabin air quality" are often poorly designed and focus primarily on general flight experiences of FAs. Although specific FA problems are linked to possible exposure to air pollutants, the link has not been established, and such complaints might also be attributed to factors other than poor air quality.

43. Hellesy, Oddh (1995) [60] A total of 1240 personnel of SAS Norway's flight deck (F/D) and cabin crews (C/C) replied to a questionnaire that included questions about crew communication. The percentage of those that responded was 84 percent. F/D and male and female C/C evaluations of information exchange and communication amongst crews were compared to see whether there were any disparities. A 250-question multi-faceted questionnaire was used, with topics including organisational and psychosocial challenges, safety concerns, and subjective health. To investigate predictors of satisfaction with information and communication, regression analyses were used. In general, half of the aircrew members were unsatisfied with information exchange and cabin-cockpit cooperation. Around 70% of respondents were disappointed with debriefing and stop interactions. In terms of debriefing, there were considerable differences between F/D and C/C. Cabin personnel, particularly females, complained about being under-informed about operational procedures and technological issues. Nine out of ten female C/Cs sought more information about the airplane's or flying's technical features. Pilots said they didn't have enough information on how emergency procedures affect C/C and passengers. Interpersonal interactions were rated as satisfactory by 72 percent to 94 percent of respondents, while supervision and social support were rated as satisfactory by 53 percent. The majority of respondents (86%) agreed that frequent crew changes were stressful. Significant connections were found in regression studies between meeting frequency, supervision and support issues, scheduling schemes, and satisfaction with information exchange and cooperation. The findings indicate that there is a pressing need for more open, constant, and effective communication between the pilot and the cabin. Several practical improvement recommendations are offered.

44. Enck, P., et al. (1995) [61] A symptom questionnaire was used to investigate the presence of intestinal and extraintestinal symptoms in crew members and as controls in age and sex matched ground based administrative employees of a charter carrier over the course of one month, and the results were compared to the actual flight schedule of the flying staff. In addition, symptom scores and flight itineraries were linked to health and sickness behaviours, as well as personal, job, and life satisfaction. Flying crews reported much more dyspeptic symptoms than ground crews, and this was mostly true for long-haul flights, since crews with only short-haul experience did not have as many upper intestine issues. In addition, cabin crew reported much more intestinal problems than cockpit personnel, and part of the upper GI symptoms could be explained by differing eating habits, particularly higher fibre intake in flying staff. Doctor visits and sick days increased as the frequency of digestive symptoms increased, whereas job and personal life satisfaction declined. Flying crews, on the other hand, were more cognizant of the necessity of healthy habits. It has been found that frequent travelling, particularly over large distances, can lead to an increase in digestive symptoms, owing to the time difference.

45. Haugli, Liv, Anders Skogstad, and Odd H. Hellesoy (1994) [62] The current study is part of a large questionnaire assessment of the work environment and health of air crew members conducted in 1989 by the Scandinavian Airline System (SAS) in Norway. The 1240 people who responded (an 83 percent response rate) were asked 250 questions about their health, job stress, well-being, sleep issues, organisation, and communication. The research focuses on the disparities between cockpit and cabin employees in terms of self-reported health concerns. The study also considers gender, employment demands, respondents' working conditions, and aircraft design when assessing the health impacts of trans meridian and short-distance flying. Dry skin, lower back pain, colds, weariness, and sleep disruptions are common concerns reported by more than 30% of people. Pilots have the fewest complaints, while female cabin staff have the highest. Long-distance trans-meridian crews experience higher health issues than short-distance crews. Irritability, weariness, sleep disorders, and low back pain are the most commonly mentioned issues among pilots. Skin and eye problems, stomach problems, and musculoskeletal issues are more common among cabin crew members. The research backs up previous findings that trans-meridian flight travel promotes stomach issues, exhaustion, and sleep problems in both male and female cockpit and cabin employees. There is a nonsignificant increase in menstruation problems among female cabin attendants on long-haul flights.

2.3.2.3 Social Isolation:

46. Bouzari, Safavi and Foroutan (2021) [63] This paper presents a research model focused on the factors and consequences of social loafing, with a specific focus on flight attendants as a study sample, and adds to the current literature. More specifically, the study aims to develop a model that looks at the impact of various stressors, such as role conflict and ambiguity, as predictors and service-oriented Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) as a result of social loafing. Social loafing is a common phenomenon that can be encountered in any organisational context, regardless of age or gender, and across a wide range of occupations and cultures, attracting the attention of workplace researchers. Surprisingly, however, this topic has not received the attention it merits in the literature or in the context of air transportation. As a result, the current study adds to our understanding of social loafing in the airline industry, which is an important yet understudied topic in the existing literature. Flight attendants must respond to a variety of passenger requests, therefore participating in service-oriented OCB volunteer events could improve passengers' satisfaction with in-flight service. As a result, research priorities must include a better knowledge of the variables and events that obstruct such actions. Specifically, it is suggested that hindrance stresses are the forerunner of service-oriented OCB through the mediation impact of social loafing, based on the job resources demands (JD-R) model. The target group and sample selection are also credited for contributing to the study's success. Airline employees are overburdened by job stressors, and there are various aspects associated with flying that exacerbate airline employees' stress levels. As a result, a thorough research of how external stressors may affect their performance becomes necessary so that suitable remedies can be implemented to avoid the aviation industry's inevitable problems. Finally, the annual cost of work-related stressors as an international problem for businesses and society has been estimated to be in the hundreds of billions of dollars. This study's practical ramifications will allow airline executives to mitigate the harmful concrete and intangible consequences of this phenomena.

47. Fila, Gloria Victoria (2021) [64] In this paper the goal of study is to look into the work-life balance of flight attendants and pilots. Work-life balance was evaluated in general, as well as the task of a crew member, in order to achieve this. In addition, work-life balance concerns in general, as well as difficulties specific to the aviation industry, are investigated. In order to reduce these conflicts and other work-life balance-

related concerns, emphasis is placed on individual and corporate incentives. A mixed technique strategy was adopted for the primary data collecting. First, in-depth expert interviews with pilots and flight attendants are used to acquire qualitative data. The interviews are aimed at gaining a realistic understanding of work-life balance and relationships. Second, quantitative data is obtained by an online survey of the same target group, and the results are tested and analysed using SPSS. The major goal is to have a better understanding of the consequences of the irregular job on an individual's work-life balance and to address a bigger, more representative sample size. A control group of air traffic controllers is also given an online survey that has been modified. The study's conclusion reveals that all aspects impacting work-life balance are heavily influenced by an individual's personality and perception of them. Certain measurements and incentives, like as planning ahead, following a sleeping regimen, socialising, and others, are important and essential to all people, but the level to which they are needed and regarded as essential varies greatly. Furthermore, the findings are intended to increase awareness among aircrew personnel as well as among airline management.

48. Levy, Diane E., Gary L. Faulkner, and Richard D. Dixon (1984) [65]
Sociologists have paid more attention to the connection between work organisations and the structure of family life in this decade as the number and proportion of married women working outside the home has increased. While the workplace affects all families with breadwinners in some way, it is more important in the "dual career" family. When both spouses work outside the home in jobs that require a high level of commitment, competition, and advancement through the corporate ladder, this imposition and interference with family life becomes enormous. The relationship between work organisation and family life for those who work as flight attendants is examined in this study. A flight attendant is a stereotypically "feminine" job, but unlike many others, it does not simply fit into the role of housewife. It truly is believed that the particular specific requirements associated with the job trigger more stress, discontentment, and stress within married flight attendants' family and friends than in single flight attendants. The particular sample includes all flight attendants of a major regional airline. Comparisons were produced depending on different actions of role turmoil, stress and fulfilment between married in addition to unmarried flight family and friends. Married and single flight attendants had been compared on several measures of function conflict, stress in addition to satisfaction. (Married folks make-up 35% associated with the population; individual people make-up 62%). The results

usually are discussed using Kanter's (1977) model associated with five aspects associated with work organization impacting family life. (62%) On most proportions, the married team showed higher amounts of role conflict, tension, and dissatisfaction compared to unmarried attendant team. Kanter's (1977) sort of five elements of work corporation affecting house lifestyle was used in order to discuss the final results.

2.3.2.4 Irregular Working Hours:

49. Bendak, Salaheddine, and Hamad SJ Rashid (2020) [66] Human performance may be harmed by factors that cause human weariness, such as sleep deprivation, circadian rhythm disorders, health-related exhaustion, and task-induced influences. In aircraft operations, these negative impacts may include severe deterioration in decision-making skills, memory sharpness, judgement competency, reaction time, and situational awareness, which can lead to mishaps. Through a thorough literature analysis, this study intends to evaluate the origins, implications, measurement, and mitigation of fatigue and the related risk in aviation operations from both academic and industrial perspectives. The author searched, gathered, and analysed articles published in peer-reviewed journals as well as publications from other aviation industry stakeholders that addressed tiredness in flight. The danger of fatigue in the aviation business has been discovered to be varied and sometimes confusing. Overall, this risk increases significantly when the workday is more than 16 hours, when the pre-duty sleep is less than 6 hours, and when the weekday overlaps with the crew's normal sleeping hours. Furthermore, it was discovered that not all aspects of this risk had been fully studied. At the end, there are recommendations for future research to look into ways to reduce this risk even more.

50. Van den Berg, M. J., Signal, T. L., & Gander, P. H. (2019) [67] To track their personal sleep during the ULR flight, 55 cabin crew members used actigraphy and a sleep/duty record in the current study. The workload necessitated ongoing monitoring of the cabin crew due to the discovery of a fatigue component. This can be accomplished by adding your workload as an important component of weariness risk management techniques into fatigue research. To quantify their own sleep during the ULR journey, 55 holiday cabin crew members completed an actigraphy and a sleep/duty log in the current study's technique. It was discovered that the workload necessitated continuous monitoring of the cabin staff as a fatigue component. This can be accomplished by incorporating one's workload as a key component of tiredness risk management systems in fatigue research.

51. Goker, Zeynep (2018) [68] Fatigue is a significant and cumulative influence in aviation safety, resulting in human errors due to a reduction in the ability to perform activities requiring higher-order cognitive processing. Chronic weariness is subtler and more subjective. A lack of sleep, crew scheduling, a long duty duration, jet or shift lag, a hard task, and a lack of physical or mental fitness all contribute to fatigue. Fatigue levels can be determined using both subjective and objective indicators. Objective interventions are based on physiological parameters of the subject (brain waves, eye gaze, facial feature identification) or bodily manifestations (muscle tone, wrist inactivity, head orientation) and aid in sustaining attentiveness and performance throughout long or uneventful job periods. Fatigue countermeasures are typically based on self-reported data, which must have a "safety" component.

52. Van Drongelen, Alwin, et al (2013) [69] Cabin crew flight plans incorporate early take offs, extended working hours, night flights, and time region changes, all of which increase the possibility of onboard occupational accidents. Because it is unknown, the goal of this study is to determine if cumulative flight schedule exposure increases the incidence of occupational accidents among cabin crew professionals. The data came from the previous more cohort, which lasted five years. A total of 6311 cabin crew members participated in the study. All flight schedules from 2005 to 2008, as well as all registered occupational accidents from 2009, were collected for each employee. Through logistics regression analysis, it was used to evaluate the relationship between various types of travel and occupational accumulation of professional accidents. 289 crew reported at least one working injury in 2009. The number of short-haul flights was positively connected to the occurrence of occupational accidents in 2009 between 2005 and 2008. This was revealed by the adjusted logistic regression models. Exposure to long-distance flying was also linked to a lower risk of reporting an occupational injury. The findings of this study indicate that cumulative short-haul flight exposure is associated with an increased risk of occupational accidents among cabin crew workers. This elevated risk could be attributed to the unique characteristics of short-haul flights. Future research should concentrate on potential underlying causes, such as tiredness accumulation, as well as the impact of short-haul schedule modifications. In order to avoid onboard disasters, airlines may focus more on short-haul flights.

53. Caldwell, John A., et al. (2009) [70] Pilot fatigue is a severe concern in modern aviation, owing to the unpredictability of work hours, long duty periods, circadian disruptions, and insufficient sleep, all of which are all too frequent in both civilian and military aircraft operations. Although the full scope of tiredness is frequently underestimated, many of its negative consequences have long been recognised. Persons who are sleep deprived think and move slower, make more mistakes, and have memory problems than people who are well-rested. These unfavourable consequences can and do result in aircraft mishaps and blunders. To combat aircrew weariness, flight time limits, prescribed stopover durations, and aircrew nap guidelines were created in the 1930s. Despite indications that revisions are needed, there have been little adjustments to aircrew schedule allowances and flying time constraints since they were first established. Despite substantial advancements in scientific understanding of fatigue, sleep, shift work, and circadian physiology over the last several decades, present rules and business practises have mostly failed to appropriately incorporate the new information. As a result, pilot fatigue has become a growing problem, as have fatigue-related concerns about air safety. Fatigue is an increasing hazard in aviation operations, according to accident data, pilot complaints, and operational flight studies. This study examines the relevant scientific literature, covers civilian and military flight restrictions in the United States, assesses prospective in-flight and pre/postflight fatigue countermeasures, and highlights emerging weariness detection and countermeasure technology. Following a consideration of each important issue, position statements address particular options for dealing with weariness, with the goal of revising legislation and providing tools and processes for improving air safety based on current scientific understanding.

54. Avers, Katrina Bedell, et al. (2009) [71] Extended duty periods, highly fluctuating schedules, frequent time zone changes, and heavier passenger loads offer significant problems for cabin crew members in today's airline business, which operates 24 hours a day, seven days a week. While these operating needs are vital, they are not optimal in terms of managing sleep and alertness in the human body's biological rhythms. In reality, weariness and fatigue-related errors are caused by acute sleep loss, prolonged periods of awakesness, and circadian factors caused by this type of mis alignment. The intent of this assessment was to pinpoint particular operational concerns that could lead to cabin crew exhaustion. In a retrospective survey, flight attendants from 30 major airlines (regional=17, low-cost=7, and network=6) were polled. The researchers gathered information on job record, workload, and employment time, as well as sleep,

health, exhaustion, work environment, and demography. The survey was completed willingly and anonymously by 9,180 cabin crew members who completed the study's inclusion requirements (i.e., active flight attendant that had flown the previous bid period with their current airline). This article sums up the survey's findings and offers specific advice for coping with fatigue in cabin crew operations.

55. Brown, Lori J., and John Niehaus. (2009) [72] As a result of the massive concessions needed of flight attendants in the wake of the airline industry's recent and ongoing financial difficulties, it is clear that airline management intends to keep crews working longer duty days with significantly less time off in between. "Some air carriers routinely exploit a "reduced rest" clause in the FAA's Flight Attendant Duty Time and Rest Regulations, which allows the mandated rest of nine hours to be reduced to eight hours," according to the AFA. Key safety precautions, such as arming doors, have been forgotten by flight attendants, who have even fallen asleep in their jump seats. As airlines restructure and cut costs to stay afloat, flight attendants are noticing a new industry trend that needs to be addressed. Due to poorly scheduled duty hours, extended working days, or severe business schedule violations, several airlines require flight attendants to work until they are exhausted. Human variables like as weariness, sleepiness, sleep disorders, and circadian rhythms have risen to the top of the priority list for transportation safety research. In the flight attendant profession, where sleep deprivation and disruption of circadian rhythms are known to occur, critical fatigue findings have been discovered (Testimony of Patricia A. Friend, 2007). Using models, contemporary technology, and easy logical interface tools, we can detect worker weariness and increase safety. We can increase operating efficiency and satisfy the business needs of today's airlines by reducing fatigue and the errors that come with it, especially during these difficult times.

56. Sharma, Lekha (2007) [73] All airlines follow a set of rules. Each airline's working environment, however, is distinct, as is the ambience of each aircraft within the same carrier. However, all aircraft crews work in an environment that involves circadian dysrhythmia, low atmospheric pressure, mild hypoxia, and exposure to sound, vibration, and cosmic radiation. Flight attendants frequently experience issues such as insufficient sleep and/or poor sleep quality, as well as inconsistent work hours. The effects of flying on Indian male and female flight attendants who had been flying for more than 10 years and up to 30 years were investigated in this study. The flight

attendants recruited for this study were all subjected to the same set of conditions, including monthly flight hours and flight routes. Questionnaires were created in response to complaints received on a regular basis, as well as interviews with a select number of FAs. About 100 of the 500 questionnaires given directly to FAs were completed and returned. Furthermore, author met with 130 FAs either before or after their leave and got complete questionnaires from them while protecting their identities. According to the study, 88.85 percent of FAs say they are stressed 'frequently' or 'sometimes.' Many participants believed that if their workplace was more employee-friendly, their stress levels would decrease. Back pain was noted by 72.65 percent of FAs, which they believe might be alleviated in significant part by providing improved equipment and user-friendly galleys. Memory loss was found in 67.47 percent of FAs tested. Headaches affect 52.32 percent of FAs. Hypoxia, jetlag, and inconsistent sleep appear to be common causes of stress, memory loss, and headaches. Hearing loss, which affected 51.37 percent of FAs, was not a major source of concern but was viewed as an annoyance.

57. Sharma, R. C., and J. K. Shrivastava (2004) [74] Aircrew sleep is critical in today's commercial aviation environment. Given the speed and range of today's aircraft, aircrew fatigue is becoming a limiting factor in aviation operations. Modern commercial aeroplanes travel through time zones at approximately the same rate as the Earth circles, and it is these rapid transmeridian transitions that induce Jet Lag or Rapid Time Zone Change Illness. Cabin crew personnel are an essential part of commercial airline flight crews and are in charge of flight safety. Jet lag reduces focus, short-term memory, and decision-making, impairing cabin crew's complete job content. As a result, cabin crew cannot afford to be 'jet lagged,' as it reflects poorly on the airline. The purpose of this article is to use a questionnaire survey to document the incidence and consequences of jet lag on a commercial airline cabin crew. It also recommends corrective actions in the medical, training, and operations fields. In total, 462 cabin staff members took part in the poll. The average age of the cabin crew is 42.9 years, which may represent the airline's recruitment policies. It's reflected in the fact that the crew in issue has a reasonably long service history (14.7 years). Supervisory rank was held by 17.3 percent of the cabin crew. The most frequent chronic conditions encountered in the survey were hypertension, coronary artery disease, and diabetes mellitus, with many people having several disabilities. 40.9 percent of the cabin staff had heard of Jet Lag,

and 91.1 percent had experienced symptoms. Almost twice as many people found flying to the Far East to be more tiring than flying to the West. The most challenging flights were the long-haul night trips, maybe due to a lack of adequate sleep. The use of alcohol or medications (anxiolytics) to promote sleep, sometimes in combination, was one of the coping techniques. To counteract Jet Lag, individuals used coping tactics such as exercising at the layover hotel or forced sleep. Understanding the physiological principles driving Jet Lag and fatigue responses necessitates an education and training module on Jet Lag management in aircraft operations. Given the nature of the job, they must be educated on the many facets of Jet Lag, and the company must establish a flight schedule to assist them in overcoming the unusual job-related disease. Short-acting hypnotics can help you adjust to your new time zone and get enough sleep. Medical standards for cabin crew, similar to those for aircrew, are urgently needed to be developed and implemented.

58. Beh, Helen C., and Peter McLaughlin (1997) [75] In this study, the experimental subjects were aviation crews who had fought for 7.5 to 9 hours to the west, north, or east. A 15-minute test battery included four tasks known to be vulnerable to stress caused by the disruption of circadian rhythms during transzonal bouts. A Grammatical Reasoning Task, a Vertical Addition Task, a Horizontal Addition Task, and a Letter Cancellation Task were among the tasks. Before the first test session, subjects were given practise on each activity, and during the experiment, they were allowed to work on each task for 3 minutes, with a 60-second rest between tasks. At each session, different versions of each task were employed, and the sequence of the tests within the battery was counterbalanced between subjects. Within one hour of take-off and landing, aircrew were assessed in groups. At the Sydney base, control participants were tested as a group at times that matched the departure and arrival periods of active aircrew. Between the test periods, the control individuals attended Qantas base training classes for air crew. In addition to performance data, each subject's sleeping patterns throughout the 24-hour period leading up to the preflight test were recorded, as well as any sleep received during the flight. For the preflight and postflight test sessions, each subject's output and error rate were calculated for each task. A two-way analysis of variance with planned contrasts was used to examine the percentage change in accuracy and output from the first to the second test session for each task. Contrast 1 looked for a difference between the control group and the flying groups, whereas Contrast 2 looked for a difference between the northbound group and the eastbound or westbound groups.

59. Ono, Yuichiro, et al. (1991) [76] The authors of this study looked into issues with working hours and their impact on flight attendant fatigue symptoms (FA). Japan Air Lines's flight schedule departing Narita International Airport was examined. The fatigue symptoms of 211 female FA assigned to the long daily nonstop flights were surveyed. It was discovered that many FA worked late at night and early in the morning, that flight hours were frequently quite lengthy, and that the time difference between Japan and destinations may have a harmful effect on workers' biological rhythms. After the second lunch service, after flying duties had been completed for 7 to 10 hours after taking off on every route, fatigue complaint rates spiked. The length of working hours, the length of night job duties, and the time difference between Japan and destinations are all thought to contribute to higher tiredness complaint rates. A questionnaire survey of female flight attendants on four Japanese airlines' domestic flights was conducted. They kept a daily journal of when they showed there and when they debriefed, as well as their fatigue symptoms. A total of 1,317 (42.3%) valid responses were examined. The tremendous unpredictability of the FA time schedule was reflected in early morning show-ups and late-night debriefings. Long working hours, frequent landings, and late debriefing hours, among other factors, were found to contribute significantly to higher fatigue complaint rates in statistical analyses, as were other factors such as the order of the day among a series of days on duty and short rest intervals between two consecutive work days.

60. Grosch, J. W. et al. (2006) [77] Large national databases that have data on working hours and health have only been the subject of a small number of research. Data from a quality of work life (QWL) module created for the 2002 General Social Survey were analysed in the current study. An N141,744 representative sample of the US population served as the source for the job and health data gathered in this module. Based on the total number of hours worked each week, descriptive analyses were done for five groups: part-time workers (1-34 hours per week), full-time workers (35-40 hours per week), lower overtime workers (41-48 hours per week), medium overtime workers (49-69 hours per week), and higher overtime workers (70 hours per week). Multiple logistic regression was used to analyse the relationship between these five categories and several health and wellbeing indicators. The three types of overtime workers were more likely to be male, Caucasian, and middle-aged than full-time employees, and they also had greater incomes and levels of education. Additionally, they were more likely

to be self-employed, salaried, independent contractors, hold multiple jobs, and work split, irregular, or on-call schedules. Though seen to be overworked and connected with higher levels of job stress, overtime labour was also linked to higher levels of participation in decision-making and possibilities for the development of unique skills. Particularly for responders in the higher overtime group (70 hr/week), several statistically significant relationships between work hours and measures of health and well-being were found.

61. Badanik, B., Duc, M. Le and Kandra, B. (2022) [78] This study demonstrated that rostering factors, such as timing of flight and duty periods, such as night shifts, brief rest periods, back-to-back early morning starts, extended duty periods, back-to-back duty days, and others, significantly affect crewmembers' fatigue, posing serious issues for flight operations. Crew weariness, which is seen as a serious safety concern and which increases errors, incidents, and accidents, is impacted by rosters. Rostering variables that induce lost sleep and circadian body clock abnormalities typically result in decreased alertness and performance. Additionally, crew members' decision-making or judgement may be compromised, their ability to communicate may be hampered, and their reaction time may slow down. Crew members' sleepiness, difficulty focusing, sleep issues, sluggish reaction times, and irritability are typical symptoms of fatigue. Additionally, crew members may have health problems including melancholy or reduced immunity as a result of the inadequate rosters. According to authors observations, crew members with more experience may feel fatigued to a greater extent, which is most likely related to their age.

2.3.3 Cabin Crews:

62. Park, Jungyi, and Sunghyup Sean Hyun (2021) [79] This study examined the impact of relationship-building behaviors (attention abnormality, normal behavior, polite behavior, connection behavior, and information sharing behavior) on Crew members' empathy for their co-workers, based on the works on relationship-building behaviors in the airline industry. The authors also look at how empathy affects things like team performance, the organizational environment, and the occasional occurrence of malice. The authors examined 230 samples of full-service domestic and international airlines in Korea collected through online questionnaires and convenience sampling. According to the structural equation modeling (SEM), abnormal attention behavior,

polite behavior, connection behavior and information sharing behavior all have a positive impact on the empathy of colleagues, thereby impact on team performance, organizational environment, and potential abnormalities. According to the study, the presence of participants' closest colleagues on the same team had no effect on the relationship between relationship development and empathic conduct among crew members. This research has important implications for protecting the dignity and emotional well-being of seafarers working in high-pressure situations. The results can be used to improve crew psychological well-being and quality of life by modifying crew management rules.

63. Kim, Haeok Liz, and Sunghyup Sean Hyun (2021) [80] The purpose of this research is to conduct a survey among stigma inflictors, or people who participate in stigmatising others, in order to create metrics for stigma-producing elements. The purpose of this study was to develop a stigma assessment scale for personnel in the service industry. This study focused on airline cabin crew personnel to derive stigma measuring elements utilising a seven-step scale building approach. As a result, the stigma scale produced in this study has 28 measuring questions and is divided into six components (work ability, conscientiousness, selfishness, work ethics, attractiveness, and neuroticism). This study highlights the necessity for interventions to decrease employee stigmatisation within businesses. On a human level, the practical implication is to prevent stigmatisation within the airline organisation by enhancing cabin staff perceptions of stigma. The practical implication at the organisational level is to assess and decrease the sources of social stigma that have a detrimental impact on organisational performance.

64. Winolo, L., & Sukandar, R. (2019) [81] Cabin staff, as the front liner in a competitive service business, will play a vital role in delivering a high-quality standard of services to passengers, allowing companies to differentiate their products and services and meet consumer expectations. In the digital age, social media may be a powerful instrument for marketing communication, helping to build a positive brand image and generate profits. However, as humans, cabin crew interacts on social media, which relates to emotional labour that can have both harmful and beneficial effects on businesses. The phenomenon of cabin staff and social media at Citilink Indonesia, one of Indonesia's low-cost carriers, is described in this qualitative study. According to this

study, social media has become one of the most effective communication channels for cabin crew to convey their deepest feelings. Furthermore, deep acting by cabin crews has been viewed as a "good faith" sort of emotional labour since the cabin crew recognises that every work must begin with sincerity. Finally, the heroes of Citilink Indonesia are the Agent of Culture, Trainer, and Senior Cabin Crew, who best exemplify or personify the cultural ideals as actual role models of behaviour that will demonstrate what is possible in Citilink.

65. Van Den Berg, M. J., Signal, T. L., & Gander, P. H. (2020) [82] There is currently lack of understanding of cabin staff fatigue on ultralong range (ULR) aircraft. As a result, current ULR cabin crew scheduling is primarily dependent on flight crew data. Cabin crew members' thoughts on fatigue, as well as their recommendations for dealing with it, have rarely been solicited. To better understand the causes and effects of cabin crew fatigue, semi-structured focus group talks were held. A theme analysis was performed using data from 25 cabin crew members. Fatigue, according to participants, has two effects: 1) health and well-being of cabin personnel; 2) cabin safety (cabin, passenger, and personal); and 3) cabin service. The most common reasons of exhaustion, according to participants, were inadequate rest, a severe workload, the work environment, a lack of business support, and insufficient fatigue management training, coupled with sleep loss and circadian disturbance. They emphasised the importance of adequate sleep, not just for healing but also for maintaining a healthy work-life balance. They also emphasised the importance of company help, open communication, and general management of engagement with cabin staff. We believe that prioritising cabin crew fatigue management training will boost corporate support and help build a better work-life balance.

66. Vatankhah, Sanaz, and Ali Raofi (2018) [83] The reason for this study is to look at the effect of mental privilege and self-absorbed hardship on cabin crew degenerate direct on relational and authoritative levels. Attribution theory is a neglected theory in organisational research that uses the mediating impact of egoistic deprivation to link psychological entitlement to interpersonal and organisational deviant conduct. In Iran, a questionnaire survey of governmental and public aviation businesses was done. The poll resulted in 294 completed questionnaires. Structural equation modelling was used to assess the study's linkages. Psychological entitlement, according to the findings,

increases cabin crews' egoistic deprivation and interpersonal and organisational deviant behaviour. Cabin crews' egoistic deprivation increases interpersonal aberrant behaviour, which supports the hypothesis. The influence of psychological entitlement on interpersonal aberrant conduct appears to be somewhat mediated by egoistic deprivation among cabin workers. Dissimilar to the authors speculations, selfish hardship doesn't work as an arbitrator in the connection between mental privilege and authoritative abnormal way of behaving. By utilizing attribution hypothesis to cabin crew hardship and work environment freak conduct, this study adds to the very little psychological entitlement literature.

2.3.4 Stress Coping Resources:

67. Ozel, Engin, and Umit Hacioglu (2021) [84] In the aviation industry, developing effective business strategies necessitates the commitment of highly motivated and qualified people who like their work. Representatives within the flying industry are anticipated to be well-educated, professionally experienced, talented, optimistic, and energetic individuals who care approximately the quality of their work and the success of the company. In the aviation area, the mix of speed and solace for travellers has turned into an essential basic dimension for by and large business execution and draws in new travellers. This paper inspects hypothetical and exact examinations on weariness risk factors in cockpit and service team to lay out a basic way to deal with flight security. This examination additionally lays the preparation for tending to exhaustion risk worries in the flying business. The paper's key commitment is that essential and auxiliary sluggishness risk factors in the cockpit and service team affect work fulfilment, functional effectiveness, and flight security.

68. Tang, A. D., Chang, M. L., Wang, T. H., & Lai, C. H. (2020) [85] Through the combination of the theory of demand for emotional event and work, this study will be promoted by the relationship between the airline's institutional property and individual results through the psychological mechanism. This study is surprising in that it is quick to quantitatively examine what inward advertising adds to joy by meaning for cabin crews work-family communication. In light of an example of 142 airline cabin crews working in Asian carrier companies, the discoveries uncover that correspondence, welfare systems, training, and management support are straightforwardly connected with satisfaction and by implication related with bliss through work-family help. Cabin

crew contentment can be shaped by improved communication, welfare systems, and management assistance, which reduces work-family friction. Compensation, on the other hand, does not appear to affect the pleasure of flight attendants. Practical ramifications and future research directions are also highlighted.

69. Cheng, Tien-Ming, Shu-Yun Chang, and Yin-Yun Chan (2018) [86] Is it genuine that getting away from work is the smartest strategy? In view of the reason of "work requests burnout-wellbeing concerns," this study researched the directed intervention impacts of relaxation benefit plans coordinated via carrier firms and recreation survival strategies took on by airline crews themselves. This study sent polls to 362 airline crews and surveyed its speculations utilizing progressive relapse investigation and interaction examination. This study's discoveries demonstrate that the "work requests burnout-medical conditions" intercession model is self-evident. As per the intercession model's directed intervention impact, relaxation benefit projects will diminish the connection between work requests and burnout, thus reducing medical problems. Relaxation ways of dealing with especially difficult times will support the lightening of the connection among burnout and medical conditions, as well as the decrease of the "work requests burnout-medical issues" cycle. At long last, this study introduced some administration suggestions to carrier organizations to foster relaxation reward frameworks and recreation survival techniques for flight attendants' leisure adapting measures will assist with easing the connection among burnout and medical conditions, while additionally diminishing the "work requests burnout-medical conditions" cycle. At long last, this examination made various administration suggestions for aircraft firms to advance recreation reward frameworks and relaxation adapting strategies for airline stewards.

70. Lee, Chongho, Myungsook An, and Yonghwi Noh (2015) [87] The reason for this study is to decide the impact of a carrier's passionate showcase necessities on airline cabin crews enthusiastic work methods (i.e., profound acting, surface acting), job burnout, and work execution. The discoveries were accumulated from a survey of 230 airline crews from a noticeable South Korean airline organization. The discoveries demonstrate that the passionate work technique of airline stewards is critical in dealing with enthusiastic showcase standards. The rules for passionate showcase had no immediate impact on work burnout or execution, however they affected the enthusiastic

work procedure of airline cabin crews. Profound acting superior work execution while diminished burnout, though surface acting better work execution however increased burnout. Because of these discoveries, airlines might have the option to increment airline cabin crews' execution and anticipated burnout by empowering profound acting. This study clarifies why airlines should focus for how their staff agree to enthusiastic showcase rules and utilize a suitable passionate work way to deal with work on in-flight administration quality after some time.

71. Cho, Ju-Eun, HS Chris Choi, and Woo Jin Lee (2014) [88] This type of research looks at the connections between work-related pressures, emotional exhaustion, and intentional non-reflexive employee turnover. Employees' emotional tiredness was caused by three key factors: job overburden, work clashes, and uncertainty. The concentrate commonly affirmed those representatives who are available to encountering superfluous or long-haul work pressure, which can cause emotional sleepiness while drawing in with clients, and this pressure can prompt wilful turnover. Airline companies are compelled to provide stress management ways for coping and acting because they build a culture of stress management within the organisation by giving specific training programmes, setting certain job criteria, and changing the physical work environment.

72. Rajaratnam, Shantha MW, Mark E. Howard, and Ronald R. Grunstein (2013) [89] Shift workers account for about 1.5 million Australians, or 16 percent of the working population. Shift work has been linked to poor health, safety, and performance. These connections are thought to be influenced by circadian rhythm misalignment, insufficient and poor-quality sleep, and sleep disorders. The most obvious effect of shift work is a reduction in alertness, which has far-reaching implications for key brain processes such as reaction time, decision-making, information processing, and the ability to sustain concentration. In high-risk environments, this impairment leads to avoidable errors, accidents, and injuries. Shift employment has been linked to long-term health problems, such as an increase in vascular events. This review assesses the health risks associated with shift employment and offers therapeutic care techniques for shift workers with sleep-wake disorders. The fundamental physiological sleep-wake factors of alertness must be included in evidence-based management techniques.

73. Leonhardt, Joerg (2010) [90] In this particular study the experts discuss about the necessity of a strong, included, structured, multi-component expert support system for aviation personnel. Aviation is a high-risk organization where air traffic controllers, pilots, flight attendants, and ground personnel are most commonly at risk. They experience high level of psychological and Physiological stress throughout the work. The authors cite the usage of an approach known as Critical Incident Stress Management to support their claims (CISM). Air traffic controllers, pilots, ground staff, and flight attendants are currently covered by the CISM Program. The aircraft industry is a High Serviceability Organization that must run smoothly and consistently. The basic resources provided by these teams are highlighted on this website, as well as the various types and levels of assistance required by peer support personnel on CISM teams in the aviation industry. According to the authors, if people feel stressed or frightened, CISM team members can intervene and assist them in returning to normal life.

74. Wahlstedt, Kurt et al., (2010) [91] The goal of this study was to investigate the relationships between stress as measured by the demands-control model, the iso-strain model, and stress-related symptoms in cabin crew. In 2005, 918 flight attendants, stewards, and pursers from a single airline firm filled out a questionnaire on their psychosocial work environment and symptoms. Multiple logistic regression was used to adjust for age, gender, smoking, job category, and journey time. As a result, 18%, 10%, 56%, and 13% of respondents, respectively, experienced weekly headaches, concentration difficulties, weariness, and stomach concerns. Pursers had less linkages between strain and symptoms in the demands-control model than stewards and flight attendants, but they scored higher on control. In a high-strain environment, all symptoms were more prevalent than in a low-strain situation (reference). An excess of symptoms was linked to a busy environment. In the iso-strain model, low social support increased symptom risk. The demands-control and iso-strain models, according to the study's findings, are both beneficial for assessing stress-related symptoms among cabin workers, and the dimension of social support in the iso-strain model adds explanatory value. Stress-relieving strategies such as modifying work schedules, slowing down, and increasing social support at work are essential, according to the research. This may generate concern not only for the examining airline, but also for the entire commercial airline industry.

75. Arendt Josephine (2010) [92] The circadian clock adjusts slowly, if at all, to the rapid transitions between different job calendars. This predisposed prospects to misalignment with the projected work-relaxation timetable due to circadian physiological settings such as sleeping, attentiveness, accomplishment, metabolic rate, and melatonin and cortisol testosterone. One of the results is little sleep and proficiency. Shift work raises the risk of major cardiovascular disease, causes cancer, and causes circadian desynchrony. There are several strategies for treating circadian desynchrony and hastening circadian rearrangement.

76. Xanthopoulou, Despoina, et al (2008) [93] Work resources such as autonomy, task identification, and social assistance have been confirmed in several research to become initiators associated with a process that will leads to function engagement and overall performance. Self-efficacy is emphasised by some writers as a element in explaining the change from job sources to positive mental and organisational outcomes. However, in the particular case of work-related engagement, this mediating impact has obtained only sporadic scientific confirmation. The Work Demands-Resources (JD-R) design is used like a guiding framework with this study of airline flight attendants to observe if colleague assistance predicts performance simply by increasing employees' self-efficacy beliefs and function engagement. Authors used a diary strategy and a multilevel design, which requires into consideration each between-person and within-person variables, in comparison to earlier study that only appeared at how individuals differed in one an additional. By analysing regardless of whether daily fluctuations within colleague support foresee day-levels of task performance through self-efficacy and work diamond, this study endeavors to gain with regards to the motivating technique of the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model. Just before and after travel arrangements to three global locations, forty-four flight attendants completed a new questionnaire and a new journal booklet. Friend's support a fresh unique positive influence on self-efficacy and work management, according to be able to multilevel studies. work management mediated typically the link between self-efficacy and (in-role and even extra-role) performance, although not the romantic relationship between support and even engagement. Furthermore, by way of job engagement, friend support had the indirect influence on in-role performance. These conclusions provide light about the JD-R model's motivational process, suggesting that colleague help is a considerable job resource intended for flight attendants inside achieving their work-related objectives.

77. Ai-Serkal, Alia (2006) [94] The purpose of this study was to examine cabin crew expectations and reality, the impact of emotional work and organizational characteristics on them, whether personality influences emotional work, and whether coping techniques are used. The participants were flight attendants from a Middle Eastern airline. Studies 1 and 2 included self-reported questionnaires on EL, organizational factors, well-being, physical symptoms, and burnout. Flight attendants' honest opinions on EL, stress and coping were examined in Study 3 using qualitative techniques. Overall, the results indicate that flight attendants from individualistic cultures have a harder time adapting to the role because their expectations of peer support, autonomy, and control do not reflect the reality of the job. The longer someone worked in the position, the more likely they were to develop physical difficulties and become more stressed. Cabin crew expectations of EL reflected their experiences in the workplace, but attitudes toward organizational variables changed and began to play a larger impact on individual perceptions of work, particularly job satisfaction, which declined over time. Personality did not affect the outcome. The EL experience affected cabin crew well-being but had little impact on employee retention. In summary, this research aimed to develop cabin crew norms related to EL, organizational characteristics and stress and to examine the interplay between these variables. In practice, organizations may need to address crews' expectations of the job early on, perhaps during hiring, by communicating the reality of the role and offering them support in dealing with EL, stress and burnout, as this could be detrimental in the long-term.

78. Kagan, Norman I., and Mary G. Watson (1995) [95] Three hundred and seventy-three employees of a municipal fire department's emergency medical service took part in this three-year field study. The researchers created a framework for identifying stress and categorising psych educational stress reduction programmes. The overall effect of seven psych educational programmes based on physiological (M), coping-with-people (A), or interpersonal awareness (I) processes, as well as the four combination programmes, A & I, M & A, M & I, and M & A & I, on measures related to job stress, as well as the relative effect of each programme in the short and long term, were determined. On standardised psychological tests and a job performance measure, there were pre- and post-follow-up improvements. The findings back up the need of psych educational training programmes in the workplace for mental health prevention.

79. Majali, S. Al and Shana, Z. (2019) [96] The research serves as a preliminary evaluation of the psychological stress levels related to work and its sources among aircrew members. The study also evaluates the methods employed by aircrew members to manage stress and assesses outcomes depending on numerous criteria. The study sample included 226 members of the aircrew, including 73 pilots (66 men and 7 women), with an average age of (45) years and an average work experience of (20 years); and 153 cabin crew (53 men and 100 women), with an average age of (26) years and an average practical experience of (four) years working for Royal Jordanian Airlines. Sources of work stress and skills for dealing with psychological stress were two scales utilised to improve this study. In terms of face validity, construction validity, differential validity, and by using the coefficient Cronbach's alpha test, these scales were created and determined to be trustworthy for the objectives of this study. According to the study's findings, 74.33 percent of aircrew members perceived their level of work stress as medium, 11.50 percent thought it was high, and 14.15 percent reported feeling no pressure at all. Interestingly, men feel work-related stress more frequently than women do, and less seasoned aircrew members experience higher levels of stress. The survey found that the most popular techniques for dealing with psychological stress are, cognitive skills, interpersonal skills, and personal skills.

80. Matheny, K. B. et al. (2003) [97] In addition to reporting the findings of a recent convergent/divergent study on six CRIS scales, this article examines earlier research using the Coping Resources Inventory for Stress (CRIS). The CRIS measures tend to be helpful in predicting sickness, emotional discomfort, personality type, drug dependency, career choice, and life satisfaction. They also exhibit strong internal consistency and test-retest reliability. 68 graduate students who volunteered at an urban institution in the Southeast made up the convergent/divergent sample. Each CRIS scale departed from a test that assesses a distinct component and converged with its validating test. The findings provide strong evidence for the construct validity of CRIS scales and imply that this tool may have promise as a research and therapeutic tool for the investigation of stress coping.

81. S P, L. J. and V, C. (2008) [98] In this study, a sample of 55 civil pilots was examined to determine their levels of psychosocial stress and coping mechanisms. Stress questionnaires were given to the participants, and the results showed that civil pilots experience professional stress at a rate of 78 percent. The majority of them

(77 %) employ emotion focused relaxation techniques to relieve stress. However, 18 percent of pilots say they utilise problem-solving as a stress-coping technique, and 5% of them say they use social support. Pilots who are prone to stress are advised to participate in stress management programmes to improve their operational effectiveness.

2.3.5 Work Engagement:

82. Karatepe, O. M., & Kim, T. T. (2020) [99] Bore out jeopardizes the health and productivity of service workers. However, there is no actual data on the effects of bore out on cabin staff. As a result of this insight, this paper examines passenger needs reading and job engagement as two parallel multiple mediators between bore out and service-oriented organisational citizenship behaviours. Employees in the South Korean aviation industry provided the data. Cabin crew views of bore out affect their reading of passenger needs, work engagement, and service-oriented organisational citizenship actions, according to the findings of structural equation modelling. Furthermore, both reading of passenger requirements and job engagement somewhat moderate the association between bore out and service-oriented organisational citizenship behaviours, according to these findings. In the link between bore out and service oriented organisational citizenship behaviours, the findings based on the use of phantom factors imply that work engagement is a more proximal variable to service oriented organisational citizenship behaviours than reading of passenger needs. In light of the foregoing findings, the penultimate section of the paper discusses implications for practise. The study developed a research model in which WENG mitigated the influence of boreout on service-oriented organisational citizenship behaviours by reading passenger demands. Authors used data collected from South Korean cabin crew to test these connections. All of the proposed connections were supported by empirical research. The findings imply that cabin crew view bore out as a major stressor that obstructs their ability to read passenger demands and negatively impacts their work engagement. It's worth noting that bore out has a far bigger negative influence on employee engagement than it does on passenger needs reading.

83. Chen, Ching-Fu, and Shu-Chuan Chen (2012) [5] Flight attendants are important in maintaining cabin safety and delivering services on board. Using an example of 305 Taiwanese flight attendants, this specific study used typically the job demands-resources unit to gauge burnout and even work engagement between cabin crew, while

well as typically the possible antecedents and even effects. There have been considerable rates regarding turnover intention and even health concerns activated by heavy workloads in various functioning conditions. The effects show that task demands are absolutely related to burnout, whereas job solutions are positively linked to work engagement although negatively related to be able to burnout when applying structural equation modelling to test typically the conceptual model. Additionally, health issues result in turnover intention and even become an intermediary between burnout and even turnover intention. Elevated degrees of work engagement can be useful inside lowering cabin staff turnover intentions.

84. Abramis, David J. (1994) [100] In this study, the structure of the link between stressors and job performance was investigated in order to analyse the potential positive effects of stress on job performance. The 281 respondents were a diverse demographic and organisational sample of people who worked in the Detroit area at the time of the study. They had been given Four formal in-home interviews were done over the period of 18 weeks, each around 6 weeks apart. Interviews were also conducted with a significant other from each respondent's work life who had been nominated by them. As stressors, role ambiguity, role conflict, and work uncertainty were all explored. As potential pressures, job dissatisfaction, anxiety, despair, and rage were all explored. Individual measurements were taken of the technical and social aspects of respondents' job performance, as well as absenteeism and tardiness. All zero-order Pearson correlations were statistically significant and pointing in the predicted directions, or they were essentially zero. All of the relationships were monotonic, indicating that the optimal levels of these stressors are frequently zero. The findings are explained using arousal and activation theory, information processing theory, and expectancy theory.

85. Bin, H. *et al.* (2017) [101] Numerous illnesses and injuries related to the workplace have been linked in large part to stress. As a result, there is a lot of interest in the subject. This research presents the results of a four-year stress study utilising an explanatory psychological model. The model provided in this research makes a connection between external pressures, stress, and occupational injury and disease by using the main stressors found in the Edinburgh Farm Survey Inventory. The overview of the theoretical framework and pertinent literature is provided in the study. Additionally, it includes early findings from phase one of the study's interviews with dairy and horticultural producers and representatives in New Zealand. Job stress is a result of stressors, and it has a detrimental impact on the job.

86. Dinh, L. (2020) [102] One of the most crucial aspects of human resource management is ensuring employee engagement in order to reduce organisational turnover. In order to have a strong labour force, employers frequently confront a variety of difficulties in figuring out how to boost connection with their workforce. This study examined the impact of various variables on job satisfaction in Vietnam's industrial sectors. The findings showed that employee engagement is positively impacted by work-life balance and workplace stress. The study's findings, however, did not support either the idea that a positive relationship with a supervisor might have a favourable impact on employee engagement or that working conditions may have such an effect. In terms of the mediation effect, work-life balance mediates the connection between working conditions and employee engagement in this study. Additionally, the relationship with the supervisor and employee engagement is mediated by work-life balance. Additionally, work stress acts as a mediator in the connection between working conditions and employee engagement. Last but not least, employee engagement and relationship with supervisor are mediated by work stress.

2.3.6 Emotional Labour:

87. Mutlu, Savaş, and Z. Benan Böke. (2020) [103] The goal of this study was to see if the demographics of cabin crew have an effect on their emotional work experiences. This study looked at the impact of demographic variables on the emotional work experiences of 265 Turkish airline flight attendants. Deep acting, surface acting, and actual feelings are the three dimensions of the emotional labour scale. Through the Internet, participants in the emotion work completed 13 items on a 5-point Likert scale. Six demographic characteristics questions were also addressed. To examine the item distribution for each component, an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was used (i.e., deep acting, surface acting, and actual emotions). To investigate differences in groups' emotional work experiences based on age, gender, position, marital status, overall work experience, and education, independent-sample t-tests and one-way ANOVA testing were utilised. Independent sample t-tests were used to compare differences between two groups, such as married-single, male-female, and flight attendant-supervisor. To analyse differences between three or more groups based on age, overall employment experience, and education, one-way ANOVA tests were used. Tukey's HSD tests were used to discern statistically distinct groups after one-way ANOVA tests. There were no statistically significant variations in the groups' expressions of emotional work, deep acting, surface acting, and true sentiments based

on gender, marital status, education, or age, according to the data. However, there are statistically significant distinctions between emotional work and surface acts performed by flight attendants and flight attendant supervisors. There is also a statistically significant difference in profound acting experience between cabin staff with 47 and 822 years of service.

88. Ho, Chien Wei, and Chi Chuan Wu (2019) [104] This study examines the impact of job design (perceived social impact and beneficiary interaction) on the psychological state of desire to enhance service quality and benefit others' lives, using the self-determination theory (SDT). The findings show that perceived social impact has a favourable influence on service quality via the mediating role of prosocial motivation, based on data obtained from 235 airline employees. Beneficiary contact also dampens the favourable impact of perceived social impact on prosocial drive. The discoveries can be actually executed through proper work plan, which permits representatives to see and communicate with clients because of their work. An all-around planned work not just urges representatives to work on the existences of their clients, yet it additionally increments administration quality. Our discoveries give a new perspective on the significant job of occupation plan in the carrier business.

89. Iqbal, Muhammad, and Indri Siti Hendarsih (2018) [105] The goal of this study is to determine the relationship between job satisfaction and emotional labour among Garuda Indonesia Airline cabin crew members. Purposive sampling was utilised to obtain data, with a sample size of 50 cabin workers. The data was obtained using a questionnaire based on Brotheridge and Lee's Emotional Labor Scale (ELS) and Spector's Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS), then processed using Pearson's correlation analysis product moment. The job satisfaction scale has a dependability rating of 0,954 and the emotional labour scale has a reliability value of 0,820. The correlation coefficients acquired -0,548 as a consequence of the investigation and analysis. These findings suggest that the cabin crew of Garuda Indonesia Airlines has a negative link between job satisfaction and emotional labour. That is, the lesser the emotional labour of the cabin staff, the better the level of job satisfaction. In contrast, the higher the emotional labour of the cabin staff, the lower the level of job satisfaction.

90. Lee, JungHoon, et al (2018) [106] This study suggested and evaluated a conceptual model outlining links between two types of emotional labour techniques, depersonalization and customer orientation, based on Hobfoll's conservation of

resources theory and Maslach's burnout theory (CO). Depersonalization, according to the hypothesis, acted as a mediator in the link between emotional labour and CO. The moderating effects of work position and job responsibility were assessed using multigroup analyses. These exchanges were studied using data from a Korean airline's cabin attendants, airport service employees, and call centre representatives. According to the results of structural equation modelling, deep acting has a positive effect on CO, but surface acting has a negative effect on CO. The statistics also demonstrate that low and high levels of depersonalization moderate these encounters, and that the strength of direct relationships varies by employee status and service work area. In light of the findings, theoretical and managerial ramifications are examined.

91. Hu, Hsin Yi, and Brian King (2017) [107] Contacts between in-cabin workers and aircraft passengers are becoming increasingly important for reasons of safety and service quality as air traffic grows in scale and breadth. Employees are placed in emotionally challenging situations as a result of such interactions, particularly when working in the restricted atmosphere of an airline cabin. Although most airline recruitment operations promote happy, smiling, and courteous personnel serving equally happy passengers, prospective hires may encounter a different reality. This study investigated the impact of customer misbehaviour on airline in-flight customer service staff. A theoretical framework was proposed to analyse the potential impact of role stress and emotional labour in the relationship between customer misbehavior and emotional exhaustion. 336 cabin crew members from international airlines participated in the poll. The anticipated model was tested using structural equation modelling using AMOS 20.0. (SEM). The data demonstrate that client misbehaviour is positively related to staff role stress, emotional labour, and emotional weariness. Furthermore, occupational stress and emotional labour play important roles in exacerbating the impacts of client misbehaviour and, as a result, influence staff emotional tiredness. The findings have the potential to influence employers both inside and beyond the airline industry by demonstrating how frontline staff can be assisted to reduce stress and fatigue, resulting in improved satisfaction. This study has provided researchers with a greater knowledge of client misbehaviour and how it affects staff role stress, emotional labour, and emotional exhaustion.

92. Jeon, Aeeun (2016) [108] According to previous study, the quality of on-board facilities offered by aircraft attendants has a significant impact on airline profitability. Flight attendants' performance is mostly influenced by their emotional intelligence (EI).

As a result, airlines strive to hire flight attendants with high emotional intelligence (EI) and to provide ongoing EI training once they are hired. A number of academies and schools have developed airline service programmes to address the demand for professional flight attendants. The impact of EI, emotional labour (EL), emotional exhaustion (EE), and commitment to customer service (CCS) on pre-flight attendants in undergraduate airline service programmes is investigated in this study. According to the study's findings, the better pre-flight attendants understand and use their emotions, the more they reveal their actual emotions and turn their negative feelings into the desired emotions needed for successful in-flight customer service. Furthermore, the more EL pre-flight attendants use, the more emotionally drained they get. This study adds to the existing body of information on EI, EL, EE, and CCS as the first study on pre-flight attendants' EI. The study's findings have practical ramifications as well, suggesting that strong EI evaluation and education provided by university-based airline service programmes can contribute to the excellence of airline service.

93. Bergman, Ann, and Gunnar Gillberg (2015) [109] In an industry progressively described by liberation and rivalry, this exposition researches how an airline Industry utilizes the work of a moderately aged cabin crews. The exploration depended on inside and out interviews with seven cabin crews who worked as cabin crews for somewhere in the range of 24 and 30 years of age. The article centres around the functioning circumstances and prosperity of ladies, and the examination shows three principal viewpoints escalation of work, weakness, and maturing that have an impact on cabin attendants' experiences and emotions at work. The cabin attendants' concerns must be grasped at the intersection of these three characteristics. Positive feelings such as job satisfaction and commitment have decreased as a result of exploitative and otherwise poor working conditions, according to the findings of the study. Using the cabin attendants' concerns as a starting point, the piece demonstrates the need to shift the conversation away from emotional labour and toward working conditions. The authors of this study emphasised three major features of cabin attendants' working circumstances as a result of their research. To begin with, their working circumstances have become more intense, reducing "the porosity of the working day." Second, when the strength of unions erodes and job conditions degrade, the work environment becomes more vulnerable. The third factor is ageing, and cabin attendants' concerns about their own health and well-being, as well as the possibility of being replaced by younger workers.

94. Baruah, Rithi, and Harold Andrew Patrick (2014) [110] The goal of this study is to look into the impact of emotional labour and its two forms-deep acting and surface acting-on airline employees' overall health. The study also attempts to see if emotional labour and its two types, deep acting and surface acting, have any effect on demographics. Gender, age, marital status, and employment tenure are among the demographics examined in the study. A quantitative research design is used in this investigation. Employees of airlines are given survey papers to fill out. A total of 295 airline employees took part in the research. 190 of the 295 members work as cabin crew, while 105 work as airline ground staff. According to the findings, emotional labour has no substantial impact on airline employees' overall health. Furthermore, neither deep nor surface acting has a major impact on employees' overall health. Deep and superficial emotional labour differs across demographics, according to the study. Female employees are subjected to higher emotional toil than male employees. Female employees also engage in more deep acting than their male counterparts. Employees between the ages of 31 and 35, as well as those with 11 to 15 years of work experience, are regarded to have greater emotional labour than their peers. This research has significant implications for industry HRM departments as well as Aviation Psychology in India. The study, however, is not without flaws. One of the study's key disadvantages is that it only covered airline cabin crew and airline ground staff, so it can't be applied to other groups.

95. Hur, Won-Moo, Tae Won Moon, and Jae-Kyoon Jun (2013) [111] The goal of this research was to see if and how perceived organisational support (POS) effects emotional labour, as well as the relationship between emotional labour and flight attendant results. A sample of 256 flight attendants in South Korea supported the assumptions using structural equation modelling. The findings showed that POS had a good influence on deep acting. Furthermore, surface acting has a favourable influence on emotional tiredness, whereas deep acting has a negative effect. Furthermore, emotional weariness lowers organisational commitment, which lowers turnover intention. Furthermore, POS altered the relationship between emotional weariness and deep vs surface acting. The current study added to the conceptual and experimental work on emotional labour by investigating the effect of POS on emotional regulation processes associated with emotional tiredness. This study also gives fresh light on customer service management in the airline business by analysing flight attendants' emotional labour, namely interactions with POS.

96. Chen, Ching-Fu, and Ya-Ling Kao (2012) [112] In the service business, frontline personnel are frequently faced with difficult and challenging conditions, like maintaining a smile while addressing demanding or rude customers. Emotional labour refers to employees' ability to manage their emotions as a part of their job function, still because the consequences of doing so. Emotional labour, within which the manifestation of organizationally desired emotions is required as a part of one's job, has aroused the interest of academics and practitioners alike. Flight attendants, who are defined as performing "emotional labour," regularly experience stress on the work, which may cause poor job performance and health problems. Using the task demand-resources paradigm, this study investigates the relationships between job demands, job resources, burnout, colleague isolation, health concerns, and job performance for flight attendants. To gather empirical data from Taiwanese airline flight attendants, a self-administered questionnaire is being employed. Employing a structural equation modelling technique, the researchers discovered that burnout mediates the link between job demands and health issues, which colleague isolation mediates the connection between job resources and job performance. Theoretical and empirical implications are given and debated.

97. Chen, Ching-Fu, and Ya-Ling Kao (2011) [113] Flight attendants, who are described as performing "emotional labour," are frequently exposed to stress on the job, which can result in poor job performance and health problems. Using the job demand-resources (JDeR) paradigm, this study investigates the relationships between job demands, job resources, exhaustion, colleague loneliness, health concerns, and job performance for flight attendants. Taiwanese airline flight attendants are being polled via a self-administered questionnaire to gather empirical data. Burnout mediates the relationship between job demands and health problems, and colleague isolation mediates the relationship between job resources and job performance, according to the researchers, who used a structural equation modelling technique. Theoretical and empirical implications are examined and given.

98. Waddar, Mahadevi S., and Vijaylaxmi A. Aminabhavi (2012) [114] Emotional labour is a type of emotional control in which employees are expected to express specific emotions as part of their job in order to help the organisation achieve its objectives. Positive emotional displays in service contacts, such as smiling and expressing friendliness, have been linked to crucial customer outcomes such as the intention to return, the intention to recommend a store to others, and the overall feeling

of service quality, according to study. It can be incredibly tiring to be in charge of the safety of multiple planes and their passengers. Airhostesses and pilots are stressed and must control their emotions as a result. This study will look into the emotional labour and organisational role stress faced by pilots, airhostesses, and air traffic controllers. 90 airline employees were given an emotional labour scale and an organisational role stress scale. A one-way ANOVA test revealed that the three groups of aviation workers differ considerably in terms of emotional labour and organisational role stress. Air traffic controllers, in particular, have substantially more organisational role stress than pilots and airhostesses, whereas airhostesses experience significantly more emotional labour than pilots and air traffic controllers. The components that contributed significantly to emotional labour and organisational role stress among airline staff, according to a stepwise multiple regression analysis. The study's findings will assist airline management authorities in developing various measures to reduce emotional labour and organisational role stress.

99. Chen, Ching-Fu, and Ya-Ling Kao (2011) [115] Flight attendants are commonly described as performing work that can lead to emotional tiredness in individuals who have little workplace autonomy and work long hours. Even in challenging conditions, such as dealing with unpleasant or belligerent passengers, flight attendants are needed to display positive feelings as part of their work. Emotional work is demanding, and it can lead to higher absenteeism and voluntary turnover. The specific antecedents of career stress, such as work-to-family and family-to-work conflicts, as well as the desired outcomes, such as career satisfaction, institutional dedication, and turnover motives, of flight family and friends who are generally characterised as performing "emotional labour," are investigated in this study. Using a sample of flight attendants from Taiwanese airlines, the researchers identified evidence of the following correlations: family-work conflict/job stress/job satisfaction/organisational commitment/turnover intention. Between August and October 2008, a self-administered questionnaire was used to collect data from a sample of Taiwanese flight attendants by snowball sampling. After removing any incomplete surveys, 500 questionnaires were sent out, with 252 valid responses.

100. Chang, Cheng-Ping, and C. H. I. U. Ju-Mei (2009) [116] Handful of studies have explored the 2 main variables involving emotional labour together with emotional exhaustion, together with even fewer currently have used flight family and friends as

subjects. By using a questionnaire approach, the actual study explored 353 Taiwanese flight attendants' feelings about mental labour, the condition of their mental weariness, and typically the relationship between mental work and mental exhaustion. The studies show that: 1) while female flight attendants' emotional time is moderate to be able to high, their conception of emotional weariness is only average; 2) female flight attendants' emotional time has an important positive correlation having their emotional weariness; and 3) between the perspectives involving emotional labour, typically the qualities of "deep emotional masking" together with "multiformity" have some sort of significant predictive effectiveness.

101. Sonnentag, Sabine, and Eva Natter (2004) [117] Working in the service business is a very stressful job. Academics classify service vocations' obligations as "emotional labour" or "emotion work." Morris and Feldman define emotional work as "the effort, planning, and control required to communicate organizationally desired feelings during interpersonal encounters." Kindergarten teachers, contact centre staff, and front-desk employees are examples of jobs that require a high level of emotion. This article describes the findings of a study conducted with flight attendants, a group of professionals who face very high emotional demands at work. This article builds on past studies on work recovery during off-work time, with a focus on flight attendants, a group of professionals whose occupations include a high level of emotional work demands. 47 flight attendants completed daily surveys on a total of four evenings, whether they stayed at home or at a hotel. According to a multilevel investigation, staying in a hotel had no effect on well-being before night. Spending time on work-related activities during off-work time reduced well-being, whereas spending time on physical activities (i.e., sports) and experiencing off-work time activities as recuperation enhanced well-being, even after controlling for immediate post-work well-being. The amount of time spent in the evening on social activities boosts the risk of depression. In general, the outcomes of this study support prior research undertaken with diverse professional groups.

102. Williams, Claire (2003) [118] This study draws on this literature to investigate emotional labour as a gendered cultural performance, but it takes issue with the individualising and pluralistic tone of the post-Hochschild debates. It employs a qualitative and quantitative study of approximately 3000 Australian flight attendants to examine organisational and occupational health and safety variables, as well as sexual

harassment and passenger abuse-concerns that Hochschild's critics have generally neglected. The qualitative results show that emotional labour can be both joyful and stressful for the same person at various times. As Hochschild pointed out, gender remains a key factor in the relationship between emotional labour and sexual harassment. At the same time, the quantitative investigation found that the most important indicators of whether emotional labour would be costly were organisational factors. The airline management context is very crucial in terms of how emotional labour is perceived, as indicated by characteristics like whether flight attendants felt respected by the organisation. The article also introduces a new concept, 'demanding publics,' to refer to violations of the legitimate boundaries of service workers in this important and eroticized area of service work, where flight attendants, airline crews, airline management, and passengers have convergent and competing interests.

103. Heuven, Ellen, and Arnold Bakker (2003) [119] The authors used 220 cabin attendants in this study to explore the hypothesis that emotional dissonance is a primary predictor of human service burnout. According to the authors, in addition to the "conventional" features in Karasek's (1979, 1998) demands-control model, emotional dissonance would provide an independent contribution to explaining variance in burnout (i.e., emotional exhaustion and depersonalization). This notion was supported by the results of a series of SEM investigations. Furthermore, emotional dissonance predicted burnout in cabin attendants more accurately than quantitative job demands or job control. Furthermore, according to Leiter's (1993) paradigm, emotional fatigue was found to have an essential mediating function between work characteristics and depersonalization. The claimed relationship between job demands and job control, as well as these two variables and emotional dissonance, was not proven. Finally, the findings of exploratory qualitative analyses highlight the significance of viewing emotion work as a dynamic process that the human care professional actively manages through contact, reciprocity, and learning.

104. Chu, Kay Hei-Lin (2002) [120] The extent to which one's inner feelings or outward behaviour are managed in order to convey the proper emotion in accordance with display guidelines or occupational norms is referred to as emotional labour. The purpose of this study is to develop an emotional work model for the hotel sector, with the goal of identifying the causes and effects of emotional labour. The study investigates the impact of individual traits on how emotional labour is performed, as

well as the linkages between various methods of performing emotional labour and their outcomes. It also investigates whether organisational and work features have a mitigating effect on emotional weariness and job satisfaction, both of which are seen as outcomes of emotional labour. The Hospitality Emotional Labor Scale, a 10-item scale, was extensively constructed for this study to assess the emotional labour performed by personnel. The outcomes of the study are consistent with a two-factor emotional labour structure: emotive dissonance and emotive effort. Employees engage in three categories of service acting: surface acting, deep acting, and true acting. The scale was used to poll 285 hotel employees. Structured equation modelling (SEM) and moderated multiple regression (MMR) were used to evaluate the suggested model and test the hypotheses. Surface acting (high emotional dissonance) and deep acting (emotive effort) were found to be positively related to job satisfaction and negatively related to emotional weariness. Genuine behaviour (low emotional dissonance) was found to be positively and negatively related to emotional tiredness and job satisfaction. In this study, no strong links were found between the antecedents (affectivity and empathy) and the emotional labour components. PREVIEW other moderators (job autonomy and social support) were likewise demonstrated to have no effect on the correlations between emotional labour and its results. Finally, the research revealed that, while both deep and superficial acting provide positive work outcomes, real acting produces negative work outcomes. The findings corroborate prior qualitative studies. Deep acting is also an important factor in determining how well employees perform at work. Based on these important study findings, theoretical and practical repercussions were thoroughly addressed.

105. Young, Joana L., and Erika Hayes James (2001) [121] The work experiences of men, the conventional workplace majority, as minority members of a female-dominated occupation were investigated in this study. The authors proposed and tested a set of hypotheses based on tokenism and social categorization theories that link token status (a less than 15% minority) with male flight attendants' work attitudes via intervening psychological and occupational factors. Low self-esteem, increased role ambiguity, and poor job fit were found to buffer a negative link between token status and work attitudes of job satisfaction and organisational attachment in a study of 236 male and female flight attendants. The finding of these hitherto unmeasured intervening variables verifies theoretical linkages between demography and work outcomes while also identifying leverage points for influencing minority workers' work attitudes.

106. Ashforth, Blake E., and Ronald H. Humphrey (1993) [122] Emotional labour is the expression of anticipated emotions by service agents during service activities. It is performed by surface behaviour, deep behaviour, or exhibiting actual emotion. Emotional work can motivate activity performance and self-expression, but it can also foster consumer needs that should not be fulfilled, leading to emotional conflict and self-isolation. Nonetheless, according to the concept of sociable identity, some impacts of emotional work are mitigated by social and personal identification, and emotional labour increases pressure to dissociate from the service role. The document examines the implications of the research for microorganisms, Mesos, and macro-organizations.

2.4 RELATION BETWEEN STRESSOR AGENT, WORKPLACE STRESS, STRESS COPING STRATEGY AND WORK ENGAGEMENT:

2.4.1 Stressors and Workplace Stress: As the study intended to analyse the impact of stressors on workplace stress, key stressors were firstly identified which impacts the workplaces stress from the above reviewed articles. This section describes various previous studies which show a relationship between each variables pertaining to study in order to establish hypothesis. The various identified stressor agents along with its hypothetical relations are described as follows:

2.4.1.1 Irregular Working Hour and Workplace Stress: Numerous earlier studies have shown that irregular working hours are associated with increased levels of fatigue, stress, performance declines, unhealthy behaviours, and both acute and chronic physical disorders [123]. There is also growing recognition within the scientific community that long working hours, particularly when combined with other unfavourable aspects of work organisation like irregular working hours and intense performance demands, are detrimental to health. Studies over a longer period of time are currently being conducted to better understand the temporal process by which irregular and extended work hours may cause acute and then chronic health consequences [124]. There have already been attempts to control extreme working hours in occupations where the effects of weariness and fatigue connected to extended work hours may negatively impact the public [125]. There were both positive and negative aspects to the psychosocial environment that overtime workers encountered. For instance, working overtime was linked to a heavier workload and a sense that not enough people or time were available to do the project. Additionally, overtime workers

reported having harder times taking time off due to the increased demands of their jobs (such as "working very fast") and fewer hours available for personal pursuits. At the same time, however, overtime workers reported generally higher levels of participation in decision-making and the chance to develop their own unique abilities, two factors frequently thought to be important in fostering a positive work environment [126][127]. It is possible to make recommendations for the management of fatigue risk given the irregular and lengthy work schedules with frequent night flights that were observed in this airline [128-129]. These recommendations include workplace (task distribution among cabin crews, responsibility and adequate rest), awareness and education apprenticeship programs (sleep, wakefulness adjustment, regular exercise, nourishment, comfortability), and specific countermeasures, like onboard meals [39]. based on the above argument it can be stated that irregular working hour has remarkable impact on workplace stress.

2.4.1.2 Work Hassles and Workplace Stress: Troubles are stresses, just as chronic stressors and stressful life events, according to earlier research [130-131]. Chronic stresses are described as any situation that, in an individual's opinion, forces them to modify or readjust their way of life or conduct [132]. The occurrence of distinct events and the occurrence of ongoing issues are the two basic causes of chronic stressors [131]. There are distinction between the three ideas of hassles, persistent stressors, and stressful life events. Physiological work pressures brought on by vibration and noise in the cabin, physical ailments brought on by jet lag, and long work hours are all features of the cabin crew profession, according to [133-136]. Cabin crew members are subjected to unfavourable working conditions while performing their duties, according to [137]. These conditions include unpredictable shift patterns [135], potential airline safety accidents, noise and vibration, a lack of available workspace [34], and passengers' disorderly in-flight behaviour [138], as well as strict workplace conditions and airline guidelines that boost their workload [135]. They feel bothered by the tension they experience when on duty. Second, they collaborate with team members, sometimes including individuals they never had worked with before. In order for the cabin crew to function as a cohesive unit and meet the demands of the passengers while on duty, they must blend their characteristics to facilitate teamwork. Because of the absence of tacit understanding and the lack of familiarity amongst coworkers, conflicts frequently arise while doing their jobs, which frustrates the flight attendants [141]. Third, [41] made the case that the primary responsibility of cabin staff is to deliver passenger services. When

they interact with demanding or rude customers, their services can be seen as competent and calm; yet, displaying the reactions that customers anticipate from them might be stressful [5]. Additionally, compared to other industries, female cabin crew are more susceptible to passenger sexual harassment [142-143], posing a unique set of issues. Last but not least, being front-line workers in the airline sector, cabin crew frequently go abroad, making it challenging for them to maintain regular social ties with family and friends, both at home and at work [18][144].

The word "hassle" was first used to refer to "irritating, aggravating, upsetting demands that to some extent characterise regular transactions with the environment" [145] and the disagreeable challenges that people deal with on a daily basis. [146] Hassles are role-related pressures that occur every day. Previous research has shown that inconveniences can have a negative impact on both personal and professional outcomes. Highly negative outcomes include unpleasant feelings like anger, worry, and disappointment, as well as poor mental and physical health, as well as dissatisfaction with one's life and family [147–149]. Additionally, unfavourable effects of the workplace include burnout, tension, tiredness, and an increase in the subjective burden [150–152]. Prior research on cabin crew has generally concentrated on high-performance work practices, leadership, organisational commitment, work engagement, work stress, burnout, emotional labour, and cabin crew scheduling [153–158]. As was already established, problems can have a negative impact on cabin crew members' personal and professional lives. Few studies, however, have examined the kinds of difficulties that might be present in the professional and private life of cabin crew. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to examine the inconveniences that cabin crew members suffer in order to make recommendations for minimising adverse personal and professional results. Related research has been done on the types of difficulties [21].

2.4.1.3 Air Craft Cabin Environment and Workplace Stress: Studies on the cabin atmosphere of aircraft have also revealed that it affects the quality of life for the cabin crew. The majority of us are used to functioning at sea level, yet aircraft are not pressurized to that level. Although the exact altitude of the airplane is significantly higher, the pressure inside the cabin ranges from 1.828 to 2.438 meters, which is comparable to someone on a small hill. Less oxygen and gas expansion inside the body are the two things that put stress on the body. If a person does not have a heart, lung, or

blood condition, their body can adapt to the lower oxygen content, which is around 7% less than at water level. Gas can cause discomfort or issues in the stomach (bloating or cramping), ears (cracking noises or ear obstruction), and respiratory/sinus difficulties when cabin altitude rises and expands in the body by up to 25% [159]. Despite the positive sample characteristics-relative youth, lower seniority (activity exposure), freedom from obligations, and healthy lifestyles-previous research have shown that weariness and the associated health symptoms are present among airline cabin crew. There are a number of environmental and work-related elements that contribute to weariness and that need to be addressed. The absence of moisture inside the cabin has a much greater impact on senior employees, who also have more stomach and sleep issues. As people get older and experience more of this activity, they may become more fatigued and experience health issues, including poor sleep. With regard to the low seniority discovered in this study, we might make the speculative suggestion that there may be some form of natural selection, causing persons with greater difficulties to leave the organization or the job of flight attendant. In addition, women typically complain more about physical pain and other fatigue symptoms than men do, and they tend to be more influenced by a variety of factors that contribute to weariness. The fact that men tend to sleep more soundly than women could be one answer for this gender disparity. Although the air hostess duty and rest regulations, several airlines are starting to adopt the minimum crew member rest duration as standard procedure. Since this minimal rest period does not match to the actual rest period, it may result in less sleep (only four to six hours). For instance, it also takes into account the time needed for a flight attendant to leave the airport, get through the customs, if necessary, find a ride to a hotel, and check in [47]. Crewmember weariness is substantially impacted by rostering considerations (such as scheduling of flights and service periods like night shifts, brief rest periods, back-to-back early hours starts, extended duty durations, back-to-back duty days, and others), which poses serious issues for flight operations. Crew weariness is a serious safety concern that is impacted by rosters and increases the likelihood of errors, mishaps, and accidents. Deteriorated alertness and performance are typically caused by lost sleep and circadian body clock abnormalities brought on by rostering variables. Additionally, crew members' moods and communication abilities may be altered, and their judgement or decision-making may be compromised. Reaction times may also slow down. Crew members' sleepiness, difficulty focusing, sleep issues, sluggish reaction times, and irritability are typical symptoms of fatigue. Additionally,

crew members may have health problems including melancholy or reduced immunity as a result of the inadequate rosters. According to our observations, crew members with greater experience may be more susceptible to weariness, which is most closely attributable to their age [78]. This observation strongly depicts the impact of air craft cabin environment on workplace stress.

2.4.1.4 Social Isolation and Workplace Stress: The front-line staff that interact with passengers on behalf of airlines are known as the cabin crew. Because of regularity of flight assignments vary with high season and off-seasons, the schedule for flight jobs is particularly erratic. For instance, when cabin crew travels abroad, they must stay there for at least 7 days and must miss significant family events or holiday celebrations. Therefore, because it is challenging for them to maintain regular social ties with their friends and family, cabin crew frequently experience problems between work and family [18][144]. According to [156], the rise in work-family disputes will make front-line workers anxious and tense, have a bad effect on their health, and cause bother. Cabin crew may interact with a variety of people in their professional and personal lives, including airlines, co-workers, passengers, family, and friends, as was previously noted. The cabin crew may experience work-family conflict, emotional weariness, emotional labour, and workplace stress, all of which have been covered in previous research. When compared to previous studies on the difficulties faced by practitioners of a certain occupation, these unfavourable work-related results are consistent [160-161][146].

The aforementioned issues have increased researchers' interest in psychological stressors connected to work. This issue is a result of changing conditions in the nature of the job, as well as the drastic change in economic globalisation, use of information and contemporary communication technology, and increased workplace diversity [162-163]. As a result, there are more claims of mental health issues in the workplace. Work stresses are the second most prevalent workplace issue that have a negative impact on general health, according to the European Working Conditions Survey [164]. Back discomfort is the first issue and is closely related to chronic health issues like heart disease and musculoskeletal illnesses [165]. Since they may have an impact on workers' health, productivity, and performance, workplace stresses have grown to be a serious concern. Physical disturbances, productivity loss, and increased absence are just a few of the detrimental effects of workplace pressures, which financially strain

organisations as a result. Workplace stress can take many different forms and have varied effects on various people [166]. All these above discussion directed the researchers attention towards remarkable impact of various stressors on workplace stress.

2.4.2 Workplace Stress and Work Engagement: Numerous research on workplace stress have found behavioural symptoms that are very comparable to those [167] characterised as coming from disengaged workers. While [168] did not provide the word "disengagement," he did mention a common pattern of behaviour in stressed-out persons, saying that these people will "strive to limit net loss of resources." They so restrict their involvement to the extent that it endangers their resources [169]-Occupational stress and disengagement [170]. Positioned otherwise, this implies that workers who are somewhat stressed will also be more likely to remain engaged. The term "engagement" refers to "an individual's involvement and contentment with as well as passion for work"[171], according to research done with more than 8,000 U.S. companies across a variety of industries. The opposite (or antipode) of burnout, according to some of the most productive researchers in the field, is involvement. Since burnout and disengagement are synonymous, it is implied by their frameworks that an engaged person cannot be burned out [172–173]. One of these, which is also the most widely used, operationalizes engagement as "the positive, rewarding job state of mind that is marked by vigour, devotion, and absorption"[174]-burnout as disengagement. One of the most crucial aspects of human resource management is ensuring employee engagement in order to reduce organisational turnover. In order to establish a great labour force, employers frequently confront a range of problems in figuring out how to boost engagement with their workforce [102]. Front-line workers like cabin crew play crucial roles in the aviation industry. Their work engagement, quality of work, and overall health will all suffer if they are bothered by problems in their personal and professional lives in the form of stress [21].

2.4.3 Stress Coping Strategies: Any person can be threatened by stress on any level. A person who experiences these pressures on a daily basis may suffer harmful repercussions. A person's performance may be affected and rendered incapable of carrying out everyday chores if they are unable to cope with and adjust to various stressors. This reduces their willingness to work, which leads to depletion and fatigue. This condition encourages a person to create a strategy to assist them understand and

cope with stressful events better, enabling them to manage issues through an individual psychological way of coping that works for them. Through stress coping techniques, these techniques can reduce levels of stress. Because people react to stressful events in a way that helps them avoid, flee, or lessen the severity of a situation and create a balance that balances the stress, psychologists characterised coping with stress as responding [174]. Stress coping techniques are methods or tools people use to deal with stress. According to Spielberg, they are a talent used to reduce or get rid of stimuli that one perceives as being dangerous. When it comes to Cohen and Lazarus, they defined them as any attempt made by a person to manage their stress [175]. To deal with the physical, psychological, and cognitive responses brought on by stressors, there are many different skills and strategies. A person will recuperate by some of the reactions when they deal with the identify and focus, and vice versa. Take note that these reactions interact with one another. Similar to this, managing emotional responses may aid in achieving more rational and balanced thought, which in turn lessens the severity of the stress [176-177]. As per the study done on pilots, the majority of pilots were shown to have medium to low levels of work-related stress. Most people there utilised an emotion-focused stress management technique. Some pilots find that problem-solving and social support are useful stress-reduction techniques [98]. The research' findings revealed that while aggression, anxiety, depression, perceived stress, and job dissatisfaction were relatively low or low among flight attendants who were actively employed, fatigue levels were moderately high. Modifiable job stressors, such as cognitive and/or psychological job requirements, an imbalance between job requirements and outside obligations, a lack of supervisor support, role ambiguity, and emotional load, even for less common outcomes, were found to be significant predictors of their variance (job dissatisfaction). Since some of these workplace stressors were discovered to coexist, it's possible that their combined impact is crucial again for prediction of discomfort. The effects of some occupational stresses were shown to be mitigated by support networks (from all examined sources), whereas the effects of other stressors were found to be exacerbated by a lack of support. The findings of this study suggested that efforts to embrace stress coping strategies at work, reduce the prevalence of particular job stressors, and improve social assistance may be important to boosting the well-being and satisfaction of flight attendants [34]. This was true even though mental harm and dissatisfaction levels were not excessive.

Overall, it can be concluded that stress at work has a detrimental impact on job satisfaction and overall well-being [101].

Previous studies have exhibited that stressors such as irregular working hours, work hassles, aircraft cabin environment and social isolation creates workplace stress which negatively impacts performance and job satisfaction that means it reduces work engagement among the employees. With this regard stress coping strategies can be a major player to reduce the negative impact. Hence, the above discussion gave hints towards formulation of the following hypothesis, which will be developed as a conceptual model, to test and prove it among selected population i.e., cabin crews working in international airports, of Karnataka.

2.5 CONCLUSION

Extensive review of literature on stress has enabled a researcher to divide the major stressors into four indicators and all the literature have been categorised based on their similar nature. Furthermore, some of the studies only concentrated on cabin crews hence it was divided under the head cabin crews. Moreover, studies concerning workplace stress, work engagement and stress coping strategies have separately categorised for an easy retrieval of previous findings on this matter. Keeping the various identified constructs as a base, the researcher attempted to assess the impact of each construct on each other. The previous scholarly research gave a direction to understand the relationship among the constructs and indicator which again helped to frame the hypothesis pertaining to study. This chapter is a foundation to obtain a theoretical base for further analysis and results.

CHAPTER-III

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 EVOLUTION OF TRANSPORTATION

Transportation's evolution, like that of people, has been beset with obstacles and setbacks as it has developed over time. Various kinds of transportation have emerged in the past, while many more have vanished. Our modes of transportation have progressed in lockstep with the advancement of our human understanding and civilization. As a result, our greatest challenges and barriers have sparked our most innovative breakthroughs, propelling us from where we are today to where we want to be. Transportation technology has been instrumental in many of our most significant sociological and teleological breakthroughs. It will continue to do so in the distant future, just as it has done in the distant past. Man has met a wide variety of forms of transport, ranging from bullock carts to aircrafts, from the stone age of antiquity to the present-day modern world.

Evolution of Aviation

For more than 2,000 years, mankind has expanded its efforts to examine the skies with man-made flying objects, resulting in a greater understanding of the universe. The history of aeronautics began with the invention of kites and lightweight planes, which eventually led to the development of the multimillion-dollar aviation industry that exists today. It was during the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries that the discovery of hydrogen resulted in the first significant progress of the hydrogen expansion, which diverted people at great heights and over long distances, mostly in the United Kingdom. As early as the nineteenth century, attached inflatables were used to transfer people and observe combat securely over the ground as they took place on the battlefield. Other logical revelations accumulated to form a collection of mechanics hypotheses that served as the foundation for Isaac Newton's laws of motion and liquid elements, which in turn paved the way for the development of today's streamlined features. The development of lightweight planes in the mid-twentieth century served as a precursor to the development of monstrous airplanes, motor innovation, and subsequent advancements in streamlined characteristics.

Indian Aeronautical Industry

India's aviation industry is one of the world's fastest-growing aviation markets, with an annual growth rate of more than 20%. The Airports Authority of India (AAI) operates 126 airports and civil enclaves in India, out of a total of 449 airports and airstrips

throughout the country. The AAI is a government-owned corporation. A total of roughly 100 airports/aerodromes handles commercial passenger flights on a daily basis. Airfields owned by private companies (or joint ventures) serve the cities of Bengaluru, Delhi, Hyderabad, Kochi, Kolkata, Mumbai, Navi Mumbai, Ahmedabad, Goa, Lucknow and Mangalore. In 2018, more than 341 million passengers passed through India's airports. India has the world's third largest domestic civil aviation industry, trailing only the United States and China in terms of size. Because of low flight fares, increased demand for domestic air travel, and a continuous high level of tourism, the aviation job market has become a popular entry point for aspirants.

Expansion of the Indian Aviation Industry

The Indian aviation business has a lengthy history and has transitioned from private to public ownership before returning to a mix of public and private ownership. As time has gone on, the transportation industry has seen a substantial improvement in the movement of traffic, both in the passenger and freight segments. Indian brand equity is ranked 9th in terms of market size, according to the India Brand Equity Survey Report published in 2017.

As India's aviation sector continues to grow at an accelerated pace, the country is reaping the benefits of greater connectivity throughout the world. The sector has undergone numerous transformations since its inception. Because of the country's extensive geographic expanse as well as its rapid economic development, the aviation industry has become increasingly important. The increasing number of working people and the economic progress of the Indian middle class are also predicted to contribute to the continued growth of the sector. Consequently, as a result of the increasing demand, the Indian government intends to raise the number of airports to 250 by the year 2030. This development in infrastructure has occurred as a result of an increase in both commercial and recreational tourism. The development of ground infrastructure is a critical demand for the aviation industry [1].

This type of resilient nature cannot be developed by the government alone; it requires the participation of private players. More crucially, the private sector has the expertise to create a technologically advanced airport, which is urgently required. Another area on which the government is concentrating these days is the development of green airports in order to lessen the environmental impact. Increasing foreign direct investment (FDI) up to 49 percent through automatic route in the case of air transport

is being done to encourage greater participation by private firms in the industry. This means that an industry that was dominated by government entities is now working in tandem with private sector companies. The rising level of competition in the market contributes to the improvement of both on- and off-airport services.

Cabin Crews

Cabin crew members operate in a demanding workplace where they are subjected to high levels of emotional stress and are required to put on a show for the passengers [179]. Crew members are on board an aircraft to ensure passenger safety and comfort. Even if no food or drink is provided, a minimum cabin crew presence is required for safety reasons in the UK. Cabin crew members must give exceptional customer service while remaining cheery, approachable, and enthusiastic at all times, as well as maintaining a professional look, because they represent the airline's public image. Cabin crew work can be physically hard, and you must be willing to work on any given day of the year, regardless of the weather. On the other side, this presents you with a fantastic opportunity to break out from the monotony of a regular 9-to-5 job. Cabin crew may encounter a range of situations when operating on board an aircraft. In order to succeed, they must be strong team players who can also operate independently, utilizing quick thinking and organizational skills.

Responsibility of the Cabin Crew

They must attend a safety briefing with the pilots and lead flight attendants before each trip. During the safety and emergency checklists, they review the locations and quantities of emergency equipment, as well as other aircraft-specific details. Passengers with special needs, small children travelling alone, and VIPs all have their information checked before boarding the plane. The meteorological conditions, as well as the risk of turbulence, are mentioned. Before each flight, an inspection is conducted to check that all safety equipment, such as life vests, torches (flashlights), and firefighting equipment, is present and in proper operating order on board, as well as that everything is in the correct condition and location. Prior to takeoff, any items that are not in working order or are missing must be reported and corrected. They need to be on the lookout for any unusual odour or conditions in the cabin. They help with carry-on baggage loading by inspecting it for weight, size, and the presence of hazardous materials. They check to determine if persons sat in emergency escape rows are willing

and capable of participating in an evacuation, and if they aren't, they are moved out of the row and into another seat. They must next do a safety demonstration or keep an eye on passengers while watching a safety film. They must next "secure the cabin," ensuring, among other things, that tray tables are stowed, chairs are upright, armrests are down, carry-ons are correctly stored, and seat belts are secured before take-off. Pre-Departure All services offered between the time of boarding and the moment of take-off are referred to as service [13-16].

Once in the air, flight attendants frequently provide passengers with food and drinks. When not serving customers, flight attendants must routinely examine the cabin for unusual sounds or happenings. Check the restroom to make sure the smoke detector isn't off and that supplies are replaced as needed. Regular cockpit inspections are essential for the pilot's health and safety. They must also respond to particular requests that activate call lights. To keep the cabin safe during turbulence. All loose things, including trays, trash, and garbage cans, must be collected and secured before landing. Warm liquids must be appropriately disposed. Then comes the final cabin inspection before landing. For take-off, flight attendants must be alert at all times. Flight attendants must remain stationed at the exits after landing to keep an eye on the plane and the cabin. On arrival at the airport, they assist those with special needs and young children to the designated person for pick-up, while completing the necessary papers and ID.

Flight attendants are trained a number of skills, including basic first aid. Emergency training covers topics such as rejected take-offs, emergency landings, cardiac and in-flight medical situations, smoke in the cabin, fires, depressurization, on-board births and deaths, dangerous goods and spills, hijackings, water landings, and survival skills for the sea, forest, arctic, and desert.

Due to COVID-19, the aviation industry has been in a slump since 2020, with difficulty in maintaining jobs and infrastructure. The number of international and domestic airport users decreased in most of the counties, for example from Korea the users decreased by 58.8% from the previous year as a result of the epidemic. The situation at Incheon International Airport, which serves the majority of domestic passengers, is deteriorating. According to the Korea Tourism Organization's 2020 report [29]., the number of travellers utilizing Incheon International Airport last year was around 12.05 million, or one-sixth of the previous year. With reference to the 1.7 percent fall in 2008,

when the financial crisis hit [20][88]. This is the first time in 12 years that a decline has occurred. Since then, productivity has been a major concern in the aviation industry. Many airlines prioritize increasing employee productivity through effective use of current resources [180-184].and they maximize techniques to reduce maintenance costs. “Technology” has become an incontrovertible truth and the glue that ties aviation together due to the tighter error margin in the flying industry. Others argue that technological innovation improves road security (aircraft security), and refer to it as the "bedrock of revolution" for better efficiency and decreasing working challenges [185-187].

3.2 STRESS-DEFINITION, EXPLANATION AND IMPORTANCE OF STRESS

Stress refers to a person's physical reaction to a danger or demand. This can be useful in short bursts, such as when you need to get out of a dangerous situation or achieve a goal. Stress, on the other hand, can have a negative impact on a person's health if it lasts for a long time. A person's capacity to work might also be harmed by stress. Stress can be beneficial or harmful. It is called eustress when it is positive and is produced by enthusiasm or a positive occurrence. Distress is the term for negative stress, which is significantly more common. Distress is a physiological imbalance that can lead to physical and mental difficulties ranging from mild to severe. The cognitive activation theory of stress explains the entire stress process (CATS).

CATS defines "stress" as a four-stage psychobiological concept (Figure 3.1). The first step is orienting. The focus is on a stressor, which reflects objective internal or external inputs that the brain automatically processes and evaluates.

Figure 3.1: Cognitive activation theory of stress [185]

In the second level, the brain filters inputs based on individual learning history, assessing or anticipating stress. In CATS, learning history includes both classical and operant conditioning-driven stimulus expectancies. These expectations shape the severity and extent of the third stage, the physiological stress reaction. The physiological stress response is a generic, non-specific arousal response in the somatic and autonomic nervous systems, as well as different endocrine axes [184]. The alarm sounds when a homeostatic imbalance is expected, such as when new or frightening stimuli are encountered, or when expectations and reality differ. Final stage of the definition represents individual experience of stress reaction, which involves information from arousal response being returned to the brain, thereby retaining, adding to, or resolving the unpleasant sense of stress.

According to CATS, stress is a useful and adaptable reaction, meaning that inducing a stress response in tough situations is helpful and adaptive. The goal of a temporary activation of the physiological stress response is to re-establish homeostasis [185], and the arousal response is eventually switched off when the individual expects to handle the challenge effectively. Arousal may be maintained otherwise, resulting in illness and disease. The stress reaction is either erased, muted, or maintained depending on the expectation filters used [184]. These filters are referred to as "stimulus expectancies" and "response result expectancies."

Mental illness has both direct and indirect effects on a person. People cope with stress in various ways. Recognizing stressors and the symptoms which result from exposure to those stresses, according to experts, is the first step in managing. Developing or retaining a balanced lifestyle that includes adequate rest, physical activity, good food, the consumption of alcoholic beverages to a minimum, and the avoidance of tobacco products, among other things. Hans Selye created the term "stress" in 1926 after observing glandular abdominal alterations in rats (research animals) as a result of the hormone injection. He used the term "stress" to describe the body's nonspecific response to a strain placed on it. Stress, according to Lazarus, is a mental condition that occurs when an individual's coping mechanisms are exhausted in the face of a frightening situation [186].

Stress in Aviation Sector

Modern tourism is frequently exemplified by the aviation sector. The level of customer service offered has a significant impact on how efficiently the aviation industry operates. Flight control centre management, managing baggage and load control, supporting customers need for travel advice at the counters, checking in passengers, offering support in the Lounge area, and a variety of other duties fall under the purview of aviation customer services. The principal sites for employees who work in airline customer service are airports and airfields.

However, there are significant practical difficulties about these conclusions being reached in an impulsive manner. Take, for example, technostress, which is the negative side of technology that has major repercussions. A technical value, or an optimistic adaptive technological sickness [188], can be defined as follows: When it comes to operating in a constantly evolving and changing work environment with conceptually and technically defined responsibilities, technology is mostly an add-on to the mix. Furthermore, according to the researchers, "air travelling" is one of the most stressful occupations [189]. Rapid technological advancements produce techno-stress [190], as a result of the overload, uncertainty, and complexity associated with them.

As an added bonus, an abundance of artefacts and management tools that surpass users' abilities worsen role-overload and lower employee productivity [191-194]. Workers' technostress is worsened when they are required to divulge information about biased relationships within the organization. As a result of their perception of equality sensitivity, employees are obligated to respond appropriately to their work assignments [195-199], for example, have discussed the inverse relationship between technostress and productivity of employees, as well as how productivity is emphasized for the expansion and efficiency of the aviation industry [199-201]. Employee role-overload (RO) and employee equity-sensitivity (ES) have both been shown to have a minor moderating effect on performance in the aviation business, but this has gotten little attention in the industry. There is the opportunity for this study to investigate the interchange outcome of staff role-overload and equity-sensitivity on crew productivity, in addition to the impact of technological-stress on crew efficiency.

When it comes to stress, and how does it relate to aviation?

A high degree of stress has been experienced by almost everyone at some point in his or her life, but determining exactly what stress is and how it affects an individual's performance can be difficult. A scenario that is stressful for one person may not be stressful for another person in the same situation, depending on their personality. Stress can occasionally enhance performance, but it can also have a negative impact on how a flight crew member performs a task on a regular basis, according to the American Psychological Association.

Accidents in aviation almost always occur as a result of a series of mistakes that occur one after another, much like a domino effect. In many cases, stress is the trigger that causes the first domino to fall and set off a chain reaction that results in the effect. The removal of at least one of these dominoes is necessary in order to prevent a tragic catastrophe from occurring in the aviation industry. Human factor studies, as well as diligent effort, can be put to good use in this situation. In order to minimize undue stress in the aviation industry, it is necessary to adopt specific measures depending on the work that a person is performing. Stress can be avoided by taking actions to alleviate other potential sources of tension. When it comes to physical issues, getting enough sleep, eating a balanced diet, and drinking plenty of water while engaging in regular physical activity will assist the body withstand weariness and stress. Mental aspects are just as significant as physical factors. Knowing one's job well and feeling confidence in one's ability to carry out employment responsibilities will both help to minimize stress. Even, if the balance of physical and mental variables does not totally eliminate the stress factor, it will make it more controllable and therefore safer for everyone involved.

Pilot Stress

A pilot's reaction to stress is critical in aviation because it determines whether or not the flight will be safe and successful. Pilots are subjected to various levels of stress throughout the flight, and how they respond will determine whether or not the trip will be successful. On the right is an illustration of the variable levels of workload and, consequently, stress that the pilot experiences during the various phases of a flight. It is during the vital phases of a flight, such as take-off and landing, that stress and workload are at their maximum levels.

Air Traffic Control (also known as ATC) Stress

Managing and deconflicting several airplanes in an efficient, timely, and safe manner while also catering for variables like as weather changes and aircraft emergencies is a stressful task. This is owing to the job's complexity, which entails balancing the efficient, expeditious, and safe control and deconfliction of several airplanes while also accounting for variables such as weather changes and aircraft emergencies. Controllers must have strong cognitive abilities, such as "spatial scanning, movement detection, image and pattern recognition, prioritizing, visual and verbal filtering, coding and decoding, inductive and deductive reasoning, short- and long-term memory, mathematical and probabilistic reasoning, and spatial and temporal navigation," as a result of this complexity.

Stress of Maintenance Staff

Aviation maintenance is a stressful task made even more so by the fact that planes make money while flying rather than being serviced in a hangar; as a result, there is a great deal of pressure to complete maintenance in a short period of time and get the plane functional and flyable to avoid flight delays and cancellations. There are various aspects to consider, including using the suitable tool and installing the necessary parts when working in dark, restricted spaces, in addition to being cautious when executing the procedure. Raising one's expectations of oneself and forcing oneself to work more than necessary in order to do the project within the time constraint can cause stress. Stress can also be induced by a manager's organizational style or approach to his or her employees. Unless management has solid communication, skills and can effectively convey information or tasks to the engineers working on the hangar floor, they risk stressing them out due to a lack of understanding.

Cabin Crew Stress

The primary goal of this research is to identify the elements that cause stress in cabin crew members, as well as the coping techniques that they use to manage their stress. Flight attendants are a distinct occupational category in many aspects, including their irregular work schedules, peculiar set of job requirements, and distinctive way of life, to name a few. Industrial relations and organizational psychology literature has largely neglected modern commercial airplanes, as well as the working conditions of airline cabin crews, despite the fact that they are among the most dangerous jobs on the planet.

New low-cost carriers' apparent successes appear to have increased competitiveness within the airline sector, resulting in significantly increased workloads and stress for cabin crew members. Another source of stress has been the airline industry's difficult financial climate, which has had an influence on workloads and job security.

As we've seen in terms of overall developments and their implications for health and safety, it makes sense to conduct more research into the health concerns associated with cabin crew work environments in order to prevent and manage job stress in this particular group.

3.3 RECENT DEVELOPMENTS IN THE FIELD OF CABIN CREW STRESS

While workplace stress cannot be completely eliminated in cabin crews, stress management training can assist employees in reducing workplace stressors and managing the negative consequences of stress [186]. Stress management training can also help employees lessen the negative impacts of stress. Existing research suggests that stress management solutions can target three main components of the stress cycle: magnitude or quantity of stressors, employees' perception of stressful situations, and employees' ability to cope with stress. In order to reduce the number of stressors that people experience on the work, job design and selection procedures are two treatments that can be implemented. It focuses on either reorganizing the job to make it less stressful or hiring individuals who are better prepared to deal with stress. Employees dealing with stress might benefit from individual-level training interventions that attempt to improve their knowledge and abilities. Individual-level training interventions are targeted at the second and third components of the stress cycle, respectively. When it comes to stress management training in the workplace, individual-level therapies are the most frequently used [189-193]. As a whole, the purpose of stress management training is to improve people's perceptions of stress while also teaching them a variety of stress-coping skills and providing them with opportunities to practice. Stress management tactics such as relaxation, writing, making adjustments to one's lifestyle, and learning cognitive-behavioural skills are frequently employed in stress management programmes, among other things. Techniques such as muscle relaxation and deep breathing are used to help people relax both physically and mentally during stressful situations, whereas cognitive-behavioural interventions are used to change people's thoughts and perceptions in order to help them respond more effectively during stressful situations. Positive behaviours and lower levels of stress have been connected to programmes that encourage people to live healthier lifestyles. Evidence-based

research shows that stress management therapies are effective for reducing stress, improving coping skills, and increasing work-life well-being, which supports their use in the workplace to manage stress and improve work-life balance. Over the course of their research, only a few researchers discovered an average impact size ranging from medium to large across all of the stress management intervention studies they examined, with cognitive-behavioural therapies having the largest average effect [189-193].

3.4 SOURCES OF STRESS IN CABIN CREWS

Stressors that are environmental or physical: Physical stressors can be caused by internal situations (e.g., pain, hunger, lack of sleep, fatigue) or external environmental occurrences (e.g., thunderstorms). Diseases that affect the body's own internal organs are classified as internal diseases or disorders (e.g., noise, pollution, over-crowding, excess heat). There is one thing that all of these stressors have in common: they all create a physically uncomfortable environment that can lead to emotions of stress. Stress is not solely defined by the intensity of a stimulus, but also by the length of time that the stimulus is subjected to it, according to research. As an example, if a low-pitched but continuous noise is made repeatedly, it can have the same effect on the listener as an abruptly loud noise.

Constant radio communication noise; sudden alarms or warning horns; uncomfortable temperature; engine and system noise; vibration; cramped workspace; poor air quality; and lighting conditions are just a few of the environmental and physical stressors that cabin attendants frequently encounter in the cockpit. Manufacturers have addressed several of these factors in order to reduce the physical stress that flight crews feel while on the job.

Figure 3.2: Karasek Job Strain Model [202]

Stressors associated with one's job: Stress in the workplace can be caused by a multitude of factors other than physical stressors, as previously stated. Examples include the tension between the demands of management to assure on-time performance and the demands of customers for safe service. The fact that there is often the possibility of an unpleasant outcome regardless of which decision the pilot makes in such circumstances is one of the reasons why such scenarios cause so much worry. There is a risk of an accident or incident if the pilot insists on doing everything on time and fulfilling management's expectations. Management may take disciplinary action against the pilot if he or she chooses to ensure utmost safety at the risk of causing a delay. Both circumstances have the potential to be quite stressful.

There are a variety of other work-related stressors that can lead to elevated levels of stress as well. These include task under- or over-loading, crew conflicts, and position uncertainty. In addition, when a person dealing with a stressful situation generates a difficult situation for others around him or her by creating a stressful atmosphere for oneself or herself, this is known as stress transfer. The job strain model (Figure 3.2) developed by Dr. Robert A. Karasek takes into account the level of strain that an individual is projected to experience as a result of job demands as well as the amount of choice latitude that an individual has while on the job. In accordance with the concept, employment with high expectations and limited decision-making autonomy will be associated with the highest levels of psychological stress and stress-related health problems [202].

Personal Stressors: Personal pressures are occurrences that take place outside of the workplace and have the potential to have a negative impact on an individual's ability to perform at their job. Many people believe that they can maintain a healthy separation between their personal and professional lives and that neither will have an impact on the other. This, on the other hand, is not a possibility. Preoccupation with personal issues depletes a person's mental resources and causes him or her to become distracted from the task at hand, which is detrimental to productivity. Furthermore, because stress accumulates over time, personal stresses have the potential to exacerbate what would otherwise be a small stressor into a major one. Things like the death of a family member, an injury, or illness can have a substantial impact on one's stress levels and, as a result, one's performance at work. Pressures can arise from minor irritants, such as computer or car troubles, which can compound into larger problems. This small amount of pressure can develop over time and have a substantial impact on the performance of crew members.

Figure 3.3. Transactional Model of Stress (17)

The transactional model of stress is a paradigm that describes how people react to stressful situations

Whenever a person is confronted with a stressful occurrence, the first thing that comes to mind is to assess the situation [203]. The evaluation and stress process is described in greater detail below, according to the Lazarus and Folkman model of stress (Figure 3.3).

A first assessment is carried out in order to establish the level of danger, the probability of suffering, loss, or discomfort, and the amount of labour required in order to properly deal with the situation. If there is no perceived threat, there is no stress to be felt. Following the detection of a threat, an individual must do an additional evaluation in which he or she examines his or her perceived available resources to deal with the problem. Previous experiences and a person's expectation of his or her capacity to cope with a stressful situation both influence how they evaluate a situation. One chooses the "best" alternative, which is usually the one that is least destructive, most likely to succeed, and for which the individual possesses the most adequate skills and abilities. The experience of positive stress occurs when a person believes that he or she is capable of dealing with a stressful situation. A person's negative stress is caused by the thought that they would be unable to completely cope with a particular event.

Duration of Stress

Stress can be classified as acute or chronic depending on whether an incident or scenario persists and/or lasts for an extended amount of time. It is possible to have a wide range of physical and psychological responses to different types of stress.

- Acute stress is caused by stressors that occur for a short period of time (i.e., less than 24 hours). After experiencing a stressful event, the majority of the time, an individual is able to calm down and return to a normal mental and physiological state of mind. In spite of the fact that acute stress can be beneficial, sustained high levels of arousal for an extended period of time can lead to exhaustion.
- Chronic stress is defined as a constant barrage of demands, risks, pressures, and dangers that lasts for an extended period of time. Chronic stress depletes one's mental and physical resources over time, leaving one feeling helpless or unable of dealing with the problem. If left untreated, this illness can lead to major health problems such as a stroke, heart disease, or even a heart attack. It has culminated in suicide in the most extreme cases. One of the biggest risks of chronic stress is that, since it lasts for such a long time, an individual may grow unconscious to its repercussions, even if the negative effects are still present. People may fail to take action to manage with stress because it has become a common occurrence that has been accepted as the norm, which can lead to more problems.

Managing Stress

As previously indicated, stress is a process that can cause the nervous system to become overstimulated on occasion, making it more difficult to regulate major risks to flight safety when they do arise on the ground. Even though retaining control over one's responses to stress can be difficult, it is not impossible. It is possible to aim coping efforts toward either the stressor or the emotions that occur as a result of stress; however, dealing with both the stressor and the emotional impact of the stressor at the same time is the most effective strategy. Many of the mental obstacles that hinder problem-solving mental processes can be addressed by reducing the negative emotional impact of the stressor on the individual.

Recognizing the presence of a difficult situation

A good stress management strategy begins with training yourself to detect the symptoms that indicate the onset of stress before your stress levels reach dangerous levels. Some of the most prevalent signs of stress are as follows:

- Physical manifestations include: chills, sweaty hands, a headache, and tension.
- Impatience, rage, haste, and obsession are some of the behavioural changes.
- The following are examples of speech patterns: rapid, irregular, nonstandard sentences, voice tone, or loudness.

How to deal with tension during a flight

It is critical to understand how to deal with acute stress that occurs during a flight as well as chronic stress that has been present for an extended length of time. To deal with both acute and chronic stress, there are a variety of reactive and preventative methods that can be used. Preventative actions are frequently found to aid in the improvement of reactive coping mechanisms. As an example, rehearsing a certain emergency technique or creating solid backup plans are both preventative measures that make it much easier to deal with an emergency when it occurs. Preparation and practice, in general, build competence and confidence while simultaneously lowering stress levels to significant levels.

Some of the tensions that passengers experience during a flight are beyond their control. It has been found that the most effective method of dealing with such stressors is a combination of planning (pre-flight) and remedial actions (in flight).

1. Preparation is the first step. It is critical for safety that pilots are familiar with ways for coping with certain flying scenarios that are not usually encountered, as well as the capacity to execute these tactics efficiently.
2. Excitement about what is to come. Even though a scenario or hazard that could arise during the trip is extremely unlikely to occur, it is beneficial to prepare for it in advance. Consequently, if something does occur, the element of surprise will be reduced.
3. Make a plan. It is not enough to simply speculate about what might happen. When all realistic situations and threats have been recognized, it is critical that an effective plan for dealing with them be developed on the ground prior to taking flight. This improves the level of preparedness even more.
4. The ability to communicate. Briefings on the ground before the flight and in the air throughout the journey are essential. Allowing other crewmembers to be aware of the plans will guarantee that everyone is on the same page and that no one is taken by surprise or does something that is in opposition to the planned activity.
5. Making the Most of Resources To fulfil your objectives, make the most of all available resources. This entails proper duty division in the cockpit as well as the utilization of additional resources, including as onboard equipment and air traffic control, which may always help by offering information and guidance to help you deal with the problem and reduce stress.

6. Crew Resource Management is the sixth point to mention (CRM). To avoid work overload, delegate duties to others. If you find yourself overwhelmed with a large number of tasks, do not be afraid to ask for help. Becoming aware of the signs and symptoms of stress, not just in yourself, but also in your fellow crewmembers, will be beneficial. When assistance or guidance is required, it should be provided. It always helps to have a positive cabin atmosphere with plenty of laughter [40].
7. Effective time management. Whenever feasible, plan ahead of time to avoid last-minute surprises. Do not put off important tasks till the last minute (e.g., asking ATC for clearances). In order to avoid rash decisions, give yourself as much time as you can to examine and resolve an issue appropriately whenever possible.

Should you find yourself in a completely unexpected stressful scenario despite all of your careful planning and anticipation, the most important things to remember are to recognize the signs, remain calm, and give yourself as much time as possible to think things through. Stress mechanisms may be understood and controlled, allowing you to manage unpleasant feelings associated with stress such as irritability, uneasiness, and anxiety, as well as strive to address the situation in the most rational and safe manner possible.

Managing long-term and chronic stress is a challenge

You can never completely avoid stressful events in flight, and there will always be personal or other pressures, some of which are out of your control, that will have an impact on your flying experience. Some of these stresses may be long-term in nature. The most fundamental components of dealing with these chronic stress difficulties are as follows:

- Maintaining the physical well-being-This involves getting adequate sleep, eating nutritiously, and engaging in physical activity. Hunger and weariness are two of the most obvious sources of stress, and the consequences of these factors are widely documented. Climbing stairs is a particularly effective means of expelling extra toxins from the body, and swimming helps to restore balance to the nervous system after exercise. Both of these activities may normally be completed in hotels during layovers, allowing for the elimination of any leftover effects of stress before the following trip.
- Ongoing professional development-Development guarantees that all standard operating procedures and emergency operating procedures are current and competent.

- When it comes to social interaction, it is important not to let personal troubles and worries to accumulate. Communicating them with others is quite important because it provides partial relief and also because other people may be able to offer assistance and guidance to the individual in need.
- Workload-Do not allow yourself to take on an excessive number of chores and responsibilities (both work-related and non-work-related), since this might lead to a feeling of overwhelm. It is critical to learn to say "no" when you are being requested to perform a large number of activities.

3.5 THE CONSEQUENCES FOR ONE'S HEALTH AND WELL-BEING: THEORETICAL ASPECTS

Stress can have a positive or negative impact on humans, having implications for both psychological and physiological well-being. In many cases, stress is misunderstood as a type of adaptive response. In the absence of stress, the body may become overly quiet and inactive, making it difficult to cope with stressful situations. Stress has an effect on the nervous system, which responds in a manner that is comparable to how the body responds to stress. It has been discovered that the level of epinephrine (an adrenaline derivative) in the blood has increased. Among the many biological responses induced by this hormone include increased metabolic rate, stimulation of heart motions, and rise of blood pressure, among others. It is a powerful stimulant that supports the body in responding to specific conditions and dealing with stressful circumstances. As a result, most people experience a sense of terror as a result of this. The ability to respond to a situation successfully is impaired in those who are panicked [217-219] [122].

According to the "demand/control/support" model of workplace stress, high levels of stress, as well as the problems and illnesses that result from them, are more likely to emerge in professional activities when there is a high psychological demand but little decision freedom and insufficient social support available to the individual ("high strain job"). Alternatively, jobs that place high psychological demands on employees while also providing them with a broad range of decision-making authority and sufficient social support are more likely to inspire active behaviour that improves learning, motivation, and overall labour productivity. Air traffic control is a job that necessitates strong psychological needs while also being subjected to a large level of external control [220-222], as demonstrated by the research.

Cabin Crew members frequently express unhappiness with their lack of personal influence, which may be a major source of stress, especially given the high amount of responsibility involved in the job. Working conditions including the work environment, gadgets, work planning and procedures, workflow distribution, team structure, working hours, rest breaks, shift schedules, and human interactions can all have a big impact on "demand" and "control," as well as "social support" [220-222].

The impact of age, lifestyles, life events, job experience, personal characteristics (social awkwardness, anxiety) and behavioural traits (emotional state, sleeping habits), attitudes, inspiration, and physical and mental health on the efficiency and well-being of Cabin Crew members may also differ significantly from one individual to the next. Numerous additional social factors, such as socioeconomic status, living conditions, transportation, family attitudes, social support, and integration, may also be important in this context [220-222].

In the case of short-term effects, changes in hormonal secretion (for example, cortisol levels), heart rate and blood pressure, muscle activity, brain waves, work performance (errors), and behaviour (for example, sleeping, smoking, eating, and drinking habits) can be observed as a result of the exposure to the substance. The existence of these symptoms can reflect either a natural, physiological response of the individual to external stimuli or an undue strain caused by an imbalance in the environment's demand-resource allocation. Variations in hormone release (e.g., adrenaline, non-adrenaline, Cortisol), pulse rate, hypertension, muscle activity, brain waves, work quality (errors), and habit (sleeping, smoking, eating, and drinking habits) can be observed in a Cabin Crew's responses in terms of short-term effects. Both a natural, physiological response to external stimuli and an excessively stressful circumstance caused by a requirement-availability imbalance could manifest as these symptoms. According to the majority of research, workload can be measured in terms of the number of aircraft under control or expected to be under control, the maximum traffic volume, the duration and type of connectivity, the number and complexity of problems to be solved, and the number and complexity of problems to be solved. Although there are significant variances amongst air traffic control centres, there are some similarities.

Figure 3.4: Various Consequences of Stress in Aviation Industry According to Professor Giovanni Costa [222-225]

There is a significant correlation between personal qualities (anxiety and social awkwardness), aptitude and ability, competence, desire and expertise, and functioning behaviour (amongst other things). It has been hypothesised, according to some research, that this physically demanding job may be associated with stress-related diagnoses like headaches and fatigue as well as serious illnesses like high blood pressure, heart disease, insulin resistance, chronic gastritis, and psychoneurotic disorders over time (Figure 3.4).

It's easy to understand the immense ramifications, both existential and economic, that these adverse stress effects can have not only on a single individual, but also on a group of individuals, businesses, and society as a whole, when they occur. Therefore, stress management and prevention become a major goal for individuals, businesses, and society as a whole in order to offer the highest possible levels of security and welfare for all those involved in and affected by this critical professional activity [223-226].

Stress-related symptoms and their impact on performance

The physical and psychological responses of an individual to stress can have a significant impact on their ability to function. Physiological and psychological reactions are intricately connected, and one can have a significant impact on the other.

Stress has both physiological and psychological consequences

Stress is an unavoidable side effect of the adaptation process. The body would be far too relaxed and docile to deal with any serious or challenging conditions if there was no stress at all. The nervous system is activated to a higher level of awareness when stressful events are detected, resulting in increased alertness and performance. An increase in the release of adrenaline (also known as epinephrine) into the body's circulation is usually associated with this increased level of alertness. The stimulation of heart action, as well as elevations in blood pressure, metabolic rate, and blood glucose concentration, are all physiologic responses that adrenaline causes. Adrenaline is the most powerful nervous system stimulant, allowing the body to function more swiftly and alertly, allowing a person to cope with more demanding situations or those requiring quick responses. The adrenal glands create adrenaline, which is then released into the bloodstream.

An overproduction of adrenaline, on the other hand, can occur if a situation is judged to be very difficult to handle. A person can become overstimulated to the point of feeling overwhelmed by the environment and unable to cope as a result of this overstimulation. Generally speaking, panic is the most extreme form of overstimulation, and a person who panics is frequently unable to respond in any constructive way. Adrenaline levels in the bloodstream begin to rise above a specific threshold, at which point the body begins to show outward indications of stress. Identifying and recognizing these signals in oneself and others is one of the most important steps in properly managing stress and anxiety. The following are the most often noticed symptoms:

1. Physiological Manifestations

Most typically reported physiologic symptoms of stress are cardiovascular symptoms such as elevated heart rate, high blood pressure, and chest discomfort, respiratory symptoms such as shortness of breath, hyperventilation, and dizziness, and gastrointestinal symptoms such as nausea and vomiting. Gastronomic symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, diarrhoea, and other signs and symptoms such as headaches, muscular tension, sleep difficulties, and overall weakness, among others, might accompany a gastrointestinal illness.

2. Psychiatric Signs and Symptoms

Anger, guilt, mood swings, low self-esteem, despair, pessimism, irritable temper, loss of interest, and loss of control are some of the most regularly reported Psychological Symptoms of stress, according to the Mayo Clinic.

Stress has a variety of effects on both physical and mental performance

As previously stated, excessive stress has been found to have a negative impact on performance. Increases in over-stimulation are generally inversely connected to reduced performance. The following are some of the common adverse effects that occur under stressful situations:

The following are some of the most common signs and symptoms:

- Defective judgement and memory are all examples of errors.
- Either slowness (due to lack of interest) or hyperactivity (due to adrenaline)
- An increase in risk-taking, which leads to an increase in infractions, particularly when frustrated by failures; Due to increased levels of adrenaline and attentiveness, people tend to act hastily even when there is no time restriction.
- Hurried acts lead to more blunders.

The following behaviours are common in situations of significant stress:

- Reverting to old practices that may or may not be appropriate any longer
- Communicating using non-standard phraseology
- Returning to one's home tongue (Native language)
- Looking for objects at a spot where they used to be but are no longer found

Other ramifications-interpersonal relationships in and around the cockpit

As may be expected, because stress has an impact on behaviour, it has an impact on interpersonal interactions as well. This is a circumstance that can be quite dangerous in the cockpit. There are two types of negative interpersonal disputes that can arise: aggressive behaviour and retreat from the situation. Increased levels of adrenaline and alertness are a normal result of high levels of alertness and aggression. In most cases, aggressive behaviour is shown verbally and can range from minor to severe. Attractive behaviours can be aimed at ATC, the other pilot, the crew, or anyone else who can be held responsible for what is taking place on the flight.

Incompetence-related withdrawal happens when a person experiences thoughts of inadequacy, which results in an inability to confront the situation at hand. In most cases, the individual will not exert any effort and will just "give up." All difficult decisions are left to the discretion of the other crew member, and the withdrawing crewmember will frequently accept instructions without hesitation or questioning their validity.

3.6 A VARIETY OF APPLICATIONS ARE BEING DEVELOPED AT SEVERAL ACADEMIES TO ADDRESS STRESS-RELATED ISSUES IN THE AVIATION INDUSTRY SECTOR

The National Civil Aviation Administration has set criteria for planning, implementing, reinforcing, and assessing CRM training programmes for flight crew members and other workers vital to flight safety. As a result of their success, these initiatives will become part of training and operations. All airlines are required by law to provide CRM training to their cabin crew. This Advisory Circular describes one approach to CRM training, but it is not the only one. CRM training is taught using a comprehensive framework of SOPs that emphasises situation awareness, communication skills, teamwork, task allocation, decision-making, and mistake management.

Human error is a contributing element in 60-80% of all air operator problems and accidents, according to investigations. Researchers discovered that these occurrences have some properties in common. Many of the issues that flight crews face have little to do with the technical aspects of multi-person cockpit flying. As a result, poor group decision-making, communication, leadership, and task or resource management are common. Pilot training programmes have typically focused on the technical aspects of flying and individual pilot performance, rather than crew management, which is also critical to safe flight.

CRM training is one technique to maximize the human-machine interface and the associated interpersonal activities. Working with automated systems and developing teams are all part of this area. CRM training promotes the development of human performance knowledge and abilities, based on the concept that safe and efficient operations demand high technology expertise. Knowledge of the topics will not substitute for lack of CRM core experience. High technical proficiency will not assure safe operations without excellent crew coordination. Executives in the aviation sector collaborated on important CRM training programme designs [40].

CRM fundamentals include the following:

There are several beneficial ways for CRM training that are currently being used, however certain elements are universally applicable:

- (1) CRM training is most effective when delivered as part of a comprehensive training programme that is based on clear, thorough standard operating procedures (SOPs).
- (2) CRM training should emphasize the importance of crewmembers working together as a team, rather than as a collection of technically proficient individuals. In order to maximize efficiency, pilots should be evaluated as a team rather than as individuals. Crew member effectiveness training (CRM) should teach crewmembers how to behave in ways that promote crew effectiveness.
- (3) CRM training should include opportunities for crew members to practice the skills necessary to be effective team leaders and participants.

Components of customer relationship management

The subjects listed below have been regarded as key components of good customer relationship management (CRM) training. There is no way around the fact that one-time exposures are insufficient, no matter how excellent each curricular piece is. It is possible that attitudes and social conventions that contribute to ineffective crew coordination have developed throughout the course of a crewmember's life. CRM should be integrated into every step of training, and CRM ideas should be highlighted in line operations as well. This will ensure that CRM is as effective as possible.

Commitment on the part of management

Operations employees respond considerably more positively to customer relationship management programmes when top managers, flight operations managers, and flight standards officers publicly embrace CRM concepts and make available the training materials that are needed to implement them.

Customer relationship management elements, such as providing crews with required policy and procedure guidance based on clear, complete standard operating procedures, should be included in flying operations and training manuals. In customer relationship management, communication is a critical component. Every level of management must promote a safety culture in which suitable questioning tactics are used to encourage dialogue. Reasonable inquiry should be encouraged in pilots' manuals and during every part of pilot training, and there should be no repercussions for another pilot who questions a decision or action taken by a pilot in the same aircraft.

CRM training (indoctrination and awareness) is the first step

The initial CRM training must be completed before the crewmember can commence unsupervised line flying operations, unless the crewmember has already completed an introductory operator's CRM course. The initial CRM training focuses on the nature of the firm's operations, as well as the procedures and culture that have been created inside the company. This will include any special dangers or risks, as well as sites of activities that create specific challenges or are prone to adverse weather conditions.

In the event that a flight crew member has not completed an Operator's Initial CRM course, they must do so. When new employees join the company, they must undergo Initial CRM Training within a particular time frame. If the flight crew member has not previously been trained in Human Factors, the theoretical course must be done before or coupled with the initial Operator's CRM training.

CRM training on a continuous basis

In order to meet the recurring training requirement, CRM training must be provided on a regular basis. In addition to modular classroom or briefing room CRM training to review and amplify CRM components, recurrent CRM training should incorporate practice and feedback tasks to reinforce CRM components. A maximum of three years will be required to cover all important topics in customer relationship management (CRM).

Topics include:

1. Human error and dependability, error chain, error prevention and detection
2. Company safety culture, standard operating procedures, and organizational factors are some of the topics covered.
3. Tension, stress management, weariness, and alertness.
4. Data gathering and processing, situational awareness, workload management.
5. decision making.
6. Communication and coordination within and outside the cockpit.
7. Leadership and team behaviour, synergy (if applicable to the type).
8. Project check list and briefing.

The accident prevention and flight safety programme has identified ten particular type-related variants, eleven case studies, and twelve additional areas that require further investigation.

Instructors and check pilots play a key role in the aviation industry

The ability of the employees who provide the training and track its effects in the field determines the effectiveness of any CRM training programme. CRM instructors, check pilots, supervisors, and course designers must be knowledgeable in all facets of customer relationship management practice and evaluation (CRM). These skills are not at the same level as those necessary for standard flying instruction and checking. Many CRM training methods include specialized training for teachers, supervisors, and check pilots to gain expertise and confidence in customer relationship management (CRM) education. To calibrate and standardize their own abilities as instructors, supervisors, and check pilots, they require specialized training and education. The best outcomes are obtained when crews assess their own behaviour with the assistance of a professional teacher who can recognize both positive and negative CRM performance on the part of the crew. When highly effective examples of crew coordination are uncovered, it is vital that these positive behaviours be shared and promoted in a positive atmosphere. Instructors, supervisors, and check pilots all need to be able to debrief and critique their students' performances. It is most successful when the feedback comes from instructors, supervisors, and the check pilot and pertains to the principles that were addressed during the original indoctrination/awareness training. The most effective feedback focuses on specific instances of behaviour rather than on overall patterns of behaviour.

3.7 ORGANIZATIONS IMPARTING SERVICES IN THE CHOSEN SUBJECT

Critical Incident Stress Management (CISM): Workers in high-risk firms are exposed to high levels of stress or significant threats to their bodily and mental well-being [13]. The aviation sector is an example of a High Reliability Organization that must operate effectively and dependably. Extremely frightening or dangerous conditions are a significant threat associated with working in these occupations. A strong, integrative, comprehensive, and multi-component peer support programme is essential for aviation personnel. CISM is a multi-component emergency response approach that is strong, organized, and systematic. Air traffic controllers, pilots, crew members, and flight

attendants are all supported under the CISM programme. A systematized and well-skilled CISM player will enable a high threat/high dependability organization to transform into a high resilience firm [203]. Program summary is a detailed, integrated, comprehensive, and multi-factor. CISM is adaptable, practical, and cost-effective. It is a common-sense stress management system. It can help ease anxiety and maintain healthy standards of operation for flight personnel. Since its inception in the 1970s, over a thousand community groups and services have quickly evolved to various types of departments, associations, and service dependability organizations in order to become a highly resilient organization [203]. CISM is often referred to as a "bundle" of intertwined crisis management tactics.

The following are the main objectives of the CISM programme:

- (1) Reduce the impact of a traumatic event
- (2) promote natural recovery process in those who have experienced traumatic events
- 3) Restore people's, groups', and organizations' adaptive functions

Paraprofessionals can give excellent crisis support, according to reports and studies from the aviation sector, which range from terminals to planes and from ground controllers to captains, including cockpit and airline employees. The CISM team responds with competence, compassion, and consideration to situations including individual mourning, family emergencies, or a crisis response team reacting to an air accident.

Figure 3.5: Wellbeing Wheel (FSF, 2020) [227]

The Flight Safety Foundation has prepared a handbook to help wellbeing management and endurance for aviation personnel both during and after the COVID-19 incident [188], based on a preventive and self-management strategy. The guide asks aviation personnel to evaluate three crucial issues about their well-being: (1) How am I experiencing, (2) how am I dealing, and (3) what am I intending to do? The handbook advises the employment of certain self-management practices based on the 'biopsychosocial' model of health and wellness. These are six key actions based on these three pillars of happiness. These actions were chosen based on previous study on stress coping in pilots. These include activities, physical activity, nutritious food, relaxation, stress management, and social interactions, as shown in Figure 3.5.

3.8 CONCEPT OF WORK ENGAGEMENT

Work engagement refers to the positive, productive, and contented mental state that is exhibited by employees and is marked by zeal, engrossment, and vitality. Employees who are committed to their jobs are frequently passionate, motivated, and deeply invested in their jobs. Such workers are described as being very invested in their work, regardless of what they perform. Work is characterised by three primary traits: dedication, vigour, and absorption. An identification-based component of engagement is what it is referred to as in a meta-analysis of work engagement [169]. Because of Kahn's early conceptions of engagement, there is a connection between job engagement and work identification. The alignment of organizational members' selves to their job duties was the broad definition of engagement at work [233]. Employees that are mentally present at work develop a strong sense of integration with their jobs. Any organization's personnel are its most important component. Employees provide the company a competitive edge and are essential to its success. Employees who are engaged are a fantastic asset to their company. High levels of work engagement encourage talent retention, boost customer loyalty, and increase the value to stakeholders for domestic and international businesses. An organization is a dynamic social unit made up of people who have similar goals but different roles and responsibilities. Common goals, a "drafted structure, relative activities," and a "relation to the external environment" are its defining characteristics [234]. Relationships inside an organization interact to create distinctive entities and traits that can be assessed psychometrically. Employers who invest in their personnel pool should expect great returns. Organizations strive to have highly engaged workforces and invest significant

financial and non-financial resources to measure workforce engagement levels, which is also vital for the organizations. Major organizational changes and ongoing success may be based on raising employee levels of work engagement. Even during a recession, it is important to continue measuring employee engagement. Employee surveys are excellent instruments for evaluating aspects like employee empowerment and the management skills of a business. To gauge the opinions and attitudes of its employees, many businesses conduct surveys.

The employee's level of work engagement, which was also previously described, is the reverse of "burnout." Individuals that are engaged are enthusiastic, energetic, and highly connected to their professional activities, whereas burnt-out employees are the exact opposite and lack both enthusiasm and energy while remaining disengaged from their jobs. Employees who are engaged are typically able to handle the demands of their jobs well, whereas those who are burnt out experience the exact opposite.

Vigour is characterized by high levels of energy among the workforce, mental clarity while working, perseverance in trying circumstances, and willingly putting effort into the work. Dedication is characterized by a keen interest in one's work, pride, inspiration, enthusiasm, and a sense of significance. While, absorption is thought to be one's concentration and joy in one's work. For these workers, time goes very quickly and it is challenging for them to step away from their jobs. As a result, it is believed that vitality and determination are just the opposites of tiredness and scepticism, respectively.

3.9 OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES TO PROGRESS OF SUBJECT

This topic has a few challenges as well as opportunities that are worth highlighting. In the current literature, the cross-sectional strategy was advocated for data gathering [184-190]. Second, self-reporting questionnaires may have been skewed due to adherence and social perception [184-197]. Third, participants' age, gender, experience, and educational background were not taken into account in the current investigations. Due to their lifelong experience, better education and seniority as workers, they have a more awareness about perception. Many people believe that these factors, when combined with other contextual and demographic factors, result in a different sense of self. As a result, as shown in the current model, they may confound, modify, and/or mediate this association, resulting in omitted-variable bias (OVB). This shed light on a

possible direction for future work in this field. As a result, it is suggested that future study examine crew job expertise, educational background, and age. Longitudinal data collection strategies should be considered in future research in this sector. Given the importance of cultural differences in employees' perceptions and technology adoption, it would be great to see future aviation studies replicate the current findings in different nations. As a result, we intend to address these concerns and challenges in our study [235-238].

3.10 MAJOR RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS

It is observed in numerous flight mishaps, including the recent air disaster at Mangalore Airport. As a result, the best remedy is to lessen stresses, which is not impossible to do. As a result, the stress level can be reduced when the stressors are handled by individuals who have received proper training. After the data has been analysed and the study has been able to comprehend the stress rank of the respondents and the stressors, the researcher will attempt to examine in depth various relevant cognitive fitness issues that have an effect on the job of the workers. Various stressors connected to work and personal characteristics will be evaluated to determine the root cause of the stress. By providing suitable training for the aviation industry team, the stressors will be reasonably reduced. Therefore, the major research contributions are divided into objectives and are mentioned below.

It has been observed in a number of aviation disasters that stress is the main cause of any mishap in the aviation field. Stress reduction is the most effective treatment, and it is not hard to achieve. When stresses are dealt with by personnel who have received appropriate training, the stress level can be reduced. In this research study, after the data has been analysed and the study has been able to comprehend the respondents' stress levels as well as the stressors, the researcher will attempt to investigate in depth a variety of relevant cognitive fitness issues that have an impact on the cabin Crews' performance at their place of employment. A variety of stressors related to job and personal traits will be assessed in order to establish the underlying cause of the anxiety. The pressures associated with the aviation industry team will be significantly minimised if they receive appropriate training. The primary scientific contributions are therefore split into objectives, which are discussed further below in detail.

- To identify the stressors that contribute to stress among airline cabin crews.
- To explore the effects of cabin crew stress on job performance.
- To get an understanding of the various stress coping techniques used by cabin crews.
- To design and develop relevant strategies to overcome stress among cabin crews
- To develop and recommend the strategies to train the cabin crews to reduce stress.

3.11 MAJOR FRAMEWORK USED

The research aims to understand more about the various factors that cause stress among cabin crew. To comprehend this, a model is required, and a study hypothesis needs to be developed based on this model. The study design is exploratory as well as descriptive. In most cases, experimental research does not begin with a problem or hypothesis. It all starts with recognizing the issue. As a result, this study began by reviewing a large body of literature on strategies installed to overcome work stress in the aviation sector and identifying topics that had not been previously addressed. As a result, it can be classified as exploratory research. For Stress in the aviation industry, closely related terminology such as Stress, Stressors, Strategies, and cognitive well-being of the employee in the aviation sector are covered in the literature study. While the research problem addressed in this work has not been addressed in previous studies, it might be considered an exploration. The study's primary focus is on identifying stress inducing factors and suitable strategies adopted to get over stress in the aviation sector in order to construct a descriptive prediction model for the same.

Figure 3.6: Proposed Conceptual Model (Developed by the Researcher)

Figure 3.6 depicts the conceptual framework for the research. Long Irregular working hours, Work Hassles, Aircraft Cabin Environment and Social Isolation are the independent variables in this model. Work Engagement is the dependent variable. The study has also addressed stress coping resources as the mediator as it effects work engagement.

3.12 RECENT INVENTION IN THE CABIN CREW STRESS REDUCTION AND ENHANCING THE WELLBEING

The Crew Care Counselling Service

British Airways has offered a confidential aviation counselling service to its crew members for more than two decades. For nearly two decades, the crew care counselling programme has been in place. The department is manned by a team of 23 highly experienced therapists, all of whom are current or former cabin crew members with at least two years of airline cabin crew experience. In addition to their flying responsibilities, they complete a six-day counselling rotation every four to five weeks. According to user comments, the peer-group component of the programme is really beneficial. Customers have expressed satisfaction with the service, claiming that speaking with someone who understands the profession's lifestyle and quirks is reassuring. If the difficulties raised by the client cannot be resolved in a single session of therapy with them, crew care may refer them to the Independent Counselling and Advisory Service, which is linked with British Airways' Employee Assistance Provider. Additional references will be provided by the British Association of Counselling and Psychotherapy (of which crew care is an organizational member adhering to their Codes of Ethics and Practice) and the United Kingdom Confederation of Psychotherapists [240].

Crew care has evolved over two decades to provide a full variety of services and support. The services include a 24-hour freephone helpline, on-site counselling, follow-up assistance for crew members involved in critical incidents, a support group for working parents juggling family and work, re-orientation for crew members returning from long-term sick leave, community awareness campaigns, manager training workshops on counselling skills, stress management programmes, and a website presence (telecommunications network). A critical incident can be anything from a passenger's death on board to an air rage episode, or any work-related event that is

traumatic for the person involved. To reduce tensions, the crew care counsellor must first listen to the crew member's experiences and respond to their urgent needs. British Airways sends quarterly company-wide data information to relevant management. While maintaining the service's status as a confidential organization, this data illustrates current trends and challenges. [240].

The care of the crew has been a big success. Overall, the success of the crew care service is very certainly due to the fact that it was created in response to a genuine need identified by the members of the aviation community. Two cabin crew members contacted management with an idea after a suicide attempt by a cabin crew member overseas. As a result of this realisation, the crew care service's entire attitude has changed to one that is sympathetic, understanding, and aware of the often hidden challenges that exist within the flying lifestyle. The fact that all of the counsellors chosen are also crew members adds to the previously stated basic idea of a peer group with insight, understanding, and empathy for its client base. The on-site, no-appointment-required facility housed at Heathrow Airport's operation centre is even more crucial to Crew care's success because the flying community is, by its very nature, a disengaged workforce. As a result, the client group views the support services as being immediately available, dependable, and responsive to their urgent, and often "in crisis," wants and requirements. The Crew Care service maintains a separate but crucial independent place within the overall support infrastructure when it comes to the overall support facilities supplied to flying crew. As a result, it works closely with occupational health, labour unions, human resources, and scheduling departments, all while keeping its own identity and secrecy within the greater support system. As a result, it is regarded by its clients as offering a one-of-a-kind service that is not duplicated by any other function, and as such, it is valued for its anonymity and independence [240].

3.13 CONCLUSION

Stress management has a vast and diverse classification and ways to cope with, as evidenced in this chapter's discussion. Many researchers and scholars have proposed various definitions. According to all of the studies, stress is an individual's physical response towards a danger or demand, and its beneficial or negative impact on employees depending on the situation and work environment. The numerous sources of stress are examined, as well as their definitions. It can be addressed by participating in

a variety of training programmes offered by a few institutions and organizations. The conversation then shifts to the consequences of stress on employee well-being, as well as how to manage it. Characteristics of such programmes and applications are discussed at length. Employee (cabin crew) stress management has become a strategic priority in the aviation industry, and effective ways for planning and implementing programmes and applications should be pursued. Companies that can apply these stress management measures would be able to have a better work atmosphere for their employees. A variety of stress management models are developed in order to grasp the perspectives of many writers and to establish a solid foundation in the concept. According to the literature, the stress levels of the selected participants can be quantified by constructing and applying an appropriate scale. If the respondents' stress levels are higher than a predetermined level, a suitable programme will be included in the tutoring provided to aviation professionals, with a focus on International Airports of Mangalore, Karnataka.

CHAPTER-IV
RESEARCH DESIGN

4.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design is a blueprint for the complete study of the project. It provides an overview of the research conducted in this study. Systematic research necessitates the use of appropriate methods and the application of a scientific framework. The previous chapters attempted to comprehend the notion of “Stress Inducing Factors and Employees’ Strategies to Reduce it: A Study with Special Reference to Cabin Crews of Selected Indian International Airports” and provided an in-depth examination of several reviews in this area. This chapter's main goal is to elaborate on the research instruments, sampling design, methods and tools used for data collection, statistical methods used for data analysis and interpretation, as well as the study's limitations and problems encountered during the study. The study design is exploratory as well as descriptive in nature. In most cases, exploratory research does not begin with a problem or hypothesis. It all starts with recognizing the issue. As a result, this study began by reviewing a large body of literature in the field of strategies deployed to overcome stress in the aviation industry sector and identifying topics that had not previously been addressed. Cabin crews stress related concepts, such as Relationship building, Stress, Physiological stress, Psychological stress, Work environment, Stressor Agents, Irregular working hours, Work engagement, Work hassles, Aircraft cabin environment, Social Isolation, Emotional labor, Stigma scale, Fatigue and sleepiness, Work life balance, Burnout, Mental health/quality of life are some of the topics covered in the literature study. While the research problem addressed in this work has not been addressed in previous studies, it might be considered an exploration. The study's main focus is on identifying various stressors that cause stress among cabin crews, to understand the coping mechanisms used by them to overcome stress and based on this study to design and develop relevant model of strategies to overcome stress among cabin crews. The research aims to understand more about the various factors that cause stress among cabin crew. To comprehend this, a model is developed, and a study hypothesis is developed based on this model. The research hypothesis aids in resolving the study's problem. It explains what the research will entail in great detail. The first stage in any investigation is to translate the research questions into a forecast. The variables, population, and relationships between them are all included. The link between the variables in this study is evaluated using simple hypotheses.

4.2 NATURE AND SOURCES OF DATA

A questionnaire-based survey method was selected for collecting the necessary data. To collect the primary data, a questionnaire was developed, keeping in mind the objectives of the study. Secondary data has been collected from various sources. The data collection through primary source includes Personal Factors, agreement level on irregular working hours, work hassles, aircraft cabin environment, social isolation, workplace stress, work engagement, stress coping resources; it also included the details on emotional labor of the cabin crews. Collection of data from primary source is mainly intended to assess the impact of various stressor agents on workplace stress which, in turn has significant impact on work engagement. In order to check its impact, the researcher has analyzed the agreement level on stressor agents, workplace stress, work engagement and stress coping resources of the cabin crews.

For further reference, secondary data was accumulated from various sources such as annual reports of airline companies, articles from Google scholar, SSRN, Srinivas Publications, emerald, science direct, Taylor and Francis etc. and also various thesis pertaining to the research topic has been referred to develop conceptual framework, theoretical back ground and literature survey.

4.3 RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

To collect primary data, a well-structured questionnaire has been formulated, which was circulated among the cabin crews targeting two international airports by giving a personal visit to them. Apart from questionnaire circulation, personal interview on the open-ended questions was also undertaken by the researcher. The research instrument was a combination of both qualitative and quantitative aspects consisting of Personal Factors, stressor agents, workplace stress level, work engagement level, stress coping resources as well as emotional labor with further details.

4.4 COMPONENTS OF THE SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CABIN CREWS

Section-I: The first section deals with the open ended as well as close ended questions concerning Personal Factors of the cabin crews.

Section-II: The second section is designed to get the agreement level of cabin crews on irregular working hours faced by them.

Section-III: The third section is formulated to obtain agreement level of cabin crews on work hassles with fourteen indicators.

Section-IV: The fourth section consists of Aircraft Cabin Environments of the cabin crews to obtain their agreement level to measure it.

Section-V: The fifth section is framed to measure the agreement level of cabin crews on Social Isolation as a stressor agent.

Section-VI: In order to get the agreement level of cabin crews on Workplace Stress Scale, section VI has been designed with 8 items.

Section-VII: The statement on work engagement has been formulated under section 7 to obtain the respondents agreement level.

Section-VIII: The 8th section aims at measuring the emotional labor with a set of close ended questions.

Section-IX: The last section consists of the close ended questions as well as numeric or scale type of questions to obtain the perception of cabin crews on their Stress Coping Resources.

Section 1 of the research instrument consists of Personal Factors as well as job description of the respondents which includes Age, Gender, Marital Status, Current function, Experience, Change in lifestyle, Maximum number of consecutive days of work, Maximum number of consecutive nights of work and Average days off per month. Section 2, 3, 4 and 5 is concerned with the agreement level of cabin crews on stressor agents. These stressor agents have been divided into the agreement level on irregular working hours, agreement level on work hassles, agreement level on aircraft cabin environment and agreement level on social isolation. The second section on irregular working hours contains a statement with respect to clearly unpredictable deadlines, long hours of work, fatigue and exhaustion, long series of flight, early morning departure, need for recovery, lack of sufficient sleep and feeling undeserved. 3rd section conversing work hassles consists of the statements on communication issues with Pilots, communication issues with the passenger, unacceptable behaviours of passengers, gap between works standards and practical operations, vacation, presence of poor work cohesion, unexpected emergency, poor work cohesion between cockpit

crew and cabin crew, antisocial behaviour of passengers, verbal and physical violence by the passengers, verbal threats to other passengers, disobeying the instructions of crew, health problems and jet lag problems. Moreover, 4th section measures aircraft cabin environment through 13 statements, which includes Flight delays leading to disruptive passengers hurting the crews emotionally, scheduling and rostering, anxiety regarding pre-flight checks, work load/time pressure/deadlines, interpersonal problems, lack of opportunities and potential advancement, lack of encouragement and support by the management and superiors, monotonous work involving underutilization of skills, irregular flight duty timings, variability in work load and uneven distribution of work, harassment by passengers, pressure causing headache and general transmission of infections. Similarly, section 5 deals with the indicators of social isolation construct; it consists of 10 items including work responsibilities impacting personal, family, and social lives, job having an adverse influence on their family and social life, work time interference with family and social life, lack of time for their family or friends, work-rest-social life, lack of time for their interests/hobbies, no time to attend any family functions, no time to be with family whenever it is required, no time to spend with their family members/friends. Section 6, 7, 8 and 9 consist of work place stress, work engagement, emotional labor and stress coping resources respectively with metric and close ended questions.

4.5 USE OF SCALE IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE

In order to measure the Personal Factors and emotional labour of the respondents, the study adopted nominal measurement as it is categorical in nature. Other parts of the questionnaire contain agreement level on irregular working hours, work hassles, aircraft cabin environment, social isolation, workplace stress and work engagement as these statements reflect its metric nature. Hence, it is measured using five-point likert scale by taking 1 as “Strongly Disagree”, 2 as “Disagree”, 3 as “Neutral”, 4 as “Agree” and 5 as “Strongly Agree”. Lastly, stress coping resources are measured using nominal measurement and scale measurement as few questions are close ended and open ended along with statement oriented questions.

4.6 CONSTRUCTION OF RESEARCH TOOL

The research instrument consists of Personal Factors and stressor agents’ i.e. irregular working hour, work hassles, air craft cabin environment which were measured using

the standardized indicators given by Johnson, J. V. (2006) [125], Grosch, J. W., Caruso, A. C. C., Rosa, R. R., & Sauter, S. L. (2006) [77], Castro, M., Carvalhais, J., & Teles, J. (2015) [39], Folkard, S., & Smith, L. (1995) [241], Tsaur, S., Hsu, F., & Kung, L. (2020) [21], Kedar, S. G., & Ujjain, S. (2020) [4], Kumar S, Iyengar J, Hirlekar A. (1994) [242], Marshall, J., & Cooper, C. L. (1976) [243], (Amornpipat, 2020) [244].

To measure the Emotional labor among the cabin crews, the questions have been selected from Ai-serkal, A. (2006) [245]; similarly workplace stress was measured through referring to Spelten, E. R., Totterdell, P., Folkard, S., & Costa, G. (1995) [246], Stanton, J. M., Balzer, W. K., Smith, P. C., Parra, L. F., Ironson, G., & Stanton, J. M. (2014) [247], Shea, T., Cieri, H. De, & Victoria, W. (2011) [248], MacDonald, L. A., Deddens, J. A., Grajewski, B. A., Whelan, E. A., & Hurrell, J. J. (2003) [249]. Stress coping resources and work engagement have been measured through the standardized measurement of Majali, S. Al, & Shana, Z. (2019) [96], Matheny, K. B., Aycock, D. W., Curlette, W. L., & Junker, G. N. (2003) [97], S P, L. J., & V, C. (2008) [98] and Chen, C., & Chen, S. (2012) [5].

4.7 DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENT

Any research project must have a reliable and valid research instrument, and the current study's questionnaire preparation procedure used a variety of techniques. Two different forms of data generation and data validation were used in the current investigation;

1. Validity Testing
2. Reliability Testing

Testing an instrument's validity entails determining whether it is capable of measuring what it is designed to. Content validity is tested as part of validity.

4.7.1 Content Validity

A research tool needs to have a variety of parts and structures. These can be created first using the currently available literature review. Once the required variables have been generated, the study instrument's statements should be understandable and should possess the appropriate content validity. This was validated thoroughly using a process. The tool was initially distributed to five researchers, whose opinions on the questionnaire were obtained. The instrument was then presented to five professors with

backgrounds in aviation studies, who were asked to review it and provide feedback. After making changes to the instrument's contents, it was then sent to airport staff to test the validity. Based on their feedback, a few elements were deleted or changed, and it was then given to three psychologists for evaluation. After carefully examining these concepts, the questionnaire's variables were correctly added, deleted, and updated. In order to make the questionnaire clearer, simpler to understand, and more helpful, some changes were made based on the topic experts' comments and suggestions. This allowed us to confirm the validity of the questionnaire's content. Finally, a well-structured questionnaire has been developed for data collection on the basis of the aforementioned change.

4.7.2 Reliability Testing

To avoid oversights, finish the interview schedule, and define the measurement scale, a pilot survey of 25 respondents from Bangalore and Mangalore International airports was conducted. After the pilot survey was conducted, the scale's reliability and validity was assessed using the correct methods. Both the interview schedule and the evaluation criteria were adjusted as needed. This process made it easier for the researcher to modify the questionnaire as needed. The improvements were developed following careful consideration and advice from experts.

Table 4.1: Reliability and Validity Results

Construct	No. of Items	Reliability		Validity			
		Composite Reliability	Cronbach Alpha	AVE	MSV	Convergent	Discriminant
Irregular Working Hours	12	0.912	0.857	0.710	0.671	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE
Work Hassles	14	0.874	0.821	0.798	0.876	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE
Aircraft Cabin Environments	13	0.754	0.731	0.612	0.691	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE
Social Isolation	10	0.803	0.779	0.542	0.678	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE
Workplace Stress	8	0.898	0.834	0.692	0.563	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE
Stress Coping Resources	8	0.747	0.790	0.722	0.643	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE
Work Engagement	12	0.873	0.812	0.712	0.695	AVE>0.5	MSV<AVE

Verifying the validity and reliability of the chosen constructs, serves as the foundation for additional organised analysis in order to evaluate the link between them. Seven constructs, including irregular working hours (12 items), work hassles (14 items),

aircraft cabin environments (13 items), social isolation (10 items), workplace stress (8 items), stress coping resources (8 items), and work engagement (12 items), have been identified based on the various related works. The above test has been used as a reliability test to assess the internal consistency of the data, and the study is regarded as reliable if the alpha value is greater than 0.70. Irregular working hours (0.857), work hassles (0.821), aeroplane cabin environments (0.731), social isolation (0.779), workplace stress (0.834), stress coping resources (0.790), and work engagement (0.812) all have Cronbach's alpha value higher than 0.7. According to (Chong, 2017; Hair Jr. et al., 2017) [250] [251], a noteworthy reliability test result is one where the Chronbach's alpha value is greater than 0.7. According to the findings, all of the aforementioned constructs and indicators meet the basic standards because their alpha values are more than 0.7. By looking at the factor loadings and average variance extracted (AVE) of the constructs, convergent validity was evaluated. According to the above table, each parameter significantly loaded onto its corresponding latent structures (P.001), with values ranging from 0.542 to 0.798. Irregular working hours (AVE:0.710), work hassles (AVE:0.798), aircraft cabin environments (AVE:0.612), social isolation (AVE:0.542), workplace stress (AVE:0.692), stress coping resources (AVE:0.722), and work engagement (AVE:0.712) were all AVEs for each construct that were greater than or equal to 0.50, further supporting the convergent validity of the constructs. According to Hair et al. (2010), the Maximum Shares Variance and Average Variance Extracted can be compared to evaluate the discriminant validity. Regular Working Hours (0.671), Work Hassles (0.876), Aircraft Cabin Environments (0.691), Social Isolation (0.678), Workplace Stress (0.563), Stress Coping Resources (0.643), and Work Engagement (0.695) had the lowest maximum shared variance of each construct, which supports the discriminant validity of the constructs. Consequently, the measuring model showed strong construct validity and favorable psychometric features.

4.8 SAMPLING DESIGN

The goal of the real research is also to identify demographic traits or parameters. For the purposes of the research study, the population is the sum of all elements that have a set of common features.

4.8.1 Population

The sample is a subset of the population under investigation. Cabin Crews in the Aviation sector from the top-level and bottom level staff in International Airports in

Karnataka will be the target population for this study. Population N- 257: Official Information, Airlines (Bangalore 147, Mangalore 110), Cabin crews of airlines operating in Mangalore and Bangalore International airports.

Sampling Frame

The sampling frame represents the total population. Because of the two key factors: time and funding, research projects are dependent on samples. This research is based on a sample study. The population has been sampled in order to provide a representative sample. With the use of primary sources, the sampling frame was created. From the top to the bottom, staff at all levels have been called to obtain accurate information on the aviation industry's stress-related details.

4.8.2 Sample Size

A small sample size will offer little information, and time, economic viability, and ethical considerations restrict us from taking a big sample size. The sampling units for this study are 220 members, with 220 employees distributed among the levels. As a result, the table below shows the total sample size as well as sample sizes for each of the sectors. Sample Size 201 Members (Bangalore 115, Mangalore 86)

Sample Size Using Taro Yamane

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N * (e)^2}$$

$$n = 257 / 1 + 257 (0.05 * 0.05),$$

$$n = 257 / 1 + 257 * 0.0025$$

$$n = 257 / 1.6425 = 156$$

Table 4.2: Sample Size Distribution between Bangalore and Mangalore Airplane Company

Aviation Sector	Sampling Frame	Sample Size
Bangalore International Airport	147	115
Mangalore International Airport	110	86
Total	257	201

A small sample size will offer little information, and time, economic viability, and ethical considerations restrict us from taking a big sample size. In statistics, a sample size of 30 is considered a large sample because it follows normal approximation (Cohen, Jacob 1977). The sampling units for this study are 220 members.

Table 4.3: Questionnaire Distribution among Cabin Crews Position wise

Cabin Crews	Number of Respondent
Cabin Service Director	7
Inflight managers	51
Senior cabin crew	90
Junior cabin crew	57
Trainers	15
Total	220

Due to the high rate of non-response and invalid responses, a total of 201 questionnaires were distributed to top and bottom level aviation cabin crew personnel.

Table 4.4: Sample Distribution among Cabin Crews Position wise

Cabin Crews	Number of Respondent
Cabin Service Director	6
Inflight managers	46
Senior cabin crew	82
Junior cabin crew	55
Trainers	12
Total	201

4.8.3 Sample Inclusion

Cabin Crews: Top-level staff (Cabin Service Director, Inflight Manager etc.) to the bottom-level staff (Junior Cabin Crews, Trainers etc.)

Airplane Companies Included: Bangalore International Airport and Mangalore International Airport

Demographic Location Considered: International Airports of Karnataka

4.8.4 Sampling Technique

Snow Ball Sampling Technique were used.

4.8.5 Data Collection Period

The data was collected during the period April 2021 to December 2021

4.9 DATA COLLECTION METHOD

Data collection method involves both primary sources and secondary sources.

1. Secondary Data: The secondary data source includes data collected from journals, newspapers, magazines, articles, reports, and internet websites.

2. Primary Data: Employee engagement levels were measured through the administration of a structured questionnaire and interview method. The questions in the questionnaire have been divided into 9 sections. Section 1 of the research instrument consists of demographic as well as job description of the respondents which includes age, gender, marital status, current function, experience, change in lifestyle, maximum number of consecutive days of work, maximum number of consecutive nights of work and average days off per month. Other sections such as stressor agents, work engagement, workplace stress and stress coping resource inventory were formulated in the form of statements, which have been rated on a rating scale of five (1-strongly disagree to 5-strongly agree and other related metrics). Emotional labour and partial portion of stress coping resource inventory were measured with specific and open-ended questions. Refer Annexure Questionnaire scoring pattern and classification. The questions were rated on a Likert scale (1-strongly disagree to 5-strongly agree and other related metrics).

Table 4.5: Variables/Factors Used in the Study

Sl. No.	Variables		
1.	Personal Factors	Age	
		Gender	
		marital status	
		Current function	
		Experience	
		change in lifestyle	
		Maximum number of consecutive days of work	
		Maximum number of consecutive nights of work	
		Average days off per month	
2.	Stressor Agents	No. of Factors	No. of Items
		Irregular Working Hour	12
		Work Hassles	14
		Aircraft Environment	13
		Social Isolation	10
3.	Workplace Stress	8	
4.	Work Engagement	12	
5.	Emotional Labour	10	
6.	Stress Coping Resources	8	

4.10 TESTING THE ASSUMPTIONS

To make sure the acquired data is suitable for use in various statistical studies, it must be evaluated to see if it satisfies specific statistical assumptions. In the current investigation, the assumptions of normality, homogeneity, linearity, and multicollinearity were used to validate the data. For structural equation modelling, each of these presumptions is necessary (SEM). To satisfy the assumption of regression analysis, linear and multicollinearity tests are needed. To perform a parametric or non-parametric test, one must first verify that the data has a normal distribution. Multiple regression analysis was used for Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

4.10.1 Normality

Applying numerous statistical tests require the normality test, which is crucial. The data's normalcy affects how the validity tests are applied. SEM and other statistical tests can be employed if the data is confirmed to be normal. The test findings become untrustworthy if the data is not determined to be normal, at which point a non-parametric test can be applied. The tests employed in the current investigation are listed below.

4.10.2 Histogram Test for Normality

Applying numerous statistical tests require the normality test, which is crucial. The data's normalcy affects how the validity tests are applied. SEM and other statistical tests can be employed if the data is confirmed to be normal. The test findings become untrustworthy if the data is not determined to be normal, at which point a non-parametric test can be applied. The tests employed in the current investigation are listed below.

Figure 4.1: Histogram showing Normality of Workplace stress

Figure 4.2: Histogram showing Normality of Work Engagement

It is clear from Figure 4.1 that the selected variables exhibit a typical histogram curve. The data thus supports the premise of normalcy.

4.10.3 Homogeneity

Levene statistics were employed in the current study to examine the homogeneity of the data. The variance being equal is the null hypothesis. Two sets of data are required for this, one with factor variables and the other with dependent variables. The construct variables were employed as dependent variables, and the demographic variables were used as factor variables. When it can be argued that the variances are equal within the population distribution, the Levene statistic value should be above 0.5, and the significant value must be more than 0.05. The respondents' Gender, Marital Status and Maximum number of consecutive days of work were taken into account as demographic variables in the current investigation.

4.10.4 Linearity

To ensure that the assumptions of the regression analysis are met, the linearity test is crucial. The linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables is explained using regression analysis. A scatter plot can be used to understand the linear relationship between two variables (Stressor agents and Workplace stress, Workplace stress and work engagement, stress coping resources and work engagement). Here, "Stressor agents, Workplace stress and stress coping resources" were chosen as the independent variables and "Workplace stress and work engagement" as the dependent variables.

Figure 4.3: Test of Linearity between Stressor Agent and the Workplace Stress

Figure 4.4: Test of Linearity between the Workplace Stress and Work Engagement

Figure 4.5: Test of Linearity between Coping Behavior and Work Engagement

From Figure 4.5, it can be seen that the line drawn is a linear line. Both the variables established a linear relationship and fulfilled linearity assumption.

4.10.5 Multicollinearity

When the researcher takes into account more than one independent variable to predict a dependent variable in the study, multicollinearity is a significant problem in the normal distribution of data. The multicollinearity issue can be discovered if there is any connection between the independent variables. Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor are part of the statistics of collinearity (VIF). Multicollinearity is present if the VIF value is greater than 5 and the tolerance level is lower than 0.2. The multicollinearity test was used in the current investigation, and the findings are displayed in Table 4.6 “Stressor agents, Workplace stress and stress coping resources” were independent variables and "Workplace stress and work engagement" are dependent variables.

Table 4.6: Results of Multicollinearity Test

Indicators	Tolerance	VIF
Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress		
Irregular Working Hours	.479	2.087
Work Hassles	.354	2.828
Aircraft Cabin Environment	.407	2.459
Social Isolation	.428	2.336
Workplace Stress and Work Engagement		
Workplace Stress	0.60	1.000
Stress Coping Resources and Work Engagement		
Stress Coping Resources	0.43	1.000

Given that the VIF value is less than five and the tolerance level value is larger than 0.2, the findings of the multiple regression analysis attest to the absence of any multicollinearity problems in the data set.

4.11 RESEARCH TOOLS AND SOFTWARE PACKAGE USED

According to the objectives' specifications, the employees' responses were tagged and entered into the software. SPSS Version 21 is used to evaluate the data. As descriptive statistics, the study utilized mean, median, mode, range, standard deviation, percentage, and cumulative percentages. Various statistical tools were used for analyzing the collected data such as:

1. Reliability Test and Validity
2. Percentage Analysis
3. Descriptive Analysis
4. Independent sample t-test
5. One-way ANOVA
6. Correlation Analysis
7. Simple Regression Analysis
8. Multiple Regression Analysis
9. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), and Path Analysis

4.12 EXPLANATION ON DIFFERENT ANALYSIS USED

Statistical software was used to tabulate and evaluate the primary data that was gathered through the questionnaire. Various statistical methods used in social science research, such as univariate, bivariate, and multivariate analysis, were used to evaluate and interpret the data gathered from primary sources. Cronbach Alpha was used to conduct the reliability test. Appropriate bivariate and multivariate analyses were employed to measure the relationship between the variables and evaluate the theoretical model, and then the SEM model was utilised to analyse the measurement model.

4.12.1 Percentage Analysis: Percentage analysis was used to understand the demographic characteristics and job nature of the cabin crews. At the same time, this analysis was used to assess the frequency as well as percentage of each of the components of the study which includes Irregular Working Hours, Work Hassles, Aircraft Cabin Environments, Social Isolation, The Workplace Stress, Work Engagement, Emotional Labour, Stress Coping Resources

4.12.2 Descriptive Analysis: Under descriptive analysis mean, minimum, maximum and standard deviation has been used which describes the agreement level of cabin crews on Irregular Working Hours, Work Hassles, Aircraft Cabin Environments, Social

Isolation, The Workplace Stress, Work Engagement, Emotional Labour, Stress Coping Resources. In this analysis, average value, Standard Deviation, Minimum and maximum of each component has been calculated through SPSS software.

4.12.3 Correlation: Correlation is that statistical measure in which the extent and nature of a link between two or more variables are described. Establishing a potential association between the variables using this approach is helpful. If a correlation is discovered, it can be positive or negative. This analysis is used for analyzing the direction of the relationship between Irregular Working Hours, Work Hassles, Aircraft Cabin Environments, Social Isolation, The Workplace Stress, Work Engagement and Stress Coping Resources.

4.12.4 Independent Sample t-test: In order to compare the means of just two groups no more, no less, independent samples t-test has been used. This test is typically used to detect whether two population means differ. This process employs samples to infer information about populations, making it an inferential statistical hypothesis test. The two sample t-test is another name for the independent samples t-test. The present study used independent sample t-test to assess the mean difference between gender, marital status, Maximum number of consecutive days of work with regard to stressor agents, workplace stress, work engagement and stress coping resources.

4.12.5 One-way ANOVA: In order to ascertain whether there is a statistical support that the linked population means are statistically substantially different, one-way ANOVA ("analysis of variance") which examines the means of two or more independent groups has been applied. One-Way ANOVA is one of the parametric tests. To test research hypothesis 1, 2 and 3, the study adopted one way ANOVA evaluating the significant difference among the various demographic factors consisting of more than two groups with respect to stressor agents, workplace stress, work engagement and stress coping resources.

4.12.6 Simple Regression Analysis: A simple regression analysis is essentially a statistical technique used to quantify the relationship between a single independent variable and a single dependent variable based on historical observations. We analyse the modelling between the single independent variable and the dependent variable in the simple linear regression model. When there is just one independent variable in the linear regression model, the model is often referred to as a simple linear regression

model. In the present research, simple regression analysis has been used to see the impact of stressor agents on workplace stress and effect of workplace stress on work engagement at the same time to see the impact of stress coping resources on work engagement.

4.12.7 Multivariate Regression Analysis: A method called multivariate regression is used to assess how linearly connected different independent variables and different dependent variables are to one another. Due to the correlation between the variables, the relationship is considered to be linear. In the present study, multivariate regression analysis was undertaken to measure the impact of various dimensions of stressor agents on workplace stress.

4.12.8 Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and Path Analysis: The structural links between measurable variables and latent constructs are examined using SEM, a multivariate statistical analysis technique. The causal connections between the constructs are measured via path analysis. SEM was employed in the current study to determine how the stressor agents of the cabin crews affected workplace stress, and ultimately their work engagement.

The discussion above suggests that the research methods employed for this project are dependable and valid. The study's comprehensive statistical analysis was required to ensure the accuracy and validity of the data.

CHAPTER-V

AVIATION SECTOR OVERVIEW

5.1 HISTORY OF AVIATION

The development of kites in China in the fifth century marks the beginning of flying. The first versions of a rational airplane were envisioned by the renowned artist Leonardo da Vinci in his paintings from the fifteenth century. Tito Livio Burattini created a miniature aeroplane in 1647 that included four sets of glider wings. But it could never bear a person's weight. Later, in 1970, the Father of Aeronautics, Francesco Terzi, published a proposal that suggested the feasibility of cylinders constructed of copper foil that could be used to create lighter-than-air aircraft. The first hydrogen balloon was created when hydrogen was discovered in the 17th century. The first unmanned hot air balloon was flown over Annonay, France, in 1783 by the Montgolfier brothers, which also included Jacques-Étienne and Joseph-Michel. The aviation sector has advanced significantly as a result of the widespread adoption of digital technologies in the modern era. The development of improved aircraft designs was boosted by the introduction of computer-aided design and production tools in the 1970s. The development of lighter yet more durable materials for the construction of aeroplanes has been aided by newer technology like computer simulations. Most analogue and mechanical instruments are replaced with digital systems found in modern aircraft. In the 1980s, more modern computer-based electronic displays took the place of cathode ray displays in the cockpit. The glass cockpit of the Boeing 767 from 1981 is one prominent instance. When integrated into automatic pilots, contemporary displays transform cockpit resource management into a critical component of flight safety. Additionally, the utilization of composite materials, such as the one used to construct the Boeing 787 Dreamliner, has greatly reduced aircraft weight, improving fuel efficiency. The development of sweeping wing tips that lessen component weight and enhance an aircraft's aerodynamics is another result of advanced composite technology [252].

In a world that is becoming more and more globalized, air travel is a crucial component that both directly and indirectly makes a significant contribution to the process of development through its many economic advantages, including the creation of jobs, support for infrastructure, trade, business production, and tourism with its built-in multiplier benefit. According to a report from the Air Transport Action Group (ATAG) from July 2016, the aviation industry supports 62.7 million jobs globally and is 3.8 times more productive than other industries as a whole. The global passenger flow is

divided between domestic and international travel by a ratio of 40% to 60%, demonstrating the close ties and positive effects on the national economies. Statistics from ATAG show that if the aviation industry were a country, it would be the 21st largest in terms of Gross Domestic Product (GDP), with an annual GDP of \$664 billion (about the same as Sweden or Switzerland) and far greater than other G20 members. Aviation not only contributes 3.5 percent of the world's GDP but also has a \$2.7 trillion worldwide economic impact. With 3.7 billion passengers, 700 new routes, and a \$44 drop in the average return cost, air transport continued to increase steadily and gradually in 2016, favourably improving affordability (IATA). Understanding where aviation is going and how it has developed and advanced is essential. The 100th anniversary of commercial aviation was celebrated in 2014. The next 65 billion passengers are anticipated to travel by air before 2030, providing a stark picture of how something that was once a risky endeavour for the few is now a chance for the many as per Airbus, 2016. According to the Director General and CEO of IATA, the issue of public policy and regulatory framework to promote a safe, secure, and sustainable aviation and to be able to increase employment and prosperity is posed by the expanding demand in addition to infrastructure. There are 104,000 flights, 9.8 million people, and \$17.5 billion worth of cargo transported per day. According to IATA (2017), global passenger traffic increased 6.7% in 2016 over 2015. Capacity increased 6.9%. Demand increased year over year in every region [253-258].

5.2 INDIAN AVIATION INDUSTRY

Over the past few years, India's civil aviation sector has become one of the fastest expanding in the world. India is currently the world's third-largest domestic aviation market. Since the turn of the millennium, India has experienced unusually rapid growth in air passenger traffic, thanks in large part to rising affluence, enhanced connectivity, and low tickets. The airline industry, however, may experience a protracted path to recovery due to the tremendous disruption brought on by the Covid-19 outbreak, increasing risk aversion among air travellers, the potential of extended travel restrictions across countries, and business travel reduction [259]. According to the history of Indian aviation, the first domestic flight between Delhi and Karachi took off in December of 1912. It all started when the Indian Air facilities joined together with the UK-based Imperial Airways to expand their London–Karachi trip. The designation of Tata Sons Ltd, the first Indian airline from Karachi and Madras, marked the

beginning of the three-year period. Nine air transport businesses operated within India at the time of independence without assistance from the Indian government [260]. Together with Air India, the Indian government established a business in 1948. The Indian aviation industry was under the supervision of government-owned airlines until the middle of the 1990s. The Indian government adopted the open-sky policy and the liberalisation guidelines in 1990. This opened the door for a quick restructuring of the aviation sector. If we examine the scale of the Indian aviation market, we can find that, for the fiscal year 2016, there were 341.05 million passengers. The 11.13 percent compound annual growth rate from 2016 to 2020. According to the data, from the fiscal year 2016 to 2020, air traffic grew at a compound annual growth rate of 5.32 percent. In 2023, it's predicted to rise to 7.27 percent. From FY16 to FY20, there was an increase in aircraft movement of 9.83 percent for domestic aircraft and 3.57 percent for foreign aircraft. The need for more aircraft operating in the area is also increasing. The demand for investment increased along with the expansion of the infrastructure. The Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade's (DPIIT's) [260] show that between April 2000 and March 2000, overseas direct investment increased to US\$2.75 billion. In scheduled air travel facilities, regional air travel services, and national scheduled passenger airlines, the regime has pushed 100 percent FDI through the automatic route. In the ensuing four years, it is predicted that this endeavour will generate 35,000 crores. Therefore, the Indian government intends to spend US\$1.83 billion by 2026 to expand airport infrastructure and aviation navigation services.

According to Oxford Economics (2011) [261], India's aviation industry is currently expanding quickly and contributes close to \$4.5 billion to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Due to its catalytic effect on tourism, it supports more than 1.7 million jobs both directly and indirectly and is predicted to rise steadily. This is made possible by rising costs and falling airfares, which draw more travellers to the airport. Domestic travel makes up the majority of India's air passenger traffic, which increased from 116.9 million in 2007–2008 to 223.6 million in 2015–2016, according to figures from the Airports Authority of India. It is challenging for airport management authorities in India to control the pedestrian movement in and around the airport terminal building because of the country's expanding aviation traffics [262]. India's civil aviation sector is a developing industry. A new era of industry growth has been ushered in by the construction of modern airports, the rise of low-cost airlines, the government of India's

increased emphasis on regional connectivity, funding for foreign direct investment in India's aviation sector, and an increased use of cutting-edge information technology. From multinational corporations, producers, airlines, tourism boards, and shippers to individual travellers, the entire world is watching Indian aviation. If all parties involved in Indian aviation could come together with a same goal, we would be looking at a bright future. We might argue that India's aviation industry got its start in 1911 when the first commercial flight left Allahabad, Uttar Pradesh, for Naini. In 1932, Mr. JRD Tata founded the first airline, which was called Tata Airlines. In 1946, this Tata Airlines changed its name to Air India. In India, aviation travel was long considered to be an exclusive hobby. This point of view originated from the "Maharajah" stereotype, according to which only the wealthy and powerful could afford flying because it was so expensive. However, in recent years, this perception of civil aviation has changed, and today, it is seen as an important link for both international travel and trade as well as access to other regions of India. The aviation sector contributes significantly to the nation's infrastructure and has a significant impact on the development of commerce, industry, business, trade, and tourism since it facilitates access to and stimulation of economic growth in the nation's remote regions. The first airmail flight in India was flown by a Frenchman, Monseigneur Pigué, and it took place on February 18, 1911, covering a distance of around 10 kilometres between Allahabad and Naini. The "Air Corporation Act" was passed by the Indian Parliament in 1953. In accordance with this Act, Air India Corporation Limited and Indian Airlines were created by uniting all eight domestic airlines. Air taxi service was initially authorised by the government. After the Act was revised in 1994, many private airlines were given permission to run regular flights and they began domestic operations. In the year 1911, Air India and Indian Airlines amalgamated. It links India with a number of significant global cities. GoAir, Air India, IndiGo, Spicejet, and Jet Airways are the principal airlines that fly into India. They operate international flights in addition to connecting more than 80 cities and commercial hubs throughout India as a result of the liberalisation of the Indian aviation industry [263]. Given that majority of the population of the country still finds flying to be expensive, India's aeronautics business remains mostly unexplored and offers tremendous growth potential. The upwardly mobile white-collar class makes up over 40%. Business partners should get in touch with policymakers and work together to implement smart decisions that will support India's responsible aviation sector. With the proper plans in place and a persistent focus on quality, pricing, and traveller

premium, India would be well-positioned to realise its goal of becoming the third-largest avionics advertising by 2025. India had a 16.52 percent increase in passenger volume year over year to 308.75 million in FY18. It expanded at a 12.72 percent CAGR (Compound Annual Growth Rate) from FY (Financial Year) 06 to FY18. Domestic passenger traffic reached 243 million in FY18 and is projected to reach 293.28 million in FY20E, an increase of 18.28 percent year over year. In the years 2017–18, India's domestic and international aviation sectors grew by 9.40% and 14.40%, respectively, to 1.886.63 million and 437.93 million [264]. Given that the bulk of the population of India, of which almost 40% is the upwardly mobile middle class, still finds flying to be prohibitively expensive, the country's aviation business is mostly unexplored and offers tremendous growth potential.

To implement effective and sensible policies that will strengthen India's civil aviation business, industry players should interact and work together with policy makers. India would be in a good position to realise its goal of being the third-largest aviation market by 2020 with the appropriate regulations and a relentless focus on quality, cost, and passenger interest. By 2021, it is anticipated that Indian travellers will spend up to Rs.9.5 lakh crore (US\$ 136 billion). India will require 2,380 new commercial aircraft by the year 2038 due to the increase in air transport demand. The travel market in India, which was estimated to be worth about US\$ 75 billion in FY20, is anticipated to reach US\$ 125 billion by FY27, according to a report titled "Travel market in India" that was released by RedCore, a RedSeer division that focuses on early-stage firms [265]. As far as this study is concerned, two international airports are mainly focused i.e., Bangalore International Airport and Mangalore International Airport; the overview of which is further provided in a next section.

5.3 BENGALURU INTERNATIONAL AIRPORT

Bengaluru District in the Indian state of Karnataka is home to Kempegowda International Airport, formerly known as Bengaluru International Airport. The third busiest airport in India, it opened in 2008. It is located at an altitude of 920 metres close to the village of Devanahalli in the rural Bengaluru District, some 40 kilometres northeast of the city of Bengaluru. Bengaluru, India's fifth-most populated city, is categorised as an urban agglomeration and served 8.5 million people in 2011[266]. Geographically, it has a varied terrain to the south and a plain plateau to the north that

is bordered by a notable ridge running NE-SW [267]. The first Greenfield Airport in India built using a Public-Private Partnership (PPP) model is Kempegowda International Airport, Bengaluru (BLR Airport), named after the city's founder, Hiriya Kempegowda. This was the beginning of a revolution in Indian aviation, and more airports in the nation were subsequently privatized [268].

Figure 5.1. The Journey of BLR Airport [269]

Bangalore International Airport Limited (BIAL), established under the Companies Act, 1956, was founded in January 2001 with the purpose of developing, owning, and running BLR Airport for a 60-year concession. Anchorage Infrastructure Investments Holdings Limited, FIH Mauritius Investments Limited, and Siemens Projects Ventures are the only private promoters with a stake in the project; the government owns the remaining 26% along with Karnataka State Industrial & Infrastructure Development Corporation Limited and the Airports Authority of India. BLR 33 months after construction began, on May 24, 2008, the airport opened for business. The Terminal's extension was finished in 2014 in order to accommodate the continual, unprecedented growth in passenger volumes. After handling 10 million passengers in 2008, KIAB saw extraordinary development in the years that followed, rising to become the airport with the fastest growth rate in the world by 2018. With 33.65 million passengers, KIAB finished the calendar year 2019. BLR Airport links Bengaluru to 61 domestic and 14 foreign destinations thanks to cutting-edge technologies including contactless passenger processing, self-bag drops, and biometric-based self-boarding. Domestic airlines dealing with BIAL includes Air Asia, Go First, IndiGo, SpiceJet, Star Air, True Jet, Vistara, and Air India [269].

5.4 MANGALORE INTERNATIONAL AIRPORT

An important hub for trade and business in India, Mangalore is the capital of the Dakshina Kannada district and home to numerous enterprises, a port, and an airport. Going back, in the 14th century, Mangalore was a highly important trading port with the Gulf States. Due to its unique location, it was ruled by numerous dynasties and colonial regimes. In India, Mangalore is one of the cities that is growing the quickest. As we can see, numerous global corporations are currently locating in Mangalore, indicating that the city will have positive economic growth in the coming years. Massive infrastructural improvements are being undertaken, and Mangalore became the banking industry's steady home. With a variety of educational streams being offered in and around the city, Mangalore is referred to as the "cradle of education." This pattern draws a lot of domestic and international travellers, creating a lovely fusion of cultures. Mangalore has the best food sector and a purchase centre that demonstrates the residents' purchasing power. Health care is not an issue in Mangalore because there are several hospitals with multiple specialties, thus medical tourism is also popular right now. Mangalore also has a number of tourist and religious destinations with a fantastic fusion of cultures. Mangalore will now concentrate on aviation in order to benefit from long-distance connectivity and grow its economic activity. The aviation industry plays a key part in the nation's economic development since infrastructure should be linked to the economic development of any region. The transportation of goods and people will raise revenues, create jobs, and allow for foreign direct investment, all of which will assist to boost the country's GDP. Other industries will be made possible by the aviation sector. Therefore, the airport will promote trade and tourism, which will boost economic growth. The airport therefore influences both the micro and macroeconomics of the system as it serves as a hub for commercial and economic development. In accordance with the research case study principles of Company analysis [270-271] and Industry analysis [272], the growth story and future developments of Mangalore International Airport (MIA) are explored and examined in this paper. Nearly 13 kilometres from the city centre, on the northeastern side of Mangalore, is where you'll find the Mangalore International Airport. It lies 4-5 kilometres from the ocean and at an elevation of roughly 300 m. It is well-known for having a tabletop runway at the top of a hill. Originally known as Bajpe Aerodrome, the current Mangalore International Airport opened on December 25, 1951. It is the second major airport in operation; the

first is Bangalore's Kempegowda International Airport. The airport had a short 1600 m runway that could accommodate a certain brand of aircraft known as a Boeing 737-400 size aircraft. The runway was constructed in 2006 so that it could accommodate the landing of somewhat bigger aircraft, such as Kingfisher Airline's Airbus A319 model. The first airport in the state of Karnataka with two runways and a concrete runway is MIA. 8,038 feet long and built in 2006 is the second runway. 95 people were transported from Bangalore on the first trip by Jet Airways. As a result, in 2012, the Airbus A310, which was carrying Saudi Arabian Hajj pilgrims, made a safe landing at Mangalore International Airport. The airport's development in 2006 allowed it to fly Air India Express to Dubai, however at first it only served domestic travel. The biggest achievement was this milestone. A step further, after serving as the customs airport for six years, the airport in Mangalore received the designation of international airport in 2012. The aviation industry continued to expand in Mangalore, which boosted the local economy. With a capacity of 34 million people annually, it has the largest terminals. The airport in Mangalore now has two terminals, 1 and 2. The domestic terminal, Terminal 1, is where planes depart for popular locations like Mumbai, Chennai, Delhi, Hyderabad, Bangalore, and Surat [6].

5.5 PROFILE OF SELECTED AIRLINE COMPANIES

5.5.1 GO FIRST

Son of Indian billionaire Nusli Wadia, Jeh Wadia founded Go First in November 2005 as GoAir. The Wadia Group owns the airline in its entirety [273]. On November 4, 2005, GoAir launched its operations and flew its first route from Mumbai to Ahmedabad utilising an Airbus A320 [273]. The airline started up serving four locations, including Goa and Coimbatore, with a single aircraft, with aspirations to add 36 aircraft by 2008 [274]. By the end of the year, the airline revealed revised intentions to fly 11 aircraft and serve new locations in the North East and South India [275] Go First was forced to reduce the number of flights in June 2008 due to rising fuel expenses. British Airways expressed interest in purchasing a stake in the airline in January 2009 [276]. In November 2009, GoAir and SpiceJet, an Indian airline, began discussing a

potential merger; however, there was no agreement reached [277]. After Kingfisher Airlines went out of business in April 2012, GoAir rose to the fifth-largest airline in India in terms of market share [278]. The airline hired JP Morgan, an investment firm, in 2013 to look for potential investors [279]. In comparison to other airlines founded at the same time as the airline, such as IndiGo and SpiceJet, who as of 2016 had a bigger market share, fleet size, and destinations served, the airline's growth has lagged [280]. The airline claims it is a planned strategy because of the challenging aviation climate in India to put more of an emphasis on preserving profitability than on gaining market share and expanding the number of destinations and fleet size [281][282]. With an 8% market share as of February 2016, it was the fifth-largest carrier in the nation [283]. In 2020, the airline intends to conduct an initial public offering (IPO) [284]. When GoAir inaugurated its first flight from New Delhi to Phuket on October 11, 2018, it became the sixth domestic airline in India to offer foreign service [285]. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic's effects, GoAir ceased its foreign flights on March 17, 2020 [286]. Go First replaced GoAir as its name in May 2021.

Cabin Staff

For our cabin crew, the company has created and put into effect a recruitment strategy in which they evaluate each candidate's educational background, interpersonal abilities, and personality attributes and we choose to hire those who speak clearly, have a good attitude, and behave politely. Cabin crews' ability to provide quality in-flight service depends on their technical proficiency, safety expertise, and people skills. To ensure high-quality service, we consistently strengthen high standards and instill them in all of our cabin crew members. At their internal training centre, GoAir Learning Academy, all of their cabin crew receive training to provide them with the necessary knowledge and abilities. Their training places a strong emphasis on safety and adherence to DGCA rules and regulations, among other things. All cabin crew members also participate in leadership training, recurring training, and as initio training.

All cabin crew members go through an initial training session when they join. Crew receive DGCA certification and are allowed to fly after a successful completion.

- Grooming and Department-Image management, hair and makeup style, and manners.
- Achieving customer delight is a core principle of customer service.
- In-flight Services-Customer service practices, product management techniques, and sales techniques.
- First Aid-Using first aid to manage medical emergencies on board.

- Safety and Emergency Procedures-Preparing crews to handle a variety of emergencies that might occur while flying.
- Practical Drills-Training in situational awareness through simulation, including exercises for ditching, opening doors, and battling fires.
- Aviation Security-BCAS-compliant security training
- Training to recognize goods that are illegal under the dangerous goods regulations.

Crew Resource Management-Instruction on the value of situational awareness and cooperation in ensuring flight safety and efficient operations. All cabin crew members go through annual compliance training. The DGCA, business policy, and other laws and regulations all call for general and type-specific safety and emergency procedure training. Customer service and onboard service protocols are also reviewed with the crew. Leadership training for senior cabin crew, who are obliged to captain every flight under [287].

5.5.2 AIR INDIA

Bharat Ratna J.R.D. Tata founded an airline in 1932, realising his ambition and beginning the journey that would become Air India. His love of flying, which led him to become the first Indian to acquire a commercial pilot's license, ignited the beginnings of Air India with the introduction of a mail service from then-Bombay to Karachi via Ahmedabad. Since becoming nationalised in 1953, Air India has grown to become a significant domestic and international brand. After joining Star Alliance, the largest global airline alliance, in July 2014, Air India's international connectivity, which includes cities in Europe, the United States, the United Kingdom, Africa, the Gulf, Asia, and Australia, was improved. The airline flies to every rural region of our nation. It has consistently stood by the country and its citizens in times of need and has been crucial in evacuation operations throughout crises like the Gulf War, the AIDS pandemic, and the most recent situation in Ukraine. After rejoining the Tata Group on January 27, 2022, Air India is ready to fly, redefining its objectives and strategy with a focus on overall excellence and customer-centric procedures. Air India operates a modern fleet of Airbus (319, 320, 320Neo, and 321) and Boeing (777-200LR, 777-300ER, and 787-800 Dreamliner) aircraft [288].

Employee Advantages:

a) Employee provident fund contributions make up defined contribution plans. Once the contributions are paid, the Company has no more debts to pay. When an employee performs the relevant service, the contributions are recognized as an employee benefit expense and are accounted for as defined contribution plans.

b) Gratuity is a part of unfunded defined benefit plans. According to Ind-AS 19, the obligation for these benefits is actuarially calculated at year's end using the Projected Unit Credit Method. The obligation is valued at the projected future cash flows' present value. The market yields on government securities as of the balance sheet date, with maturity durations roughly matching the terms of corresponding commitments, are used to calculate the present value of obligations under defined benefit plans. Re-measurements Gains and losses resulting from actuarial assumptions revisions and experience adjustments are recorded immediately in Other Comprehensive Income in the period in which they take place. Both the Statement of Changes in Equity and the Balance Sheet list them under "Other Equity." Settlement or curtailment-related changes to the defined benefit obligation's current value are recognised as past service cost right away in the profit and loss statement.

c) Other Long-Term Employee Benefits: The Company's net obligation in respect of Leave Encashment is the amount of benefit to be settled or utilized in future, that employees have earned in return for their service in the current and previous years. The benefit is discounted to determine its present value. The obligation is measured on the basis of an actuarial valuation using the projected unit credit method. Re-measurements are recognized in Statement of Profit and Loss in the period in which they arise.

d) Short Term Benefits Short Term Employee Benefits are accounted for in the period during which the services have been rendered [289].

5.5.3 SpiceJet

Indian low-cost carrier SpiceJet has its main office in Gurgaon, Haryana. By number of domestic passengers transported, it is the second largest airline in the nation, with a market share of 13.6% as of March 2019. [290] From its hubs in Delhi and Hyderabad, the airline offers 630 flights per day to 64 destinations, including 54 in India and 15 abroad. ModiLuft, an air taxi service provider founded in 1994, was bought out by

Indian businessman Ajay Singh in 2004 and changed its name to SpiceJet. In May 2005, the airline conducted its inaugural flight. Through Sun Group, Indian media tycoon Kalanidhi Maran bought a majority share in SpiceJet in June 2010. In January 2015, he gave that stake back to Ajay Singh [291].

The goal of SpiceJet is to establish itself as India's go-to low-cost carrier by offering price-conscious clients the lowest flight rates combined with the best customer value. Also, the goal of SpiceJet is to make flying accessible to all people. As of March 31, 2021, the company employed 14,578 people, 4,299 of whom were contracted workers. There are about 3,548 women working for the company on a permanent basis. To ensure that they receive appropriate support to work as effectively as possible, the company employees to declare any disabilities they may have such workers were employed as of March 31, 2021. The policies forbid the use of child labour, forced labour, or involuntary labour; as a result, the company does not employ child labour or use forced labour, and it does not work with vendors or suppliers who do so. The following information relates to complaints received during the fiscal year 2020-21:

S. No.	Category	No. of complaints filed during the financial year	No. of complaints pending as on end of the financial year
1.	Child labour/forced labour/involuntary labour	-	-
2.	Sexual harassment	16	2
3.	Discriminatory employment	-	-

Figure 5.2 Complaints received during the fiscal year 2020-21 [259].

Through various learning programmes, the company aims to upskill and improve the competencies of its personnel. These training sessions are available to all of the staff, regardless of their colour, gender, or physical limitations. The company provided 3,864 employees with safety and skill-upgrading training throughout the 2020–21 fiscal year (including training imparted to employee more than once). The company acknowledges that employees may be interested in participating in organisations or civic or public issues in their individual capacities, so long as their endeavours do not directly or indirectly interfere with the objectives of the business. As of March 31, 2021, the Company has not recognized any employee associations [259].

5.5.4 INDIGO

Indian low-cost carrier InterGlobe Aviation Ltd., operating as IndiGo, has its headquarters in Gurgaon, Haryana. By number of passengers transported and fleet size, it is the biggest airline in India [292]. As of October 2021, it has a 53.5% share of the domestic market [293]. With nearly 6.4 crore (64 million) passengers carried in the fiscal year 2018–19, it is also the largest individual Asian low-cost carrier in terms of jet fleet size and passengers carried, and the fourth largest carrier in Asia. As of 2019 [294], the airline offered 1,500 daily flights to 96 locations (71 domestic and 25 foreign) [295]. At Delhi's Indira Gandhi International Airport, it has its main hub. With a market share of 55.5 percent as of January 2022, IndiGo is the biggest passenger airline in India. It is low-cost carrier that focuses on three pillars of providing inexpensive rates, being on time, and providing a polite and hassle-free service. The airline primarily serves the domestic air travel market in India. Being on time is now a given with IndiGo. The airline began operations in August 2006 with a single aircraft and have since expanded to a fleet of 279 aircraft. It is one of the most dependable airlines in the world thanks to the uniform fleet for every type of operation, great operational reliability, and award-winning service. IndiGo has a total of 97 destinations, including 24 international and 73 domestics [296].

IndiGo boasts more female pilots than any other airline in the world (14.1%). 94 percent of the organisation was covered when the first diversity and inclusion e-learning programme was released.

Annual Report 2020-21

Figure 5.3 Number of employees [297].

This business is dedicated to supporting workplace diversity and giving all employees the same opportunities regardless of their race, colour, religion, age, gender, sexual orientation, national origin, disability, or other characteristics. Employees have a right to a workplace that is free from all forms of discrimination, including harassment, coercion, and disruptive behaviour, including conduct that could be considered sexual harassment. The company strictly prohibits any form of sexual harassment. The goal is to create a workplace free from all sorts of harassment, provide everyone an equal chance, respect personal space, and acknowledge the right to be heard. All of your company's employees are provided with a clean, safe, and healthy working environment. Activities that promote employee engagement are carried out frequently to keep a positive work atmosphere. The company prioritises the welfare of all of its employees, and all required measures are taken to guarantee it. The following information pertains to the number of personnel classified under various heads as of March 31, 2021:

Details relating to complaints received during FY 2021:

S. No.	Category	No. of complaints received during FY 2021	
		Filed during the year	Pending as at end of the year
1	Child labour/ forced labour / involuntary labour	-	-
2	Sexual harassment	15	2*
3	Discriminatory employment	-	-

*complaints were under investigation as on March 31, 2021 (which have since been resolved within the prescribed timelines)

Figure 5.4 Complaints received during FY 2021 by Indigo [297].

There have been no recorded incidents of child labour, forced labour, involuntary labour, or discriminatory employment during FY 2021. The company is committed to maximizing employee engagement, which is a cornerstone of our culture and essential to delivering first-rate customer service. In order to inspire the employees, the company routinely give out awards like "Employee of the Month," "Employee of the Quarter," or "Employee of the Year." Additionally, the company launched a programme to solicit ongoing feedback from its employees from the beginning of 2020. The "6e Speaks" method involves asking 4-6 questions on predetermined topics that have been shown in study to have an effect on employee engagement twice a month in order to get rapid pulse-type answers. The Company then continuously evaluates these inputs and modifies any necessary essential employee processes. Additionally, training is a powerful motivator, and the company's learning and development philosophy is one of

the ways it develops the talents of its employees at all levels. "IFly" academies in Gurugram and Bangalore offer a wide range of courses that focus on fostering self-development and self-directed learning while addressing skills and behaviour that are pertinent to present employment and potential future advancement. Their strategy goes from introductory programmes that are intended to acquaint new hires with our principles, help them comprehend SOPs, service standards, regulatory guidelines, IndiGo culture, etc., to advanced training in leadership and team management as employees move up the corporate ladder [297].

5.5.5 AIR ASIA

Founded on March 28, 2013, Air Asia (India) Limited is an unlisted public corporation. It is based in Bangalore, Karnataka, and is categorised as a public limited corporation. Its total paid-up capital is INR 3,521.00 crore, and its authorised share capital is INR 5,200.00 crore. The operating revenue range for Air Asia (India) Limited's fiscal year that ends on March 31, 2021, is over INR 500 crore. It's EBITDA has decreased by -178.75 percent over the previous year. Its book net worth has also dropped by -197.04 percent over this time. The business offers services for passenger air transportation. AirAsia Travel Protection, duty-free shopping, ROKKI Wi-Fi, entertainment, and in-flight meals are among the goods and services offered. Air Asia (India) Limited's current status is Active. According to our records, Air Asia (India) Limited's most recent recorded AGM (Annual General Meeting) took place on June 29, 2021. Additionally, according to our records, its most recent balance sheet was created for the time frame ending on March 31, 2021 [298].

Gender Pay Gap – Air Asia:

Job Category	Gender	2021		
		Number of employees	Percentage, %	Pay Gap
Captain	Male	1,062	97%	-8.86%
	Female	32	3%	
First Officer	Male	1,026	91%	-8.09%
	Female	103	9%	
Licensed Aircraft Engineer	Male	336	96%	-12.73%
	Female	15	4%	
Other Engineer	Male	152	82%	-23.34%
	Female	34	18%	
Cabin Crew	Male	981	32%	3.76%
	Female	2,073	68%	

Figure 5.5 Gender pay gap -Air Asia [298].

According to their research, there is no systematic discrimination against women in the pay schedules. JG1 is the only job grade that stands out with a gap that is close to the 15% cutoff that we have internally established as acceptable variance, taking into consideration variations in work categories and countries of employment. The disparities in salary are the result of a historical bias at the industry level that generated more male engineers and pilots. By hiring and training more female pilots over the previous ten years than any other airline in Asean, AirAsia has made major efforts to solve this issue. Flexible work schedules, such as working from home when practical [299].

Financial Well-being:

Upskilling Through AirAsia Academy, the company offers a variety of development opportunities and programmes that enable Allstars to consistently improve and empower their skills. Career Development Through their internal talent marketplace, which is supported by the nimble AI system Eight Fold, they assist Allstars in identifying and utilising their talents to open to new career prospects. In order to assist Allstars in navigating their careers and increase clarity in the career pathways, they also organise stretch assignments through our AirAsia got Talent initiative. They provide financial education with AKPK, BNM, and other providers on debts, personal financial management, and legacy planning [299].

Physical Fitness:

They give Allstars the freedom to choose how they function best based on the role. They also promote relaxation and recuperation with advantages like annual leave. Travel Advantages Employee e-coupons and ID90 for travel needs allow Allstars to take advantage of their flights. Life/Medical benefits along with perks like an on-site clinic, physiotherapy, and life and personal accident insurance, they offer medical insurance. To ensure that Allstars have a comfortable environment to work and relax when needed, they offer amenities including a building-based gym and sleeping pods [299].

Emotional Health:

Through their Red Heart Fund, they offer assistance with paternity leave, marriage leave, and provide medical and bereavement support. Office culture through their dedicated internal platforms, EkoChilli and workplace, they strive for a culture of fun,

transparency, and active communication. Companies culture team sponsors seminars on health-related subjects as well as events for fun and involvement. They provide Allstars with simple access to a variety of interactive and instructional services online through our Allstar Health Coach, a holistic well-being and wellness brand called Naluri [299].

Employee Participation:

Because they appreciate the input of all Allstars and believe that open conversation fosters a sense of belonging, they have always worked to establish a highly engaging workplace where Allstars can openly discuss ideas and perspectives. This, in turn, increases work happiness and productivity. The four pillars of Capital A's employee engagement strategy are learning, social, information and support, and well-being. They are now using online platforms like EkoChilli, Workplace, and Google Meet to keep Allstars updated on corporate-related topics, when before a lot of involvement took place physically. On EkoChilli, there is a tonne of engagement between Allstars. Some teams have their own channels for engagement [299].

5.5.6 VISTARA

The airline was established in 2013 as a joint venture (JV) between Singapore Airlines and Indian conglomerate Tata Sons (SIA) [300][301]. The two businesses attempted to establish a full-service airline in India in the middle of the 1990s but were unsuccessful after the Indian government rejected their application for regulatory permission [302]. Tata and SIA planned to create a JV airline firm in India once more when India opened up its airline sector to 49 percent foreign direct investment (FDI) in 2012 [303]. In India's civil aviation sector, which is dominated by low-cost carriers, the JV, Tata SIA Airlines Limited (TSAL), was designed as a premium full-service carrier to meet the needs of high-end business travellers. The JV received approval from India's Foreign Investment Promotion Board in October 2013, enabling SIA to acquire a 49 percent interest in the airline [304]. Initial start-up capital commitments from the two parent firms totaled \$100 million, with Tata Sons owning 51% and Singapore Airlines holding

the remaining 49% [305]. Along with acquiring a small share in AirAsia India, this was Tata's second significant entry into the aviation industry [306]. The initial business of the corporation, Tata Airlines, was founded in the 1930s and, after being nationalised, changed its name to Air India [307]. On August 11, 2014, the business introduced its "Vistara" brand identity [308]. The Sanskrit term *vistra*, which means "limitless expanse," served as the inspiration for the name [309] [310].

5.6 CURRENT INVESTMENTS IN AVIATION INDUSTRY

The Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade (DPIIT) reported that between April 2000 and June 2021, FDI investment into India's air transport sector (including air freight) reached US\$ 3.06 billion. In scheduled air transport, regional air transport, and domestic scheduled passenger airlines, the government has approved 100 percent FDI via the automatic route. Government clearance is necessary for FDI above 49%, though. Current investments in Indian aviation industry include:

- In July 2021, IndiGo committed to looking into the use of renewable fuel in aircraft.
- As of August 2021, Raghu Vamsi intends to construct a US\$ 15 million facility in Hyderabad to accommodate Boeing's needs.
- In order to capitalise on the demand for domestic air travel, Rare Enterprises wants to launch an ultra-low-cost airline in 2021 in conjunction with the former CEOs of IndiGo and Jet Airways.
- In the upcoming four years, investments totaling Rs. 35,000 crore (US\$ 4.99 billion) are anticipated in India's aviation sector. By 2026, the Indian government intends to spend US\$1.83 billion on the expansion of airport infrastructure and aviation navigation services [311].

Significant investments and advances in India's aviation sector:

- For the development of the airport sector, the Airports Authority of India (AAI) and other airport developers set a capital outlay target of Rs.91,000 crore (US\$12.08 billion) in February 2022.
- In October 2021, Tata Sons won the bid to acquire state-run Air India by offering Rs.18,000 crore (US\$ 2.4 billion) to acquire 100% shares.
- The Ministry of Civil Aviation granted Akasa Air, a start-up airline, a "No Objection" licence to begin operations in October 2021. The startup intends to start operating in the middle of 2022.

- Private aviation firm JetSetGo said in September 2021 that it would implement a carbon management programme to make its aircraft operations carbon neutral by 2024.
- At the Skytrax World Airport Awards in August 2021, Indira Gandhi International Airport was named the best airport in India and Central Asia.
- Under the auspices of the World Economic Forum, SpiceJet declared its audacious goal to fly 100 million domestic passengers on Sustainable Aviation Fuel (SAF) blend by 2030 in June 2021. (WEF).
- An aircraft manufacturer named Boeing declared in April 2021 that it has teamed up with the Indian Aviation Academy (IAA) and the University of Southern California (USC) to provide safety management system training to all parties involved in the domestic aviation sector.
- To increase tourism and connectivity, the government announced plans to build four water aerodromes in the Andaman & Nicobar Islands this year and two water aerodromes in Assam in March 2021.
- Under the Ministry of Civil Aviation's UDAN-RCS, the government made a proposal in March 2021 to create a water aerodrome project near the Ujjani Dam (regional connectivity scheme).
- In a virtual ceremony on March 25, 2021, Union Minister of Civil Aviation Hardeep Singh Puri opened the Kurnool Airport in Orvakal, Andhra Pradesh. Under the Regional Connectivity Scheme-Ude Desh Ka Aam Nagrik, flight operations at Kurnool Airport will begin on March 28, 2021. (RCS-UDAN). Up till November 7th, 2021, UDAN flights carried 34,38,955 passengers.
- WTTC estimates that India's total contribution of travel and tourism (4.7 percent) to the GDP in 2020 placed it seventh out of 185 nations. The contribution was worth 121.9 billion US dollars.
- For the next five years, AAI intends to invest Rs.25,000 crore (US\$ 3.58 billion) to upgrade airport infrastructure and facilities.
- A UK consortium will invest US\$ 135.9 million (about Rs.950 crore) in the new airline TruStar from Turbo Aviation [311].

5.7 GOVERNMENT INITIATIVES

India's aviation industry has grown significantly in recent years, both economically and socially. The number of air travellers increased along with the economy. In the last few

years, the industry has seen an increase in development and investments. In Andaman & Nicobar, AAI set up plans to launch the first three water airports in 2019. It was also noted that IndiGo was announced to be the first Indian airline to raise the aircraft fleet size to 250 planes in January 2020, right before the COVID-19 breakout. IndiGo was hailed to fly 1500 flights per day. In order to provide quality service to consumers in December 2019, the Indian Aviation Industry has to invest US\$ 150 million [273] for the aircraft maintenance, repair, and overhaul unit. The customs and countervailing charges on this service were totally waived. Adani Properties Private Limited was given permission by the Indian Competition Commission to purchase a part of Mumbai International Airport Limited in November 2019. AAI has a long-term five-year strategy to meet all of the aviation industry's needs, therefore it invested approximately 25,000 crores to upgrade facilities and infrastructure at airports. It also implemented a plan to achieve this goal, developing Agartala, Imphal, and Dibrugarh as intra-regional centres and Guwahati as an inter-regional hub. The aviation industry was highly praised for the services it provided. Air traffic was estimated to be 341.05 million [312] in 2020, growing at a compound annual growth rate of 11.13 percent. The fact that the national passenger circulation reached 274.50 million in FY20, with 66.54 million passengers and a compound growth rate of 5.01 percent, contributed to this development as well. In FY20, 2,155 thousand aircrafts were moved internationally. In order to accommodate these advances, India had 103 operating airports in FY20, an increase of 190–200. Between mid-April 2000 and mid-March 2020, it was noted that India's air transportation industry generated 2.75 billion US dollars. The proposed air transport service, regional air transport facility, and national scheduled passenger airline are all subject to government approval of 100 percent FDI under the automatic route. However, FDI above 49% must have government clearance. Investment in India's aviation sector is anticipated to total Rs 35,000 crore (US\$ 4.99 billion) during the next four years. Over the next four years, an estimated Rs.35,000 crores (US\$4.99 billion) would be invested in India's aviation sector. The Indian government also intends to invest US\$1.83 billion by 2026 for the expansion of airport infrastructure and aviation navigation services [313].

As a result, the Indian government has launched numerous initiatives to advance the aviation sector. Flights were performed under the "Lifeline Udan" initiative by the Indian government to transfer vital medical supplies to remote areas of the nation in

support of India's fight against COVID-19. Air India, Alliance Air, the IAF, as well as other airlines, operated 465 flights as of May 5, 2020. In order to assist farmers in shipping agricultural products and raising the value of such products, the government also launched the "Krishi Udan Scheme" on both national and international routes. This programme was unveiled in the Union Budget for 2020–21. In order to make the Indian aviation market self-sufficient, the government of India is also boosting aircraft finance and leasing activities under the Union Budget 2019–20. The Government of India is building a new greenfield airport in Hirasar, Gujarat. sanctioned in February 2019 with an estimated \$194.73 million (Rs.1,405 crore) investment. The Indian government began developing a comprehensive plan in January 2019 to encourage indigenous aircraft finance and production. Over 1,200 delegates from 83 nations attended the Global Aviation Summit, which the government held in Mumbai in January 2019. By the end of the next ten years, Indian air cargo and logistics would be the most effective, open, and profitable in the world, according to the government of India's 2019 National Air Cargo Policy Overview. RCS, or Regional Connectivity Scheme, is now being implemented. The government's numerous improvements stimulated significant economic growth. Hence In 2019 under the RCS-Udan initiative, 33 airports were served by 335 routes, carrying around 34,74,000 passengers (20 unserved, 3 underserved, 10 water aerodromes). There has been a lot of work done to increase the promotion of the environment. As a result, 55 IAA airports have been reported as having single-use plastic-free airport terminals as of October 2019. By December 2019, it was anticipated that India would have the most aircraft operating on its scheduled airlines [314].

The following are a few of the government's important projects:

- As of October 18, 2021, no capacity restrictions will apply to airlines operating domestic flights, according to the Ministry of Civil Aviation (MoCA).
- Under the RCS-UDAN (Regional Connectivity Scheme - Ude Desh Ka Aam Naagrik) programme, the Union Minister of Civil Aviation, Mr. Jyotiraditya M. Scindia, essentially signalled the start of the first direct flight between Shillong and Dibrugarh in October 2021.
- The Krishi UDAN 2.0 programme was introduced by the Ministry of Civil Aviation in October 2021. The plan calls for financial support and incentives for moving agricultural goods by air. It is anticipated that farmers, freight forwarders, and

airlines will gain from the Krishi UDAN 2.0, which will be implemented at 53 airports across the nation with a concentration mostly on the Northeast and tribal areas.

- On October 20, 2021, Uttar Pradesh's Kushinagar International Airport was officially opened by Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi. The international airport is likely to meet the needs of foreign Buddhist pilgrims visiting India for air travel.
- The government intends to introduce a biometric boarding system utilising facial recognition technology in six airports, including Bengaluru, Hyderabad, and Pune, in August 2021. Currently, the project is at the testing stage. With effect from July 5, 2021, the Ministry of Civil Aviation (MoCA) increased the capacity of domestic flights to 65% from 50%.
- The Ministry of Civil Aviation (MoCA) is optimistic that soon, prospective commercial pilots will be able to receive training in India without having to travel outside of the nation. Regarding this, the government announced in July 2021 that eight new flying academies will be established at the following five airports: Belagavi and Kalaburagi in Karnataka, Jalgaon in Maharashtra, Khajuraho in Madhya Pradesh, and Lilabari in Assam.
- In March 2021, the Ministry of Civil Aviation (MoCA) proposed 392 routes under the UDAN 4.1 bidding process in response to the launch of the "Azadi Ka Amrit Mahotsav (India@75)" by the Government of India. • On May 8, 2021, AAI began commercial operations at Rupsi airport—Northeast India's 15th airport and Assam's 7th airport.
- To encourage MRO companies to establish facilities at its airports, the Airport Authority of India proposes to remove royalty and grant significant leasing rent concessions.
- After Prime Minister Narendra Modi successfully launched seaplane service between the Statue of Unity at Kevadiya in Gujarat's Narmada district and Sabarmati Riverfront in Ahmedabad in October 2020, the government plans to open 14 other water aerodromes throughout the nation.
- The government reduced the customs duty on components or parts, including engines, used in the production of aircraft by public sector entities of the Ministry of Defence from 2.5 percent to 0 percent under Union Budget 2021–22.
- In accordance with Operation Green Scheme, the Indian government enlarged the reach of "Krishi Udaan" under the Union Budget 2021–22. As a result, the North

East states and four Himalayan states/UTs will receive a 50% air freight subsidy for perishable agricultural goods. The "Krishi Udaan" programme will benefit from the extension of product coverage, which will also enhance air cargo traffic from these states.

- A programme called Regional Connectivity Scheme (RCS) has been introduced.
- Jyotiraditya M. Scindia, Minister of Civil Aviation, requests collaboration between the Central and State Governments to construct 16 new airports in Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan, and Maharashtra in order to better carry out the PM-Gati Shakti vision [314].

The Indian aviation business has a lengthy history and has transitioned from private to public ownership before returning to a mix of public and private ownership. As time has gone on, the transportation industry has seen a substantial improvement in the movement of traffic, both in the passenger and freight segments. Hence, this chapter described the overview of aviation industry in the Indian context by discussing the history of aviation industry. Furthermore, two major international airports of India have been discussed as it is pertaining to the study. Various domestic airline company profiles along with employee benefits of these companies also have been described in this chapter.

CHAPTER-VI

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION AND QUANTITATIVE ABCD ANALYSIS

6.1 DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

6.1.1 INTRODUCTION

Chapter four presents the results of the study obtained from the quantitative survey, which are in accordance with the research design and methodology described in previous chapters.

This chapter includes four sections. The first section presents the percentage analysis. Followed by descriptive analysis by applying simple mean and standard deviation, which is the second section. The third section presents testing of hypotheses using statistical tools namely, independent sample t-test, One-way Anova, Correlation, simple regression, simple regression (multi-group and multiple regression analysis. Fourth section is a causal model, in which hypotheses testing has been tested by using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). Path analysis were analyzed using correlation and Regression Analysis using Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS) software. Results are represented in tabular and figurative forms. Standard Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24.0 software was used for analyzing the data. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) using AMOS version 21.0 was used.

6.1.2 PERSONAL AND JOB PROFILE

Table 6.1: Age Profile of the Respondents

Age (in Years)	Number of Respondent	Percentage
20 and below	2	1.0
21 to 29	102	50.7
31 to 39	75	37.3
40 and above	22	10.9
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Age of the respondents table depicts that most of the Cabin crews belong to the age category of 21-29 years (50.7%). There are 37.3% of the cabin crew who belong to the age category of 31-39 years and against the 10.9% of 40 and above age. Remaining 1% cabin crew belong to the age group of 20 and below.

Table 6.2: Gender Wise Distribution of the Respondents

Gender	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Male	35	17.4
Female	166	82.6
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Gender of the respondents depicts that for the purpose of study 82.6% of female population is taken into consideration against 17.4% of male respondents. It may be due to the demography of the job and may be more Cabin crew is dominated by women.

Table 6.3: Marital Status of the of the Respondents

Marital Status	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Married	46	22.9
Unmarried	155	77.1
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Marital status of the respondents reveals that most (77.1%) of the crew members are unmarried and 22.9% of the crew members are married. It may be due to the tendency of preferring a cabin crew job as a bachelor or bachelorette.

Table 6.4: Position wise distribution of the of the Respondents

Position	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Cabin Service Director	6	3.0
Inflight Managers	46	22.9
Senior Cabin Crew	82	40.8
Junior Cabin Crew	55	27.4
Trainers	12	6.0
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Present table depicts the various position held by the crew members. Out of the total respondents 40.8% of respondents are in the senior crew position against the 27.4% of Junior crew members. The percentage of Inflight managers position is 22.9%. There are 6% of the respondents with the position of trainers and 3% of the respondents with the position of cabin service director.

Table 6.5: Experience wise distribution of the of the Respondents

Experience	Number of Respondent	Percentage
0 to 1 Years	16	8.0
1 to 3 Years	72	35.8
3 to 6 Years	48	23.9
6 to 9 Years	32	15.9
9 to 12 Years	13	6.5
12 to 15 Years	16	8.0
Above 15 Years	4	2.0
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

As far as number of years of experience of the respondents are considered, most (35.8%) of the respondents are having the experience of 1 to 3 years as the cabin crew/flight attendant. Cabin crew/flight attendant with the experience of 3 to 6 years are 23.9% whereas there are 15.9% of respondent with 6 to 9 years of working experience. Percentage of respondents with less than 1 years of experience and 12 to 15 years of working experience are same in number i.e., 8%. Even there are 6.5% of respondents with the working experience of 9 to 12 years against 2% of above 15 years experienced.

Table 6.6: Changes in Lifestyle of the of the Respondents

Experience	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Took time away from social life	21	10.4
Difficulties following regular workout routine	35	17.4
The frequent crossing of the time zones and diet	60	29.9
Took now more time to take care of myself	22	10.9
Spending longer periods of time away from home	33	16.4
Need More Exercise, healthier diet and need more time to sleep	9	4.5
Less time to exercise and harder to follow a diet	14	7.0
Changed Sleeping Habits	6	3.0
Hard work come early morning late in the evening	1	.5
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Current table depicts the changes in lifestyle of the respondents after they joined as the crew members. For 29.9% of the respondents said that, the frequent crossing of the time zones is a difficult task as far as work is considered. For 17.4% of the respondents, it is the difficulties following regular workout routine where as 16.4% of respondents feels like it is spending longer periods of time away from home which is affecting their life. Percentage of respondents those who responded took time away from social life, less time to exercise and harder to follow and need more exercise, healthier diet and need, changed sleeping habits and hard work come early morning late in the evening are 10.4%, 7%, 4.5%, 3% and 0.5% respectively.

Table 6.7: Maximum Number of Consecutive Days of Work

Day work	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Up to 6 days	77	38.3
7 days or more	124	61.7
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Present table depicts that number of consecutive days of work. It is recorded that more than 60% of respondents (approximately 61.7%) work more than 7 days consecutively. Whereas 38.3% of the respondents said that they will have up to 6 days of consecutive work.

Table 6.8: Maximum Number of Consecutive Nights of Work

Night work	Number of Respondent	Percentage
One or two Nights	49	24.4
Three or Four Nights	79	39.3
Five Nights or more	73	36.3
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Present table depicts that no. of consecutive days of work. It is recorded that most the respondents (39.3%) work for three or four night continuously against 36.3% of respondents with five nights or more work on a continues basis. Whereas 24.4% of the said that they will have one or two consecutive nights of work. More numbers of days of continuous night shift might impact the lifestyle of the crew members adversely.

Table 6.9: Average Days off Per Month

Night work	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Less than 5 days	29	14.4
5-10 days	94	46.8
10 days or more	78	38.8
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table depicts that 46.8 % of respondents tends to get 5-10 days of off per month on an average. Even there 38.8% of the crew members they get an average days off of 10 or more days per month against 14.4% those who get less than 5 days off per month. Days off will have an positive impact on the work life of the employee's if they get enough number of days off.

6.1.3 AGREEMENT LEVEL OF CABIN CREW ON STRESSORS AGENT FACTORS

6.1.3.1 Irregular Working Hours

Respondents were asked to respond with their agreement level starting from strongly agree to strongly disagree on five scale rating. It is clear that most of the (39.3%) respondents responded with “strongly disagree” for the question related to job events are clearly predictable, they are not subject to last-minute deadlines. It is clear that most of the (51.7%) respondents responded with “disagree” for the question about not spending long time at work and that outside relationships are not suffering due to their work. For the question about ‘Working for long day makes me fatigued/exhausted during the flight’ most of the (49.3%) respondents responded to be neutral. It is evident from the table that Most of the (36.3 %) respondents responded with “disagree” for the question about ‘they don’t feel that night flights or a series of night flights are serious contributors to fatigue’. As far as series of early morning departures as not problematic and not contributing to fatigue is considered 32.3% respondents disagreed for the statement and even agreement level goes same for not feeling the need for recovery after work with 36.3%. As far as getting sufficient sleep after the work is considered most of the people are insomniac as 31.3% of the responded with a “disagree” response. Most (34.3%) of the people disagree related to “reported unfit for duty due to fatigue/exhaustion and not making a mistake in the flight due to fatigue/exhaustion disagreement percentage was also 32.8%. For the statement “I have not remarked (out loud or to myself) about how tired I was, but proceeded to go on the flight anyway” most (36.3%) of the respondents responded with disagree option as the matter of getting enough time to rest due to long working hours is considered 31.3% of respondents disagreed for the statement and against of disagreement of 33.3% respondents about Airlines policies have not caused them extra time/pressure to complete job.

6.1.3.2 Work Hassles

Respondents were asked to respond with their agreement level starting from strongly agree to strongly disagree on five scale rating. It is clear that most of the (35.3%) respondents strongly agree for the question related to caused stress related to communication issue with pilot during the flight. As far as statement related stress due to flight communication with the passengers most (48.3%) of the respondents agreed the statement. As far stress due to the unacceptable behaviours (smoking when

prohibited or Drunk passengers) of passengers (45.3%) of the respondents prefers to be neutral; agreement level goes same for work pressure due to difference in work standard and actual operation with 33.8%. For the statement related to stress due to not able to take planned vacation due to irregular most the responded opted to choose agree with 31.3%. When the statement was posed like “Due to different cultures there is presence of poor work cohesion among cabin crew and this hassle makes me stressed during a flight” most of the respondent agreed with the statement with 31.8% of response. Even most (31.8%) of crew members prefers to be neutral about unexpected emergency on a flight, and whenever there is a trouble in managing this situation and that makes the crew member feel exhausted. Most (32.3%) of the crew members agree for the statement related stress during the flight due poor work cohesion between cockpit crew and cabin crew affects flight safety and even agreement level goes same for the stress due to antisocial behaviour in the flight with 33.8% of agreement. It may be due to a smaller number of such kind of incidents. Stress due to verbal and physical violence by the passengers toward the cabin crew most the respondents prefer to be neutral with 30.3% of response. As far as stress due to verbal threats to other passengers most of the respondents agreed the statement with a disagreement percentage of 33.3% and respondents are neutral about stress due to disobeying the instructions of crew by passengers with 37.3% of highest response. As far as negative impact of job on the health of the respondents most (31.8%) of the respondents agree with the statement. As far as hassles due to jet lag and its effect on sleeping pattern is considered there are 32.8% each respondents who belong to neutral and agree response category.

6.1.3.3 Aircraft Cabin Environments

Agreement level of the respondents towards Aircraft Cabin Environments. Respondents were asked to respond with their agreement level starting from strongly agree to strongly disagree on five scale rating. It is clear that most (36.8%) of the respondents responded with “agree” for the statement related to bothering due to flight delays and being hurt by disruptive passengers. Stressed due to the scheduling and rostering 34.8% of respondents prefers to be neutral and even for being anxious regarding pre-flight checks most (36.3%) of the respondents prefer to be neutral along with stressed over work load/time pressure/deadlines with neutral percentage of 34.8%. For the statement related to interpersonal problems with other cabin crew/ flight crew is considered most (48.8%) of the respondents preferred to agree with whopping percentage of 38.8 even

33.3% of responded preferred to say “agree” for statement related to lack of opportunities and potential advancement in the job. As far there is lack of encouragement and support by the management and superiors is considered most (34.8%) of the respondents opted to be neutral. It is evident from the table that Most of the (33.8%) respondents responded with “agree” for the question about monotonous work involving underutilization of skills. It is clear that even 35.8% of responded preferred to say “neutral” about irregular flight duty timings. For the statement about ‘experience variability in work load and uneven distribution of work among the cabin crews’ most of the of the respondents responded to say “agree” i.e., 32.8%. As far experienced kind of harassment by passengers or the crew either sexual/nonsexual such as looking/touching/comments etc. during flights is considered most of the (34.3%) preferred opted to be neutral and Even 36.3% of responded preferred to say “neutral” about potential for general transmission of infections during flights is concerned. Headache due to Aircraft cabin pressure most (36.3%) of the cabin crew member agree with the statement.

6.1.3.4 Social Isolation

Section 6 reflects about Social Isolation and agreement level of the respondents towards Social Isolation. Respondents were asked to respond with their agreement level starting from strongly agree to strongly disagree on five scale rating.

As far as statement related to responsibilities have impacted on my personal, family, and social lives considered most (36.8%) of the respondents opted to be neutral and it is evident from the table that Most (33.3 %) of the respondents responded with “agree” for the question about ‘job has an adverse influence on my family and social life’. However, most of the respondents i.e., 36.8% preferred to stay “neutral” about work time interferes with family and social life with an agreement percentage of 29.9%. As far as not seems to have enough time for family or friends due to wide range of activities in work most (31.8%) preferred to stay neutral again. However, experience in managing a balance with Work-Rest-Social life is considered there are 30.3% each respondent who prefer to opt neutral and agree response in both options. Agreement level about no time for many interests/hobbies outside of work 37.8 % of crew members were neutral. Time to attend family function after joining this job is considered most of (31.3%) respondents agreed for the statement.

As far as statement related to ‘family members often say that, I do not have time to be with them whenever it is required’ is considered most of the (30.3%) of the respondents preferred opted to be neutral and Even 34.3% of responded preferred to say “neutral” want to spend some time with family members/friends but due to this work and not able to spare.

6.1.4 AGREEMENT LEVEL OF CABIN CREWS ON WORKPLACE STRESS AND WORK ENGAGEMENT

6.1.4.1 The Workplace Stress Scale

Respondents were asked to respond with their agreement level starting from strongly agree to strongly disagree on five scale rating.

It is clear that most (33.3%) of the respondents agree that Conditions at work are unpleasant or sometimes even unsafe. As far as statement related to job is negatively affecting physical or emotional well-being is considered most (37.8%) of the respondents preferred to say agree and it is a negative remark about job. Even 61.2% of crew member agree that too much work to do and/or too many unreasonable deadlines is the tendency during the work time. For the statement related to it difficult to express my opinions or feelings about my job conditions to my superiors most (41.8%) of the respondents are neutral. As far as statement related to job pressures interfere with my family or personal life is considered most (32.3%) of the respondents preferred to say agree. Even for the statement related to have adequate control or input over work duties most (36.8%) of the respondents also preferred to say agree along with a highest agree response for receiving appropriate recognition or rewards for good performance.

It the stated fact that most (37.3%) of the respondents strongly agree that they are able to utilize my skills and talents to the fullest extent at work along with 32.3% who said “agree”.

6.1.4.2 Work Engagement

Respondents were asked to respond with their agreement level starting from strongly agree to strongly disagree on five scale rating. It is clear that most (49.8%) of the respondents responded with “agree” for the question related to job has caused them to become burnt out. As far as statement related to working making them emotionally

exhausted is considered most (48.8%) of the respondents preferred opted to be neutral and Even 33.8% of responded preferred to say “neutral” for getting up in the morning and facing another day at work, feeling exhausted statement. For the statement about ‘Working all day is quite exhausting for me’ most (27.4%) of the respondents responded to say “disagree”. It is evident from the table that Most (33.3%) of the respondents responded with “agree” for the question about ‘After joining this job, I have lost interest in my career’. As far as not as enthused about my job as respondent is used to be is considered 37.3% respondents agreed for the statement. Agreement level for bosses are frequently willing to listen to my work-related issues with 36.8 % was neutral along with statement “My co-workers assist and support me” with 31.8%. As far as co-workers are frequently willing to listen to concerns about work is considered most (36.8%) of the people are neutral. For the statement job demands me to be self-motivated, I can learn new things at work, and I can put my personal abilities or knowledge to use 30.8% of the responded with a “agree” response. Most (33.3%) of the people said agree related to “have experienced derogatory public view of my profession. For the statement related to stress due to chief flight attendant most of (34.3%) of the respondents are neutral.

6.1.5 EMOTIONAL LABOUR

Table 6.10: Emotional Labour Factors (A)

Emotional Factors	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Put on an act in order to deal with passengers in an appropriate way	31	15.4
Fake a good mood when interacting with passengers	71	35.3
Put on a “show” or “performance” when interacting with passengers	75	37.3
Just pretend to have the emotions you need to display for your job	24	11.9
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 6.10 depicts that When doing job as a member of cabin crew, 37.3% of respondents feel that they Put on a “show” or “performance” when interacting with passengers against 35.3% those who Fake a good mood when interacting with passengers. However, there is 15.4% of crew member who said they Put on an act in order to deal with passengers in an appropriate way along with 11.9% of crew member who Just pretend to have the emotions you need to display for your job.

Table 6.11: Emotional Labour Factors (B)

Emotional Factors	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Try to actually experience the emotions I must show to passengers	82	40.8
Work hard to feel the emotions that, I need to show to passengers	82	40.8
Make an effort to actually feel the emotions that I need to display towards passengers	37	18.4
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 6.11 depicts that when doing job as a member of cabin crew 40.8% of respondents Try to actually experience the emotions, they must show to passengers against 40.8 % those who Work hard to feel the emotions that they need to show to passengers. However, there is 18.4% of crew member who said they Make an effort to actually feel the emotions that needed to display towards passengers.

Table 6.12: Emotional Labour Factors (C)

Emotional Factors	Number of Respondent	Percentage
I look sincere when dealing with passengers	65	32.3
Show friendliness and warmth to most passenger	40	19.9
The passengers seem to like interacting with me	96	47.8
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 6.12 depicts that when doing job as a member of cabin crew 47.8% of respondents said that the passengers seem to like interacting with me even there are 32.3% who said look sincere when dealing with passengers. As far crew members those Show friendliness and warmth to most passenger respondents is considered their percentage 19.9%.

Table 6.13: Emotional Labour Factors (D)

Emotional Factors	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Feel exhausted at my job	22	10.9
Feel run down	48	23.9
Feel tired	64	31.8
Feel wiped out	67	33.3
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 6.13 depicts that When doing job as a member of cabin crew 32.3% of crew members responded that Feel wiped out. against 31.8% those who said feel tired. Even 23.9% of respondents who said feel run down along with 10.9% who said they feel exhausted at job. Working as a crew member in the flight has its own adversity.

Table 6.14: Emotional Labour Factors (E)

Emotional Factors	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Adequately complete all duties assigned to me	104	51.7
Feel that my overall performance is better than that of your colleagues	47	23.4
Perform tasks and roles that are expected of me	50	24.9
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 6.14 shows When doing job as a member of cabin crew most (51.7%) of the crew member said that they Adequately complete all duties assigned to them. Even there are 23.4% of respondents who said Feel Adequately complete all duties assigned against those 24.9% who responded with Perform tasks and roles that are expected.

Table 6.15: Emotional Labour Factors (F)

Emotional Factors	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Have to do things that should be done	66	32.8
Have to work under vague directives	7	3.5
Receive an assignment without the manpower to complete it	43	21.4
Receive incompatible requests from two	19	9.5
Work under incompatible policies and guidelines	66	32.8
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Above table 6.15 depicts that When doing my job as a member of the cabin crew 32.8% crew member feel that they Work under incompatible policies and guidelines along 32.8% of crew member who said have to do things that should be done. There are 21.4% of respondents who preferred to say Receive an assignment without the map. Even there are 9.5% of crew member who said Receive incompatible requests from two against 3.5% who said have to work under vague directives.

Table 6.16: Emotional Situational and Problems

Particulars	Yes		No	
	F	%	F	%
During a flight, I cannot show my personal problems and sometimes have to give false smile	120	59.7	81	40.3
During a flight I hide my true feelings about a situation	98	48.8	103	51.2
During a flight in certain situations, I Remain calm even when I am astonished	103	51.2	98	48.8
During a flight I try to hide my fear even when someone who appears threatening	93	46.3	108	53.7

Source: Survey Data

From the above table 6.16 it is clear that 59.7% crew members said yes about the question related during a flight, they cannot show their personal problems and sometimes have to give false smile against 40.3% they said no. 51.2% of respondents are not able hide their true feelings during the flight against 48.8% of respondents those who can. Faking the emotions might be a difficult task to do for any member. 51.2% of crew members are able to remain calm even when I am astonished during the flight against 48.8% those who cannot. 53.7% of respondents are not able to hide fear when someone who appears threatening and 46.3% of respondents are able to hide.

6.1.6 STRESS COPING RESOURCES INVENTORY: A SELF ASSESSMENT

Table 6.17: Provides Appropriate/Measures to Relieve Work Stress

Particulars	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Yes	109	54.2
No	92	45.8
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 6.17 shows that 54.2% of crew member said that company provides appropriate/ any measures to help you relieve your work stress.

Table 6.18: Organization/Industry ever invested effort in development and implementation of new stress management strategies

Particulars	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Lot of effort	60	29.9
Not enough effort	100	49.8
Not putting any effort	41	20.4
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 6.18 shows that effort of Organization/Industry ever invested effort in development and implementation of new stress management strategies. 49.8% of respondents said that not enough has put against 29.9% of who said lot of effort has been initiated by Organization/Industry ever invested effort in development and implementation of new stress management strategies. There are 20.4% crew member they feels that origination is not putting any efforts in development and implementation of new stress management strategies.

Table 6.19: History of Coping Well with Highly Stressful Situations

Particulars	Number of Respondent	Percentage
To a very great extent	58	28.9
To a great extent	83	41.3
To a little extent	39	19.4
To a very little extent	21	10.5
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

From the table 6.19 it is clear that 41.3% of respondents believe that they have a history of coping well with highly stressful situations to a great extent against 28.9% who are able to cope to a great extent. There 19.4% of respondents who said that they believe that they have a history of coping well with highly stressful situations to a little extent against the 10.5% who said to be a very little extent in their belief about coping with stress.

Table 6.20: Exaggerating importance of bad situations

Particulars	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Very unlikely	38	18.9
Unlikely	70	34.8
Likely	56	27.9
Very likely	37	18.4
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 6.20 shows that when something bad happens 34.8% of crew member are unlikely exaggerate its importance as compared to 27.9% who are likely to exaggerate. Even there are 18.9% of crew member who are very unlikely exaggerate its importance as compared to 18.4% who are very likely to exaggerate when something bad happens.

Table 6.21: Decision-making power in the family

Particulars	Number of Respondent	Percentage
More power than any other member of my family	36	17.9
As much power as any other member of my family	86	42.8
Less power than most members of my family	52	25.9
Less power than any other member of my family	27	13.4
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 6.21 shows that for 42.8% of have as much as any other member in the family while making any decision as compared to 25.9% of crew member who have less power than most of family members. There are 17.9% of crew members who have more power than any other member in making decision against 13.4% who have less power than any other member.

Table 6.22: Decision-making power in your working environment

Particulars	Number of Respondent	Percentage
More power than most members of my family	47	23.4
As much power as any other member of my family	90	44.8
Less power than most members of my family	46	22.9
Less power than any other member of my family	18	9.0
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 6.22 shows that for 44.8 % of have as much as any other member in the working environment while making any decision as compared to 22.9% of crew member who have less power than most of members. There are 23.4% of crew members who have more power than any other member in making decision against 9.0% who have less power than any other member.

Table 6.23: Likeliness of seeing others as threatening, uncooperative, or exploitative

Particular	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Highly unlikely	32	15.9
Unlikely	78	38.8
Likely	63	31.3
Highly likely	28	13.9
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

Table 6.23 shows that 38.8% of crew members are unlikely to see others as threatening, uncooperative, or exploitative against 31.3% crew member who said that they are likely to see others as threatening, uncooperative, or exploitative. However, there are 15.9% of crew members are highly unlikely to see others as threatening, uncooperative, or exploitative against 13.9% crew member who said that they are highly likely to see others as threatening, uncooperative, or exploitative.

Table 6.24: Extent of belief in the purposeful life

Particular	Number of Respondent	Percentage
To a very great extent	36	17.9
To some extent	76	37.8
To little extent	57	28.4
To very little extent	32	15.9
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

From the above table 6.24 it is evident that 37.8% of crew members to some extent believe that their life has purpose as compared to 28.4% of who said that they believe to a little extent. Even there are 17.9% crew members they believe that their life has purpose to a greater extent as compared to 15.9% those who believe to very little extent.

Table 6.25: Level of Contact with Spiritual Community

Particular	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Very much	41	20.4
Much	83	41.3
Very little	62	30.8
None	15	7.5
Total	201	100.0

Source: Survey Data

From the table 6.25 it is clear that 41.3% of the crew members are in much touch with spiritual community as compared to 30.8% of crew members who have very little touch. Even there are 20.4% crew members they are in very much touch 7.5% those who are not in touch with spiritual community.

6.1.7 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS ON STRESSOR AGENT FACTORS, WORKPLACE STRESS AND WORK ENGAGEMENT

Table 6.26: Descriptive Statistics on Irregular Working Hours

Irregular Working Hours	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
My job events are clearly predictable, they are not subject to last-minute deadlines	1.00	5.00	2.1592	1.23066
I don't feel that I spend so long at work that my outside relationships are suffering.	1.00	5.00	2.6418	.98033
Working for long day makes me fatigued/exhausted during the flight	1.00	5.00	3.1592	.98210
I don't feel that night flights or a series of night flights are serious contributors to fatigue	1.00	5.00	2.6517	1.09914
I don't feel that a series of early morning departures as problematic and contributing to fatigue	1.00	5.00	2.3781	1.23544
I usually don't feel the need for recovery after work	1.00	5.00	2.6219	1.21915
I get sufficient sleep time after my work	1.00	5.00	2.6567	1.14742
Many times, I have reported unfit for duty due to fatigue/exhaustion	1.00	5.00	2.5373	1.09538
I have not made any mistake in the flight due to fatigue/exhaustion	1.00	5.00	2.4527	1.07192
I have not remarked (out loud or to myself) about how tired I was, but proceeded to go on the flight anyway.	1.00	5.00	2.4975	1.10961
I get enough time to rest due to long working hours	1.00	5.00	2.5721	1.16877
My Airlines policies have not caused me extra time/pressure to complete my job	1.00	5.00	2.5871	1.17628
Overall			2.576275	1.12635

The above table 6.26 illustrated the descriptive statistics on irregular working hours. Irregular working hour was measured using 12 indicators, in which mean values ranged between 2.1592 to 3.1592. Out of 12 indicators, majority of the indicators found to be above average indicating the respondents' agreement level on the above-mentioned statements. Working for long day causes fatigue and exhaustion during the flight was highly agreed statement by the respondents with the mean value of 3.1592; the least agreed statement was lack of job prediction and last-minute deadlines as it indicates the lowest mean value of 2.1592. Overall, the agreement level on irregular working hours shows the mean and S.D as 2.57627 ± 1.12635 .

Table 6.27: Descriptive Statistics on Work Hassles

Work Hassles	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
Most of the times during a flight, communication issues with Pilots has caused me stress	1.00	5.00	2.1891	1.14196
Most of the times during a flight communication issues with the passengers has caused me stress	1.00	5.00	2.6219	.94674
Most of the times unacceptable behaviours (smoking when prohibited or Drunk passengers) of passengers have caused me stress during a flight	1.00	5.00	3.1045	.97161
The presence of gap between works standards and practical operations in a flight makes me feel stressed	1.00	5.00	2.7015	1.18341
When I cannot take a vacation during the planned dates due to irregular work schedule I feel stressed	1.00	5.00	2.6517	1.18664
Due to different cultures there is presence of poor work cohesion among cabin crew and this hassle makes me stressed during a flight	1.00	5.00	2.5622	1.13020
When there is an unexpected emergency on a flight, and when there is trouble in managing this situation, it makes me exhausted	1.00	5.00	2.5224	1.10487
Most often during flying, poor work cohesion between cockpit crew and cabin crew affects flight safety and this makes me stressed	1.00	5.00	2.5771	1.13810
Most of the time antisocial behaviour of passengers cases me stress	1.00	5.00	2.6468	1.15741
During a flight verbal and physical violence by the passengers toward the cabin crew makes me stressed	1.00	5.00	2.6468	1.15741
During a flight verbal threats to other passengers make me feel stressed	1.00	5.00	2.6965	1.11912
During a flight disobeying the instructions of crew by passengers makes me stressed	1.00	5.00	2.7065	1.06227
I have many health problems due to this job. This work has had a negative impact on my body and caused hassles in my life.	1.00	5.00	2.5373	1.14885
Sometimes I suffer from jet lag problems which affects my sleep and it's a hassle for my work	1.00	5.00	2.6617	1.08396
Overall			2.630429	1.109468

The above table 6.27 depicted the descriptive statistics on work hassles. The construct “work hassles” was measured using 14 indicators, in which the mean values ranged between 2.1891 to 3.1045. Out of 14 indicators, majority of the indicators found to be above average indicating the respondents’ agreement level on the above mentioned statements. As per the descriptive statistics, the statement on “unacceptable behaviours of passengers” (M=3.1045), “disobeying the instructions of crew by passengers” (M=2.7065), “the presence of gap between works standards and practical operations in a flight” (M=2.7015) makes them feel stressed was agreed to the highest extent, as the mean values in these cases found to be higher compared to other indicators. Communication issues with Pilots being a cause of stress was a least agreed statement, as the mean value in this case is 2.1891. Overall, the agreement level on work hassles shows the mean and S.D as 2.630429±1.109468.

Table 6.28: Descriptive Statistics on Aircraft Cabin Environments

Aircraft Cabin Environments	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
Flight delays bother me and due to this delay disruptive passengers have hurt me emotionally	1.00	5.00	2.4527	1.08582
I get stressed due to the scheduling and rostering	1.00	5.00	3.0199	.96933
I face anxiety regarding pre-flight checks	1.00	5.00	3.2836	1.02673
I get stressed over work load/time pressure/ deadlines	1.00	5.00	3.0199	1.02937
I often face interpersonal problems with other cabin crew/ flight crew	1.00	5.00	2.6318	1.08341
I feel there is a lack of opportunities and potential advancement in this job	1.00	5.00	2.6517	1.09000
I feel that there is lack of encouragement and support by the management and superiors	1.00	5.00	2.7512	1.02850
I often find monotonous work involving underutilization of skills	1.00	5.00	2.8706	1.09233
I experience irregular flight duty timings	1.00	5.00	2.9204	1.05054
I experience variability in work load and uneven distribution of work among the cabin crews	1.00	5.00	2.8060	1.11228
I have experienced kind of harassment by passengers or the crew either sexual/nonsexual such as looking/ touching/comments etc. during flights	1.00	5.00	2.7164	1.05080
Aircraft cabin pressure causes me headache	1.00	5.00	2.7711	1.04755
There is potential for general transmission of infections during flights for which I am concerned	1.00	5.00	2.9055	1.04691
Overall			2.830831	1.05489

The above table 6.28 demonstrated the descriptive statistics on aircraft cabin environment. The construct “aircraft cabin environment” was measured using 13 indicators, in which the mean values ranged between 2.4527 to 3.2836. Out of 13 indicators, majority of the indicators found to be above average indicating the respondents’ agreement level on the above mentioned statements. As per the descriptive

statistics, the statement on “anxiety regarding pre-flight checks” (M=3.2836), “stressed due to the scheduling and rostering” (M=3.0199), “work load/time pressure/deadlines” (M=3.0199), irregular flight duty timings (M=2.9204) was agreed to the highest extent, as the mean values in these cases found to be higher compared to other indicators. “Due to delay disruptive passengers have hurt me emotionally” was the least agreed statement, as the mean value in this case is 2.4527. Overall, the agreement level on aircraft cabin environment shows the mean and S.D as 2.830831±1.05489.

Table 6.29: Descriptive Statistics on Social Isolation

Social Isolation	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
Work responsibilities have impacted on my personal, family, and social lives.	1.00	5.00	2.5075	1.14943
My job has an adverse influence on my family and social life.	1.00	5.00	2.9950	.94073
My work time interferes with my family and social life.	1.00	5.00	3.4677	1.02966
I don't seem to have enough time for my family or friends. My work includes a wide range of activities.	1.00	5.00	3.0448	1.11937
I have experienced managing a balance with my Work-Rest-Social life	1.00	5.00	2.6368	1.14124
I find that I don't have time for many interests/hobbies outside of work.	1.00	5.00	2.6468	1.09069
I find that after joining this job I don't have time to attend any family functions.	1.00	5.00	2.9154	1.15231
My family members often say that, I do not have time to be with them whenever it is required	1.00	5.00	2.9104	1.14976
I always feel that I want to spend some time with my family members/friends but due to this work I am not able to do it	1.00	5.00	2.8856	1.13659
Overall			2.89	1.101087

The above table 6.29 showed the descriptive statistics on social isolation. The construct “social isolation” was measured using 9 indicators, in which the mean values ranged between 2.5075 to 3.4677. Out of 9 indicators, majority of the indicators found to be above average indicating the respondents’ agreement level on the above mentioned statements. As per the descriptive statistics, the statement on “interference of work time with family and social life” (M=3.4677), “no time for family and friends due to wide range of work activities” (M=3.0448), “adverse impact of job on their family and social life” (M=2.9950), no time for family functions (M=2.9154) was agreed to the highest extent, as the mean values in these cases found to be higher compared to other indicators. Overall, the agreement level on social isolation shows the mean and S.D as 2.89±1.101087.

Table 6.30: Descriptive Statistics on Workplace Stress

Workplace Stress	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
Conditions at work are unpleasant or sometimes even unsafe.	1.00	5.00	2.8109	1.25860
I feel that my job is negatively affecting my physical or emotional well-being.	1.00	5.00	2.8856	1.25373
I have too much work to do and/or too many unreasonable deadlines.	1.00	5.00	2.7512	1.48587
I find it difficult to express my opinions or feelings about my job conditions to my superiors.	1.00	5.00	2.8259	1.26670
I feel that job pressures interfere with my family or personal life.	1.00	5.00	3.0448	1.06442
I have adequate control or input over my work duties.	1.00	5.00	2.6368	1.23387
I receive appropriate recognition or rewards for good performance.	1.00	5.00	2.7761	1.42289
I am able to utilize my skills and talents to the fullest extent at work.	1.00	5.00	2.6219	1.40225
Overall			2.79415	1.298541

The above table 6.30 presented the descriptive statistics on Workplace Stress. The construct “Workplace Stress” was measured using 8 indicators, in which the mean values ranged between 2.6219 to 3.0448. Out of 8 indicators, majority of the indicators found to be above average indicating the respondents’ agreement level on the above mentioned statements. As per the descriptive statistics, the statement on interference of job pressures with their family or personal life (M=3.0448), negative effect of job on their physical or emotional well-being (M=2.8856), finding difficult to express their opinions or feelings about their job conditions to superiors (M=2.8259) was agreed to the highest extent, as the mean values in these cases found to be higher compared to other indicators. Overall, the agreement level on workplace stress showed the mean and S.D as 2.79415±1.298541.

Table 6.31: Descriptive Statistics on Work Engagement

Work Engagement	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
My job has caused me to become burnt out.	1.00	5.00	2.2537	1.05371
My work has emotionally exhausted me.	1.00	5.00	2.7711	.84697
When I get up in the morning and have to face another day at work, I am exhausted.	1.00	5.00	3.1891	.99704
Working all day is quite exhausting for me.	1.00	5.00	3.1891	1.18915
After joining this job, I have lost interest in my career.	1.00	5.00	2.6169	1.10793
I'm not as enthused about my job as I used to be.	1.00	5.00	2.5721	1.02275
My bosses are frequently willing to listen to my work-related issues.	1.00	5.00	2.7264	1.03429
My co-workers assist and support me.	1.00	5.00	2.9950	1.10679
My co-workers are frequently willing to listen to my concerns about work.	1.00	5.00	2.9701	1.07662
My job demands me to be self-motivated. I can learn new things at work, and I can put my personal abilities or knowledge to use.	1.00	5.00	2.7413	1.13699
I have experienced derogatory public view of my profession.	1.00	5.00	2.6468	1.09982
Sometimes my chief flight attendant typically cause additional stress for me.	1.00	5.00	2.7313	1.08971
Overall			2.783575	1.063481

The table 6.31 presented the descriptive statistics on work engagement. The construct “work engagement” was measured using 12 indicators, in which the mean values ranged between 2.2537 to 3.1891. Out of 12 indicators, majority of the indicators found to be above average indicating the respondents’ agreement level on the above mentioned statements. As per the descriptive statistics, the statement on “another day at work feels exhausted” (M=3.1891), “Working all day is exhausting” (M=3.1891), “co-workers assistance and support” (M=2.9950), co-workers are willing to listen to their concerns about work. (M=2.9701) was agreed to the highest extent, as the mean values in these cases found to be higher compared to other indicators. “Job causing to burnout” was the least agreed statement, as the mean value in this case is 2.2537. Overall, the agreement level on work engagement shows the mean and S.D as 2.783575±1.063481.

Table 6.32: Descriptive Statistics on Stress Coping Resources

Stress coping resources	Min.	Max.	Mean	S.D.
I am fully aware of the practical, healthy ways of relaxing and I frequently exercise it.	1.00	5.00	3.5792	1.37358
When things are not going well, I view the situation as being temporary rather than permanent.	1.00	5.00	3.6040	1.40418
When stressed by a complex situation, I focus my attention on those aspects of the situation that I can manage.	1.00	5.00	3.2871	1.52809
When I am thoroughly frustrated, I identify an alternate goal and pursue it.	1.00	5.00	3.5644	1.43458
I control my emotions when I am stressed.	1.00	5.00	3.8416	1.19894
When an unexpected, negative event happens to me, I actively seek information about the event and cope with it.	1.00	5.00	3.7277	1.40366
When I am highly stressed, I ask my friends or relatives for help.	1.00	5.00	3.6584	1.41673
I frequently engage in spiritual practices such as prayer, meditation, or inspirational reading to enrich my interior life.	1.00	5.00	3.5842	1.43702
Overall			3.6058	.64575

The table 6.32 presented the descriptive statistics on stress coping resources. The construct “stress coping resources” was measured using 8 indicators, in which the mean values ranged between 3.2871 to 3.8416. Out of 8 indicators, majority of the indicators found to be above average indicating the respondents’ agreement level on the above mentioned statements. As per the descriptive statistics, the statement on “I control my emotions when I am stressed.” (M=3.8416), “seek information about the event and cope with it.” (M=3.7277), “I ask my friends or relatives for help” (M=3.6584), was agreed to the highest extent, as the mean values in these cases found to be higher compared to other indicators. “I focus my attention on those aspects of the situation that I can manage” was the least agreed statement, as the mean value in this case is 3.2871. Overall, the agreement level on stress coping resources shows the mean and S.D as 3.6058± .64575.

Table 6.33: Descriptive Statistics on Stressor Agent Factors, Workplace Stress, Stress Coping Resources and Work Engagement Variable

Overall Results	Mean	Std. Deviation
Irregular Working Hours	2.5763	.89294
Work Hassles	2.6304	.90092
Aircraft Cabin Environments	2.8308	.85117
Social Isolation	2.8871	.89024
The Workplace Stress Scale	2.7836	.73613
Stress Coping Resources	3.6058	.64575
Work Engagement	2.8988	.87853

The table 6.33 demonstrated the overall descriptive statistics on all the selected parameters; in which the agreement level on Irregular Working Hours (M=2.5763), Work Hassles (M=2.6304), Aircraft Cabin Environments (M=2.8308), Social Isolation (M=2.8871), The Workplace Stress Scale (M=2.7836), Stress Coping Resources (M=3.6058) and Work Engagement (M=2.8988) showed a mean values above average. Highest agreement level was shown in Work Engagement (M=2.8988), Social Isolation (M=2.8871) and Stress Coping Resources (M=2.8081) compared to other construct.

6.1.8 CORRELATION BETWEEN STRESSOR AGENT FACTORS, WORKPLACE STRESS AND WORK ENGAGEMENT

Table 6.34: Correlation Results between Stressor Agent Factors, Workplace Stress and Work Engagement

Variables	Irregular Working Hours	Work Hassles	Aircraft Cabin Environments	Social Isolation	The Workplace Stress Scale	Stress Coping Resources	Work Engagement
Irregular Working Hours	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Work Hassles	.697**	1	-	-	-	-	-
Aircraft Cabin Environments	.595**	.709**	1	-	-	-	-
Social Isolation	.600**	.684**	.698**	1	-	-	-
The Workplace Stress Scale	.620**	.694**	.585**	.578**	1	-	-
Stress Coping Resources	-.051	-.039	.023	.028	.005	1	-
Work Engagement	-.178*	-.176*	-.129	-.058	-.199**	.252**	1

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

The correlation table 6.34 demonstrated positive significant correlation between each pairs of variables which can be discussed in detail as below:

Irregular Working Hours of the cabin crews showed high degree significant positive correlation with Work Hassles ($r=.697^{**}$) compared to The Workplace Stress ($r=.620^{**}$), Social Isolation ($r=.600^{**}$) and Aircraft Cabin Environments ($r=.595^{**}$). But irregular working hour is negatively correlated with work engagement ($r= -.178^*$), indicating high irregular working hour leading to low work engagement. Considering work hassles, it showed a highest significant positive correlation with Aircraft Cabin Environments with r value of $.709^{**}$ and also showed a significant positive association with Social Isolation ($r=.684^{**}$) and The Workplace Stress Scale ($r=.694^{**}$); although, work hassles among cabin crew showed significant negative correlation with work engagement ($r=-.176^*$). Aircraft Cabin Environments is highly and significantly associated with social isolation ($r=.698^{**}$) and work place stress ($r=.585^{**}$) but it is negatively associated with work engagement ($-.129$). While Social Isolation showed high degree positive correlation with The Workplace engagement ($r=.578$) but negatively correlated with Work Engagement ($r= -.058$) which has a insignificant effect. As far as work place stress is concerned, it shows negative significant correlation with Work Engagement ($r= -.199^{**}$). Lastly Stress Coping Resources has positive significant relation with Work Engagement ($r=.252^{**}$), which demonstrates higher the stress coping resources more we will be the work engagement. Overall, it was evidenced that majority of the stressor agents, stress coping resources, workplace stress as well as work engagement variables are highly associated with each other.

6.1.9 HYPOTHESIS TESTING

H1: The Stressor Agents of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their personal factors.

H1.a: The Irregular working hours of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their personal factors.

Table 6.35: One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test results between personal factors and Irregular working hours of cabin crews

Personal Factors		Mean	SD	F	P Value
Age	20 and Below	3.5	.23570	.864	P>0.05
	21 to 29	2.5482	.91868		
	31 to 39	2.6156	.87281		
	40 and Above	2.4886	.86537		
Current function	Junior cabin crew	2.5152	.81493	3.630	P<0.01**
	Senior cabin crew	2.3720	.83140		
	Inflight managers	2.8388	.99728		
	Trainers	3.1528	.70606		
	Cabin Service Director	2.7639	1.12967		
Experience	0 to 1 Years	2.8177	1.01069	3.985	P<0.01**
	1 to 3 Years	2.4340	.80527		
	3 to 6 Years	2.4826	.80041		
	6 to 9 Years	2.3724	.80933		
	9 to 12 Years	2.7949	.80408		
	12 to 15 Years	3.1406	1.13559		
	Above 15 Years	3.9583	1.01493		
Maximum number of consecutive days of work	Up to 6 days	2.9924	.98899	5.194	P<0.01**
	7 days or more	2.3179	.71862		
Maximum number of consecutive nights of work	One or two Nights	3.0901	.95967	12.811	P<0.01**
	Three or Four Nights	2.4947	.82381		
	Five Nights or more	2.3196	.78223		
Average days off per month	Less than 5 days	3.0172	.88455	7.621	P<0.01**
	5-10 days	2.6543	.88790		
	10 days or more	2.3184	.82842		
Independent sample t-test					
Personal Factors		Mean	SD	t-value	P Value
Gender	Male	3.0452	.95771	3.515	P<0.01**
	Female	2.4774	.84911		
Marital Status	Married	2.9601	.99981	3.407	P<0.01**
	Unmarried	2.4624	.82846		

**Significance at 1% level *Significance at 5% level

Table 6.35 demonstrates the inferential statistics of irregular working hours with respect to various personal factors. The result of One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test is discussed below to assess the influence of personal factors on the irregular working hours of the cabin crews.

Age: The first section of the table exhibits mean difference in the irregular working hours among different age groups. As per the mean value, 20 and below age group showed highest level of agreement on irregular working hours (M=3.5) compared to 31 to 39 (M=2.6156) and 21 to 29 age category (M=2.5482). Although the result of one-way Anova revealed no significant difference in the perception of irregular working hours among different age groups, as the p value obtained in case of age

category is more than 0.05. Therefore, Irregular working hours of cabin crews are not significantly influenced by their age groups.

Current Function: The second section of the table presents mean difference in the irregular working hours among the current functions of cabin crews. As per the table, Trainers showed highest level of agreement on irregular working hours (M=3.1528) compared to inflight managers (M=2.8388) and Cabin Service Director (M=2.7639) followed by junior cabin crew (M=2.5152). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is evidenced that there is significant difference in the perception level of irregular working hours among various current functions, as the p value obtained in this case is less than the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, irregular working hours of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their current functions.

Experience: In the next section of the table mean difference in the irregular working hours among various year of experiences have been presented. As per the mean values, cabin crews with Above 15 Years of experience showed highest level of agreement on irregular working hours (M=3.9583) compared to 12 to 15 Years (M=3.1406) and 0 to 1 Years of experience (M=2.8177) followed by 9 to 12 Years of experience (M=2.7949). Moreover, result of one-way Anova revealed significant difference in the perception of irregular working hours among year of experience, as the p value obtained in this case is below the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, irregular working hours of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their experience.

Maximum number of consecutive days of work: The fourth section of the table demonstrates mean difference in the Maximum number of consecutive days of work with respect to irregular working hours. As per the table, the respondents having 7 days or more consecutive days of work showed highest level of agreement on irregular working hours (M=2.3179) compared to the cabin crews having Up to 6 days consecutive days of work (M=2.9924). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is witnessed that there is significant difference in the perception level of irregular working hours among Maximum number of consecutive days of work done by the cabin crews, as the p value obtained in this case is less than the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, irregular working hours of cabin crews are significantly influenced by the maximum number of consecutive days of work done by cabin crews.

Maximum number of consecutive nights of work: The next section of the table demonstrates mean difference in the maximum number of consecutive nights of work with respect to irregular working hours. As per the mean values, the respondents having one or two nights of work showed highest level of agreement on irregular working hours (M=3.0901) compared to the cabin crews having three or four nights (M=2.4947) and Five Nights or more (M=2.3196). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is witnessed that there is significant difference in the perception level of irregular working hours among maximum number of consecutive nights of work done by the cabin crews, as the p value obtained in this case is less than the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, irregular working hours of cabin crews are significantly influenced by the maximum number of consecutive nights of work done by the cabin crews.

Average days off per month: In the sixth section of the table mean difference in the irregular working hours among Average days off per month taken by cabin crews have been presented. As per the mean values, cabin crews who have taken Less than 5 days as Average days off per month showed highest agreement level on irregular working hours (M=3.0172) compared to one who have taken 5-10 days (M=2.6543) and 10 days or more as average days off per month (M=2.3184). Moreover, the result of one-way Anova revealed significant difference in the perception of irregular working hours among average days off per month, as the p value obtained in this case is below the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, irregular working hours of cabin crews are significantly influenced by the average days off per month taken by cabin crews.

Gender: The second part of table demonstrates the results of t-test for independence on irregular working hours between the genders. Considering the results, Male showed highest level of agreement on irregular working hour causing to stress as the mean value in this case is more (3.0452) compared to Female (2.4774). Result of t-test for independence shows there is significant mean difference between male and female with respect to the perception level of irregular working hours, as the p value is less than 0.01. Therefore, irregular working hour is significantly different between male and female.

Marital Status: Second section under the second part of table exhibits the results of t-test for independence on irregular working hours between the marital status. Referring to the results, married showed highest level of agreement on irregular working hour as the mean value in this case is more (2.9601) compared to unmarried (2.4624). Outcome of t-test for independence shows there is significant mean difference

between married and unmarried respondents with respect to the perception level of irregular working hours, as the p value is less than a 0.01. Therefore, irregular working hour is significantly different between the marital status.

Based on the above inferences, one can state that there is significant difference in the perception level of irregular working hours among all the personal factors of the selected cabin crews except in case of age, as the alpha value found to be below 0.01 at 99% confidence interval. Therefore, the Irregular working hours of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their personal factors. Hence, H1.a is supported.

H1.b: The Work Hassles of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their personal factors.

Table 6.36: One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test results between personal factors and work hassles of cabin crews

Personal Factors		Mean	SD	F	P Value
Age	20 and Below	4.1071	1.26269	2.390	P>0.05
	21 to 29	2.5497	.87936		
	31 to 39	2.719	.93393		
	40 and Above	2.5682	.76820		
Current function	Junior cabin crew	2.5974	.92932	2.412	P<0.05*
	Senior cabin crew	2.5026	.85135		
	Inflight managers	2.6708	.87553		
	Trainers	3.1607	1.13231		
	Cabin Service Director	3.3095	.39297		
Experience	0 to 1 Years	3.1920	1.05293	4.166	P<0.01**
	1 to 3 Years	2.4385	.77714		
	3 to 6 Years	2.7173	.86558		
	6 to 9 Years	2.3281	.85961		
	9 to 12 Years	2.6923	.84736		
	12 to 15 Years	2.9152	.90095		
	Above 15 Years	3.8750	1.33933		
Maximum number of consecutive days of work	Up to 6 days	2.9981	1.03685	4.425	P<0.01**
	7 days or more	2.4021	.71992		
Maximum number of consecutive nights of work	One or two Nights	2.8673	.95231	2.581	P>0.05
	Three or Four Nights	2.6085	.96382		
	Five Nights or more	2.4951	.76574		
Average days off per month	Less than 5 days	3.0369	.86826	7.760	P<0.01**
	5-10 days	2.7348	.90294		
	10 days or more	2.3535	.83434		
Independent sample t-test					
Personal Factors		Mean	SD	T-value	P Value
Gender	Male	3.0878	.70052	3.390	P<0.01**
	Female	2.5340	.91049		
Marital Status	Married	2.8447	.97431	1.848	P>0.05
	Unmarried	2.5668	.87116		

**Significance at 1% level

*Significance at 5% level

Table 6.36 depicts the inferential statistics of work hassles with respect to various personal factors. The result of One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test is discussed below to assess the influence of personal factors on the work hassles of the cabin crews.

Age: The first section of the table exhibits mean difference in the work hassles among different age groups. As per the mean value, 20 and below age group showed highest level of agreement on work hassles ($M=4.1071$) compared to 31 to 39 ($M=2.719$) and 40 and above age category ($M=2.5682$) followed by 21 to 29 age category ($M=2.5497$). Although the result of one-way ANOVA revealed no significant difference in the perception of work hassles among different age groups, as the p value obtained in case of age category is more than 0.05. Therefore, Work Hassles of cabin crews are not significantly influenced by their age groups.

Current Function: The second section of the table presents mean difference in the Work Hassles among the current functions of cabin crews. As per the table, Cabin Service Directors showed highest level of agreement on Work Hassles ($M=3.3095$) compared to Trainers ($M=3.1607$), In flight managers ($M=2.6708$) and Junior cabin crew ($M=2.5974$). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is evidenced that there is significant difference in the perception level of work hassles among various current functions, as the p value obtained in this case is less than the alpha value 0.05. Therefore, Work Hassles of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their current functions.

Experience: In the next section of the table mean difference in the Work Hassles among various year of experiences have been presented. As per the mean values, cabin crews with Above 15 Years of experience showed highest level of agreement on Work Hassles ($M=3.8750$) compared to 0 to 1 Years ($M=3.1920$) and 12 to 15 Years of experience ($M=2.9152$) followed by 3 to 6 Years of experience ($M=2.7173$). Moreover, result of one-way Anova revealed significant difference in the perception of Work Hassles among year of experience, as the p value obtained in this case is below the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, Work Hassles of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their experience.

Maximum number of consecutive days of work: The fourth section of the table demonstrates mean difference in the Maximum number of consecutive days of work with respect to Work Hassles. As per the table, the respondents having Up to 6 days consecutive days of work showed highest level of agreement on Work Hassles

(M=2.9981) compared to the cabin crews having 7 days or more consecutive days of work (M=2.4021). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is witnessed that there is significant difference in the perception level of Work Hassles among Maximum number of consecutive days of work done by the cabin crews, as the p value obtained in this case is less than the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, Work Hassles of cabin crews are significantly influenced by the Maximum number of consecutive days of work done by cabin crews.

Maximum number of consecutive nights of work: The next section of the table demonstrates mean difference in the Maximum number of consecutive nights of work with respect to Work Hassles. As per the mean values, the respondents having One or two Nights of work showed highest level of agreement on Work Hassles (M=2.8673) compared to the cabin crews having Three or Four Nights (M=2.6085) and Five Nights or more (M=2.4951). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is witnessed that there is no significant difference in the perception level of Work Hassles among Maximum number of consecutive nights of work done by the cabin crews, as the p value obtained in this case is more than the alpha value 0.05. Therefore, Work Hassles of cabin crews are not significantly influenced by the Maximum number of consecutive nights of work done by the cabin crews.

Average days off per month: In the sixth section of the table mean difference in the Work Hassles among Average days off per month taken by cabin crews have been presented. As per the mean values, cabin crews who have taken Less than 5 days as Average days off per month showed highest agreement level on Work Hassles (M=3.0172) compared to one who have taken 5-10 days (M=2.6543) and 10 days or more as a Average days off per month (M=2.3184). Moreover, the result of one-way Anova revealed significant difference in the perception of Work Hassles among Average days off per month, as the p value obtained in this case is below the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, Work Hassles of cabin crews are significantly influenced by the Average days off per month taken by cabin crews.

Gender: The second part of table demonstrates the results of t-test for independence on Work Hassles between the genders. Considering the results, Male showed highest level of agreement on Work Hassles causing to stress as the mean value in this case is more (3.0878) compared to Female (2.5340). Result of t-test for independence shows there is significant mean difference between male and female with respect to the perception level of Work Hassles, as the p value is less than 0.01. Therefore, Work Hassles is significantly different between male and female.

Marital Status: Second section under the second part of table exhibits the results of t-test for independence on Work Hassles between the marital status. Referring to the results, Married showed highest level of agreement on Work Hassles as the mean value in this case is more (2.8447) compared to Unmarried (2.5668). But Outcome of t-test for independence shows there is no significant mean difference between Married and Unmarried respondents with respect to the perception level of Work Hassles, as the p value is less than a 0.01. Therefore, Work Hassles is not significantly different between the marital status.

Based on the above inferences, one can state that there is significant difference in the perception level of Work Hassles among all the personal factors of the selected cabin crews except in case of age, Maximum number of consecutive nights of work and Marital Status, as the alpha value found to be below 0.01 at 99% confidence interval. Therefore, the Work Hassles of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their personal factors. Hence, H1.b is supported.

H1.c: The aircraft cabin environments of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their personal factors.

Table 6.37: One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test results between personal factors and the Aircraft Cabin Environments of cabin crews

Personal Factors		Mean	SD	F	P Value
Age	20 and Below	4.0385	1.35982	3.157	P<0.05*
	21 to 29	2.7089	.82584		
	31 to 39	2.9938	.85516		
	40 and Above	2.7308	.79897		
Current function	Junior cabin crew	2.8685	.84908	.672	P>0.05
	Senior cabin crew	2.7430	.76687		
	Inflight managers	2.8411	.93235		
	Trainers	3.0577	1.05478		
	Cabin Service Director	3.1538	1.00177		
Experience	0 to 1 Years	3.2596	1.10186	3.355	P<0.01**
	1 to 3 Years	2.7457	.78049		
	3 to 6 Years	2.7853	.88306		
	6 to 9 Years	2.5938	.58753		
	9 to 12 Years	2.6805	.80485		
	12 to 15 Years	3.2260	.81479		
	Above 15 Years	4.0000	1.25615		
Maximum number of consecutive days of work	Up to 6 days	3.0929	.94651	3.347	P<0.01**
	7 days or more	2.6681	.74485		
Maximum number of consecutive nights of work	One or two Nights	2.9796	.91392	1.495	P>0.05
	Three or Four Nights	2.7167	.87598		
	Five Nights or more	2.8546	.77100		
Average days off per month	Less than 5 days	3.1247	.90817	5.279	P<0.01**
	5-10 days	2.9272	.79417		
	10 days or more	2.6055	.85139		

Independent sample t-test					
Personal Factors		Mean	SD	T-value	P Value
Gender	Male	3.2088	.85812	2.946	P<0.01**
	Female	2.7512	.83052		
Marital Status	Married	2.9565	.91444	1.141	P>0.05
	Unmarried	2.7935	.83093		

**Significance at 1% level

*Significance at 5% level

Table 6.37 depicts the inferential statistics of Aircraft Cabin Environments with respect to various personal factors. The result of One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test is discussed below to assess the influence of personal factors on the Aircraft Cabin Environments of the cabin crews.

Age: The first section of the table exhibits mean difference in the Aircraft Cabin Environments among different age groups. As per the mean value, 20 and below age group showed highest level of agreement on Work Hassles (M=4.0385) compared to 31 to 39 (M=2.9938) and 40 and above age category (M=2.7308) followed by 21 to 29 age category (M=2.7089). The result of one-way ANOVA revealed significant difference in the perception of Aircraft Cabin Environments among different age groups, as the p value obtained in case of age category is less than 0.05. Therefore Aircraft Cabin Environments is significantly influenced by their age groups.

Current Function: The second section of the table presents mean difference in the Aircraft Cabin Environments among the current functions of cabin crews. As per the table, Cabin Service Directors showed highest level of agreement on Aircraft Cabin Environments (M=3.1538) compared to Trainers (M=3.0577) and Junior cabin crew (M=2.8685). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is evidenced that there is no significant difference in the perception level of Aircraft Cabin Environments among various current functions, as the p value obtained in this case is more than the alpha value 0.05. Therefore, Aircraft Cabin Environment of cabin crews is not significantly influenced by their current functions.

Experience: In the next section of the table mean difference in the Aircraft Cabin Environments among various year of experiences have been presented. As per the mean values, cabin crews with Above 15 Years of experience showed highest level of agreement on Aircraft Cabin Environments (M=4.0000) compared to 0 to 1 Years (M=3.2596) and 12 to 15 Years of experience (M=3.2260) followed by 3 to 6 Years of experience (M=2.7853). Moreover, result of one-way Anova revealed significant

difference in the perception of Aircraft Cabin Environments among year of experience, as the p value obtained in this case is below the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, Aircraft Cabin Environments of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their experience.

Maximum number of consecutive days of work: The fourth section of the table demonstrates mean difference in the Maximum number of consecutive days of work with respect to Aircraft Cabin Environments. As per the table, the respondents having Up to 6 days consecutive days of work showed highest level of agreement on Aircraft Cabin Environments (M=3.0929) compared to the cabin crews having 7 days or more consecutive days of work (M=2.6681). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is witnessed that there is significant difference in the perception level of Aircraft Cabin Environments among Maximum number of consecutive days of work done by the cabin crews, as the p value obtained in this case is less than the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, Aircraft Cabin Environments of cabin crews are significantly influenced by the Maximum number of consecutive days of work done by cabin crews.

Maximum number of consecutive nights of work: The next section of the table demonstrates mean difference in the Maximum number of consecutive nights of work with respect to Aircraft Cabin Environments. As per the mean values, the respondents having One or two Nights of work showed highest level of agreement on Aircraft Cabin Environments (M=2.9796) compared to the cabin crews having Five Nights or more (M=2.8546) and Three or Four Nights (M=2.7167). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is witnessed that there is no significant difference in the perception level of Aircraft Cabin Environments among Maximum number of consecutive nights of work done by the cabin crews, as the p value obtained in this case is more than the alpha value 0.05. Therefore, Aircraft Cabin Environments of cabin crews are not significantly influenced by the Maximum number of consecutive nights of work done by the cabin crews.

Average days off per month: In the sixth section of the table mean difference in the Aircraft Cabin Environments among Average days off per month taken by cabin crews have been presented. As per the mean values, cabin crews who have taken Less than 5 days as Average days off per month showed highest agreement level on Aircraft Cabin Environments (M=3.1247) compared to one who have taken 5-10 days (M=2.9272) and 10 days or more as an Average days off per month (M=2.6055).

Moreover, the result of one-way Anova revealed significant difference in the perception of Aircraft Cabin Environments among Average days off per month, as the p value obtained in this case is below the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, Aircraft Cabin Environments of cabin crews are significantly influenced by the Average days off per month taken by cabin crews.

Gender: The second part of table demonstrates the results of t-test for independence on Aircraft Cabin Environments between the genders. Considering the results, Male showed highest level of agreement on Aircraft Cabin Environments causing to stress as the mean value in this case is more (M=3.2088) compared to Female (M=2.7512). Result of t-test for independence on there is significant mean difference between male and female with respect to the perception level of Aircraft Cabin Environments, as the p value is less than 0.01. Therefore, Aircraft Cabin Environments is significantly different between male and female.

Marital Status: Second section under the second part of table exhibits the results of t-test for independence on Aircraft Cabin Environments between the marital status. Referring to the results, married showed highest level of agreement on Aircraft cabin environment as the mean value in this case is more (M=2.9565) compared to Unmarried (M=2.7935). But Outcome of t-test for independence shows there is no significant mean difference between Married and Unmarried respondents with respect to the perception level of Aircraft Cabin Environments, as the p value is less than a 0.01. Therefore, Aircraft Cabin Environments is not significantly different between the marital status.

Based on the above inferences, one can state that there is significant difference in the perception level of Aircraft Cabin Environments among all the personal factors of the selected cabin crews except in case of current function, Maximum number of consecutive nights of work and Marital Status, as the alpha value found to be below 0.01 at 99% confidence interval. Therefore, the Aircraft Cabin Environments of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their personal factors. Hence, H1.c is supported.

H1.d: The Social Isolation of cabin crews is significantly influenced by their personal factors.

Table 6.38: One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test results between Personal Factors and the Social Isolation of cabin crews

Personal Factors		Mean	SD	F	P Value
Age	20 and Below	3.95	.77782	1.582	P>0.05
	21 to 29	2.8049	.87432		
	31 to 39	2.9853	.90070		
	40 and Above	2.8364	.89791		
Current function	Junior cabin crew	2.8764	.89110	.556	P>0.05
	Senior cabin crew	2.8061	.82497		
	Inflight managers	2.9696	.96029		
	Trainers	2.9917	1.03613		
	Cabin Service Director	3.2500	1.04067		
Experience	0 to 1 Years	3.1750	.93630	3.782	P<0.01**
	1 to 3 Years	2.7556	.82801		
	3 to 6 Years	2.8396	.84871		
	6 to 9 Years	2.7813	.75024		
	9 to 12 Years	2.5769	.92480		
	12 to 15 Years	3.4687	.99714		
	Above 15 Years	4.2000	1.09545		
Maximum number of consecutive days of work	Up to 6 days	3.1935	1.03432	3.683	P<0.01**
	7 days or more	2.6968	.72962		
Maximum number of consecutive nights of work	One or two Nights	3.1000	.97681	2.098	P>0.05
	Three or Four Nights	2.7722	.93561		
	Five Nights or more	2.8685	.75588		
Average days off per month	Less than 5 days	3.3310	.84899	9.278	P<0.01**
	5-10 days	2.9947	.87219		
	10 days or more	2.5923	.83740		
Independent sample t-test					
Personal Factors		Mean	SD	T-value	P Value
Gender	Male	3.3657	.70249	4.214	P<0.01**
	Female	2.7861	.89449		
Marital Status	Married	3.0435	.96047	1.360	P>0.05
	Unmarried	2.8406	.86615		

**Significance at 1% level

*Significance at 5% level

Table 6.38 depicts the inferential statistics of Social Isolation with respect to various personal factors. The result of One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test is discussed below to assess the influence of personal factors on the Social Isolation of the cabin crews.

Age: The first section of the table exhibits mean difference in the Social Isolation among different age groups. As per the mean value, 20 and below age group showed highest level of agreement on Social Isolation (M=3.95) compared to 31 to 39 (M=2.9853) and 40 and above age category (M=2.8364) followed by 21 to 29 age

category (M=2.8049). Although the result of one-way ANOVA revealed no significant difference in the perception of Social Isolation among different age groups, as the p value obtained in case of age category is more than 0.05. Therefore, Social Isolation is not significantly influenced by their age groups.

Current Function: The second section of the table presents mean difference in the Social Isolation among the current functions of cabin crews. As per the table, Cabin Service Directors showed highest level of agreement on Social Isolation (M=3.2500) compared to Trainers (M=2.9917), Inflight managers (M=2.9696) and Junior cabin crew (M=2.8764). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is evidenced that there is no significant difference in the perception level of Social Isolation among various current functions, as the p value obtained in this case is more than the alpha value 0.05. Therefore, Social Isolation of cabin crews is not significantly influenced by their current functions.

Experience: In the next section of the table mean difference in the Social Isolation among various year of experiences have been presented. As per the mean values, cabin crews with Above 15 Years of experience showed highest level of agreement on Social Isolation (M=4.2000) compared to 12 to 15 Years (M=3.4687) and 0 to 1 Years of experience (M=3.1750) followed by 3 to 6 Years of experience (M=2.8396). Moreover, result of one-way Anova revealed significant difference in the perception of Social Isolation among year of experience, as the p value obtained in this case is below the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, Social Isolation of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their experience.

Maximum number of consecutive days of work: The fourth section of the table demonstrates mean difference in the Maximum number of consecutive days of work with respect to Social Isolation. As per the table, the respondents having Up to 6 days consecutive days of work showed highest level of agreement on Social Isolation (M=3.1935) compared to the cabin crews having 7 days or more consecutive days of work (M=2.6968). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is witnessed that there is significant difference in the perception level of Social Isolation among Maximum number of consecutive days of work done by the cabin crews, as the p value obtained in this case is less than the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, Social Isolation of cabin crews is significantly influenced by the Maximum number of consecutive days of work done by cabin crews.

Maximum number of consecutive nights of work: The next section of the table demonstrates mean difference in the Maximum number of consecutive nights of work with respect to Social Isolation. As per the mean values, the respondents having One or two Nights of work showed highest level of agreement on Social Isolation (M=3.1000) compared to the cabin crews having Five Nights or more (M=2.8685) and Three or Four Nights (M=2.7722). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is witnessed that there is no significant difference in the perception level of Social Isolation among Maximum number of consecutive nights of work done by the cabin crews, as the p value obtained in this case is more than the alpha value 0.05. Therefore, Social Isolation of cabin crews are not significantly influenced by the Maximum number of consecutive nights of work done by the cabin crews.

Average days off per month: In the sixth section of the table mean difference in the Social Isolation among Average days off per month taken by cabin crews have been presented. As per the mean values, cabin crews who have taken Less than 5 days as Average days off per month showed highest agreement level on Social Isolation (M=3.3310) compared to one who have taken 5-10 days (M=2.9947) and 10 days or more as an Average days off per month (M=2.5923). Moreover, the result of one-way Anova revealed significant difference in the perception of Social Isolation among Average days off per month, as the p value obtained in this case is below the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, Social Isolation of cabin crews is significantly influenced by the Average days off per month taken by cabin crews.

Gender: The second part of table demonstrates the results of t -test for independence on Social Isolation between the genders. Considering the results, Male showed highest level of agreement on Social Isolation causing to stress as the mean value in this case is more (M=3.3657) compared to Female (M=2.7861). Result of t-test for independence on there is significant mean difference between male and female with respect to the perception level of Social Isolation, as the p value is less than 0.01. Therefore, Social Isolation is significantly different between male and female.

Marital Status: Second section under the second part of table exhibits the results of t-test for independence on Social Isolation between the marital status. Referring to the results, married showed highest level of agreement on Social Isolation as the mean value in this case is more (M=3.0435) compared to Unmarried (M=2.8406). But Outcome of t-test for independence shows there is no significant mean difference

between Married and Unmarried respondents with respect to the perception level of Social Isolation, as the p value is less than a 0.01. Therefore, Social Isolation is not significantly different between the marital status.

Based on the above inferences, one can state that there is significant difference in the perception level of Social Isolation among all the personal factors of the selected cabin crews except in case of age, Current function, Maximum number of consecutive nights of work and Marital Status, as the alpha value found to be below 0.01 at 99% confidence interval. Therefore, the Social Isolation of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their personal factors. Hence, H1.d is supported.

H2: The Personal Factors of cabin crews have significant influence on Workplace Stress.

Table 6.39: One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test results between Personal Factors and Workplace Stress

Personal Factors		Mean	SD	F	P Value
Age	20 and Below	3.4583	.53033	.799	P>0.05
	21 to 29	2.7361	.72279		
	31 to 39	2.83	.73998		
	40 and Above	2.7841	.80206		
Current function	Junior cabin crew	2.7000	.69825	1.897	P>0.05
	Senior cabin crew	2.7114	.71172		
	Inflight managers	2.8714	.78640		
	Trainers	3.0208	.71255		
	Cabin Service Director	3.3889	.84437		
Experience	0 to 1 Years	2.9323	.79420	4.724	P<0.01**
	1 to 3 Years	2.6516	.69205		
	3 to 6 Years	2.7865	.60139		
	6 to 9 Years	2.6198	.70136		
	9 to 12 Years	2.8205	.64983		
	12 to 15 Years	3.1354	.80730		
	Above 15 Years	4.3125	1.15545		
Maximum number of consecutive days of work	Up to 6 days	2.9686	.92708	2.562	P<0.05*
	7 days or more	2.6687	.56153		
Maximum number of consecutive nights of work	One or two Nights	3.0969	.76874	6.379	P<0.01**
	Three or Four Nights	2.7173	.74731		
	Five Nights or more	2.6450	.64430		
Average days off per month	Less than 5 days	2.9339	.78312	2.291	P<0.05*
	5-10 days	2.8484	.68205		
	10 days or more	2.6496	.76863		
Independent Sample t-test					
Personal Factors		Mean	SD	T-value	P Value
Gender	Male	3.0667	.62420	2.537	P<0.05*
	Female	2.7239	.74563		
Marital Status	Married	3.0362	.82676	2.692	P<0.01**
	Unmarried	2.7086	.69231		

**Significance at 1% level

*Significance at 5% level

Table 6.39 shows the inferential statistics of Workplace Stress with respect to various personal factors. The result of One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test is discussed below to assess the influence of personal factors on the workplace stress of the cabin crews.

Age: The first section of the table exhibits mean difference in the workplace stress among different age groups. As per the mean value, 20 and below age group showed highest level of agreement on Workplace Stress (M=3.4583) compared to 31 to 39 (M=2.83) and 40 and above age category (M=2.7841) followed by 21 to 29 age category (M=2.7361). Although the result of one-way ANOVA revealed no significant difference in the perception of Workplace Stress among different age groups, as the p value obtained in case of age category is more than 0.05. Therefore, Workplace Stress is not significantly influenced by their age groups.

Current Function: The second section of the table presents mean difference in the Workplace Stress among the current functions of cabin crews. As per the table, Cabin Service Directors showed highest level of agreement on Workplace Stress (M=3.3889) compared to Trainers (M=3.0208), Inflight managers (M=2.8714) and Senior cabin crew (M=2.7114). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is evidenced that there is no significant difference in the perception level of Workplace Stress among various current functions, as the p value obtained in this case is more than the alpha value 0.05. Therefore, Workplace Stress of cabin crews is not significantly influenced by their current functions.

Experience: In the next section of the table mean difference in the Workplace Stress among various year of experiences have been presented. As per the mean values, cabin crews with Above 15 Years of experience showed highest level of agreement on Workplace Stress (M=4.3125) compared to 12 to 15 Years (M=3.1354) and 0 to 1 Years of experience (M=2.9323) followed by 9 to 12 Years of experience (M=2.8205). Moreover, result of one-way Anova revealed significant difference in the perception of Workplace Stress among year of experience, as the p value obtained in this case is below the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, Workplace Stress of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their experience.

Maximum number of consecutive days of work: The fourth section of the table demonstrates mean difference in the Maximum number of consecutive days of work with respect to Workplace Stress. As per the table, the respondents having Up to 6 days consecutive days of work showed highest level of agreement on Workplace Stress

(M=2.9686) compared to the cabin crews having 7 days or more consecutive days of work (M=2.6687). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is witnessed that there is significant difference in the perception level of workplace stress among maximum number of consecutive days of work done by the cabin crews, as the p value obtained in this case is less than the alpha value 0.05. Therefore, Workplace Stress of cabin crews is significantly influenced by the Maximum number of consecutive days of work done by cabin crews.

Maximum number of consecutive nights of work: The next section of the table demonstrates mean difference in the Maximum number of consecutive nights of work with respect to Workplace Stress. As per the mean values, the respondents having One or two Nights of work showed highest level of agreement on Workplace Stress (M=3.0969) compared to the cabin crews having Three or Four Nights (M=2.7173) and Five Nights or more (M=2.6450). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is witnessed that there is significant difference in the perception level of Workplace Stress among Maximum number of consecutive nights of work done by the cabin crews, as the p value obtained in this case is less than the alpha value 0.05. Therefore, Workplace Stress of cabin crews is significantly influenced by the Maximum number of consecutive nights of work done by the cabin crews.

Average days off per month: In the sixth section of the table mean difference in the Workplace Stress among Average days off per month taken by cabin crews have been presented. As per the mean values, cabin crews who have taken Less than 5 days as Average days off per month showed highest agreement level on Workplace Stress (M=2.9339) compared to one who have taken 5-10 days (M=2.8484) and 10 days or more as an Average days off per month (M=2.6496). Moreover, the result of one-way Anova revealed significant difference in the perception of Workplace Stress among Average days off per month, as the p value obtained in this case is below the alpha value 0.05. Therefore, Workplace Stress of cabin crews is significantly influenced by the Average days off per month taken by cabin crews.

Gender: The second part of table demonstrates the results of t-test for independence on Workplace Stress between the genders. Considering the results, Male showed highest level of agreement on Workplace Stress causing to stress as the mean value in this case is more (M=3.0667) compared to Female (M=2.7239). Result of t-test for independence on there is significant mean difference between male and female with respect to the perception level of Workplace Stress, as the p value is less than 0.05. Therefore, Workplace Stress is significantly different between male and female.

Marital Status: Second section under the second part of table exhibits the results of t-test for independence on Workplace Stress between the marital status. Referring to the results, married showed highest level of agreement on Workplace Stress as the mean value in this case is more (M=3.0362) compared to Unmarried (M=2.7086). Outcome of t-test for independence shows there is significant mean difference between Married and Unmarried respondents with respect to the perception level of Workplace Stress, as the p value is less than a 0.01. Therefore, Workplace Stress is significantly different between the marital status.

Based on the above inferences, one can state that there is significant difference in the perception level of workplace stress among all the personal factors of the selected cabin crews except in case of age and Current function, as the alpha value found to be below 0.01 at 99% confidence interval. Therefore, the workplace stress of cabin crews is significantly influenced by their personal factors. Hence, H2 is supported.

H3: Work Engagement is significantly different among various personal factors of cabin crews.

Table 6.40: One-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test results between Personal Factors and Work Engagement

Personal Factors		Mean	SD	F	P Value
Age	20 and Below	4.0625	.61872	1.843	P>0.05
	21 to 29	2.8103	.85169		
	31 to 39	2.995	.89121		
	40 and Above	2.875	.91882		
Current function	Junior cabin crew	2.8968	.89234	.554	P>0.05
	Senior cabin crew	2.8149	.83020		
	In flight managers	2.9837	.91262		
	Trainers	2.9792	.99623		
	Cabin Service Dir	3.2500	1.04067		
Experience	0 to 1 Years	3.0938	.84076	3.606	P<0.01**
	1 to 3 Years	2.7826	.84838		
	3 to 6	2.8792	.83882		
	6 to 9 Years	2.7813	.75024		
	9 to 12 Years	2.5615	.90603		
	12 to 15 Years	3.4687	.93806		
	Above 15 Years	4.2000	1.09545		
Maximum number of consecutive days of work	Up to 6 days	3.2156	.99771	3.908	P<0.01**
	7 days or more	2.7020	.73353		
Maximum number of consecutive nights of work	One or two Nights	3.1383	.96117	2.554	P>0.05
	Three or Four Nights	2.7899	.92545		
	Five Nights or more	2.8558	.73912		
Average days off per month	Less than 5 days	3.3569	.81028	10.350	P<0.01**
	5-10 days	3.0117	.85114		
	10 days or more	2.5923	.83740		

Independent sample t-test					
Personal Factors		Mean	SD	T-value	P Value
Gender	Male	3.4329	.54922	5.579	P<0.01**
	Female	2.7861	.89449		
Marital Status	Married	3.0891	.97103	1.681	P>0.05
	Unmarried	2.8423	.84427		

**Significance at 1% level

*Significance at 5% level

Table 6.40 demonstrates the inferential analysis of Work Engagement with respect to various personal factors. The result of one-way ANOVA and Independent sample t-test is discussed below to assess the influence of personal factors on the work engagement of the cabin crews.

Age: The first section of the table exhibits mean difference in the Work Engagement among different age groups. As per the mean value, 20 and below age group showed highest level of agreement on Work Engagement (M=4.0625) compared to 31 to 39 (M=2.995) and 40 and above age category (M=2.875) followed by 21 to 29 age category (M=2.8103). Although the result of one-way ANOVA revealed no significant difference in the perception of Work Engagement among different age groups, as the p value obtained in case of age category is more than 0.05. Therefore, work engagement is not significantly influenced by their age groups.

Current function: The second section of the table presents mean difference in the Work Engagement among the current functions of cabin crews. As per the table, Cabin Service Directors showed highest level of agreement on work engagement (M=3.2500) compared to Inflight managers (M=2.9837), Trainers (M=2.9792) and Junior cabin crew (M=2.8968). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is evidenced that there is no significant difference in the perception level of Work Engagement among various current functions, as the p value obtained in this case is more than the alpha value 0.05. Therefore, work engagement of cabin crews is not significantly influenced by their current functions.

Experience: In the next section of the table mean difference in the Work Engagement among various year of experiences have been presented. As per the mean values, cabin crews with Above 15 Years of experience showed highest level of agreement on Work Engagement (M=4.2000) compared to 12 to 15 Years (M=3.4687) and 0 to 1 Years of experience (M=3.0938) followed by 3 to 6 Years of experience (M=2.8792). Moreover, result of one-way Anova revealed significant difference in the perception of Work Engagement among years of experience, as the p value obtained in this case is below the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, work engagement of cabin crews is significantly influenced by their experience.

Maximum number of consecutive days of work: The fourth section of the table demonstrates mean difference in the Maximum number of consecutive days of work with respect to Work Engagement. As per the table, the respondents having Up to 6 days consecutive days of work showed highest level of agreement on Work Engagement (M=3.2156) compared to the cabin crews having 7 days or more consecutive days of work (M=2.7020). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is witnessed that there is significant difference in the perception level of Work Engagement among Maximum number of consecutive days of work done by the cabin crews, as the p value obtained in this case is less than the alpha value 0.01. Therefore, work engagement of cabin crews is significantly influenced by the maximum number of consecutive days of work done by cabin crews.

Maximum number of consecutive nights of work: The next section of the table demonstrates mean difference in the Maximum number of consecutive nights of work with respect to Work Engagement. As per the mean values, the respondents having One or two Nights of work showed highest level of agreement on Work Engagement (M=3.1383) compared to the cabin crews having Five Nights or more (M=2.8558) and Three or Four Nights (M=2.7899). As far as ANOVA result is concerned it is witnessed that there is no significant difference in the perception level of Work Engagement among Maximum number of consecutive nights of work done by the cabin crews, as the p value obtained in this case is more than the alpha value 0.05. Therefore, Work Engagement of cabin crews is not significantly influenced by the Maximum number of consecutive nights of work done by the cabin crews.

Average days off per month: In the sixth section of the table mean difference in the Work Engagement among Average days off per month taken by cabin crews have been presented. As per the mean values, cabin crews who have taken Less than 5 days as Average days off per month showed highest agreement level on Work Engagement (M=3.3569) compared to one who have taken 5-10 days (M=3.0117) and 10 days or more as an Average days off per month (M=2.5923). Moreover, the result of one-way Anova revealed significant difference in the perception of Work Engagement among Average days off per month, as the p value obtained in this case is below the alpha value 0.05. Therefore, work engagement of cabin crews is significantly influenced by the average days off per month taken by cabin crews.

Gender: The second part of table demonstrates the results of t-test for independence on Work Engagement between the genders. Considering the results, Male showed highest level of agreement on Work Engagement causing to stress as the mean value in this case is more (M=3.4329) compared to Female (M=2.7861). Result of t -test for independence on there is significant mean difference between male and female with respect to the perception level of Work Engagement, as the p value is less than 0.05. Therefore, work engagement is significantly different between male and female.

Marital Status: Second section under the second part of table exhibits the results of t-test for independence on Work Engagement between the marital status. Referring to the results, Married showed highest level of agreement on Work Engagement as the mean value in this case is more (M=3.0891) compared to Unmarried (M=2.8423). But the outcome of t-test for independence shows there is no significant mean difference between Married and Unmarried respondents with respect to the perception level of Work Engagement, as the p value is more than a 0.05. Therefore, Work Engagement is not significantly different between the marital status.

Based on the above inferences, one can state that there is significant difference in the perception level of work engagement among all the personal factors of the selected cabin crews except in case of age, current function, maximum number of consecutive nights of work and marital status, as the alpha value found to be below 0.01 at 99% confidence interval. Therefore, the work engagement of cabin crews is significantly influenced by their personal factors. Hence, H3 is accepted.

H4: Stressor Agents have direct effect on Workplace Stress.

Table 6.41: Model Summary: Direct Effect of Stress Agents on Workplace Stress

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.729 ^a	.532	.522	.50872	.532	55.694	4	196	.000	2.103
a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Isolation, Irregular Working Hours, Aircraft Cabin Environments, Work Hassles										
b. Dependent Variable: The Workplace Stress Scale										

As per the model summary results Coefficient of correlation(R) is .729, which illustrates that there is a relationship between the stressor agents and workplace stress of cabin crews. R² value (.532) in the table presents the influential extent of Coefficient of determination on independent variable (Stressor agents) to dependent variable (workplace stress). The model summary demonstrates that indicators of stressor agents

contribute to workplace stress by 53.2% and remaining 46.8% is not studied. Lastly, the adjusted R square (.522) highlighted the variation in the variables.

Table 6.42: Anova Results: Direct Effect of Stress Agents on Workplace Stress

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	57.653	4	14.413	55.694	.000 ^b
	Residual	50.724	196	.259		
	Total	108.377	200			
a. Dependent Variable: The Workplace Stress Scale						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Social Isolation, Irregular Working Hours, Aircraft Cabin Environments, Work Hassles						

Contemplating the result of ANOVA, it is evidenced that the model is significant, as the p value is below 0.01; which indicates statistical significant relationship of Independent variable (stressor agents) with the dependent variable (workplace stress) at 99% confidence interval. Therefore, the stressor agents have direct effect on workplace stress among cabin crews.

Table 6.43: Coefficients Results: Direct Effect of Stress Agents on Workplace Stress

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.967	.136		7.112	.000
	Irregular Working Hours	.182	.058	.221	3.127	.002
	Work Hassles	.326	.067	.399	4.859	.000
	Aircraft Cabin Environments	.085	.066	.098	1.275	.204
	Social Isolation	.087	.062	.105	1.403	.162

a. Dependent Variable: The Workplace Stress Scale

From the coefficient table 6.43 it is observed that coefficient of stressor agent is affirmative with the workplace stress. The indicators which are statistically significant at 99% confidence interval include Irregular Working Hours (t=3.127, p=.002) and Work Hassles (t=4.859, p=.000). Although Aircraft Cabin Environments (t=1.275, p=.204) and Social Isolation (t=1.403, p=.162) is not statistical significant. In order to assess the impact of stressor agents on workplace stress, beta coefficients have been referred. Increase in one unit of the agreement level on work hassles contributes to increase in the workplace stress of cabin crews by 32.6% (B=.326 units); one unit increase in irregular working hours would lead to 18.2% increase in workplace stress (B=.182). Overall, considering Model summary, ANOVA and Coefficient results it can be inferred that stressor agents have direct effect on workplace stress. Hence, H4 is accepted.

H5: Workplace Stress of cabin crews will have impact on work engagement

Table 6.44: Model Summary: Workplace Stress and Work Engagement

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.199 ^a	.040	.035	.78530
a. Predictors: (Constant), The Workplace Stress Scale				

As per the model summary table 6.44 results Coefficient of correlation(R) is .199, which illustrates that there is a relationship between the workplace stress of cabin crews and their work engagement. R² value (.040) in the table presents the influential extent of Coefficient of determination on independent variable (Workplace Stress) to dependent variable (work engagement). The model summary exhibits that workplace stress contributes to work engagement by 40% and remaining 60% is not studied. Lastly, the adjusted R square (.035) highlighted the variation in the variables.

Table 6.45: ANOVA Results: Workplace Stress and Work Engagement

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.075	1	5.075	8.230	.005 ^b
	Residual	122.723	199	.617		
	Total	127.798	200			
a. Dependent Variable: Work Engagement						
b. Predictors: (Constant), The Workplace Stress Scale						

Considering the result of ANOVA, it is evidenced that the model is significant, as the p value is below 0.01; which indicates statistical significant relationship of Workplace Stress (IV) with the work engagement (DV) at 99% confidence interval. Therefore, the workplace stress has impact on work engagement among cabin crews.

Table 6.46: Coefficients Results: Workplace Stress and Work Engagement

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.205	.217		19.365	.000
	The Workplace Stress Scale	-.216	.075	-.199	-2.869	.005
a. Dependent Variable: Work Engagement						

From the coefficient table 6.46 it is noticed that coefficient of workplace stress has contrary relationship with the work engagement. Impact of workplace stress on work engagement is statistically significant, since the p value is below 0.01. In order to assess the impactful extent of workplace stress on work engagement, beta coefficients have

been referred. Which implies that increase in one unit of workplace stress contributes to -21.6% (-.216) decrease in work engagement, as the Beta value shown in the table is negative. Overall, considering Model summary, ANOVA and Coefficient results it can be inferred that workplace stress have negative significant effect on work engagement. Hence, H5 is accepted.

H6: Stress coping behaviour plays a mediating role in relationship between Workplace Stress and work engagement.

H6: Stress Coping Resources acts as a mediator between Workplace Stress and work engagement.

Figure 6.1: Mediating effect of Stress coping behaviour in relationship between Workplace Stress and Work Engagement

Table 6.47: Estimate and Significant Value of Stress coping behaviour in relationship between Workplace Stress and Work Engagement

Variable		Variable	S. Estimate	U. Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Stress Coping Resources	<---	Workplace Stress	.008	.007	.062	.111	.911	Not Significant
Work Engagement	<---	Stress Coping Resources	.254	.315	.083	3.799	***	Highly Significant
Work Engagement	<---	Workplace Stress	-.199	-.217	.073	-2.974	.003	Significant

The table 6.47 demonstrates the effect of three major constructs on each other. Firstly, workplace stress shows direct positive effect on stress coping resources but not a significant impact (Estimate=.007, p=.911). Secondly, Stress coping resources has direct significant impact on work engagement (Estimate=.315, p=0.000). Lastly, workplace stress has negative significant effect on work engagement (Estimate=-.217, p=.003). from the direct effect analysis it is observed that workplace has direct effect on

stress coping resources; stress coping resources directly effects work engagement. Furthermore workplace stress negatively effects work engagement. To analyse the mediation effect of stress coping resources to assess the indirect impact of workplace stress on work engagement [315][316] the below table 6.48 can be referred.

Table 6.48: Standardized Estimation (SE) with Direct Effect, Indirect Effect and Total Effect

	Standardized Estimation (SE)	P-value	Results
Effect (Total)	-0.197	0.000**	Statistically significant
Effect (Direct)	-.199	0.000**	Statistically significant
Effect (Indirect)	0.002	0.000**	Statistically significant

Stress Coping resources as a mediator between workplace stress and work engagement can be measured through standerzided estimates. As per the result workplace stress has a direct negative impact on work engagement (Estimate=-.199, p=0.000). Contemplating the indirect effect it is strongly evidenced that stress coping resource acts as a mediator between Workplace Stress and work engagement (Estimate=0.002, p=0.000). Consequently, it can be inferred that Stress Coping Resources acts as a mediator between Workplace Stress and work engagement. Therefore, H6 is accepted.

Table 6.49: Results of Goodness of Fit Indices

Fit statistic	Recommended	Obtained
χ^2	-	24.139
df	-	7
χ^2 significant	$p \geq 0.01$.067
χ^2 / df	$\leq 2- 5.0$	3.4484
GFI	≥ 0.90	0.926
NFI	≥ 0.90	0.971
AGFI	>0.80	0.914
CFI	≥ 0.90	0.935
RMSEA	≤ 0.05	0.042

The table 6.49 depicts recommended and obtained value to check the goodness of fit of the proposed model, the obtained value satisfies the recommended value as χ^2/df is between 2-5 (3.4484); GFI is above .90 (0.926); NFI is above .90 (0.971); AGFI is above 0.8 (0.914); CFI is above .90 (0.935) and RMSEA is below 0.05 (0.042). Hence, the proposed model tends to be valid and fit for further analysis.

H7: Personal Factor of the employees tends to moderate the relationship between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress.

H7.a: Age of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress.

Table 6.50: Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients Results showing age as a moderator between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress

Age	Stressor Agents	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
20 and Below						
B	.583	1.000 ^a	1.000	.	35.560	.000 ^b
t	7.112					
Sig.	0.000					
21 to 29						
B	0.717	.746 ^a	.557	.552	125.510	.000 ^b
t	11.203					
Sig.	0.000					
31 to 39						
B	0.646	.672 ^a	.452	.444	60.125	.000 ^b
t	7.754					
Sig.	0.000					
40 and Above						
B	0.797	.713 ^a	.508	.484	20.689	.000 ^b
t	4.548					
Sig.	0.000					
<i>a. Dependent Variable: The Workplace Stress Scale</i>						

Contemplating the result of ANOVA, it is evidenced that the model is significant, as the p value is below 0.01. Furthermore, to assess the impact of stressor agents on workplace stress, the study examined Beta coefficients with respect to selected age categories. The results revealed statistical significant impact of stressor agents on workplace stress with respect to all the age categories, as the alpha value is less than 0.01. Referring to beta coefficients, 40 and above age category (B=0.797) considers stressor agents as the highest predictor of stress level at workplace compared to 21 to 29 (B=0.717), 31 to 39 (B=0.646) followed by 20 and below age category (B=.583). This recommends that one unit of increase in stressor agents contributes to 79.7% (or 0.797 unit) increase in workplace stress for 40 and above age category; in case of 21 to 29 age category, 1 unit increase in stressor agents leads to 71.7% (or .717 unit) escalation in workplace stress; while for 31 to 39 and 20 and 20 age category, one unit increase in stressor agents would lead to 64.6% and 58.3% increase in stress level of workplace respectively. Hence, it can be inferred that Age tends to moderate the relationship between stressor agents and workplace stress of the cabin crews. Therefore, H7.a is accepted.

H7.b: Gender of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress.

Table 6.51: Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients Results showing gender as a moderator between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress

Gender	Stressor Agents	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
Male						
B	.578	.630 ^a	.397	.379	21.740	.000 ^b
t	3.057					
Sig.	.004					
Female						
B	.715	.718 ^a	.516	.513	174.972	.000 ^b
t	5.663					
Sig.	0.000					
<i>a. Dependent Variable: The Workplace Stress Scale</i>						

As per table 6.51 the result of ANOVA, it is evidenced that the model is significant, as the p value is below 0.01. To measure the impact of independent variable (stressor agents) on dependent variable (workplace stress), Beta coefficient has been referred. Considering the beta coefficients of male and female, it can be inferred that stressor agents are the strongest predictor of workplace stress (B=.715) in case of female compared to male (B=.578). In case of female, one unit increase in stressor agent leads to 71.5% (or .715 units) increase in workplace stress; although, one unit increase in stressor agent leads to 57.8% (or .578 unit) increase in workplace stress in case of male. Hence, gender of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between the Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress. Therefore, H7.b is supported.

H7.c: Marital status tends to moderate the relationship between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress.

Table 6.52: Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients Results showing marital status as a moderator between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress

Marital status	Stressor Agents	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
Married						
B	.814	.844 ^a	.713	.706	109.318	.000 ^b
t	10.456					
Sig.	.000					
Unmarried						
B	.624	.653 ^a	.426	.422	113.635	.000 ^b
t	10.660					
Sig.	0.000					
<i>a. Dependent Variable: The Workplace Stress Scale</i>						

As per table 6.52 the result of ANOVA, it is evidenced that the model is significant for both married and unmarried respondents, as the p value is below 0.01. Moreover, to assess the impact of stressor agents on workplace stress, the study examined Beta coefficients with respect to marital status. The results revealed statistical significant impact of stressor agents on workplace stress with respect to marital status. Considering the beta coefficients stressor agents are the strongest predictor of workplace stress (B=.814) among married compared to unmarried (B=.624), this implies that a one unit increase in stressor agent leads to 81.4% (or .814 units) increase in workplace stress in case of married and in case of unmarried, one unit increase in stressor agent leads to 62.4% (or .624 units) increase in workplace stress. Hence, marital status of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between the Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress. Therefore, H7.c is supported.

H7.d: Current function of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress.

Table 6.53: Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients Results showing Current Function as a moderator between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress

Current Function	Stressor Agents	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
Junior cabin crew						
B	.657	.697 ^a	.486	.477	50.176	.000 ^b
t	7.083					
Sig.	0.000					
Senior cabin crew						
B	.694	.694 ^a	.481	.475	74.214	.000 ^b
t	8.615					
Sig.	0.000					
Inflight managers						
B	.737	.770 ^a	.593	.584	64.141	.000 ^b
t	8.009					
Sig.	0.000					
Trainers						
B	.559	.680 ^a	.463	.409	8.613	.015 ^b
t	2.935					
Sig.	.015					
Cabin Service Director						
B	.627	.606 ^a	.367	.209	2.319	.202 ^b
t	1.523					
Sig.	.202					
<i>a. Dependent Variable: The Workplace Stress Scale</i>						

Conducive to assess the impact of stressor agents on workplace stress, the study examined Beta coefficients with respect to current functions of the cabin crews. The results revealed statistical significant impact of stressor agents on workplace stress with respect to Junior cabin crew (p=0.000), Senior cabin crew (p=0.000), Inflight managers (0.000) at 1% level of significance and trainer (0.015) at 5% level of significance. Although statistical significant impact of stressor agents on workplace stress was not witnessed with respect to Cabin Service Director (p=.202). The above table shows that, independent variable has statistical significant impact on workplace stress in majority of the current functions, since its p-value is below the alpha level which is 0.01. Referring to the beta coefficients, stressor agents are considered to be the strongest contributor of stress at workplace among Inflight managers (.737), followed by senior cabin crew (.694), junior cabin crew (.657), Cabin Service Director (.627) and Trainers (.559). It indicates that increase in one unit of stressor agents leads to 73.7% (or .737 units) increases in workplace stress among Inflight managers; in case

of Senior cabin crew, Junior cabin crew, Cabin Service Director and Trainers, one unit inclination in stress contributes to 69.4%, 62.7% and 55.9% increase in stress level respectively. Overall, it implies that Current function of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress. Therefore, H7.d is supported.

H7.e: Experience of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress.

Table 6.54: Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients Results showing experience as a moderator between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress

Experience	Stressor Agents	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
0 to 1 Years						
B	.511	.581 ^a	.338	.290	7.136	.018 ^b
t	2.671					
Sig.	0.018					
1 to 3 Years						
B	.698	.677 ^a	.458	.450	59.149	.000 ^b
t	7.691					
Sig.	0.000					
3 to 6						
B	.552	.679 ^a	.460	.449	39.248	.000 ^b
t	6.265					
Sig.	0.000					
6 to 9 Years						
B	.863	.724 ^a	.523	.508	32.957	.000 ^b
t	5.741					
Sig.	0.000					
9 to 12 Years						
B	.468	.508 ^a	.258	.190	3.822	.076 ^b
t	1.955					
Sig.	0.076					
12 to 15 Years						
B	.757	.815 ^a	.664	.640	27.623	.000 ^b
t	5.256					
Sig.	0.000					
Above 15 Years						
B	.747	.817 ^a	.667	.651	29.314	.073 ^b
t	3.495					
Sig.	0.073					
<i>a. Dependent Variable: The Workplace Stress Scale</i>						

In order to assess the impact of stressor agents on workplace stress, the study examined Beta coefficients with respect to experience. The results revealed statistical significant impact of stressor agents on workplace stress with respect to 1 to 3 Years (p=0.000), 3 to 6 years (p=0.000), 6 to 9 Years (0.000) of experience at 1% level of significance

and 0 to 1 Years of experience (0.015) at 5% level of significance. Although statistical significant impact of stressor agents on workplace stress was not witnessed with respect to 9 to 12 Years ($p=.076$) and above 15 Years of experience ($p=0.073$). The above table revealing ANOVA results show that, independent variable has statistical significant impact on workplace stress in majority of the experiences, since its p-value is below the alpha level which is 0.01. Referring to the beta coefficients, stressor agents are considered to be the strongest contributor of stress at workplace in case of Above 15 Years ($B=.947$) of experience, followed by 6 to 9 Years ($B=.863$), 12 to 15 Years ($B=.757$), 1 to 3 Years ($B=.698$) and 3 to 6 years ($B=.552$) of experience. It implies that increase in one unit of stressor agents leads to 74.7% (or .747 units) increases in workplace stress among the respondents having Above 15 Years of experience; in case of 6 to 9 Years, 12 to 15 Years, 1 to 3 Years and 3 to 6 years of experiences, one unit hike in stress contributes to 86.3%, 75.7%, 69.8% and 55.2% increase in stress level respectively. Overall, it implies that Experience of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress. Therefore, H7.e is accepted.

As all the sub hypotheses under H7 rejects null hypothesis leading to the acceptance of H7.a, H7.b, H7.c, H7.d and H7.e indicated that personal factors of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress. Therefore H7 is accepted.

H8: Personal factors of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Workplace Stress and work Engagement.

H8.a: Age of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Workplace Stress and work Engagement.

Table 6.55: Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients Results showing age as a moderator between Workplace Stress and work Engagement

Age	The Workplace Stress Scale	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
20 and Below						
B	2.400	1.000 ^b	1.000	.	.	. ^c
t	7.512					
Sig.	0.000					
21 to 29						
B	-.282	.263 ^b	.069	.060	7.417	.008 ^c
t	-2.723					
Sig.	.008					
31 to 39						
B	-.251	.219 ^b	.048	.035	3.662	.060 ^c
t	-1.914					
Sig.	.060					
40 and Above						
B	-.015	.018 ^b	.000	-.050	.007	.936 ^c
t	-.081					
Sig.	.936					
<i>a. Dependent Variable: Work Engagement</i>						

Contemplating the result of ANOVA, it is evidenced that the model is significant for 20 and below, 21 to 29 age categories, as the p value is below 0.01. Furthermore, to assess the impact of Workplace Stress on work Engagement, the study examined Beta coefficients with respect to selected age categories. The results revealed statistical significant impact of Workplace Stress on work Engagement with respect to 20 and below and 21 to 29 age categories, as the alpha value in this case is less than 0.01. Referring to beta coefficients, 20 and below age category (B=2.400) considers Workplace Stress as the highest predictor of work Engagement at workplace compared to 21 to 29 (B= -.282) and 31 to 39 (B= -.251). This recommends that one unit of increase in Workplace Stress contributes to 240% (or .240 unit) increase in work Engagement for 20 and Below age category; In contrary, in case of 21 to 29 age category, 1unit increase in Workplace Stress leads to -28.2% (or -.282 unit) decrease in work Engagement; while for 31 to 39 age category, one unit increase in Workplace Stress would lead to -25.1% (or -.251 unit) decrease in work Engagement; it indicates that higher the stress level at workplace, lower will be the work engagement among the cabin crews among different age groups. Hence, it can be inferred that Age tends to moderate the relationship between Workplace Stress and work Engagement of the cabin crews. Therefore, H8. is supported.

H8.b: Gender of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Workplace Stress and Work Engagement.

Table 6.56: Model Summary: Mediating role of Gender in relationship between Workplace Stress and Work Engagement

Gender	The Workplace Stress Scale	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
Male						
B	-.152	.152 ^b	.023	-.007	.780	.384 ^c
t	-.883					
Sig.	.384					
Female						
B	-.250	.224 ^b	.050	.044	8.674	.004 ^c
t	-2.945					
Sig.	.004					
<i>a. Dependent Variable: Work Engagement</i>						

As per table 6.56 the result of ANOVA, it is evidenced that the model is significant for female, as the p value is below 0.01. To measure the impact of independent variable (Workplace Stress) on dependent variable (work Engagement), Beta coefficient has been referred. Considering the beta coefficients of male and female, it can be inferred that Workplace Stress is the strongest predictor of work Engagement (B= -.250) in case of female compared to male (B= -.152). In case of female, one unit increase in Workplace Stress leads to -25% (or -.250 units) decrease in work Engagement; although, one unit increase in Workplace Stress leads to -15.2% (or -.152 units) decrease in work Engagement in case of male. Negative impact of workplace stress on work engagement is highly significant in case of female. Hence, it implies that gender of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between the Workplace Stress and work Engagement. Therefore, H8.b is supported.

H8.c: Marital status of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Workplace Stress and Employees Engagement. Model Summary, ANOVA and Coefficients^a

Table 6.57: Model Summary: Mediating role of Marital Status in relationship between Workplace Stress and Employees Engagement

Marital Status	The Workplace Stress Scale	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
Married						
B	-.116	.114 ^b	.013	-.009	.580	.450 ^c
t	-.762					
Sig.	.450					
Unmarried						
B	-.217	.194 ^b	.038	.032	6.015	.015 ^c
t	-2.453					
Sig.	.015					
<i>a. Dependent Variable: Work Engagement</i>						

As per table 6.57 the result of ANOVA, it is evidenced that the model is significant for unmarried respondents, as the p value is below 0.01. Moreover, to assess the impact of Workplace Stress on work Engagement, the study examined Beta coefficients with respect to marital status. The results revealed statistical significant impact of Workplace Stress on work Engagement with respect to marital status. Considering the beta coefficients Workplace Stress is the strongest predictor of work Engagement (B= -.217) among Unmarried compared to Married (B=-.116), this implies that a one unit increase in Workplace Stress leads to -21.7% (or -.217 units) decrease in work Engagement in case of Unmarried and in case of Married, one unit increase in Workplace Stress leads to -11.6% (or -.116 units) decrease in work Engagement. Hence, marital status of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between the Workplace Stress and work Engagement. Therefore, H8.c is supported.

H8.d: Current function of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Workplace Stress and Employees Engagement.

Table 6.58: Model Summary: Mediating role of Current Function of the Cabin Crews in relationship between Workplace Stress and Employees Engagement

Current Function	The Workplace Stress Scale	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
Junior cabin crew						
B	-.229	.247 ^b	.061	.043	3.452	.069 ^c
t	-1.858					
Sig.	.069					
Senior cabin crew						
B	-.233	.216 ^b	.047	.035	3.910	.051 ^c
t	-1.977					
Sig.	.051					
Inflight managers						
B	-.391	.322 ^b	.104	.084	5.105	.029 ^c
t	-2.259					
Sig.	.029					
Trainers						
B	-.136	.162 ^b	.026	-.071	.271	.614 ^c
t	-.520					
Sig.	.614					
Cabin Service Director						
B	.341	.233 ^b	.054	-.182	.229	.657 ^c
t	.478					
Sig.	.657					
<i>a. Dependent Variable: Work Engagement</i>						

Conducive to assess the impact of Workplace Stress on work Engagement, the study examined Beta coefficients with respect to current functions of the cabin crews. The results revealed statistical significant impact of Workplace Stress on work Engagement with respect to In flight managers (0.029) at 5% level of significance. But significant impact of Workplace Stress on work engagement was not witnessed with respect to other current functions. The above table shows that, independent variable does not have statistical significant impact on work Engagement in majority of the current functions, since its p-value is above the alpha level 0.01. Referring to the beta coefficients, Workplace Stress is considered to be the strongest contributor of work Engagement among Inflight managers (B=-.391), followed by Cabin Service Dir (.341), Senior cabin crew (-.233) and Junior cabin crew (-.229). It indicates that increase in one unit of Workplace Stress leads to 39.1% (or .391 units) decreases in work engagement among In-flight managers; Overall, it implies that Current function of the cabin crews does not moderate the relationship between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress except in case of inflight manager. Therefore H8.d is not supported.

H8.e: Experience of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Workplace Stress and Employees Engagement.

Table 6.59: Model Summary: Mediating role of Experience of the Cabin Crews in relationship between Workplace Stress and Employees Engagement

Experience	The Workplace Stress Scale	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
0 to 1 Years						
B	.016	.033 ^b	.001	-.070	.016	.902 ^c
t	.125					
Sig.	.902					
1 to 3 Years						
B	-.262	.215 ^b	.046	.033	3.405	.069 ^c
t	-1.845					
Sig.	.069					
3 to 6						
B	-.552	.452 ^b	.205	.187	11.835	.001 ^c
t	-3.440					
Sig.	.001					
6 to 9 Years						
B	-.195	.263 ^b	.069	.038	2.236	.145 ^c
t	-1.495					
Sig.	.145					
9 to 12 Years						
B	-.113	.106 ^b	.011	-.079	.125	.731 ^c
t	-.353					
Sig.	.731					
12 to 15 Years						
B	.066	.048 ^b	.002	-.069	.032	.861 ^c
t	.178					
Sig.	.861					
Above 15 Years						
B	.362	.300 ^b	.090	-.365	.198	.700 ^c
t	.444					
Sig.	.700					
<i>a. Dependent Variable: Work Engagement</i>						

In order to assess the impact of Workplace Stress on work Engagement, the study examined Beta coefficients with respect to experience. The results revealed statistical significant impact of Workplace Stress on work Engagement with respect to 3 to 6 years of experience (p=0.001), at 1% level of significance. Although statistical significant impact of Workplace Stress on work Engagement was not witnessed in other experience level. The above table revealing ANOVA results show that, independent variable does not have statistical significant impact on workplace stress in majority of the experiences, since its p-value is above the alpha level which is 0.01. Referring to the

beta coefficients, Workplace Stress is considered to be the strongest predictor of work engagement in case of 3-6 Years (B=-.552) of experience. It implies that increase in one unit of Workplace Stress leads to -55.2% (or -.552 units) decrease in workplace stress among the respondents having 3-6 Years of experience. Overall, it implies that Experience of the cabin crews does not moderate the relationship between Workplace Stress and work Engagement except in case of 3-6 years of experience. Therefore H8.e is rejected.

As majority of the sub hypotheses under H8 rejects null hypothesis leading to the acceptance of H8.a, H8.b and H8.c indicated that personal factors of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Workplace Stress and work Engagement. Therefore, H8 is accepted.

H9: The negative impact of workplace stress on work engagement is low in case of the cabin crews opted for high stress coping resources.

Table 6.60: Estimate Workplace Stress and Work Engagement between low and high stress coping resources

		Lower stress coping resources					Higher stress coping resources				
		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
ST	<--- IWH	.116	.070	1.656	.098	NS	.199	.047	4.203	***	HS
ST	<--- WH	.255	.071	3.577	***	HS	.342	.046	7.363	***	HS
ST	<--- ACE	.184	.071	2.587	.010	S	.070	.050	1.392	.164	NS
ST	<--- SI	.003	.074	.039	.969	NS	.107	.047	2.294	.022	S
WEF	<--- ST	-.324	.221	-1.466	.143	NS	-.166	.095	-1.746	.081	NS

Contemplating the multi-group effect results on the impact of stressor agents on workplace stress and the effect of workplace stress on work engagement, it is confirmed that with respect to higher stress coping strategy, the effect of irregular working hours on stress level (p=0.000, E=.199) is more compared to lower stress coping resources (p=.098, E=.116); similarly work hassles (p=0.000, E=.342) and social isolation (p=.022, E=.107) in case of higher coping resources strongly impacts workplace stress compared to work hassles (p=0.000, E=.255) and social isolation (p=.969, E=.003) in case of lower stress coping resources. But the effect of aircraft cabin environment on workplace stress (p= .010, E=.184) is comparatively higher in case of lower stress coping resources than higher coping resources (p= .164, E=.070). Finally, the negative impact of work place stress level on work engagement is more in lower stress coping resources (p=.143, E=-.324) compared to higher stress coping resources (p=.081,

E=-.166); it indicates that when the stressed cabin crew adopts high stress coping resources the negative impact of stress level on work engagement is comparatively less than the one who has adopted lower stress coping resources. Hence work engagement in case of higher coping resources is comparatively better than the one who has opted for lower stress coping resources. Hence it is proved that the negative impact of workplace stress on work engagement is low in case of the cabin crews opted for high stress coping resources. H9 is accepted.

H10: Stress Coping Resources of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Workplace Stress and work Engagement.

Table 6.61: Model Summary: Role of Stress Coping Resources in relationship between Workplace Stress and Work Engagement

Stress Coping Resources	The Workplace Stress Scale	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F	p
Lower						
B	-.324	.231 ^a	.054	.035	2.942	.092 ^b
t	-1.715					
Sig.	.092					
Higher						
B	-.165	.172 ^a	.029	.023	4.401	.038 ^b
t	-2.098					
Sig.	.038					
<i>a. Dependent Variable: Work Engagement</i>						

As per the result of ANOVA, it is evidenced that the model is significant for higher stress coping resources, as the p value is below 0.01. To measure the impact of independent variable (Workplace Stress) on dependent variable (work Engagement), Beta coefficient has been referred. Considering the beta coefficients of lower and higher stress coping resources, it can be inferred that Workplace Stress is the strongest predictor of work Engagement (B= -.165) in case of higher stress coping resources compared to lower stress coping resources (B=-.324). as a result of low coping strategy, one unit increase in workplace stress leads to -32.4% (or -0.324 units) decrease in work engagement; although, in case of high coping strategy, one unit increase in workplace stress leads to -16.5% (or -.165 unit) decrease in work engagement. This indicates that higher coping strategy improves the work engagement compared to lower coping strategy, as lower coping strategy badly impacts work engagement (by 32.4%) whereas higher coping strategy reduces its bad impact on work engagement as it contributes only by 16.5%. Hence Stress Coping Resources of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between the workplace stress and work engagement. Therefore, H10 is accepted.

H11: Stressor Agent directly affects the workplace stress which in turn impacts work engagement.

Figure 6.2: Path Analysis Stressor Agent its impact on workplace Stress leading to Work Engagement

Table 6.62: Regression Weights: Estimate Value

			S. Estimate	U. Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
ST	<---	IWH	.264	.182	.040	4.564	***	Highly Significant
ST	<---	WH	.478	.326	.040	8.256	***	Highly Significant
ST	<---	ACE	.117	.085	.042	2.020	.043	Significant
ST	<---	SI	.126	.087	.040	2.166	.030	Significant
WEF	<---	ST	-.167	-.217	.090	-2.402	.016	Significant

The above table 6.61 reflects positive influence of independent variable on the dependent variable. Regression weights have been calculated to estimate the direct effect of stressor agents on workplace stress of the cabin crews and also to assess the impact of workplace stress on work engagement.

The above table 6.62 depicts the effect of each stressor agents on workplace stress. Firstly irregular working hour shows direct positive influence on stress level at workplace (p=0.000, E=.182). Also Work Hassles (p=0.000, E=.326), Aircraft Cabin Environments (p=.043, E=.085), Social Isolation (p=0.000, E=.087) has positive significant effect on workplace stress. This indicates that escalation in irregular working hours, work hassles, air craft cabin environment and social isolation will result in more stress at workplace. Lastly the stress at workplace contributed by stressor agents also impacts work engagement. As per the tabular illustration stress at workplace negatively effects work engagement (p= 0.016, E= -.217), this negative impact is significant which indicates high workplace stress negatively impacts work engagement. Hence it is proved that stressor agents directly effects stress level at workplace which in turn impacts work engagement. Hence, H11 is accepted.

6.2 QUANTITATIVE ABCD ANALYSIS

6.2.1 INTRODUCTION

Individuals cannot be separated from distress in their lives, which ranges from work to society and family [317]. Employees may be stressed as a result of potential workplace stressors [318]. Potential conditions or stressors include organisational change [319], challenging personal and social relationships at work [320], managers' perceptions of allocation of resources fairness [321], bureaucracy, independence, tools and equipment, workload, role conflicts, work/home assimilation, job security, and career progression [322]. However, if the level of stress exceeds a certain threshold and cannot be controlled, the individual may experience psychological, physical, mental, or physiological problems [323]. These workplace pressures can result in negative emotions such as tension, anger, anxiety, irritation, or depressed mood [324-327]. Technology-induced stress, also known as techno-stress, has been identified as one of the latest workplace stressors [328-329]. Burnout, in particular, was discovered to be a significant predictor of a variety of physical, psychological, and occupational problems, such as job dissatisfaction, absenteeism, recently pensions, and job demands. Prolonged fatigue, cramps, gastrointestinal issues, and respiratory issues were among the physical issues [330]. The Coping Inventory for Stressful Situations measures the three characteristics of assignment, emotion, and evasion coping that is present for most theories of coping methods (CISS). For example, the interactional framework of stress, anxiety [331], and coping was established as a result of broadening the integrative approach of nervousness to include coping variables [332]. Coping strategies have included an individual's efforts to straight change dangerous situations as well as his attempts to alter his perception of them so that he does not feel threatened. It is obvious that there aren't just one (or even a few) effective coping mechanisms; rather, the fashion that works best will most likely be determined by the circumstances and type of stress encountered [333]. As a result, this chapter analyses the quantitative advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of stress coping mechanisms in improving employee well-being.

6.2.2 DETERMINANT ISSUES CONCERNING STRESS

In many organisations across industries, the place of work had become a high-stress environment. Employees were stressed out due to a variety of factors such as a heavy workload, strict deadlines, high targets, the nature of the work, a low level of job

satisfaction, long work hours, performance pressure, and so on. Interpersonal workplace conflicts, such as supervisor relationships and peer relationships, were also a source of anxiety [334]. Any circumstances, situations, or occurrences that make you feel stressed out are known as stressors [335]. Job autonomy, long hours [336], irregular schedules [39], biological work stresses due to noise and motion in the cabin [34], and illnesses and mental fatigue caused by jet lag are all characteristics of the cabin crew profession [138]. These special work characteristics result in work hassles to cabin crew

6.2.2.1 Irregular working hours:

Members of the cabin crew operate in a special setting with a variety of stressors [337] [338]. Employees who work unusual hours may experience a variety of physiological issues, which may lead to stress at work [339]. Long hours at work have been and continue to be a significant source of concern for working people's health and well-being [340]. 16-hour work days, six days a week, were relatively common a century ago [341]. The campaign for shorter working hours galvanised the labour movement in both the United States and Europe at the time to demand the 8-hour day [342]. A growing body of scientific literature demonstrates the effects of long and non-standard work time on a variety of health outcomes, including both intense reactions such as stress, fatigue, and sleep disorders; adverse health behaviour such as smoking and sedentary lifestyle; and more lengthy effects such as heart disease, gastrointestinal disorders, musculoskeletal problems (MSDs), and mental illness [343]. Because reducing overtime work time does not directly reduce psychogenic stress responses, getting enough sleep and eating regularly are important for workers' mental health. Furthermore, even if you work long hours, taking steps to maintain sleep duration and dinnertime regularity can help you avoid psychosomatic stress responses [344].

6.2.2.2 Work Hassles:

[345] defined hassle as "the irritating, annoying, distressing demands that to some extent characterize everyday transactions with the environment," which includes some annoying practical problems like losing publications or encountering traffic congestion, as well as some random occurrences like confronting bad weather, arguing with the others, getting frustrated and concerned about financial problems and relatives. Cabin crews face numerous challenges at work. According to [346], cabin crew have a lower

work condition and different working conditions in the highly competitive aviation industry due to lower fares, larger planes, so many passengers, and fewer crew members. The most important duties of cabin crew are safety and service [144]. As a result, in order to develop hassle preventative measures and coping strategies, aviation industry management must first understand the hassles in cabin crew work and life [21].

6.2.2.3 Social Isolation:

Social isolation is a multidimensional concept defined as an insufficient quantity and/or quality of interactions with other people, including interactions at the individual, group, and/or community levels [347-350]. Some measures of social isolation concentrate on external isolation, which refers to the frequency with which one interacts with others. Other measures concentrate on internal or regarded social isolation, which refers to the individual's feelings of loneliness, trust, and gratification with their relationships. This distinction is crucial because a person has the subjective experience of being isolated sometimes when they have frequent contact with other people, and conversely, they can have the subjective experience of not being isolated also when their contact with others is restricted [351]. This is a common problem in the aviation sector as well.

6.2.2.4 Burnout:

Burnout is a long-term reaction to chronic emotional workplace stressors. It has three dimensions: exhaustion, pessimism, and professional lack of effectiveness [351]. As per [352] observations of sentimental depletion in individuals working in a health-care agency gave rise to the term burnout. Burnout was defined as the emotional exhaustion and loss of enthusiasm that these people experienced. Exhaustion is the primary frequent complaint among those having to suffer from job burnout. Burnout's primary symptom and most visible manifestation is exhaustion. Job burnout symptoms include lost creative thinking, reduced job commitment, disassociation from various job elements, physical and emotional maladies, inappropriate attitudes toward self and clients, and a general sense of exhaustion [353]. Employees may unknowingly cause harm to themselves, work colleagues, clients, and/or the organisation as their burnout levels rise. Researchers discovered that burnout workers are more likely to be absent from work, have lower productivity, and leave the organisation [354-355].

All the above aspects results in stress leading to high pressure and low productivity. Hence adopting some effective measure to tackle this problem is very vital. The next section deals with the stress coping mechanism and its overview.

6.2.3 OVERVIEW ON STRESS COPING MECHANISM

Workplace stressors can disrupt a steady state, resulting in stress, and inability to cope with the situation can result in continued stress [356]. Coping has been defined as a reaction to an emotion, particularly unpleasant emotions [357]. To deal with stress, people use both problem-focused and emotion-focused coping strategies. While active problem-focused coping attempts to remove the stressor [358] through actions such as taking charge of the situation, brainstorming alternatives, and seeking help, emotion-focused coping encompasses all regulative efforts to reduce the psychological consequences of stressful events [359]. Avoidance strategies such as escapism, wishful thinking, and denial are examples of emotional coping strategies, as are efforts to acknowledge, understand, and show emotion [360]. Lazarus and colleagues identified two different types of coping in previous studies: 1. Problem-focused coping entails altering the environment to reduce stress; and 2. Emotional coping entails altering our response to or explanation of the situation [17]. Similarly, [361] proposed a three-step model of coping consisting of Active coping (e.g., trying to see the bright side; evaluating several alternatives); Active behavioural (e.g., talking with a friend, attempting to learn more about the situation); and Avoidance also created the 'Coping Strategy Indicator' by beginning with 161 coping responses. A three-factor solution was produced by principal-factor analysis: 1. problem-solving; 2. looking for support; and 3. Avoidance [362]. Finally, [363] classified coping strategies into three broad categories: 1. task-oriented, 2. emotionally-oriented, and 3. avoidance-oriented Based on these stress and coping mechanisms, the researcher identified several stress coping mechanisms, which are discussed in the following section.

6.2.4 ABCD ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK

The ABCD Analysis Framework, proposed by Aithal et al. (2016) [364], is used to analyse various "business models, company strategy, concept, idea, or business systems". A matrix is drawn in this method, and "advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages" are identified as well as "Critical Constituent Elements [365] has been noted." The ABCD analysis framework includes both individual and system features;

the efficiency of a concept or strategic plan can also be studied using ABCD analysis. It begins with a list of the benefits, constraints, and drawbacks of a concept, system, strategy, and so on [366]. Through factor and elementary analysis, it also allows for more detailed analysis by identifying influential issues and critical constituent elements. The ABCD analysis has progressed to the quantitative stage [366]. Because it considers other strategic methods of analysis such as "SWOC, Competitive Profile Matrix (CPM) analysis, EFE & IFE Matrices, BCG matrix, Porter's Five Forces Model, and PESTLE Analysis" [367-369], many research-based papers have been published based on this analysis framework. After conducting qualitative analysis, one could use the framework to list significant advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of each identified determinant issue. There are various studies which ponders on identifying the determinant issues using ABCD analysis such as Work from home [370], Black Ocean Strategy [371], Research Productivity [372], Six Thinking Hats [373], Online food delivery system [374], Wealth at the Base of the Pyramid [375], Well-being of Care takers [376], Nanotechnology as Green Technology [377], Private University System [378], Stage Model in Higher Education [379], Industrial Internship Programme [380], Systems & Technology [381], Multifactor Authentication Model [382], Fingerprint Biometric Attendance [383], institutional ranking system [384] and Choice Based Credit System [385] etc. It also introduces the concept of ABCD listing, which is a prerequisite for ABCD analysis [386]. This will provide a basic understanding and can be used as a scenario for ABCD analysis, also known as ABCD listing.

6.2.5 ABCD LISTING OF STRESS COPING MECHANISM

Numerous studies have been conducted on the ABCD analysis framework, which explains the various advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages, as well as quantitative analysis of the ABCD framework. Particularly there are various studies pertaining to ABCD listing which includes ABCD listing on New Research indices[387], International Business and its Environments' study [388], Six Thinking Hats Based Analysis[389], Innovation in B.Tech. Curriculum as B.Tech. (Hons) [390], Organizing the Unorganized Lifestyle Retailers [391], Green Education [392], Student Centric Learning Though Planned Hard work [393], Online Education and Higher Education System[394], Green Energy and Global Warming [395], Srinivas University B.Com Model In Corporate Auditing [396], Smart Library Models for Future Generations [397], Performance Evaluation of Dabur India Ltd [398], MUDRA [399],

Social Media [400], Electricity from microbial fuel cell in rural India [401], Online Pharmacy Model [402], Livestream as an Innovative Marketing Medium [403], Theory A [404], Furniture Manufacturing Companies [405], Grading In Higher Education For Competency Based Education System [406], Ideal Software [407], Virtualization [408], E-Campus Recruitment Process [409], Student Centric Curriculum Design and Implementation[410], Holistic Integrated Student Development Model & Service Delivery Model[411], Mobile Information Communication Technologies[412], Role of ICCT Underlying Technologies[413], Innovations & Business Opportunities[414], Srinivas University B. COM Model[415], Retrieval Time of Manual and Electronic Medical Records [416], Online E-Campus Interview Training [417], Block chain [418], new attitude-behaviour (AB) theory [419], Indian Pharmaceutical Sector [420] and Women Entrepreneurship in Food Processing Sector [421]. Before proceeding with the analysis, the researcher has listed the following Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages of stress coping mechanisms in order to better comprehend its problems and prospects:

ADVANTAGES:

- The stress coping mechanism provides purpose clarity, which leads to efficient work performance;
- It ensures employee confidence, which helps to increase passenger satisfaction.
- It gives them a sense of security and well-being.
- The use of stress coping mechanisms promotes creativity and mindfulness.

BENEFITS:

- Allows a guide to priorities the task and thus saves time.
- Adoption of stress coping resources may lead to reduced absenteeism and promotion.
- Employees benefit from this mechanism as well through network building.
- It allows for the simplification of complex tasks and the spread of positive vibes.

CONSTRAINTS:

- Using stress coping resources creates a rigid framework to follow, which may lead to unrealistic expectations.
- Religious conflicts may arise as a result of SCM involvement in religious practices.
- Emotional instability may contribute to a lack of SCM adoption.

DISADVANTAGES:

- Failure to adhere to SCM reduces alertness and performance.
- Employees may become less visible if they are fully involved in an SCM such as work life balance.
- It may lead to lack of focus on business goals.
- Incomplete tasks lead to feelings of guilt.

6.2.6 STRUCTURE OF ABCD FRAMEWORK

There are various studies conducted using quantitative ABCD analysis such as IEDRA Model [422], Education for Corporate Sustainability [423], Task Shifting [424], Online Food Delivery Services [425] used the below framework. Figure 6.3 depicts how the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages (ABCD) of each concept or strategy can be analysed by trying to identify determinant issues and key attributes and measuring the critical Constituent elements.

Figure 6.3: Factors affecting stress coping mechanism as per ABCD Analysis Framework [426]

6.2.7 KEY ATTRIBUTES AFFECTING STRESS COPING MECHANISM:

According to the previous discussion on stress coping mechanisms, stress coping mechanisms are concerned with changing the environment, displaying a positive side, seeking help from friends and family, avoiding the situation, solving problems, and taking care of one's health, among other things. The table shows key attributes based on the determinant issue pertaining to study, which is highly related to stress.

Table 6.63: Stress coping mechanism determinants and key characteristics

Sl. No.	Determinant Issues	Key Attributes
1	Irregular working hours	Precise Schedule, Checklist, Power Naps
2	Work Hassles	Job And Peer Management, Passenger Management, Personal Hassle Management
4	Social Isolation	Social Support, Spirituality, Relaxation
5	Burnout	Task Strategies, Better Sleep Quality, Positive Reappraisal

Source: Author

Table 6.63 shows various stress coping mechanisms for dealing with irregular working hours, work hassles, social isolation, and burnout. Each issue's key attributes have been identified.

An irregular work schedule has been linked to both moderate and severe sleep disturbances. The degree of emotion suppression at work was another factor associated with sleep disturbances. Employees were more likely to experience sleep disturbances if they were required to suppress emotion on a regular basis [427]. As a result, this problem can be solved by using Power Naps, a Precise Schedule, and a Checklist.

When it comes to work annoyances, there are three types: job annoyances caused by work standards, peer interaction annoyances caused by uneven work assignments, and passenger service annoyances caused by verbal and physical violence toward cabin crew, sexual harassment toward air crew, theft situations on night flights, and travelers concealing infectious diseases. Personal difficulties include work-family conflict and physical health issues [21]. As a result, it is manageable through Job and Peer Management, Passenger Management, and Personal Hassle Management.

Loneliness is frequently defined as the state of being alone or isolated from one's community or society. It is regarded as a dark and miserable feeling, as well as a risk factor for a variety of mental disorders such as depression, anxiety, emotional problem, chronic stress, insomnia, and even late-life dementia [428]. Loneliness is common among the elderly, leading to higher depression and suicide rates. Long periods of isolation in custodial care or quarantine for illness have been well-documented to have negative effects on mental well-being [429]. The cornerstone of public health is emotional readiness for solitude in times of crisis, as well as psycho-social well-being. As a result, social support, spirituality, and relaxation are critical for coping with stress.

The smothering of a fire or the extinguishing of a candle is referred to as burnout. It implies that a fire was once burning, but it cannot continue to burn brightly unless sufficient resources are replenished. Employees who are burnt out lose their ability to make intense contributions that have an impact over time. If they keep working, the end result will be more like smoldering, uneventful, and insignificant than burning [430]. All of this research has resulted in a conceptualization of job burnout as a psychological syndrome caused by chronic interpersonal stressors on the job. This response has three main dimensions: overwhelming exhaustion, feelings of cynicism and detachment from the job, and a sense of ineffectiveness and lack of accomplishment. The exhaustion component is the fundamental individual stress dimension of burnout. It refers to the sensation of being overburdened and depleted of one's emotional and physical resources [431]. Hence, Positive Reappraisal, Task Strategies, and Better Sleep Quality becomes vital to tackle this issue.

All of these mechanisms will be discussed further in the following section, along with their advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages.

6.2.8 FACTOR ANALYSIS OF STRESS COPING MECHANISM

Irregular working hours, Work Hassles, Social Isolation, and Burnout are all addressed by the stress coping mechanism. Table 6.64 shows the advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of the identified determinant issues and key attributes.

Table 6.64: Factor Analysis of Stress Coping Mechanism using ABCD Framework

Determinant Issues	Key Attributes	Advantages	Benefits	Constraints	Disadvantages
Irregular Working Hours	Precise Schedule	Purpose Clarity	Task Prioritization	Complexity	Pressure
	Checklist	Efficient	Time Saver	Rigid Frame	Low Quality Performance
	Power Naps	Quicker Reaction Time	Enhanced Cognitive Performance	Lack Of Free Time	Impaired Alertness And Performance
Work Hassles	Job And Peer Management	Improves Confidence	Team Efficiency	Poor Work Cohesion	Rigid Work Standards
	Passenger Management	Passenger Satisfaction	Promotion	Verbal And Physical Violence	High Emotional Labor
	Work-Life Balance	High Productivity	Less Absenteeism	Unrealistic Expectations	Make Employees Less Visible
Social Isolation	Social Support	Sense Of Security	Build Network	Lack Of Acceptance	Excessive Reliance

	Spirituality	Well Being	Motivation And Commitment	Religious Conflicts	Lack of Focus on Business Objectives
	Relaxation	Improved Focus	Better Decision Making	Work Load	Fear Of Losing Control
Burnout	Task Strategies	Reduces Mistakes	Simplification Of Complex Task	Poor Goal Setting	Incomplete Task Causes Guilty Feeling
	Better Sleep Quality	Creativity	Uplifts Mood	Task Deadlines	Laziness And Less Productivity
	Positive Reappraisal	Mindfulness And More Tolerable	Spread Of Positive Vibes	Instability Of Emotions	Exploitation By Over Workload

Source: Author

As demonstrated above in table 6.64 various stress coping mechanism or key attributes to tackle the determinant issues has been discussed along with its advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages which is further explained below.

In order to overcome the stress as a result of irregular working hours, one can adopt précises schedule which helps an individual to gain clarity on their purpose which further helps them to prioritise their task. On contrary having a precise schedule may also lead to much complexity and increase the pressure to complete the entire pre-planned task. Furthermore, the second coping mechanism can prepare checklist which has its own advantages and benefits such as efficient utilization of time thereby reducing the time and saving time for relaxation. In some cases, preparing checklist may create a rigid framework leading to their low-quality performance. As various literatures have shown that irregular working hour's causes sleep disturbance, taking a power nap also can be an effective stress coping mechanism which increases quicker reaction time which further enhances cognitive performance. On contrary taking a power nap also may have a negative consequence leading to impaired alertness and performance, apart from that the employees may not get a sufficient time to sleep.

Second major component of stress is resulted due to work hassles which can be coped up through Job and Peer Management where one can build confidence and further improves team efficiency. It has certain constraints if the work is not distributed according to the ability of the individual which further entails the employers to make the work standards even more rigid. Similarly, passenger management is also an important mechanism through which passenger satisfaction can be ensured leading to

their growth through promotion. This strategy also has certain loopholes due to uncontrollable passenger behaviour in the form of verbal and physical violence which results into high emotional labour. Furthermore, work hassles also can be tackled through work life balance which entails high productivity and less absenteeism. But at the same time, it creates unrealistic expectations making employees less visible in the organisation.

Third major determinant issue causing stress includes social isolation due to high workload. With this regard social support plays an active role in enhancing sense of security among the employees which helps them to build wide network. Sometimes lack of acceptance among the society is a constraint in this matter. Moreover, social support may again contribute to excessive reliance on others which is a disadvantage of this mechanism. Social isolation can also be tackled through spirituality leading to wellbeing which further motivates the employees but it may create religious conflict in the organisation. This conflict will result in lack of focus on business objectives. Relaxation through exercise can also be considered as one of stress coping mechanism which improves individual focus which leads to better decision making. But due to workload this is not easy to practice, at the same time this has disadvantage of losing control.

Burnout being another major contributor of stress can be tackled through task strategies which reduce future mistakes and simplify the task. Sometimes poor goal setting does not let the accomplishment of task strategy which leads to guilty feeling. Stress can also be reduced through better quality of sleep which enhances creativity and uplifts the mood. Completing achieving the task on time is another constraint for a better quality of sleep. But more sleeping habit may cause laziness and less productivity. Lastly burnout can be reduced using positive reappraisal which improves mindfulness, tolerance and spread of positive vibes. As a human being there is instability of emotions practicing positive reappraisal by the employees. But more positive reappraisal may also allow others to take disadvantage by exploiting through overload.

These are the various advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages of stress coping mechanism which was categorized into several actors. As a major step to perform ABCD analysis, elementary analysis has been undertaken which identifies the critical constituent elements of each attribute, which is further discussed below.

6.2.9 ELEMENTARY ANALYSIS BASED ON CRITICAL CONSTITUENT ELEMENTS

The factors affecting irregular working hours, work hassles, social isolation, and burnout issues are identified using the ABCD analysis framework for Stress Coping Mechanism. The CCEs of these factors are tabulated in tables 3-6 under the four constructs - advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of the ABCD technique.

Table 6.65: Advantageous factors affecting the determinant issues of stress coping mechanism and its critical constituent elements

Determinant Issues	Key Attributes	Advantageous Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Element
Irregular Working Hours	Precise Schedule	Purpose Clarity	Goal Setting
	Checklist	Efficient	Well Organized
	Power Naps	Quicker Reaction Time	Responsive
Work Hassles	Job And Peer Management	Improves Confidence	Skills, Expertise And Capabilities
	Passenger Management	Passenger Satisfaction	Sustainability And Profitability
	Work-Life Balance	High Productivity	Efficiency
Social Isolation	Social Support	Sense Of Security	Safety
	Spirituality	Well-Being	High Performance
	Relaxation	Improved Focus	High Quality Work
Burnout	Task Strategies	Reduces Mistakes	Accurate Service Delivery
	Better Sleep Quality	Creativity	High Problem-Solving Ability
	Positive Reappraisal	Mindfulness And More Tolerable	Enhanced Engagement

Source: Author

Table 6.65 exhibits advantageous factors effecting determinant issue has been studied along with its critical constituent element. As per the elementary analysis of advantageous factors affecting irregular working hour, determining a precise schedule is advantageous in setting a purpose clarity which is further essential to determining the long-term goals for the employees. Further more efficient working as advantageous factor of checklist makes an employee well organised. Furthermore, to tackle irregular working hour power nap is quite essential as it gives the advantage of quick reaction time which further enhances responsive behaviour.

Secondly the elementary analysis of advantageous factors affecting Work Hassles showed, Job and Peer Management is advantageous in Improving Confidence which is further essential to build Skills, Expertise and Capabilities among the employees. Furthermore, Passenger Satisfaction as advantageous factor of Passenger Management

enhances Sustainability and Profitability in the organisation. Likewise, to ensure High Productivity Work-Life Balance is quite essential as it gives the advantage of higher efficiency in the organisation.

As per the elementary analysis of advantageous factors affecting Social Isolation, enabling Social Support is advantageous in gaining Sense of Security which is further essential to determine the employees Safety. Furthermore, Well-being of employees as advantageous factor of Spirituality makes an employee's highly performing. Also, Relaxation is quite essential as it gives the advantage of Improved Focus which further enhances High Quality Work.

Lastly the elementary analysis of advantageous factors affecting Burnout showed, Task Strategies is advantageous in Reducing Mistakes which is further essential to deliver accurate service. Furthermore, Creativity as advantageous factor of Better Sleep Quality enhances High Problem-Solving Ability among employees. Moreover, to ensure Mindfulness and More tolerance, Positive Reappraisal is quite essential as it gives the advantage of Enhanced Engagement in the organisation.

Table 6.66: Benefit factors affecting the determinant issues of stress coping mechanism and its critical constituent elements

Determinant Issues	Key Attributes	Beneficial Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Element
Irregular Working Hours	Precise Schedule	Task Prioritization	Avoid Procrastination
	Checklist	Time Saver	New Opportunities
	Power Naps	Enhanced Cognitive Performance	Remember Tasks
Work Hassles	Job And Peer Management	Team Efficiency	Reduction In Individual Pressure
	Passenger Management	Promotion	Facilities And Privileges
	Work-Life Balance	Less Absenteeism	Reliability And Trustworthiness
Social Isolation	Social Support	Build Network	Recognition
	Spirituality	Motivation And Commitment	Loyalty And Stability
	Relaxation	Better Decision Making	Favorable Outcome
Burnout	Task Strategies	Simplification Of Complex Task	Easier And Faster Completion Of Work
	Better Sleep Quality	Uplifts Mood	Commitment
	Positive Reappraisal	Spread Of Positive Vibes	Employee Retention

Source: Author

Table 6.66 exhibits benefiting factors effecting determinant issue has been studied along with its critical constituent element. As per the elementary analysis of benefiting factors affecting irregular working hour, determining a precise schedule is benefiting in Task Prioritization which is further essential to Avoid Procrastination. Furthermore, Time Saver as benefiting factor of Checklist makes an employee avail New Opportunities. Moreover, to tackle irregular working hour, power nap is quite essential as it gives the benefit of Enhanced Cognitive Performance which further enhances Remembering Tasks.

Secondly the elementary analysis of benefiting factors affecting Work Hassles showed, Job and Peer Management is advantageous in Team Efficiency which is further essential to Reduce Individual Pressure among the employees. Additionally, Promotion as benefiting factor of Passenger Management enhances more Facilities and Privileges in the organisation. Moreover, to ensure Less Absenteeism, Work-Life Balance is quite essential as it gives the benefit of Reliability and Trustworthiness among employees.

As per the elementary analysis of benefiting factors affecting Social Isolation, enabling Social Support is benefiting to Build Network which is further essential to gain Recognition. Still, Motivation and Commitment among employees is benefiting factor of Spirituality which makes an employee enhance Loyalty and Stability. Moreover, Relaxation is quite essential as it gives the benefiting factor of Better Decision Making which further enhances Favourable Outcome.

Lastly the elementary analysis of benefiting factors affecting Burnout showed, Task Strategies is advantageous in Simplification of Complex Task which is further essential for Easier and Faster Completion of Work. Besides, Uplifts Mood as benefiting factor of Better Sleep Quality enhances High Commitment among employees. Moreover, to ensure Spread of Positive Vibes, Positive Reappraisal is quite essential as it gives the benefit of Employee Retention in the organisation.

Table 6.67: Constraint factors affecting the determinant issues of stress coping mechanism and its critical constituent elements

Determinant Issues	Key Attributes	Constraints Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Element
Irregular Working Hours	Precise Schedule	Complexity	Lack of Clarity
	Checklist	Rigid Frame	Confusion
	Power Naps	Lack of Free Time	Lack of Focus
Work Hassles	Job And Peer Management	Poor Work Cohesion	Conflicts
	Passenger Management	Verbal And Physical Violence	Increased Turnover
	Work-Life Balance	Unrealistic Expectations	Disappointment
Social Isolation	Social Support	Lack of Acceptance	Violence
	Spirituality	Religious Conflicts	Hatred
	Relaxation	Work Load	Stress
Burnout	Task Strategies	Poor Goal Setting	Low Utilization of Action and Energy
	Better Sleep Quality	Task Deadlines	Low Creativity
	Positive Reappraisal	Instability Of Emotions	Anxiety

Source: Author

Table 6.67 exhibits Constraint factors effecting determinant issue has been studied along with its critical constituent element. As per the elementary analysis of Constraint factors affecting irregular working hour, Complexity is Constraint in determining a precise schedule which further leads to Lack of Clarity. Also, Rigid Frame as Constraint factor of Checklist makes an employee more Confused. Moreover, Lack of Free Time is the Constraint of power nap which leads to Lack of Focus.

Secondly the elementary analysis of Constraint factors affecting Work Hassles showed, Poor Work Cohesion is Constraint in Job and Peer Management which leads to Conflicts among the employees. Additionally, Verbal and Physical Violence as Constraint factor of Passenger Management leading to Increased Turnover in the organisation. Moreover, Unrealistic Expectations acts as a constraint in maintaining Work-Life Balance which leads to Disappointment.

As per the elementary analysis of Constraint factors affecting Social Isolation, disadvantageous factor of social support is Lack of Acceptance which further leads to Violence. Besides, Religious Conflicts is Constraint factor of Spirituality which spreads hatred. Moreover, Work Load acts as a Constraint to Relaxation which leads to Stress.

Lastly the elementary analysis of Constraint factors affecting Burnout showed, Poor Goal Setting is Constraint in Task Strategies which further leads to Low Utilization of Action and Energy. Besides, Task Deadlines as Constraint factor of Better Sleep Quality leading to Low Creativity among employees. Moreover, to ensure Positive Reappraisal, Instability of Emotions is Constraint which again leads to Anxiety.

Table 6.68: Disadvantageous factors affecting the determinant issues of stress coping mechanism and its critical constituent elements

Determinant Issues	Key Attributes	Disadvantageous Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Element
Irregular Working Hours	Precise Schedule	Pressure	Mental Distress
	Checklist	Low Quality Performance	Job Dissatisfaction
	Power Naps	Impaired Alertness and Performance	Ignorance
Work Hassles	Job And Peer Management	Rigid Work Standards	Lack Of Involvement
	Passenger Management	High Emotional Labor	Lack Of Job Performance
	Work-Life Balance	Make Employees Less Visible	Loss Of Productivity
Social Isolation	Social Support	Excessive Reliance	Low Self-Esteem
	Spirituality	Lack Of Focus on Business Objectives	Low Success Rate
	Relaxation	Fear of Losing Control	Job Loss
Burnout	Task Strategies	Incomplete Task Causes Guilty Feeling	Low Morale
	Better Sleep Quality	Laziness and Less Productivity	Low Customer Service Quality
	Positive Reappraisal	Exploitation By Over Workload	Lack of Transparency

Source: Author

Table 6.68 exhibits Disadvantageous factors effecting determinant issue has been studied along with its critical constituent element. As per the elementary analysis of Disadvantageous factors affecting irregular working hour, Pressure is Disadvantageous factor determining a precise schedule which further leads to Mental Distress. Moreover, Low Quality Performance as Disadvantage factor of Checklist creates Job Dissatisfaction among employees. Moreover, Impaired Alertness and Performance is the Disadvantage of power nap which in turn leads to Ignorance.

Secondly the elementary analysis of Disadvantageous factors affecting Work Hassles showed, Rigid Work Standards is a Disadvantage in Job and Peer Management which leads to Lack of Involvement among the employees. Besides, High Emotional Labor as Disadvantageous factor of Passenger Management leading to Lack Of Job Performance in the organisation. Moreover, Making Employees Less Visible acts as a Disadvantageous factor by encouraging Work-Life Balance which leads to Loss of Productivity.

As per the elementary analysis of disadvantageous factors affecting Social Isolation, disadvantageous factor of social support is Excessive Reliance which further leads to Low Self-Esteem. Still, Lack of Focus on Business Objectives is disadvantageous factor of Spirituality which leads to Low Success Rate. Moreover, Fear of Losing Control acts as a disadvantageous factor of Relaxation which leads to Job Loss.

Lastly the elementary analysis of Disadvantageous factors affecting Burnout showed, Incomplete Task Causing Guilty Feeling is disadvantageous factor in Task Strategies which further leads to Low Morale. Additionally, Laziness and Less Productivity as Disadvantageous factor of Better Sleep Quality leading to Low Customer Service Quality among employees. Moreover, in case of Positive Reappraisal, Exploitation by over Workload is a Disadvantage which again leads to Lack of Transparency.

6.2.10 QUANTITATIVE CRITICAL CONSTITUENT ELEMENT OF STRESS COPING MECHANISM AS PER ABCD ANALYSIS

The CCE for every key attribute for stress coping mechanism under its determinant issues as per the ABCD analysis framework construct are identified below and shown in tables 7.7 to 7.10.

The weights assigned to each CCE are determined by the focus group. The following is a ranking for different weights:

Agree [3];
Neutral [2];
Disagree [1].

Quantitative analysis of advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantageous factors of stress coping mechanism has shown the following result

The table below displays the advantageous elements of stress coping mechanisms and their important constituent element as identified by focus groups.

Table 6.69: Total mean score of Advantageous factors influencing stress coping mechanisms and their CCEs

Determinant Issues	Key Attributes	Advantages	Critical Constituent Element	Key Attributes (Total Score)	Determinant Issues (Total Score)	Total Mean Score
Irregular Working Hours	Precise Schedule	Purpose Clarity	Goal Setting	45	133	98.066
	Checklist	Efficient	Well Organized	44		
	Power Naps	Quicker Reaction Time	Responsive	44		
Work Hassles	Job And Peer Management	Improves Confidence	Skills, Expertise and Capabilities	43	127	
	Passenger Management	Passenger Satisfaction	Sustainability and Profitability	45		
	Work-Life Balance	High Productivity	Efficiency	39		
Social Isolation	Social Support	Sense Of Security	Safety	45	133	
	Spirituality	Well Being	High Performance	43		
	Relaxation	Improved Focus	High Quality Work	45		
Burnout	Task Strategies	Reduces Mistakes	Accurate Service Delivery	45	129	
	Better Sleep Quality	Creativity	High Problem-Solving Ability	40		
	Positive Reappraisal	Mindfulness and More Tolerable	Enhanced Engagement	44		

Source: Author

Table 6.69 demonstrated the quantitative analysis of advantageous factors of stress coping mechanism by tackling the determinant issues. The quantitative analysis showed the effectiveness of stress coping mechanism for Irregular Working Hours (133) and Social Isolation (133) is high compared to Burnout (129) followed by Work Hassles (127). It demonstrates that stress coping mechanism is very effective in preventing stress occurring due to irregular working hours and social isolation. Overall, the total mean score derived from the analysis of quantitative advantageous factor is 98.066.

Table 6.70: Total mean score of benefit factors influencing stress coping mechanisms and their CCEs

Determinant Issues	Key Attributes	Benefits	Critical Constituent Element	Key Attributes (Total Score)	Determinant Issues (Total Score)	Total Mean Score
Irregular Working Hours	Precise Schedule	Task Prioritization	Avoid Procrastination	40	120	81.46
	Checklist	Time Saver	New Opportunities	42		
	Power Naps	Enhanced Cognitive Performance	Remember Tasks	38		
Work Hassles	Job And Peer Management	Team Efficiency	Reduction In Individual Pressure	41	118	
	Passenger Management	Promotion	Facilities And Privileges	33		
	Work-Life Balance	Less Absenteeism	Reliability And Trustworthiness	44		
Social Isolation	Social Support	Build Network	Recognition	43	122	
	Spirituality	Motivation And Commitment	Loyalty And Stability	36		
	Relaxation	Better Decision Making	Favorable Outcome	43		
Burnout	Task Strategies	Simplification Of Complex Task	Easier And Faster Completion Of Work	33	109	
	Better Sleep Quality	Uplifts Mood	Commitment	42		
	Positive Reappraisal	Spread Of Positive Vibes	Employee Retention	34		

Source: Author

Table 6.70 demonstrated the quantitative analysis of benefiting factors of stress coping mechanism by tackling the determinant issues. The quantitative analysis showed the effectiveness of stress coping mechanism for Social Isolation (122) and Irregular Working Hours (120) is high compared to Work Hassles (118) followed by Burnout (109). It demonstrates that stress coping mechanism is very much benefiting in preventing stress occurring due to Social Isolation and Irregular Working Hours. Overall, the total mean score derived from the analysis of quantitative benefiting factor is 81.46.

Table 6.71: Total mean score of constraint factors influencing stress coping mechanisms and their CCEs

Determinant Issues	Key Attributes	Constraints	Critical Constituent Element	Key Attributes (Total Score)	Determinant Issues (Total Score)	Total Mean Score
Irregular Working Hours	Precise Schedule	Complexity	Lack Of Clarity	42	99	69.73
	Checklist	Rigid Frame	Confusion	30		
	Power Naps	Lack of Free Time	Lack Of Focus	27		
Work Hassles	Job And Peer Management	Poor Work Cohesion	Conflicts	39	91	
	Passenger Management	Verbal And Physical Violence	Increased Turnover	27		
	Work-Life Balance	Unrealistic Expectations	Disappointment	25		
Social Isolation	Social Support	Lack Of Acceptance	Violence	26	92	
	Spirituality	Religious Conflicts	Hatred	34		
	Relaxation	Work Load	Stress	32		
Burnout	Task Strategies	Poor Goal Setting	Low Utilization of Action and Energy	34	107	
	Better Sleep Quality	Task Deadlines	Low Creativity	29		
	Positive Reappraisal	Instability Of Emotions	Anxiety	44		

Source: Author

Table 6.71 demonstrated the quantitative analysis of constraints factors of stress coping mechanism in its implementation. The quantitative analysis showed highest constraints in the implementation of stress coping mechanism is in the case of Burnout (107) and Irregular Working Hours (99) compared to Social Isolation (92) followed by Work Hassles (91). It demonstrates that stress coping mechanism has highest constraints in the implementation of stress coping mechanism in the case of Burnout and Irregular Working Hours. Overall, the total mean score derived from the analysis of quantitative constraint factor is 69.73.

Table 6.72: Total mean score of disadvantageous factors influencing stress coping mechanisms and their CCEs

Determinant Issues	Key Attributes	Advantages	Critical Constituent Element	Key Attributes (Total Score)	Determinant Issues (Total Score)	Total Mean Score
Irregular Working Hours	Precise Schedule	Pressure	Mental Distress	28	86	57.4
	Checklist	Low Quality Performance	Job Dissatisfaction	27		
	Power Naps	Impaired Alertness and Performance	Ignorance	31		
Work Hassles	Job And Peer Management	Rigid Work Standards	Lack Of Involvement	29	86	
	Passenger Management	High Emotional Labor	Lack Of Job Performance	29		
	Work-Life Balance	Make Employees Less Visible	Loss Of Productivity	28		
Social Isolation	Social Support	Excessive Reliance	Low Self-Esteem	26	81	
	Spirituality	Lack Of Focus on Business Objectives	Low Success Rate	26		
	Relaxation	Fear Of Losing Control	Job Loss	29		
Burnout	Task Strategies	Incomplete Task Causes Guilty Feeling	Low Morale	28	86	
	Better Sleep Quality	Laziness and Less Productivity	Low Customer Service Quality	33		
	Positive Reappraisal	Exploitation By Over Workload	Lack of Transparency	25		

Source: Author

Table 6.72 demonstrated the quantitative analysis of disadvantageous factors of stress coping mechanism in its implementation. The quantitative analysis showed highest disadvantage in the implementation of stress coping mechanism is in the case of Irregular Working Hours (86) Work Hassles (86) and Burnout (86) compared to Social Isolation (81). It demonstrates that stress coping mechanism has highest disadvantages in the implementation of stress coping mechanism in the case of Irregular Working Hours (86) Work Hassles (86) and Burnout (86). Overall, the total mean score derived from the analysis of quantitative disadvantageous factor is 57.4.

From the overall quantitative analysis of advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages of stress coping mechanism, it is witnessed that stress coping mechanism has more advantages (98.066) and benefits (81.46) compared to constraints (69.73) and disadvantages (57.4). Hence stress coping mechanism can be proved to be an effective measure to cope up with stress at workplace. This result is further demonstrated with the graphical representation which is explained below;

6.2.11 GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF FACTORS AFFECTING STRESS COPING MECHANISM

Figure 6.4: Graphical Representation of ABCD

Figure 6.4 depicted the total mean score of stress coping mechanism advantage, benefits, constraints, and disadvantage factors using the ABCD framework. According to the mean score, stress coping mechanism has more advantages (MS=98.06) than benefits (MS=81.46), followed by constraints (MS=69.73). Finally, it was discovered that stress coping mechanism has the fewest disadvantages (57.4), so it can be recommended that stress coping mechanism is an effective tool for increasing employee productivity.

6.2.12 CONCLUSION

The purpose of this chapter was to assess the impact of various factors on the adoption of stress coping mechanisms by examining their advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages. Despite evaluating various determinant issues, the study also considered critical constituent elements of stress coping mechanisms. As a result of the analysis, researchers strongly recommend workplace stress coping mechanisms because the advantages and benefits of this mechanism outweigh the constraints and disadvantages. Furthermore, this analysis not only allows for a more in-depth understanding of the various factors influencing stress coping mechanisms, but it also points the way toward developing measurement scales for stress coping mechanisms in future research. As a result, this study serves as a guide for academics, researchers, psychiatrists, and HR policymakers seeking to improve employee productivity.

CHAPTER-VII

SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

7.1 INTRODUCTION

The main intention of present research was to assess the impact of various stressor agents on workplace stress among cabin crews which again impacts work engagement. As workplace stress has negative working engagement as per the previous studies, this study intended to identify the role of stress coping resources between workplace stress and work engagement. Hence stress coping resources acted as a mediator in the study to measure its impact on work engagement. This chapter reveals in-depth findings of all the tests, analysis adopted to support the research objectives along with various suggestions provided to cabin crews and management. Furthermore, the chapter also addresses direction for future research by further pondering on its implications.

In this chapter finding section is subdivided into 12 parts consisting of sample profile summary, agreement level on irregular working hours, work hassles, aircraft cabin environment, social isolation, workplace stress and work engagement; also findings concerning emotional labour, stress coping resources inventory have been discussed. Lastly but importantly this chapter demonstrates summarized findings on Correlation, hypothesis testing and path model.

7.2 SAMPLE PROFILE

The sample profile of the study includes age, gender, marital status, current function, experience, changes in lifestyle of the respondents. The profile also includes maximum number of consecutive days of work, maximum number of consecutive nights of work done by the respondents. At last, this section also discussed on the average days off per month in their job.

1. The study revealed that 51.7% of the Cabin crews belong to the age category of 21-29 years; 37.3% of the cabin crew belongs to the age category of 31-39 and 10.9% of them belong to 40 and above age category.
2. 82.6 % of the respondents are female against 17.4% of male respondents. It may be due to the demography of the job and may be more Cabin crew job will be dominated by women.
3. Marital status of the respondents reveals that most (77.1%) of the crew members are unmarried and 22.9% of the crew members are married. It may be due to the tendency of preferring a cabin crew job as a bachelor or bachelorette.

4. The study also demonstrated that, out of the total respondents 40.8% of respondents are in the senior crew position against the 27.4% of junior crew members. The percentage of In-flight managers' position is 22.9%. There are 6% of the respondents with the position of trainers and 3% of the respondents with the position of cabin Service Director.
5. As far as the year of experience is concerned 35.8% of the respondents are having 1 to 3 years of experience as the cabin crew/flight attendant; 23.9% of them are having 3-6 years of experience whereas 15.9% of respondent have 6 to 9 years of working experience.
6. Changes in lifestyle of the respondents after they joined as the crew members showed that 29.9% of the respondents stated that they face frequent crossing of the time zones and difficult tasks in their work and 17.4% of them stated it is Difficult for them to follow regular workout routine and 16.4% of respondents feels they Spend longer periods of time away from home which is affecting their life.
7. 60% of respondents (approximately 61.7%) work for 7 days or more consecutively.
8. 39.3 % of the respondents work for three or four night continuously against 36.3% of respondents with five nights or more work on continues basis.
9. 46.8 % of cabin crews tend to get 5-10 days of days off per month on an average; 38.8% of them get an average days off 10 or more days per month.

7.3 AGREEMENT LEVEL ON STRESSOR AGENT FACTORS

7.3.1 AGREEMENT LEVEL ON IRREGULAR WORKING HOURS

Irregular working hour was measured using 12 indicators, in which mean values ranged between 2.1592 to 3.1592. Working for long day not causing to fatigue and exhaustion during the flight was highly disagreed statement by the respondents with the mean value of 3.1592; the least disagreed statement was lack of job prediction and last minute deadlines as it indicates the lowest mean value of 2.1592. The percentage analysis findings are discussed below;

1. 39.3% of the respondents responded strongly disagreed for the statement “job events are clearly predictable, they are not subject to last-minute deadlines”.
2. Not spending long time at work and outside relationships are not suffering due to their work disagreed by 51.7% of the respondents.
3. 49.3% of the respondents showed neutralized opinion on working for long day making them fatigued/exhausted during the flight.

4. 36.3% of the respondents responded with “disagree” for the statement of not feeling night flights or a series of night flights as serious contributors to fatigue.
5. 32.3% of the respondents opined that early morning departures as problematic and contributing to fatigue.
6. Disagreement level was shown for not feeling the need for recovery after work by 36.3% of the respondents.
7. As far as getting sufficient sleep after the work is considered 31.3% of the people showed disagreement level.
8. 34.3% of the cabin crews disagreed on being unfit for duty due to fatigue/exhaustion.
9. 32.8% of the respondents perceived that they make a mistake in the flight due to fatigue/exhaustion.
10. 36.3% disagree for the statement “I have not remarked (out loud or to myself) about how tired I was, but proceeded to go on the flight anyway.”
11. As the matter of getting enough time to rest due to long working hours is considered 31.3% of respondents disagreed for this statement.
12. 33.3% of the cabin crews opined that Airlines policies have caused them extra time/pressure to complete job.

7.3.2 AGREEMENT LEVEL ON WORK HASSLES

The construct “work hassles” was measured using 14 indicators, in which the mean values ranged between 2.1891 to 3.1045. As per the descriptive statistics, the statement on “unacceptable behaviour of passengers” (M=3.1045), “disobeying the instructions of crew by passengers” (M=2.7065), “the presence of gap between works standards and practical operations in a flight” (M=2.7015) makes them feel stressed was agreed to the highest extent, as the mean values in these cases found to be higher compared to other indicators. Communication issues with Pilots being a cause of stress was a least agreed statement (M=2.1891).

1. 35.3% of the respondents strongly agree that communication issue with pilot during the flight has caused stress in them.
2. 48.3% of the respondents agreed that stress has been caused due to communication with the passengers in flight.
3. 45.3% of the respondents prefers to be neutral on stress due to the unacceptable behaviour (smoking when prohibited or Drunk passengers) of passengers.

4. On work pressure due to difference in work standard and actual operation, 33.8% of them have given neutral response.
5. 31.3% of the cabin crews agree that they get stressed as they are unable to take planned vacation due to irregular work schedule.
6. 31.8% of the cabin crews agree that due to different cultures there is presence of poor work cohesion among cabin crew and this hassle makes them stressed during a flight.
7. 31.8% of crew members prefer to be neutral about unexpected emergency on a flight, and whenever there is a trouble in managing this situation and that makes the crew member feel exhausted.
8. 32.3% of the crew members agree that during the flight due to poor work cohesion between cockpit crew and cabin crew affects flight safety they get stressed.
9. Antisocial behaviour in the flight causing stress was agreed by 33.8% of the respondents.
10. Stress due to verbal and physical violence by the passengers found to be neutral among 30.3% of respondents.
11. As far as stress due to verbal threats to other passengers is concerned most (33.3%) of the respondents showed agreement level.
12. 37.3% of the respondents are neutral about stress due to disobeying the instructions of crew by passengers.
13. As far as negative impact of job on the health of the respondents is concerned most (31.8%) of the respondents agree to it.
14. 32.8% of the cabin crews have neutralized and agreed opinion on hassles due to jet lag and its effect on sleeping pattern.

7.3.3 AGREEMENT LEVEL ON AIRCRAFT CABIN ENVIRONMENT

The construct “aircraft cabin environment” was measured using 13 indicators, in which the mean values ranged between 2.4527 to 3.2836. As per the descriptive statistics, the statement on “anxiety regarding pre-flight checks” (M=3.2836), “stressed due to the scheduling and rostering” (M=3.0199), “work load/time pressure/deadlines” (M=3.0199), irregular flight duty timings (M=2.9204) was agreed to the highest extent, as the mean values in these cases found to be higher compared to other indicators. “Due to delay disruptive passengers have hurt me emotionally” was the least agreed statement (M=2.4527).

1. 36.8% of the cabin crews agree that they are bothered due to flight delays and being hurt by disruptive passengers.
2. 34.8% of them have neutralized opinion on being stressed due to the scheduling and rostering.
3. Neutralized opinion was given for being anxious regarding pre-flight checks by 36.3% of the respondents.
4. Being stressed over work load/time pressure/deadlines was also given neutralized opinion by 34.8% of the respondents.
5. For the statement related to interpersonal problems with other cabin crew/ flight crew, 38.8% of the respondents preferred to agree it.
6. 33.3% of responded agreed that lack of opportunities and potential advancement in the job has caused them stress.
7. As far as the respondents opinion on there is lack of encouragement and support by the management and superiors is concerned, most of the (34.8%) of the respondents preferred to be neutral.
8. 33.8% of the respondents responded with “agree” opinion for the statement on monotonous work involving underutilization of skills.
9. 35.8% of the cabin crews preferred to say “neutral” about irregular flight duty timings.
10. 32.8% of the cabin crews agreed that ‘experience variability in work load and uneven distribution of work leads to stress.
11. 34.3% of them neutralized their opinion on the kind of experiences such as harassment by passengers or the crew either sexual/nonsexual such as looking/ touching/comments etc. being a reason for stress.
12. 36.3% of respondents expressed “neutral” opinion about potential for general transmission of infections during flights.
13. 36.3% of the cabin crew agrees that they get Headache due to Aircraft cabin pressure.

7.3.4 AGREEMENT LEVEL ON SOCIAL ISOLATION

The construct “social isolation” was measured using 9 indicators, in which the mean values ranged between 2.5075 to 3.4677. As per the descriptive statistics, the statement on “interference of work time with family and social life” (M=3.4677), “no time for family and friends due to wide range of work activities” (M=3.0448), “adverse impact

of job on their family and social life” (M=2.9950), no time for family functions (M=2.9154) was agreed to the highest extent, as the mean values in these cases found to be higher compared to other indicators.

1. 36.8% of the cabin crews have neutral opinion on Work responsibilities having impacted on their personal, family, and social lives.
2. 33.3% of the respondents agreed that this job has an adverse influence on their family and social life.
3. 36.8% of them have given neutral opinion on interferes of work time with family and social life; 29.9% of them have agreed to it.
4. As far as not seems to have enough time for family or friends due to wide range of activities in work is considered most (31.8%) of they show neutral perception.
5. 30.3% of the respondent prefers to opt for neutral and agreed perception each on experience in managing a balance with Work-Rest-Social life.
6. 37.8% of crew members showed neutral perception on no time for many interests/hobbies outside of work.
7. Majority of the respondents (31.3%) agree that they don't have time to attend family function after joining this job.
8. As far as statement related to 'family members often say that, I do not have time to be with them whenever it is required' is considered most of the (30.3%) of the respondents preferred to be neutral.
9. 34.3% of them have neutralized perception on them wanting to spend some time with family members/friends but due to this work, not able to spare.

7.4 AGREEMENT LEVEL ON WORKPLACE STRESS, STRESS COPING RESOURCES INVENTORY AND WORK ENGAGEMENT

7.4.1 AGREEMENT LEVEL ON WORKPLACE STRESS

To measure the agreement level on workplace stress, Respondents were asked to respond with their agreement level starting from strongly agree to strongly disagree on five scale ratings. As per the descriptive statistics, the statement on interference of job pressures with their family or personal life (M=3.0448), negative effect of job on their physical or emotional well-being (M=2.8856), finding difficult to express their opinions or feelings about their job conditions to superiors (M=2.8259) was agreed to the highest extent. Findings on percentage analysis are described below;

1. 33.3% of the respondents agree that Conditions at work are unpleasant or sometimes even unsafe.
2. 37.8% of the cabin crews agree that job is negatively affecting their physical or emotional well-being.
3. 61.2% of crew members agree to the fact that they get too much work to do and/or too many unreasonable deadlines.
4. 41.8% of the respondents have neutralized agreement level on expressing their opinions or feelings about job conditions to their superiors.
5. 32.3% of the cabin crews agree that job pressures interfere with their family or personal life.
6. 36.8% of respondents agree that they have adequate control or input over work duties.
7. 33.3% of the samples strongly agree that they receive appropriate recognition or rewards for good performance.
8. 37.3% of the respondents strongly agree that they are able to utilize their skills and talents to the fullest extent at work.

7.4.2 AGREEMENT LEVEL ON STRESS COPING RESOURCES INVENTORY

The construct stress coping resources inventory was measured using agreement scale in the form of statement as well as using close ended questions. The construct “stress coping resources” was measured using 8 statement types of questions. As per the descriptive statistics, respondents ability to control their emotions (M=3.8416), seeking information about the event and coping with it (M=3.7277) and asking their friends or relatives for help (M=3.6584) was agreed to the highest extent by the cabin crews as measure stress coping strategy.

Findings on percentage analysis of stress coping resources are discussed below:

1. As per the result concerning the close ended questions, it was found that 54.2% of crew member say that company provides appropriate/any measures to help relieve their work stress.
2. 49.8% of respondents said that Organization/Industry have not put enough effort in development and implementation of new stress management strategies.
3. 41.3% of respondents believe that they have a history of coping well with highly stressful situations to a great extent against 28.9% who are able to cope to a great extent.

4. When something bad happens 34.8% of crew member unlikely exaggerate its importance.
5. 38.3% of crew members are capable of changing thinking to calm down during the stressful situation against 26.9% those who preferred to say incapable or not capable.
6. 42.8% of them have decision making power as much as any other member of their family.
7. 44.8 % of them have decision making power as much as any other member in the working environment.
8. 38.8% of crew members are unlikely to see others as threatening, uncooperative, or exploitative.
9. 37.8% of crew members to some extent believe that their life has purpose as compared to 28.4% of them who said that they believe to a little extent.
10. 41.3% of the crew members are in much touch with spiritual community.

7.4.3 AGREEMENT LEVEL ON WORK ENGAGEMENT

The construct “work engagement” was measured using 12 indicators, in which the mean values ranged between 2.2537 to 3.1891. As per the descriptive statistics, the statement on “another day at work feels exhausted” (M=3.1891), “Working all day is exhausting” (M=3.1891), “co-workers assistance and support” (M=2.9950), co-workers are willing to listen to their concerns about work (M=2.9701) was agreed to the highest extent. “Job causing to burnout” was the least agreed statement, as the mean value in this case is 2.2537.

1. 49.8% of the respondents agreed that this job has caused them to become burnt out.
2. 48.8% of them preferred to be neutral on work being the reason for their emotional exhaustion.
3. As per the result, 33.8% showed neutral perception on getting up in the morning and facing another day at work leading to exhaustion.
4. 27.4% of the respondents disagree that Working all day is quite exhausting for them.
5. 33.3% of the respondents feel that after joining this job, they have lost interest in their career.
6. Majority (37.3%) of the cabin crews agreed that they are not as enthused about their job as they used to be.

7. 36.8 % of them gave neutral opinion on bosses' frequent willingness to listen to their work-related issues.
8. 31.8% of them gave neutral perception on assistance and support from co-workers.
9. Perception of 36.8% of cabin crews found to be neutral on co-workers frequent willingness to listen to the concerns about work.
10. 30.8% of them agreed that job demands to be self-motivated, learn new things, and use of personal knowledge and abilities.
11. Most (33.3%) of the people agreed that they have experienced derogatory public view of their profession.
12. For the statement related to stress due to chief flight attendant most of (34.3%) the respondents showed neutral perception.

7.5 FINDINGS ON EMOTIONAL LABOUR

1. As per the results, 37.3% of respondents feel that they put on a "show" or "performance" when interacting with passengers and 35.3% of them fake a good mood when interacting with passengers.
2. 40.8% of cabin crews try to actually experience the emotions they must show to passengers and 40.8 % them Work hard to feel the emotions that they need to show to passengers.
3. 47.8% of respondents said that the passengers seem to like interacting with; even there are 32.3% who said they look sincere when dealing with passengers.
4. When doing job as a member of cabin crew 32.3% of crew members feel wiped out and 31.8% feel tired.
5. 51.7% of the crew member said that they adequately complete all duties assigned to them.
6. 32.8% crew member feels that they work under incompatible policies and guidelines when doing their job; similarly, 32.8% of crew member said they have to do things that should be done.
7. 51.2% of respondents are not able to hide their true feelings during the flight.
8. 51.2% of crew members are able to remain calm even when they are astonished during the flight.
9. 59.7% of the crew members affirmed that during a flight, they cannot show their personal problems and sometimes have to give false smile.

10. As per the percentage analysis, 51.2% of respondents are not able hide their true feelings during the flight.
11. 53.7% of respondents are not able hide fear when someone who appears threatening.

7.6 FINDINGS RELATED TO CORRELATION RESULTS BETWEEN STRESSOR AGENT, WORK PLACE STRESS, STRESS COPING RESOURCES AND WORK ENGAGEMENT:

1. Irregular Working Hours of the cabin crews showed high degree significant positive correlation with Work Hassles ($r=.697^{**}$) compared to The Workplace Stress ($r=.620^{**}$), Social Isolation ($r=.600^{**}$) and Aircraft Cabin Environments ($r=.595^{**}$). But irregular working hour is negatively correlated with work engagement ($r= -.178^*$), indicating high irregular working hour leading to low work engagement.
2. Considering work hassles, it showed a highest significant positive correlation with Aircraft Cabin Environments with r value of $.709^{**}$ and also showed a significant positive association with Social Isolation ($r=.684^{**}$) and The Workplace Stress Scale ($r=.694^{**}$). Work hassles among cabin crew showed significant negative correlation with work engagement ($r=-.176^*$).
3. Aircraft Cabin Environments is highly and significantly associated with social isolation ($r=.698^{**}$) and work place stress ($r=.585^{**}$) but it is negatively associated with work engagement ($-.129$).
4. Social Isolation showed high degree positive correlation with The Workplace engagement ($r=.578$) but negatively correlated with Work Engagement ($r= -.058$) which has a insignificant effect.
5. As far as work place stress is concerned, it shows negative significant correlation with Work Engagement ($r= -.199^{**}$).
6. Stress Coping Resources has positive significant relation with Work Engagement ($r=.252^{**}$), which demonstrates higher the stress coping resources more we will be the work engagement.

7.7 FINDINGS RELATED TO HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Table 7.1: One-way ANOVA and Independent Sample t-test Results

Sl. No.	Hypotheses	Personal Factors	Test	Result
1.	H1.a: The Irregular working hours of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their personal factors	Age	P>0.05	H1.a is accepted
		Gender	P<0.01**	
		Marital Status	P<0.01**	
		Current function	P<0.01**	
		Experience	P<0.01**	
		Maximum number of consecutive days of work	P<0.01**	
		Maximum number of consecutive nights of work	P<0.01**	
		Average days off per month	P<0.01**	
2.	H1.b: The Work Hassles of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their personal factors	Age	P>0.05	H1.b is accepted
		Gender	P<0.01**	
		Marital Status	P>0.05	
		Current function	P<0.05*	
		Experience	P<0.01**	
		Maximum number of consecutive days of work	P<0.01**	
		Maximum number of consecutive nights of work	P>0.05	
		Average days off per month	P<0.01**	
3.	H1.c: The Aircraft Cabin Environments of cabin crews are significantly influenced by their personal factors	Age	P<0.05*	H1.c is accepted
		Gender	P<0.01**	
		Marital Status	P>0.05	
		Current function	P>0.05	
		Experience	P<0.01**	
		Maximum number of consecutive days of work	P<0.01**	
		Maximum number of consecutive nights of work	P>0.05	
		Average days off per month	P<0.01**	
4.	H1.d: The Social Isolation of cabin crews is significantly influenced by their personal factors	Age	P>0.05	H1.d is accepted
		Gender	P<0.01**	
		Marital Status	P>0.05	
		Current function	P>0.05	
		Experience	P<0.01**	
		Maximum number of consecutive days of work	P<0.01**	
		Maximum number of consecutive nights of work	P>0.05	
		Average days off per month	P<0.01**	
5.	H2: The personal factors of cabin crews have significant influence on Workplace Stress	Age	P>0.05	H2 is accepted.
		Gender	P<0.05*	
		Marital Status	P<0.01**	
		Current function	P>0.05	
		Experience	P<0.01**	
		Maximum number of consecutive days of work	P<0.05*	
		Maximum number of consecutive nights of work	P<0.01**	
		Average days off per month	P<0.05*	

6.	H3: Work Engagement is significantly different among various personal factors of cabin crews	Age	P>0.05	H3 is accepted.
		Gender	P<0.01**	
		Marital Status	P>0.05	
		Current function	P>0.05	
		Experience	P<0.01**	
		Maximum number of consecutive days of work	P<0.01**	
		Maximum number of consecutive nights of work	P>0.05	
		Average days off per month	P<0.01**	

Table 7.2: Simple Linear and Multiple Regression Analysis Results

Sl. No.	Hypotheses	Variable	Test	Result
1.	H4: Stressor Agents have direct effect on Workplace Stress.	Irregular Working Hours	P<0.01**	H4 is accepted
		Work Hassles	P<0.01**	
		Aircraft Cabin Environments	P>0.05	
		Social Isolation	P>0.05	
2.	H5: Workplace Stress of cabin crews will have impact on work engagement	Workplace Stress Scale	P<0.01**	H5 is accepted.
3.	H7: Personal factor of the employees tends to moderate the relationship between Stressor Agents and Workplace Stress.	Age	P<0.01**	H7 is accepted.
		Gender	P<0.01**	
		Marital status	P<0.01**	
		Current function	P<0.01**	
		Experience	P<0.01**	
4.	H8: Personal factor of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Workplace Stress and work Engagement.	Age	P<0.01**	H8 is accepted
		Gender	P<0.01**	
		Marital status	P<0.01**	
		Current function	P>0.05	
		Experience	P>0.05	
5.	H10: Stress Coping Resources of the cabin crews tends to moderate the relationship between Workplace Stress and work Engagement.	Lower coping resources	P>0.05	H11 is accepted
		Higher coping resources	P<0.01**	

Table 7.3: Structural Equation Modelling Results

Sl. No.	Hypotheses	Estimates	P	Result
1.	H6: Stress Coping Resources acts as a mediator between Workplace Stress and work engagement.	Effect (Total) = -0.197	S	H6 is accepted
		Effect (Direct) = -.199	S	
		Effect (Indirect) = 0.002	S	
2.	H9: The negative impact of workplace stress on work engagement is low in case of the cabin crews opted for high stress coping resources.	ST<--- IWH=.116	HS	H9 is accepted
		ST<--- WH= .255	HS	
		ST<--- ACE=.184	NS	
		ST<--- SI= .003	S	
		WEF<--- ST= -.324	NS	
3.	H11: Stressor Agents directly affects the workplace stress which in turn impacts work engagement.	ST <- IWH = .182	HS	H10 is accepted
		ST <- WH = .326	HS	
		ST <- ACE = .085	HS	
		ST <- SI = .087	S	
		ST <- WE = -.217	S	

Note: IWH-Irregular working hour, ST-Stress level at workplace, WH-Work hassles, ACE-Air craft cabin environment, SI-Social isolation, WE-Work engagement, HS-Highly significant. S-Significant.

7.8 SUMMARY OF FINAL PATH MODELING

From the recommended and obtained value to check the goodness of fit of the proposed model, it is observed that the obtained value satisfies the recommended value as χ^2/df is between 2-5 (3.4484); GFI is above .90 (0.926); NFI is above .90 (0.971); AGFI is above 0.8 (0.914); CFI is above .90 (0.935) and RMSEA is below 0.05 (0.042). Hence the proposed model tends to be valid and fit. The findings on the path model are discussed below;

1. Workplace stress shows direct positive effect on stress coping resources; which means more work place stress contributes to higher adoption of stress coping resources.
2. Stress coping resources has direct significant impact on work engagement. It indicates that increase in stress coping resources increases work engagement.
3. Workplace stress has negative significant effect on work engagement; which implies that increase in workplace stress decreases the work engagement among cabin crews.
4. Contemplating the indirect effect it is strongly evidenced that stress coping resource acts as a mediator between Workplace Stress and work engagement.

7.9 FINDINGS RELATED TO QUANTITATIVE ABCD ANALYSIS OF STRESS COPING MECHANISM

Table 7.4: Quantitative ABCD Analysis of Stress Coping Mechanism

Factors	Total Mean Score	Inference
Advantageous factors	98.066	Stress Coping Mechanism is highly advantageous
Benifiting factors	81.46	
constraint factors	69.73	
disadvantageous factors	57.4	

7.10 SUGGESTIONS

Based on the summarized results of the study, suggestion section has been divided into two - i) suggestions to the management ii) suggestions to the cabin crews. Based on the interviews as well as results following suggestions can be given;

7.10.1 SUGGESTION TO CABIN CREWS

- To reduce the work load and exhaustion it is suggested to create a checklist, Prioritize the most difficult tasks, taking a quick break or even asking for help may help in reduce the workload of a cabin crew.
- Teamwork plays a vital role in a stressful situation. Each cabin crew can thoroughly understand what her/his duty is. Thorough observation and properly marking the check list will help senior cabin crews and other staff to take action for the shortcomings.
- After joining to the new profession as cabin crews they may take steps to educate their family and friends about their career and gain their support. This will help the family members to know their nature of work, schedules, and their job stress.
- As study showed work load/time pressure/deadlines (M=3.0199) are the major cause of stress, the staff may build the habit of saying “no” in a respectful way for the more work assigned to them which was not in their prescribed work schedule.
- At the end of the day they can ask themselves, whether they are suffering from any illness? Are they having any psychological pressure such as financial matters or any other matters, are they emotionally upset and are they having adequate amount of rest? Based on these questions they should resolve their imbalance.
- When cabin crews are stressed by a complex situation, they can focus on those aspects of situations which can be managed rather than being vulnerable. As the complex situation helps to identify their weakness to tackle this same problem in the future, as

- the study showed high agreement level on “unacceptable behaviour of passengers” (M=3.1045), “disobeying the instructions of crew by passengers” (M=2.7065).
- One more way to address the stress can be done by viewing the challenges as opportunities where the cabin crews can think unacceptable behaviour as a part of their job and avoid it and concentrate on what is important for them.
 - The staff with high stress level can focus on talking to themselves, taking a deep breath, being realistic in setting the goal, analyse what went wrong and what can be done.
 - As spiritual practices reduce stress, one should make an effort to find mosques, churches, temples and organizations that provide an opportunity for them to worship or recognize a holiday.
 - As the findings depicted the awareness level of cabin crews on practical, healthy ways of relaxing (M=3.4056) and engagement in a spiritual practice to enrich interior life (M= 3.0091), which can be implemented through practicing yoga, meditation, counselling and daily exercise also keeps the mind and body active and enthusiastic. All the cabin crews should practice this in their everyday routine.
 - Overall the major stress coping activities which the cabin crews can acquire in their stress time includes future planning, time management, healthy habits, better communication as well as coordination, proper sleep, problem solving attitude, adequate amount of knowledge on their profession, positive attitude, clear thinking and self-confidence.

7.10.2 SUGGESTIONS TO MANAGEMENT

- As the findings depicts high exhaustion level of cabin crews due to work load, Increasing the number of Cabin Crew members in a flight may help cabin crews to reduce their exhaustion level.
- Airlines should strive to simplify and regularize cabin crew’s schedule, encourage cabin crew with good attendance to have priority to pre-select schedule types, and abolish the strict regulations of making up the shifts after taking leave, so that cabin crew can balance their relationships between work and family, thereby enhancing their dedication and enthusiasm to work, achieve customer satisfaction for airlines, and improve performance.

- Due to too much work, the cabin crews lack quality time and sleep. The cabin crews may be given ample time to have a quality sleep and proper distribution of workload between all the cabin crews may reduce their exhaustion level.
- The management may take steps to interact with the cabin crews, listen to their problems and may come up with a plan to help the cabin crews to have a positive mind set about their job.
- Moreover, to tackle occupational disease hassles faced by cabin crews, airlines may include healthcare-related courses (e.g., Testing and Managing of Blood Pressure, Shoulder & Neck pain, about taking care of migraine headache etc.) in training courses and regularly arrange health check-ups for cabin crew, so that they are physically equipped to perform their duties.
- The findings of the study strongly argued that Unacceptable behaviors of passengers has caused them huge stress (M=3.1045). Hence, all the passengers who are drunk must restrain from boarding a flight. If a passenger displays any unruly behaviour, he may not be allowed to board any flights in the future. This will bring awareness among other passengers and this type of behaviour will be slowly reduced.
- The major findings of the study revealed that Coping behaviour plays a vital role in enhanced work engagement, it is essential to provide a training programmes on coping behaviour to cabin crews in order to manage the stress.
- Management may make sure that there is proper coordination of work between pilots, co-pilots, cabin crews and other staff to build the synergy among all the members.
- Make sure that training instructions and actual procedures are consistent. To alleviate the difficulties that arise when there is a disconnect between what cabin crew members learn in the classroom and what they do on the job, airlines can update and strengthen their training programmes on a regular basis. This will give cabin crew members the confidence they need to pass government and other department safety inspections.
- Increased focus on the mental and physical well-being of flight attendants is essential. Having a gym on-site, complete with regular sports events and a selection of exercise classes, may do wonders for an occupational health strategy. Hiring a seasoned mental health specialist to counsel and offer psychological healing courses is suggested to improve cabin crew members' emotional well-being.

- Experienced crew members may be valued by airlines. The importance of senior crew cannot be overstated. It is strongly advised to encourage the transmission of senior cabin crew experiences through concrete approaches. Because job resources can improve work engagement and alleviate burnout symptoms among the cabin crews. Airlines are encouraged to create a socially supportive working environment and assist cabin crew in developing effective career development plans. When flight attendants sense a friendly and supportive working environment with clear visions for the future, they tend to put in more effort.
- Boost productivity and send out just the right number of people to get the job done. Tasks like selling duty-free items, cooking meals, and checking in with passengers who have ordered special meals can be exhausting on cabin crew, and those who are assigned to these jobs may experience increased stress during their shifts. When the crew members are busy, the cabin manager should actively assist the staff members or assign other crew members to support them. The peer assistance between cabin crew in the task will enable cabin crew to ease the work pressure and inconveniences created by overloaded work.
- Airlines can also pay attention to the number of flight crew members deployed to each flight, and not reduce the crew size just to save cost. Otherwise, the crew members would have to bear a huge workload, which will result in great physical and mental pressure health and cause their hassles.
- When airlines set up recruitments, they may use a psychological capital scale to hire crew members with high psychological capital to reduce the impact of emotional labor burden on the crew members. In addition, airlines can employ psychological consultants and regularly arrange psychological consultations for their crew members.
- Accustom themselves to celebrating special events with family and friends such as special parties or gatherings so that it will work with their career and schedule. Find ways to celebrate and recognize important occasions with their crew or on their flights.

In the opinion of crew members, the airline should focus on conducting more of practical trainings then emphasizing on the theory portion as this affects their level of understanding towards the subject.

7.11 DIRECTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

- Few studies have been conducted with respect to stressor agents and coping behaviour leading to work engagement, hence this study opens a new door for further research in different geographical area such as other developing countries.
- Comparative study of different airline companies in managing stressor agents can also be examined in future research.
- Considering stress as an indicator, work life balance also can be analyzed in future studies.
- Further research can be conducted on a different set of aviation workers on the same model to assess the impact of each selected variables.
- This study also provides a future direction to adopt longitudinal research such as measuring the changes in employees work engagement before and after attending stress management training programs.

7.12 CONCLUSION

Cabin Crews are a distinct occupational category in many aspects, including their irregular work schedules, peculiar set of job requirements, and distinctive way of life, to name a few. All these aspects may result to Stress among the Cabin Crews. Hence the primary goal of this research was to identify the elements that cause stress in cabin crew members, as well as the coping techniques that they use to manage their stress which enhances their work engagement. This study intended to assess the impact of various stressor agents on the workplace stress effecting work engagement in the cabin crew environment, based on which the study also attempted to assess the role of stress coping resources in improving the level of work engagement. Result demonstrated the positive and mediating role in reducing the negative work engagement. This study strongly argues that stress coping resource inventory if modified and improved can be an optimal solution for the stress at work place, which again ensures better work engagement among the cabin crews. This study demands the holistic growth and quality of life of the cabin crews by constantly conducting stress management programme, stress coping behaviour programme during the training provided to the aviation workers with special consideration on Mangalore and Bangalore International Airport.

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ANNEXURE

QUESTIONNAIRE (Cabin Crews)

Section I: Introduction

1. In what age group are you?
 - a. 20-29yrs
 - b. 30-39yrs
 - c. 40yrs and Above
 - d. 20yrs and below
2. What is your Gender?
 - a. I am Male
 - b. I am Female
3. What is your marital status?
 - a. I am Married
 - b. I am Unmarried
4. Current function
 - a. Junior cabin crew
 - b. Senior cabin crew
 - c. Inflight managers
 - d. Trainers
 - e. Cabin Service Director
5. Experience working as a Cabin Crew
 - a. 0-1 years
 - b. 1-3 years
 - c. 3-6 years
 - d. 6-9 years
 - e. 9-12 years
 - f. 12-15 years
 - g. 15 years and above
6. Has the start of your career as a CCM required you to change something in your lifestyle?
 - a. Took time away from social life
 - b. difficulties following regular workout routines and diet
 - c. The frequent crossing of the time zones and disruptive sleeping schedules
 - d. Took now more time to take care of myself
 - e. Spending longer periods of time away from home
 - f. Need More Exercise, healthier diet and need more time to sleep
 - g. Less time to exercise and harder to follow a diet
 - h. Changed Sleeping Habits
 - i. Other _____
7. Maximum number of consecutive days of work
 - a. Up to 6 days
 - b. 7 days or more

8. Maximum number of consecutive nights of work

- a. One or two Nights
- b. Three or Four Nights
- c. Five Nights or more

9. Average days off per month

- a. Less than 5 days
- b. 5-10 days
- c. 10 days or more

Section II: Irregular Working Hours

Instructions: Please tick the box (✓) next to the rating that best represents your view on each question.

		Score	5	4	3	2	1
Sl. No.	Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
1	My job events are not clearly predictable, they subject to last-minute deadlines						
2	I feel that I spend so long at work that my outside relationships are suffering.						
3	Working for long day makes me fatigued/exhausted during the flight						
4	I feel that night flights or a series of night flights are serious contributors to fatigue						
5	I feel that a series of early morning departures as problematic and contributing to fatigue						
6	I usually feel the need for recovery after work						
7	I get sufficient sleep time after my work						
8	Many times I have reported unfit for duty due to fatigue/exhaustion						
9	Many times I have made a mistake in the flight due to fatigue/exhaustion						
10	I have remarked (out loud or to myself) about how tired I was, but proceeded to go on the flight anyway.						
11	I do not get enough time to rest due to long working hours						
12	My Airlines policies have caused me extra time/pressure to complete my job						

Section III: Work Hassles

Instructions: Please tick the box (✓) next to the rating that best represents your view on each question.

		Score				
Sl No.	Statement	5 Strongly Agree	4 Agree	3 Neutral	2 Disagree	1 Strongly Disagree
1	Most of the times during a flight, communication issues with Pilots has caused me stress					
2	Most of the times during a flight communication issues with the passengers has caused me stress					
3	Most of the times unacceptable behaviours (smoking when prohibited or Drunk passengers) of passengers have caused me stress during a flight					
4	The presence of gap between works standards and practical operations in a flight makes me feel stressed					
5	When I cannot take a vacation during the planned dates due to irregular work schedule I feel stressed					
6	Due to different cultures there is presence of poor work cohesion among cabin crew and this hassle makes me stressed during a flight					
7	When there is an unexpected emergency on a flight, and when there is trouble in managing this situation, it makes me exhausted					
8	Most often during flying, poor work cohesion between cockpit crew and cabin crew affects flight safety and this makes me stressed					
9	Most of the time antisocial behaviour of passengers cases me stress					
10	During a flight verbal and physical violence by the passengers toward the cabin crew makes me stressed					
11	During a flight verbal threats to other passengers make me feel stressed					
12	During a flight disobeying the instructions of crew by passengers makes me stressed					
13	I have many health problems due to this job. This work has had a negative impact on my body and caused hassles in my life.					
14	Sometimes I suffer from jet lag problems which affects my sleep and it's a hassle for my work					

Section IV: Aircraft Cabin Environments

Instructions: Please tick the box (✓) next to the rating that best represents your view on each question.

		Score	5	4	3	2	1
Sl. No.	Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
1	Flight delays bother me and due to this delay disruptive passengers have hurt me emotionally						
2	I get stressed due to the scheduling and rostering						
3	I face anxiety regarding pre-flight checks						
4	I get stressed over work load/time pressure/deadlines						
5	I often face interpersonal problems with other cabin crew/ flight crew						
6	I feel there is a lack of opportunities and potential advancement in this job						
7	I feel that there is lack of encouragement and support by the management and superiors						
8	I often find monotonous work involving underutilization of skills						
9	I experience irregular flight duty timings						
10	I experience variability in work load and uneven distribution of work among the cabin crews						
11	I have experienced kind of harassment by passengers or the crew either sexual/nonsexual such as looking/ touching/comments etc. during flights						
12	Aircraft cabin pressure causes me headache						
13	There is potential for general transmission of infections during flights for which I am concerned						

Section V: Social Isolation

Instructions: Please tick the box (✓) next to the rating that best represents your view on each question.

		Score	5	4	3	2	1
Sl. No.	Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
1	Work responsibilities have impacted on my personal, family, and social lives.						
2	My job has an adverse influence on my family and social life.						
3	My work time interferes with my family and social life.						
4	I don't seem to have enough time for my family or friends. My work includes a wide range of activities.						
5	I have experienced managing a balance with my Work-Rest-Social life						
6	I find that I don't have time for many interests/hobbies outside of work.						
7	I find that after joining this job I don't have time to attend any family functions.						
8	My family members often say that, I do not have time to be with them whenever it is required						
9	I always feel that I want to spend some time with my family members/friends but due to this work I am not able to do it						
10	My friends call me and tell me that I have changed a lot after joining this work						

Section VI: The Workplace Stress Scale

Instructions: Thinking about your current job, how often does each of the following statements describe how you feel?

Statement	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Very Often
1. Conditions at work are unpleasant or sometimes even unsafe.	1	2	3	4	5
2. I feel that my job is negatively affecting my physical or emotional well-being.	1	2	3	4	5
3. I have too much work to do and/or too many unreasonable deadlines.	1	2	3	4	5
4. I find it difficult to express my opinions or feelings about my job conditions to my superiors.	1	2	3	4	5

5. I feel that job pressures interfere with my family or personal life.	1	2	3	4	5
6. I have adequate control or input over my work duties.	5	4	3	2	1
7. I receive appropriate recognition or rewards for good performance.	5	4	3	2	1
8. I am able to utilize my skills and talents to the fullest extent at work.	5	4	3	2	1

Section VII: Work Engagement

Instructions: Please tick the box (✓) next to the rating that best represents your view on each question.

Score		5	4	3	2	1
Sl No.	Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	My job has caused me to become burnt out.					
2	My work has emotionally exhausted me.					
3	When I get up in the morning and have to face another day at work, I am exhausted.					
4	Working all day is quite exhausting for me.					
5	After joining this job, I have lost interest in my career.					
6	I'm not as enthused about my job as I used to be.					
7	My bosses are frequently willing to listen to my work-related issues.					
8	My co-workers assist and support me.					
9	My co-workers are frequently willing to listen to my concerns about work.					
10	My job demands me to be self-motivated. I can learn new things at work, and I can put my personal abilities or knowledge to use.					
11	I have experienced derogatory public view of my profession.					
12	Sometimes my chief flight attendant typically cause additional stress for me.					

Section VIII: Emotional Labour

Instructions: Please tick the circle (✓) that best represents your view on each question.

- “When doing my job as a member of cabin crew, I often;
 - Put on an act in order to deal with passengers in an appropriate way.
 - Fake a good mood when interacting with passengers.
 - Put on a “show” or “performance” when interacting with passengers.
 - Just pretend to have the emotions you need to display for your job.

2. "When doing my job as a member of cabin crew, I often
 - Try to actually experience the emotions I must show to passengers.
 - Work hard to feel the emotions that I need to show to passengers.
 - Make an effort to actually feel the emotions that I need to display towards passengers.
3. "When doing my job as a member of cabin crew, I often;
 - I look sincere when dealing with passengers.
 - The passengers seem to like interacting with me.
 - Show friendliness and warmth to most passengers.
4. "When doing my job as a member of the cabin crew, I often;
 - Feel tired
 - Feel wiped out
 - Feel run down
 - Feel exhausted at my job
5. "When doing my job as a cabin crew, I often
 - Perform tasks and roles that are expected of me.
 - Adequately complete all duties assigned to me.
 - Feel that my overall performance is better than that of your colleagues.
6. When doing my job as a member of the cabin crew, I often
 - Have to do things that should be done differently.
 - Work under incompatible policies and guidelines.
 - Receive an assignment without the manpower to complete it.
 - Receive incompatible requests from two or more people.
 - Have to work under vague directives or orders
7. During a flight, I cannot show my personal problems and sometimes have to give false smile?
 - Yes
 - No
8. During a flight I hide my true feelings about a situation.
 - Yes
 - No
9. During a flight in certain situations I Remain calm even when I am astonished
 - Yes
 - No
10. During a flight I try to hide my fear even when someone who appears threatening.
 - Yes
 - No

Section IX: Stress Coping Resources Inventory: A Self-Assessment

Instructions: People differ remarkably in their responses to potentially stressful events. What are the factors associated with coping success? The questions below relate to factors most closely associated with the capacity to cope successfully with stress. Circle the letter which lists the option that you choose. Answer each question as honestly as possible.

1. Do you think that your company provides appropriate/any measures to help you relieve your work stress?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
2. Has your Organization/Industry ever invested effort in development and implementation of new stress management strategies
 - a. Lot of effort
 - b. Not enough effort
 - c. Not putting any effort
3. To what extent do you believe that you have a history of coping well with highly stressful situations?
 - a. to a very great extent
 - b. to a great extent
 - c. to a little extent
 - d. to a very little extent
4. When something bad happens to you, how likely are you to exaggerate its importance?
 - a. very unlikely
 - b. unlikely
 - c. likely
 - d. very likely
5. How much decision-making power do you have in your family?
 - a. more power than any other member of my family
 - b. as much power as any other member of my family
 - c. less power than most members of my family
 - d. less power than any other member of my family
6. How much decision-making power do you have in your working environment?
 - a. more power than most members of my work team
 - b. as much power as any other member of my work team
 - c. less power than most members of my work team
 - d. less power than any other member of my work team
7. In comparison with other people, how likely are you to see others as threatening, uncooperative, or exploitative?
 - a. highly unlikely
 - b. unlikely
 - c. likely
 - d. highly likely

8. To what extent do you believe your life has purpose?
- to a very great extent
 - to some extent
 - to little extent
 - to very little extent
9. How much contact do you have with what you would consider a spiritual community?
- very much
 - much
 - very little
 - none

Instructions: Please tick the box (✓) next to the rating that best represents your view on each question.

		Score				
Sl. No.	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1.	I am fully aware of the practical, healthy ways of relaxing and I frequently exercise it.					
2.	When things are not going well, I view the situation as being temporary rather than permanent.					
3.	When stressed by a complex situation, I focus my attention on those aspects of the situation that I can manage.					
4.	When I am thoroughly frustrated, I identify an alternate goal and pursue it.					
5.	I control my emotions when I am stressed.					
6.	When an unexpected, negative event happens to me, I actively seek information about the event and cope with it.					
7.	When I am highly stressed, I ask my friends or relatives for help.					
8.	I frequently engage in spiritual practices such as prayer, meditation, or inspirational reading to enrich my interior life.					

10. What do you personally think would be the best way for you and your colleagues to reduce stress? (Any changes in the workload, workplace or personal lifestyle?)

Stress Coping Mechanism: A Quantitative ABCD Analysis

Note: This section delves into the numerous CCE for each key attribute concerning stress coping mechanism under the focal area belonging to the ABCD analysis constructs.

Please mark the box that best expresses your ideas.

Agree [3]; Neutral [2]; Disagree [1].

1. The table below displays the advantageous elements of stress coping mechanisms and their important constituent element as identified by focus groups.

Table 1: Advantageous factors influencing stress coping mechanisms and their CCEs

Determinant Issues	Key Attributes	Advantageous Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Element
Irregular working hours	Precise Schedule [1] [2] [3]	Purpose Clarity [1] [2] [3]	Goal Setting [1] [2] [3]
	Checklist [1] [2] [3]	Efficient [1] [2] [3]	Well Organized [1] [2] [3]
	Power Naps [1] [2] [3]	Quicker Reaction Time [1] [2] [3]	Responsive [1] [2] [3]
Work Hassles	Job And Peer Management [1] [2] [3]	Improves Confidence [1] [2] [3]	Skills, Expertise And Capabilities [1] [2] [3]
	Passenger Management [1] [2] [3]	Passenger Satisfaction [1] [2] [3]	Sustainability And Profitability [1] [2] [3]
	Work-Life Balance [1] [2] [3]	High Productivity [1] [2] [3]	Efficiency [1] [2] [3]
Social Isolation	Social Support [1] [2] [3]	Sense Of Security [1] [2] [3]	Safety [1] [2] [3]
	Spirituality [1] [2] [3]	Well Being [1] [2] [3]	High Performance [1] [2] [3]
	Relaxation [1] [2] [3]	Improved Focus [1] [2] [3]	High Quality Work [1] [2] [3]
Burnout	Task Strategies [1] [2] [3]	Reduces Mistakes [1] [2] [3]	Accurate Service Delivery [1] [2] [3]
	Better Sleep Quality [1] [2] [3]	Creativity [1] [2] [3]	High Problem Solving Ability [1] [2] [3]
	Positive Reappraisal [1] [2] [3]	Mindfulness And More Tolerable [1] [2] [3]	Enhanced Engagement [1] [2] [3]

2. The table below displays the benefit elements of stress coping mechanisms and their important constituent element as identified by focus groups.

Table 2: Benefit factors influencing stress coping mechanisms and their CCEs

Determinant Issues	Key Attributes	Beneficial Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Element
Irregular working hours	Precise Schedule [1] [2] [3]	Task Prioritization [1] [2] [3]	Avoid Procrastination [1] [2] [3]
	Checklist [1] [2] [3]	Time Saver [1] [2] [3]	New Opportunities [1] [2] [3]
	Power Naps [1] [2] [3]	Enhanced Cognitive Performance [1] [2] [3]	Remember Tasks [1] [2] [3]
Work Hassles	Job And Peer Management [1] [2] [3]	Team Efficiency [1] [2] [3]	Reduction In Individual Pressure [1] [2] [3]
	Passenger Management [1] [2] [3]	Promotion [1] [2] [3]	Facilities And Privileges [1] [2] [3]
	Work-Life Balance [1] [2] [3]	Less Absenteeism [1] [2] [3]	Reliability And Trustworthiness [1] [2] [3]
Social Isolation	Social Support [1] [2] [3]	Build Network [1] [2] [3]	Recognition [1] [2] [3]
	Spirituality [1] [2] [3]	Motivation And Commitment [1] [2] [3]	Loyalty And Stability [1] [2] [3]
	Relaxation [1] [2] [3]	Better Decision Making [1] [2] [3]	Favorable Outcome [1] [2] [3]
Burnout	Task Strategies [1] [2] [3]	Simplification Of Complex Task [1] [2] [3]	Easier And Faster Completion Of Work
	Better Sleep Quality [1] [2] [3]	Uplifts Mood [1] [2] [3]	Commitment [1] [2] [3]
	Positive Reappraisal [1] [2] [3]	Spread Of Positive Vibes [1] [2] [3]	Employee Retention [1] [2] [3]

3. The table below displays the constraints elements of stress coping mechanisms and their important constituent element as identified by focus groups.

Table 3: Constraint factors influencing stress coping mechanisms and their CCEs

Determinant Issues	Key Attributes	Constraints Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Element
Irregular working hours	Precise Schedule [1] [2] [3]	Complexity [1] [2] [3]	Lack Of Clarity [1] [2] [3]
	Checklist [1] [2] [3]	Rigid Frame [1] [2] [3]	Confusion [1] [2] [3]
	Power Naps [1] [2] [3]	Lack Of Free Time [1] [2] [3]	Lack Of Focus [1] [2] [3]
Work Hassles	Job And Peer Management [1] [2] [3]	Poor Work Cohesion [1] [2] [3]	Conflicts [1] [2] [3]
	Passenger Management [1] [2] [3]	Verbal And Physical Violence [1] [2] [3]	Increased Turnover [1] [2] [3]
	Work-Life Balance [1] [2] [3]	Unrealistic Expectations [1] [2] [3]	Disappointment [1] [2] [3]
Social Isolation	Social Support [1] [2] [3]	Lack Of Acceptance [1] [2] [3]	Violence [1] [2] [3]
	Spirituality [1] [2] [3]	Religious Conflicts [1] [2] [3]	Hatred [1] [2] [3]
	Relaxation [1] [2] [3]	Work Load [1] [2] [3]	Stress [1] [2] [3]
Burnout	Task Strategies [1] [2] [3]	Poor Goal Setting [1] [2] [3]	Low Utilization Of Action And Energy [1] [2] [3]
	Better Sleep Quality [1] [2] [3]	Task Deadlines [1] [2] [3]	Low Creativity [1] [2] [3]
	Positive Reappraisal [1] [2] [3]	Instability Of Emotions [1] [2] [3]	Anxiety [1] [2] [3]

4. The table below displays the disadvantageous elements of stress coping mechanisms and their important constituent element as identified by focus groups.

Table 4: Disadvantageous factors influencing stress coping mechanisms and their CCEs

Determinant Issues	Key Attributes	Disadvantageous Factors Affecting Determinant Issues	Critical Constituent Element
Irregular working hours	Precise Schedule [1] [2] [3]	Pressure [1] [2] [3]	Mental Distress [1] [2] [3]
	Checklist [1] [2] [3]	Low Quality Performance [1] [2] [3]	Job Dissatisfaction [1] [2] [3]
	Power Naps [1] [2] [3]	Impaired Alertness And Performance [1] [2] [3]	Ignorance [1] [2] [3]
Work Hassles	Job And Peer Management [1] [2] [3]	Rigid Work Standards [1] [2] [3]	Lack Of Involvement [1] [2] [3]
	Passenger Management [1] [2] [3]	High Emotional Labor [1] [2] [3]	Lack Of Job Performance [1] [2] [3]
	Work-Life Balance [1] [2] [3]	Make Employees Less Visible [1] [2] [3]	Loss Of Productivity [1] [2] [3]
Social Isolation	Social Support [1] [2] [3]	Excessive Reliance [1] [2] [3]	Low Self-Esteem [1] [2] [3]
	Spirituality [1] [2] [3]	Lack Of Focus On Business Objectives [1] [2] [3]	Low Success Rate [1] [2] [3]
	Relaxation [1] [2] [3]	Fear Of Losing Control [1] [2] [3]	Job Loss [1] [2] [3]
Burnout	Task Strategies [1] [2] [3]	Incomplete Task Causes Guilty Feeling [1] [2] [3]	Low Morale [1] [2] [3]
	Better Sleep Quality [1] [2] [3]	Laziness And Less Productivity [1] [2] [3]	Low Customer Service Quality [1] [2] [3]
	Positive Reappraisal [1] [2] [3]	Exploitation By Over Workload [1] [2] [3]	Lack Of Transparency [1] [2] [3]

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